

PROCEEDINGS

IX International Conference on Management of the Diamondback Moth and Other Crucifer Insect Pests

R. Srinivasan
Editor

2-5 May 2023
Phnom Penh, Cambodia

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World Vegetable Center

Agricultural Chemicals Research Institute, Ministry of Agriculture, Taiwan (R.O.C.)

Royal University of Agriculture, Cambodia

World Vegetable Center

The World Vegetable Center is an international nonprofit research and development institute committed to healthier lives and more resilient livelihoods through the increased production and consumption of nutritious, diverse, and health-promoting vegetables.

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and Other Crucifer Insect Pests

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Foreword

Brassica vegetables are globally significant crops, valued for their rich nutritional profile—providing essential vitamins, minerals, folic acid, and dietary fiber—and their health-promoting properties. Their high glucosinolate content has been linked to a reduced risk of cancer, making them an important component of balanced diets. Additionally, brassicas are high-value, quick-turnover crops that hold the potential to significantly improve the livelihoods of smallholder farmers. However, their production faces major challenges from biotic stresses, particularly insect pests, which often drive the over-reliance on chemical pesticides.

The diamondback moth (DBM), a globally pervasive pest, is a primary challenge. Still, secondary pests such as head caterpillars, webworms, cabbage butterflies, armyworms, flea beetles, and aphids contribute significantly to yield losses worldwide. Farmers often resort to frequent pesticide applications as a preventive measure. In some developing countries, the cost of pest management is staggering. For example, a study in Pakistan reported pesticide applications twice a week. At the same time, farmers in Cambodia, Laos, and Vietnam apply 1–2 sprays per week to manage DBM, often mixing multiple pesticides in a single spray. Alarmingly, farmers in these countries apply approximately 1 kg of pesticides per hectare weekly. Globally, DBM management and associated crop damage amount to an estimated US\$ 4–5 billion annually, highlighting the scale of this challenge. Beyond escalating production costs, the overuse and misuse of pesticides pose severe risks to human health and the environment.

The World Vegetable Center (WorldVeg) has been at the forefront of sustainable solutions for managing DBM. Between 1985 and 2005, WorldVeg led efforts to scale out biological control of DBM across South and Southeast Asia, introducing parasitoids for classical biological control. This successful initiative was extended to East Africa from 2004 to 2008 in collaboration with the International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (*icipe*). Additionally, WorldVeg coordinates the International Working Group on DBM and Other Crucifer Insects—an informal network of global researchers dedicated to advancing brassica pest management. Since its inception in 1985, this group has organized nine international conferences to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration.

For the first time, WorldVeg, in partnership with the Agricultural Chemicals Research Institute (ACRI), Ministry of Agriculture, Taiwan, and the Royal University of Agriculture, hosted the 9th International Conference on DBM and Other Crucifer Insects in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, from May 2 to 5, 2023. The event brought together 80 participants from 18 countries to discuss cutting-edge research and practical solutions for managing DBM and other brassica pests.

This conference proceedings volume captures the latest advancements in pest management for brassica crops. It is a valuable resource for researchers, extension agents, and plant protection practitioners striving to promote safer, more sustainable approaches to pest management.

Marco Wopereis
Director General
World Vegetable Center

Acknowledgements

The World Vegetable Center, in collaboration with the Agricultural Chemicals Research Institute (ACRI), Ministry of Agriculture, Taiwan, and the Royal University of Agriculture, Cambodia, organized the 9th International Conference on Management of the Diamondback Moth and Other Crucifer Insect Pests. The conference was held in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, from May 2–5, 2023.

The program featured 41 oral presentations and four poster presentations across five scientific sessions:

1. Insect-Plant Interactions, Host Plant Resistance, and Chemical Ecology of Crucifer Pests and Their Natural Enemies
2. Constraints and Opportunities for the Sustained Adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) for Diamondback Moth (DBM) and Other Crucifer Pests
3. Insecticide Resistance and Management in Crucifer Pests: The Ongoing Challenge
4. Biological and Non-Chemical Methods of Managing Crucifer Pests (Including Organic Agriculture)
5. Genetic Approaches for Managing Crucifer Pests: Transgenic Plants, CRISPR, RNAi, and Genetic Pest Management

The success of the conference was made possible by the active participation of 80 delegates from 18 countries. I want to extend my sincere gratitude to the Scientific Committee members who contributed significantly to shaping the scientific program: Dr. Paola Sotelo-Cardona, Dr. Li-Hsin Huang, Dr. Myron P. Zalucki, Dr. Michael Furlong, Dr. Tho Kim Eang, Dr. Zhenyu Li, Dr. Hugh A. Smith, Dr. Francisco Ruben Badenes Perez, and Dr. Subramanian Sevgan. I am also deeply thankful to Dr. Marco Wopereis, Dr. Yann-rong Lin, Dr. Sopana Yule, and Ms. Ariel Wu of the World Vegetable Center for their invaluable support in ensuring the successful organization of this event.

The conference would not have been possible without the generous financial support of the Ministry of Agriculture (Taiwan), the World Vegetable Center, and its long-term strategic donors: Taiwan, the Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office (FCDO) of the UK government, the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (ACIAR), Germany, Thailand, the Philippines, Korea, and Japan. Their contributions enabled the participation of leading Brassica IPM researchers as both invited speakers and conference attendees.

Finally, I would like to express my gratitude to Ms. Ariel Wu of the World Vegetable Center for her outstanding work formatting the conference proceedings.

*Dr. Srinivasan Ramasamy
Lead Entomologist and Flagship Program Leader –
Safe & Sustainable Value Chains, World Vegetable Center
Conference Organizing Secretary*

SESSION 1

*Insect Plant Interactions, Host Plant Resistance and
Chemical Ecology of Crucifer Pests and
Their Natural Enemies*

Ecosystem Services Within the Vegetable Integrated Push-Pull (VIPPT) Protect Brassicas against Diamondback Moth with Improved Yield and Quality

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ABSTRACT

Diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* is a key pest of cruciferous vegetables in the tropics, including sub-Saharan Africa. Recognizing the need for sustainable intensification of cropping systems to boost food production and nutritional diversity, we recently integrated kales, *Brassica oleracea*, a high-value vegetable preferred by farmers, into the cereal push-pull technology to form the VIPPT. The VIPPT involves intercropping maize and vegetables with *Desmodium* companion plants, with *Brachiaria* grasses as border crops around the plot. The semiochemicals produced by the *Desmodium* and *Brachiaria* companion plants are known to be important for controlling key lepidopteran pests of maize, including the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda*, through a stimulo-deterrent diversion strategy. To test a similar stimulo-deterrent mechanism of VIPPT on DBM, we conducted on-farm trials and assessed the damage caused by DBM on kales. We also evaluated the total and quantity of spoiled yield unsuitable for each plot.

Additionally, we assessed the impact of VIPPT. Our results showed that DBM infestations were reduced by over 60% in kales within the VIPPT compared to when grown solely or intercropped with maize only. This was followed by a 35% increase in yield and limited losses due to crop damage. Further standard oviposition choice tests under greenhouse conditions showed non-preference by DBM for kales paired with *Desmodium* compared to those solely grown. Interestingly, our olfactometry assays also revealed higher attraction of the DBM larval parasitoid, *Cotesia vestalis*, and aphid parasitoids to *Desmodium*.

Therefore, we conclude that Kales benefits from the pest control ecosystem services provided by the companion plants, which leads to improved productivity.

Keywords

stimulo-deterrent, *plutella xylostella*, *cotesia vestalis*, cropping system.

INTRODUCTION

For sub-Saharan Africa, achieving food and nutritional security remains at the top of the agenda. This is against multiple production constraints, including climate change, land degradation, poor soil fertility, and the scourge of pests and diseases (Chidawanyika et al., 2023). These constraints are further compounded by rapidly increasing population growth, where the land area for agricultural expansion and other land-use changes is scarce as priority shifts to meet other societal needs such as biodiversity conservation.

Sustainable intensification (SI), an approach that seeks to increase productivity using existing agricultural land without adverse environmental and social impacts, has been promoted as a key to solving some of the current challenges in agriculture (Struik et al. 2014; Droppelmann et al. 2017). Over the years, one leading trend for SI has been intercropping, which improves crop productivity by harnessing various ecosystem services below and above ground.

The cereal push-pull technology (PPT) is a form of SI companion cropping system where maize or sorghum is intercropped with leguminous fodder plants of the genus *Desmodium* [Fabaceae] while surrounded by Napier grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*) or those of the *Brachiaria* sp [all Poaceae] (Cheruiyot et al., 2021). The *Desmodium* repels (push factor) stemborer pests and *Spodoptera frugiperda* (fall armyworm) while recruiting parasitoids that serve as biological control agents for the pests (Sobhy et al. 2022; Chidawanyika et al., 2023). The grasses planted around the field serve as attractants (pull factor), which lure away the pests from the crop for oviposition, albeit with poor conditions that arrest larval development. Thus, the grasses serve as ecological traps that naturally decrease pest populations and crop damage with yield benefits (Midega et al., 2018). The leguminous *Desmodium* further provides below-ground ecosystem services by fixing nitrogen and suppressing the genus *Striga* parasitic weeds (Drinkwater et al., 2021; Ndayisaba et al., 2021).

To further sustainably intensify the PPT, we recently integrated vegetables and edible legumes to improve nutritional diversity. The resultant novel cropping system, therefore, not only aimed at achieving nutritional diversity but also sought to enhance crop productivity through the same ecosystem services essential for cereals, such as nitrogen fixation and pest management that were initially developed for cereals (Fig. 1). From the foregoing, we sought to investigate the impact of integration of kales within the VIPPT on the damage by DBM and yield in on-

farm trials. We also investigated how DBM and its parasitoid, together with those for aphids, respond to the headspace volatiles of Desmodium and Kales.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the vegetable integrated push-pull technology (VIPPT) and the associated ecosystem services.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Farmer field trials

In western Kenya, we selected 30 farmers cultivating kales in VIPPT and maize as a sole crop, with plot sizes ranging from 400 to 500 m². In the VIPPT treatment, maize's inter- and intra-row spacing was 75cm and 30cm, respectively. Single rows of kales and desmodium were then planted between the maize rows (Fig. 1). In the sole crops, kales were planted with inter and intra-row spacing of 30cm. Three weeks post-crop emergence, observations were made on 20 randomly sampled plants per plot to determine the level of aphid and DBM damage following the Likert scale. These observations were done 4 times (once per week). At the end of the 4-week pest observation period, the kales were harvested and separated according to marketable (high quality) and non-marketable (severe pest damage). The experiment was repeated for 3 seasons. We also assessed farmers' perceptions of the performance of the VIPPT with the aid of semi-structured questionnaires using Open Data Kit (ODK) software installed on Android tablets. First, a pilot study was conducted to refine the monitoring tool before the official survey. An ordered probit model, using the maximum likelihood method, was used to evaluate the factors influencing farmers' perceptions of the effectiveness of the VIPPT.

Insect behavioral responses

To test the impact of Desmodium and maize on DBM host selection, we conducted choice tests in both greenhouse (Fig. 2A) and wind tunnel bioassays (Fig. 2B). For the greenhouse bioassays, 3 treatments were established where 2 rows of potted kales (N=12) were set as sole crops (control), with other kales set between rows of maize (N=12) or Desmodium (N=12). Gravid DBM moths were then released in the greenhouse at a central release point and left for 3 days before egg counting was done. This procedure was repeated 5 times. For the wind tunnel bioassays, live plants were used for the same treatments

where the headspace volatiles were drawn into the tunnel before releasing individual moths and monitoring upward flight behavior. The procedure was repeated 18 times for each treatment. Data for oviposition preferences were regarded as count data and analyzed Using GLZ, a Poisson distribution, and an identity link function assumed in R statistical software.

Figure 2: Set-up for assaying behavioral responses of diamondback moth responses to volatiles from desmodium, maize, and kales.

A Perspex four-arm olfactometer was used to test the responses of the parasitoids to volatiles collected from the headspace of desmodium plants. First, the headspace samples (μL aliquots) were applied, using a micropipette (Drummond "microcap", Drummond Scientific Co., Broomall, PA, USA), to a piece of filter paper (5×20 mm) subsequently placed in an inlet port at the end of each Olfactometer arm. The odor was then carried by charcoal-filtered air drawn through the four arms towards the center at 260 mL min^{-1} . After that, gravid parasitoids, without prior plant exposure, were transferred individually into the central chamber of the Olfactometer using custom-made glass tubing. The time spent in each arm was recorded with "Olf" software (F. Nazzi, Udine, Italy) for 12 min. A choice test was conducted to compare insect responses to headspace samples from Desmodium against the organic solvent dichloromethane and blank control. These bioassays were replicated 11 times with a clean Olfactometer and glassware each time. The average proportion of time spent by the parasitoid in each olfactometer arm across all replications was calculated before comparisons using analysis of variances (ANOVAs).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Farmer field trials

Crop diversity is widely associated with many benefits, including pest suppression, soil health, and the recruitment of beneficial arthropods in agroecosystems (Drinkwater et al., 2021; Magrath et al., 2022; Ndayisaba et al., 2021). In our study, farmer field surveys revealed that kales integrated into the push-pull gain significant protection from the devastating DBM when planted in the full VIPPT compared to when planted as sole crops or with maize (Fig.

3). The associative resistance provided by *Desmodium* sp. has widely been documented in the context of maize-desmodium intercrops where protection against stemborers and the fall armyworm is conferred (Sobhy et al., 2022; Bass et al., 2024). However, it has yet to be demonstrated in other crops to new pest complexes. Across seasons, the protection against DBM improved more in VIPPT plots. Although this could be subject to prevailing pest pressure, we attribute this to the strengthened effect of the companion plants upon full establishment. Indeed, previous observations in maize have shown that the protection in PPT improves when the companion plants are well established. Such resistance can either be due to volatiles of *Desmodium* acting as repellants or the whole plants acting as barriers impeding direct access to the protected crop. These findings also corroborate the resource concentration hypothesis, which posits that specialist herbivorous insects tend to be abundant where their host plants are in large patches and are easily perceived (Grez and González 1995).

In all the 3 seasons of the study, the yield of kales within VIPPT had a competitive advantage over those planted as sole crops or intercropped with maize. This is likely due to the improved soil fertility and moisture conservation that is known to be prevalent in PPT (Drinkwater et al., 2021; Ndayisaba et al., 2021). Furthermore, the reduced pest infestation in VIPPT led to higher marketable yield than other treatments (Fig. 4). Such benefits were validated by farmers who rated the VIPPT as a better practice than traditional farmer practices (Fig 5).

Figure 3: Damage by diamondback moth in kales grown as sole crop, intercropped with maize and in a full vegetable integrated push-pull technology (VIPPT). Different letters above error bars denote statistically significant different groups.

Figure 4: Marketable and non-marketable yield among kales grown as sole crop, intercropped with maize and in a full vegetable integrated push-pull technology

(VIPPT). Different letters above error bars denote statistically significant different groups.

Figure 5: Gender disaggregated farmer perspectives on the effectiveness of the vegetable-integrated push-pull to control kale pests in relation to other farmer practices.

Laboratory insect behavioral responses

Desmodium has repellent properties against several Lepidopteran pests. Through a series of behavioral assays, we tested the responses of DBM to its volatiles. Our results showed significant effects of [F (2, 11) = 5.7, $p < 0.001$] *Desmodium* on host selection by gravid DBM. Oviposition rates were highest in the kales arranged separately, suggesting non-preference, as with maize pests (Figure 6). The importance of the quality of volatiles in host locations has previously been documented (Bruce and Pickett, 2011), where any disruptions are challenging for specialist herbivores such as DBM (Li et al., 2016). Here, our results strongly suggest the protection of kales by the VIPPT as supported by both pest damage and yield assessments (Figures 3 and 4). This may be attributed to the transformation of airborne volatile blends of kales when paired with *Desmodium*. Further bioassays within the wind tunnel supported this as DBM preferred kales as sole hosts compared to when they were paired with *Desmodium* (Figure 7).

The ecological complexity typical of intercropped systems is also associated with higher assemblage of natural enemies (Cardinale et al., 2003) and recruitment of parasitoids (Khan et al., 1997). Hence, we tested how *Desmodium* headspace volatiles influence the behavior of *Cotesia vestalis*, *Aphidius radii*, and *A. raphae* (Figure 8). Generally, there was a higher attraction for *Desmodium* volatiles than the control. This suggests that *Desmodium* can play a critical role in enhancing the biological control of both aphids and DBM through parasitoid recruitment.

Figure 6: Mean (\pm s.e.) number of eggs laid by 60 diamondback moths on potted kale plants arranged as sole, maize, or Desmodium. Different letters above error bars denote statistically significant different groups.

Figure 7: Wind tunnel responses of gravid diamondback moth to headspace volatiles of potted kale plants presented individually, with maize and Desmodium (n=18). Different letters above error bars denote statistically significant different groups.

Figure 8: Behavioral responses of diamondback moth (*Cotesia vestalis*) and aphid (*Aphidius radii*; *A. raphae*) parasitoids to volatiles from Desmodium plants. Different letters above error bars denote statistically significant different groups.

CONCLUSION

The current study shows intercropping in the VIPPT can protect kales against DBM through associational resistance. Although the protection mechanisms are not fully explored, our study shows that Desmodium may disrupt the host location by DBM's non-acceptance of intercropped kales. There was evidence that the Desmodium volatiles are attractive to the parasitoids of DBM and aphids, which may enhance crop protection. However, there is a need to characterize the chemical

compounds involved. Our study also shows how the VIPPT can improve yield and reduce non-consumable harvest. These attributes can increase the profitability of the enterprise. Furthermore, our study showed a substantial yield increase in VIPPT kales, likely resulting from improved soil fertility as previously documented in maize (Drinkwater et al., 2021; Ndayisaba et al., 2021). Overall, the present study provides an important platform for further innovation to improve the productivity of kales through various ecosystem services provided in intercropping in VIPPT.

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Management of Major Pests in Cabbage Production Using Vegetable Push-Pull Technology

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ABSTRACT

The push-pull technology used in the control of pests of cereal crops has not been commonly used in vegetable cropping systems. A study to evaluate the effectiveness of

various plants on their capacity to deter (push) or attract (pull) diamondback moth (DBM) and aphids in cabbage was conducted at World Vegetable Center in Arusha, Tanzania in collaboration with International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Kenya. Crops selected as push or pull candidates for DBM and aphids were: spider plant as pull crop for both DBM and aphids, onion and marigold as push crops for both DBM and aphids, and French bean sprayed with kale extract as pull crop for DBM. Nine treatments including a control in RCBD were evaluated in three replications. Data on cabbage growth parameters and yield, plant damage severity caused by DBM and aphids on both cabbage and push-pull crops were collected. While DBM occurred on cabbage at the early stages of crop development and increased steadily in population for three weeks then dropped before it increased again until harvest, aphids occurred later in the fourth week of transplanting and the population kept increasing until harvest. DBM damage severities were significantly different ($p = 0.023$) among the treatments whereas damage due to aphids wasn't ($p = 0.143$). DBM and aphid damage severities on the pull crops were so sporadic and negligible on the push crops. Treatment five (T5) produced significantly ($p = <0.001$) higher yield (total and marketable yield (191.1 and 175.4t/ha), and bigger head size (21.3cm) than T1, T4, T7 and T8 (140.3 and 99.6, 93.6 and 61.3, 74.8 and 56.8, and 60.6, 41.1t/ha respectively, and 17.7, 14.5, 13.5 and 12.5cm respectively). However, the yield (total and marketable) for T5 did not differ significantly with those of T2 (160.3 and 109.4t/ha), T3 (176.3 and 136.0t/ha), T6 (155.6 and 124.6t/ha) and T9 (control) (156.9 and 120.1t/ha). The results in this study may contribute knowledge to the global efforts to safeguard and improve the quality of environment, and safe vegetable consumption while controlling sustainably target pests effectively.

Keywords

cabbage, agro-ecology, pest control

INTRODUCTION

Ranked third after tomato and onion, cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L.) and other leafy brassicas are important vegetable crops in Tanzania (Massomo et al. 2005). Apart from their nutritional value, as reviewed by Satheesh and Fanta (2020), crucifers also have medicinal (Stefan and Ona, 2020) and soil-borne pathogen control properties (bio-fumigation) (Kumar 2017; Zuluaga et al., 2015; Laznik et al., 2014; Oliveira et al., 2011). As such, crucifers can be used in the bio-control of plant soil-borne pathogens.

Cabbage has a high water requirement, although 500mm of rainfall during the growing period is sufficient (Ernest

and Njogu 2011). Both rain-fed and irrigation cropping systems are used in cabbage production in Tanzania. As it is for crucifers, cabbage prefers soils with a pH between 5.5 and 6.5, well-drained, and an optimum air temperature between 16 and 35°C at an altitude between 700 and 2,200 meters above sea level (Ochieng et al. 2016). Depending on the type of variety, cabbage yield varies. For the variety Gloria F1 used in this study, the yield is reported to reach 15 to 30 tonnes per acre (37.1 to 74.1 t/ha) (Ochieng et al. 2016) and 74.1 to 123.6 t/ha (Simlaw Seeds Company Limited, 2020). According to Syngenta, the variety Gloria F1 yields up to 284.2 t/ha (Farmpays, 2023).

Women in both rural and urban areas in Tanzania have been reported to involve themselves in either the production or small-scale trading of vegetables (including cabbage) for income. The horticulture subsector in the country accounts for 26.7% of the GDP and employs most of the population (Ekka and Mjawa, 2020; Everaarts et al., 2014; HODECT, 2010). Vegetables contribute to poverty alleviation among individuals, households, and the nation.

However, cabbage production in Tanzania is a constraint, among other factors, by pests and diseases, as is the case in all cabbage-producing places all over the world (Mayanglambam et al., 2021; Segura and Lardizábal, 2013; Ernest and Njogu 2011; Masomo et al., 2005). Apart from diseases, the major insect pests devastating cabbage crop in Africa are: diamondback moth (*Plutella xylostella*), cabbage aphid (*Brevicoryne brassicae*), green peach aphids (*Myzus persicae*), Indian Mustard Aphid (*Lipaphis erysimi pseudobrassicae*), cabbage cluster caterpillar (*Crociodolomia pavonana*), cabbage webworm (*Helula undalis*), cabbage looper (*Trichoplusia ni*) and cabbage white butterfly (*Pieris brassicae*) (Mbogho et al., 2021; Fening et al., 2020; Baidoo and Mochiah, 2016; Baidoo and Adam, 2012). The most destructive pest is *P. xylostella*, which can cause yield loss of up to 100% if the crop is severely infested (Furlong et al., 2013).

Synthetic chemical pesticides have long been the primary means of controlling crop pests on crops, which has resulted in diverse problems such as adverse environmental effects on non-target organisms and a build-up of insecticide resistance by the pests (Tudi et al., 2021; Mpumi et al., 2020; Foster et al., 2007). Consequently, the ill-health effects on the environment and the untargeted organisms caused by chemical synthetic pesticides are increasingly raising concerns (Ali et al., 2020; Boni et al., 2020; Kapeleka et al., 2020; Godwin, 2019; Lekei et al., 2014) which call for alternative control methods which are cost-effective, biodegradable, low toxic effect on non-target organisms and eco-friendly (Rajashekar, 2021; Inglis et al., 2001; Lacey et al., 2015).

Several alternative means, like using biological control techniques such as plant-based extracts, biopesticides, live

organisms, etc., with integrated pest management packages, have been used to control pests on crucifers in both organic and conventional agriculture (Forchibe, et al., 2023; Mayanglambam, 2021; Dara, 2019; Shah, et al., 2019; Razek, 2003). The push-pull is a relatively new technology (Bhattacharyya, 2017) that is based on the use of repellent and attractive stimuli (habit manipulation/management) in integrated pest management (IPM) on crops and was first conceived by Pyke et al. (1987). It was later formalized and refined by Miller and Cowles (1990). Since then, technology has been used to control pests, mainly on cereal crops and less on vegetable crops (Akter et al., 2019; Hassanali, 2008; Cook, 2007).

This study aimed to validate the push-pull technology to control pests on crucifers, enhance intercropping, enhance eco-friendly and sustainable IPM technologies, and upscale improved varieties in Tanzania. To reach this primary objective, a study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of various plants on their capacity to deter (push) or attract (pull) diamondback moth (DBM) and aphids in cabbage crops. This technology is expected to provide a more ecologically-friendlier vegetable production system than the conventional pest control methods commonly used worldwide. The approach may contribute knowledge to global efforts to safeguard and generally improve the quality of the environment, as well as safe vegetable production and consumption while controlling the target pests sustainably and effectively.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As an on-station activity, the study was conducted at the World Vegetable Center (WorldVeg), Eastern and Southern Africa (ESA) premises in Arusha, Tanzania, in collaboration with the International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (icipe) in Nairobi, Kenya. The activities started (from land preparation to harvest) between October 2022 and January 2023.

Cabbage variety Gloria F1 and the crops used as push and pull candidates were selected based on field experiences, baseline survey, and some information obtained from the literature (Zhu et al., 2020 with some modifications). While Zhu et al. (2020) used cabbage extract sprayed on faba bean to attract DBM, we used African kale as a source of leaves for extraction in this study. This crop ensures a continuous supply of leaves as it keeps on producing new leaves after picking the matured ones; we used French bean because it is plentifully available compared to faba bean, which was unavailable on time. Table 1 below shows the crops used in this study and the respective target pests. The plants were irrigated using a drip system (16mm diameter, 2L/hr discharge, 0.4mm wall thickness), twice to three times a week, depending on the weather conditions, and

there were no other means of pest control applied after transplanting.

Table 1: Rate of plant damage (means of 10 readings of data collection) by DBM and aphids on both cabbage and push-pull crops over the growing period

Treatment	Pest damage severity (%) per crop					
	Aphids on Cabbage	Aphids on Pull crops	Aphids on Push crops	DBM on Pull crops	DBM on Push crops	DBM on Cabbage
T1	3.2	1.6	0	0.3	0	13.5
T2	3.6	2.1	0	0.6	0	16
T3	3.7	0	0	0	0.1	12.2
T4	4.6	0	0	0	0.1	16.9
T5	3.3	0.1	0	0	0.2	10.7
T6	3.3	5	0	0	0	10.6
T7	1.6	1.3	0	0	0.2	11.8
T8	7.4	4.2	0	0	0.2	16.2
T9	5.3	0	0	0	0	12.1
Mean	4	1.6	0	0.1	0.2	13.3
Probability	0.143	<0.001	-	<0.001	0.92	0.023
SED (+-)	1.7	0.5	-	0.02	0.2	1.92
LSD (5%)	3.6	1.06	-	0.03	0.42	4.06

Note: T1 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T2 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T3 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (onion for both DBM and aphid), T4 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphid), T5 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T6 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T7 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T8 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T9 = Main crop (cabbage) only (without push or pull crops-control treatment)

Cabbage seed was purchased from a reliable trader in Arusha, sown in peat-moss in 66-hole nursery trays, and transplanted on the 18th of October, 2022. From experience, the push and pull crops (onion, French bean, marigold, and spider plant) were planted/sown on staggering dates to synchronize with the cabbage transplanting date. As such, cabbage was transplanted when the push-pull plants were almost the same size as cabbage and had already been established on the ground. French bean, marigold, and spider plants were sown directly in the experimental plots, while onion was first sown in similar (as for cabbage - above) medium and nursery trays, then transplanted. All planting materials (seeds) of the push-pull crops were sourced from the WorldVeg's Gene Bank in Arusha. African kale (*Brassica oleracea*) was transplanted four weeks before the other crops to give it time to put up enough leaves to be picked for extraction of the plant content.

Matured African kale leaves were harvested from the field, washed in tap water to remove dirt, rinsed in distilled water, and placed on a wire mesh to drain the water. Then 100g of the leaves were placed in a 1.5-liter flask and placed in a boiling water bath for one minute, then quickly transferred to ice and cooled to room temperature, and then blended using a laboratory blender (YON, model no. VSBT 04 BCK) in 250mls of distilled water, then added distilled water to make a total of 1000mls. The mixture was then filtered using a clean sterile cotton cloth, and the filtrate was ready for spraying on the French bean plants or stored in the refrigerator at 4°C if it wasn't used immediately (Zhu et al. 2020). The filtrate did not exceed 24 hours in storage. Without further dilution, the filtrate was sprayed on the French bean plants using a knapsack sprayer (Jacto XP 16L – OSHO Company Ltd) once a week.

The experimental design was the randomized complete block design (RCBD) with nine treatments, replicated three times. Below is the list of the treatments

1. Treatment 1 (T1) – Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid)
2. Treatment 2 (T2) – Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM)
3. Treatment 3 (T3) – Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (onion for both DBM and aphid)
4. Treatment 4 (T4) – Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphid)
5. Treatment 5 (T5) – Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM)
6. Treatment 6 (T6) – Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid)
7. Treatment 7 (T7) – Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM)
8. Treatment 8 (T8) – Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid)
9. Treatment 9 (T9) – Main crop (cabbage) only (without push or pull crops-control treatment)

Each treatment was planted in a plot of 4.5 by 1.2 m (5.4 m²), and each plot was separated by 8m on all sides. There were two rows of cabbage in each plot separated by 0.6 m, and each row had 15 plants with 30 cm spacing within the row (Simlaw Seeds Company Limited, 2020). In the middle of the cabbage rows, a double line of a push crop was planted (where it was required), and the pull plants (where needed) were planted in double rows, 0.5 m from and at all sides of the plot. Where the push or pull plants were not required, the respective space was left empty. Nothing was planted in the control plots as push or pull crops, so their respective places remained empty.

Weekly data collection for 10 consecutive weeks on cabbage started three weeks after transplanting, involving counting the number of leaves, measuring the diameter of the plant canopy (canopy width/spread), and scoring for damage severity by DBM and aphids. The damage severity score caused by the pests was calculated using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents no damage while 5 represents the highest damage by the pest. The severity score scale is described as follows:

- 1 = No damage
- 2 = Mild damage (1 - 20% of the plant is damaged)
- 3 = Medium damage (21 - 50% of the plant is damaged)
- 4 = Severe damage (51 - 70% of the plant is damaged)
- 5 = Very severe damage (71 - 100% of the plant is damaged)

Shortly before harvest, a Farmers' Field Day was conducted to introduce the technology to farmers and ask them to evaluate the quality of the cabbage in each treatment without knowing the distribution of the treatments to avoid bias. The farmers used a score scale of zero to four to evaluate the crop where 0 represents very

poor, 1 represents poor, 2 represents good, 3 represents very good and 4 represents excellent. The fresh weight of 20 individual cabbage heads (plants) from the middle of each experimental plot was recorded at harvest. Then, they were sorted into two categories: marketable (without or with very minimum pest damage) and non-marketable (with pest damage) heads, recording their number and weight. The total weight per experimental plot recorded in kg was converted into tonnes per hectare.

The data were analyzed by GenStat (VSN International (VSNi)) on GLM ANOVA to find the significance of the observed differences amongst the treatments, and all pairwise multiple comparison procedures (Holm-Sidak method) tests with an overall significance level at $P = 0.05$ were conducted on the treatments with significant differences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Growth parameters - number of leaves and the plant canopy width/spread) the means of 10 data collection dates)

All nine treatments showed significant differences, but in pairwise multiple comparisons, no pair significantly differed from the other (Figure 1). This may indicate that the observed differences in the number of leaves and the size of the plant canopy are so general that, in combination, the treatments tend to vary. Still, there is no consistency when they are separated. Since all the other growing conditions given to the plants, like irrigation and weeding, were similar in all treatments, these variations are probably brought about by the effects of the plant combination, providing a synergistic effect to leverage the impact of extrinsic growth factors such as light, aeration pests, and diseases. However, in the treatments with

marigold as a push crop (T4, T7, and T8), the number of leaves and plant canopy size was observed to be the minimum compared to the other treatments (T1, T2, T3,

T5, T6, and T9), possibly due to resource (space, light, and nutrients) competition as marigold grew more vigorously and spread wide to partially cover the cabbage canopy.

Figure 1: Growth characteristics over the growing period of cabbage grown in combination with other crops in the push-pull technology. T1 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T2 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T3 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (onion for both DBM and aphid), T4 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphid), T5 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T6 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T7 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T8 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T9 = Main crop (cabbage) only (without push or pull crops-control treatment)

Rate of plant damage by DBM and aphids on both cabbage and push-pull crops over the growing period

The percentage damage of the plants by both DBM and aphids did not differ significantly among the nine treatments on both cabbage and the push-pull crops (Figure 2). The damage on the push-pull crops was negligible, with a tendency to be more visible on the pull than on the push crops, especially spider plants. Some damage was observed on the beans sprayed with kale extract (another pull crop). However, this was sporadic and could be compromised with leaf miner damage observed in the field, which could easily be confused with DBM damage during data collection, as the French bean is not a host of DBM. In this case, the French bean becomes a false host to DBM due to the presence of crucifer plants' volatile compounds due to the kale extract sprayed on them, which attracts DBM and, contrary, becomes its dead-end as the DBM eggs laid on the plants

do not develop into adults (Zhu et al., 2020). Studies elsewhere indicate that DBM is the most important pest on crucifers than other pests, including aphids (Fening et al., 2020; Baidoo and Mochiah, 2016; Baidoo and Adam, 2012). However, in this study, this fact is not vividly depicted, although by general observation, it seemed DBM damage on the cabbage was comparatively more prominent compared to aphids, whereas damage by aphids appeared to be more prominent in the pull crops compared to DBM (Figure 2). This may be attributed to the fact that both pests had a wider range of host choices such that their visits and effects were shared between the cabbage and the two pull crops, the spider plant and the French bean sprayed with kale extract. As for the push crops (onion and marigold), we did not expect to have them damaged by the pests as they are their deterrents, so their presence on these plants could have been for temporary rest and not for feeding purposes and the sporadic damages observed could have possibly been caused by other insects/organisms.

Figure 2: Cabbage total and marketable yields and cabbage head size in a push-pull technology against DBM and aphids (bars with similar color and triangular points with different letters are significantly different while those with similar letters are not). T1 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T2 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T3 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (onion for both DBM and aphid), T4 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphid), T5 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T6 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T7 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T8 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T9 = Main crop (cabbage) only (without push or pull crops-control treatment)

The occurrence and dynamics of DBM and aphids (damages) over the crop growing duration

As for the occurrence and dynamics of DBM and aphids (damages) over the crop growing duration, aphids (and hence their damages) appeared in the middle of the crop growing duration and continuously built up until harvest (Table 2). On the contrary, DBM (damages) started at the

early stages of the crops and built up to a maximum over 3 weeks, then dropped drastically, remained at a minimum for about 5 weeks, then increased continuously until harvest (Table 3). This phenomenon may be caused by the presence of rainfall, which came up at the end of November through the end of December 2022 and may have acted as a control of the insects' population as has been the case reported in other studies (Abbasi et al., 2019; Kobori and Amano, 2003; Kaakeh and Dutcher, 1993).

Table 2: Rate of aphid damage (severity) on cabbage on each day of data collection in a push-pull technology trial

Treatment	Severity (%) of plant damage by aphids by date of data collection									
	10-Nov-22	17-Nov-22	24-Nov-22	28-Nov-22	06-Dec-22	13-Dec-22	20-Dec-22	27-Dec-22	03-Jan-23	11-Jan-23
T1	0	0	0	0	0	2.8	2.5	1	7.8	16.7
T2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.7	1.4	15.8	13.2
T3	0	0	0	1.2	0	1.2	1.4	3.1	9.4	16.6
T4	0	0	0	0	0	0.7	0.7	5.6	10.3	19.3
T5	0	0	0	0	0	2.4	1.4	6.5	9.8	12.7
T6	0	0	0	1.2	0.3	0.3	2.1	4.6	6.2	15.2
T7	0	0	0	0	0.7	1.9	2.1	2.1	2.9	5.5
T8	0	0	0	0	0.3	2.2	2.8	8.6	17.9	41.3
T9	0	0	0	0	1.9	2.2	4.2	4.3	17.4	21.9

Mean	0	0	0	0.3	0.4	1.6	2	4.1	10.8	18.1
Probability	-	-	-	0.594	0.594	0.92	0.239	0.545	0.259	0.099
SED (+-)	0	0	0	0.81	1	1.96	1.29	3.74	6.14	9.63
LSD (5%)	-	-	-	1.72	2.11	4.16	2.73	7.93	13.02	20.42

Note: T1 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T2 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T3 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (onion for both DBM and aphid), T4 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphid), T5 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T6 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T7 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T8 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T9 = Main crop (cabbage) only (without push or pull crops-control treatment)

Table 3: Rate of DBM damage (severity) on cabbage on each day of data collection

Treatment	Severity (%) of plant damage by DBM by date of data collection									
	10- Nov-22	17- Nov-22	24- Nov-22	28- Nov-22	06- Dec-22	13- Dec-22	20- Dec-22	27- Dec-22	03- Jan-23	11- Jan-23
T1	26.5	37.7	33	6	8.6	3.7	3.5	4	2.9	3.1
T2	30.2	41.3	40.5	8.2	8.2	4.8	4.1	4.5	7.8	5.6
T3	18.3	34.3	35.3	9.4	5.6	5.3	3.1	4.1	2	0
T4	21.1	36	30.3	8.4	8.1	10.6	7.4	9.6	19.7	20
T5	13.9	29.9	26.9	6.6	5.3	2.2	4.7	3.6	4	4.4
T6	20.8	28.6	23.8	6.5	6.1	3.6	2.6	2.7	1.9	6.4
T7	6.9	24.3	34.8	4.5	5.6	2.8	1.8	2.8	12	18.8
T8	16.4	32.7	40.5	5.2	4.9	2.8	2.8	6.6	15.3	29.9
T9	15.2	30.5	37.2	9.8	4.7	3.5	2.6	2.9	4.1	6.1
Mean	18.8	32.8	33.6	7.2	6.3	4.4	3.6	4.5	7.8	10.5
Probability.	0.053	0.177	0.204	0.477	0.867	0.18	0.331	0.18	0.011	0.001
SED (+-)	6.12	5.6	6.45	2.63	3.18	2.76	2.11	2.46	4.69	5.86
LSD (5%)	12.98	11.87	13.68	5.57	6.75	5.85	4.47	5.21	9.93	12.43

Note: T1 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T2 = Main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T3 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (onion for both DBM and aphid), T4 = Main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphid), T5 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T6 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T7 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), T8 = Main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid), T9 = Main crop (cabbage) only (without push or pull crops-control treatment)

Cabbage total and marketable yields and head size at harvest

Treatment five (T5) in which plant combination was the main crop (cabbage) + push crop (onion) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), produced significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher yield (total and marketable yields, 191.1 and 175.4t/ha) and bigger head size (21.3cm) than treatments one (T1), four (T4), seven

(T7) and eight (T8) (140.3 and 99.6, 93.6 and 61.3, 74.8 and 56.8, and 60.6, 41.1t/ha respectively and 17.7, 14.5, 13.5 and 12.5cm respectively) (Figures 1 and 2). The combination of plants was: main crop (cabbage) + only pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid) for T1, main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphid) for T4, main crop (cabbage) + push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphids) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM) for T7 and main

crop (cabbage) + push (marigold for both DBM and aphids) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid) for T8 (Figure 3). The yield (total and marketable) for T5 (191.1 and 175.4t/ha) did not differ significantly from those of T2 (160.3 and 109.4t/ha), T3 (176.3 and 136.0t/ha), T6 (155.6 and 124.6t/ha) and T9 (control) (156.9 and 120.1t/ha). However, T5 produced a significantly higher marketable yield than T2 (Figure 3).

Treatment 4 with main crop (cabbage) + only push crop (marigold for both DBM and aphid), T7 with main crop (cabbage) + push (marigold) + pull crop (French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM), and T8 with main crop (cabbage) + push (marigold for both DBM and aphid) + pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid) produced significantly ($p = <0.001$) the least yield (total and marketable) (93.6 and 61.3, 74.8 and 56.8, and 60.8 and 41.1t/ha respectively) and the smallest head size (14.5, 13.5 and 12.5cm respectively) than all the other treatments (Figure 3). The plant combination in each of these treatments involved marigold as a push crop. It seems that the presence of marigolds produced a challenge to cabbage in the form of a competition for resources, possibly light, minerals, water, and air since marigold was observed to grow more vigorously than cabbage and partially covered the sides of the cabbage plants. As such, the cabbage plants might have been deprived of sufficient resources, which resulted in reduced growth and, consequently, less biomass production than marigolds. Comparatively, T1 (main crop -cabbage) + only pull crop (spider plant for both DBM and aphid) and T2 (main crop + only pull crop - French bean sprayed with kale extract for DBM) produced the second smaller head size (17.7 and 18.4cm, respectively) as compared to treatments T3, T5, and T6. Unexpectedly, T9 (control experiment without any of the push and pull crops) did not differ in performance (156.9t/ha as total and 120.1t/ha as marketable yield and 19.1cm head size) from the best-performing treatments (T2, T3, T5, T6 above) (Figure 3). This phenomenon may be due to a holistic effect of the presence of the pus-pull crops in that field, such that this combination of plants creates an ecological niche that affects the area synergistically and hence reduces the population and/or the efficiency of the pests to destroy the main crop (cabbage) to an extent that would have been if they were not present.

Moreover, we do not know the coverage of the volatile compounds in the push-and-pull plants to deter or attract pests effectively. More studies are needed to determine the types of volatile compounds found in the push-pull plants used in this study and the distance (coverage) from which the two types of pests (DBM and the aphids) can detect them. The results of such analyses can help determine the distances that the push and pull plants are supposed to be planted from the main crop (cabbage) to control the pests efficiently. This knowledge can also help avoid resource

competition between the main crop and the push and pull crops, as this study has suspected that marigold is a push crop for both DBM and aphids, as explained above.

When comparing the performance of the cabbage variety Gloria F1 used in this study, each of the nine treatments generally realized yield within the ranges reported by Syngenta (the variety's producer) and in other studies elsewhere (Farm Pays, 2023; Simlaw Seeds Company Limited, 2020; Ochieng et al. 2016) (Figure 3).

Cabbage quality evaluation by farmers during Farmers' Field Day shortly before harvest

Of the 31 farmers who attended a farmers' field day conducted shortly before harvesting the cabbage, 21 were asked to evaluate the crop according to their preferences using a score scale described in the Materials and Methods chapter above. Farmers' preferences did not vary among the nine treatments, including the control experiment, ranking their quality very good (Figure 4). This suggested that most of the heads harvested in this study would fetch a better price in the face of sellers and consumers. This was further confirmed by retail sellers who were asked (informally) to rank the harvest (data not shown), and they admitted to being ready to buy the marketable big heads at the market price and the small heads at half of the big-sized heads price if they were for business.

According to the vegetable retail sellers, the average farmgate price for big heads was Tanzanian Shillings (T.Shs.) 500.00 per head, equivalent to USD 0.21. If we were to sell the cabbage harvested, the traders would buy the big marketable heads at T.Shs. 1000.00 per head (USD 0.43) and the small heads at T.Shs. 500.00 (USD 0.215). According to the traders, the suggested price (T.Shs. 1000 and 500) is higher than the average farmgate price (T.Shs. 500) because our cabbage was produced without the use of synthetic chemical pesticides, so it is considered to be of higher quality than those sprayed with synthetic chemical pesticides. Since there were 308 big heads and 96 small heads, the total income would have been T.Shs. 356,000.00 (USD 151.49) if the cabbages were sold. This equals USD 10,390.26 per hectare (our trial area was 0.01458ha). However, this income projection needs a formal experimental study to verify the figures.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the performance of cabbage (main crop) in combination with onion as push crop and French bean sprayed with kale extract and spider plant as both pull crops for both DBM and aphids was better (higher yield

and less pest damage) than when it was in combination with marigold as a push crop for the two types of pests. It is therefore recommended to repeat this combination in an on-station trial in the 2023/24 season to validate the results obtained in this study before the technology is carried forward to on-farm trials on farmers' fields succeeded by scaling up to cabbage producers in various places. Marigold, as a push crop, compromises the growth of cabbage by possibly causing competition for resources with cabbage due to its big canopy, which was observed to cover the cabbage plants partially and hence its lower performance.

However, more studies are needed to identify the composition of volatile compounds found in all the push and pull plants used in this study and to determine the distance from which the pests can detect the volatile compounds that are known to be the deterrents or attractants of the pests in the push or pull context respectively. Such study may give results to qualify each push and pull plant in terms of, among other things, the proper distance the push and pull plants should be planted from the main crop and perhaps qualify the suitability of marigold, which did not appear to be a good candidate as a push plant in this study.

In general, the ecological niche provided by combining all the treatments (the push and pull crops) in the experimental site may have contributed synergistically to controlling the two types of pests on cabbage in all treatments. This may have been attributed to the unexpectedly good performance of the cabbage plants in the control plots. This study has indicated that the push-pull technology provides a more ecologically-friendlier vegetable production system than the conventional pest control methods commonly used worldwide. As such, this technology contributes knowledge to the global efforts to safeguard and generally improve the quality of the environment and ensure safe vegetable consumption while controlling sustainably and effectively targeting pests.

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The Larvae of *Phyllotreta striolata* Share the Same Olfactory Cues for Locating Brassicaceae Plants with Conspecific Adults

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ABSTRACT

The sophisticated olfactory system of insects plays crucial roles in host plant location. Compared with comprehensive studies on the molecular mechanisms of olfactory cue detection in lepidopteran moths, little is known about how coleopteran beetles detect host plant cues. *Phyllotreta striolata* is a devastating coleopteran pest of Brassicaceae crops, and its larvae feed on roots underground, while its adults destroy leaves aboveground. In this study, we focus on the molecular basis of olfactory cue detection in *P. striolata* and attempt to determine whether *P. striolata* larvae share the same specific olfactory cues for host plant location with conspecific adults and whether the detection mechanism is conserved. A two-choice behavioral bioassay was conducted to examine the behavioral responses of *P. striolata* to different types of isothiocyanates, which are the characteristic volatiles of Brassicaceae crops. The results showed that both *P. striolata* adults and larvae were attracted by allyl isothiocyanates, although adults showed a broader behavioral response range. The transcriptome sequencing of *P. striolata* adults and larvae was performed, and 157 chemosensory genes were identified, among which 6 OBPs, 2 CSPs, 1 OR, 1 IR, and 1 GR were found to be preferentially expressed in both *P. striolata* adults and larvae. Functional studies of PstrOBP9, PstrOBP13, and PstrOBP17, three of the six OBPs that were highly expressed in both adults and larvae, revealed that PstrOBP9 firmly bound allyl isothiocyanates and eight other isothiocyanates. These findings demonstrated that *P. striolata* larvae and adults could employ the same olfactory proteins to detect specific plant volatiles for host location, providing a new perspective on developing environmentally friendly pest management targeting both *P. striolata* adults and larvae.

Keywords

Isothiocyanates; Odorant-binding proteins; Host plant location; olfaction; behavioral responses

INTRODUCTION

Plant volatiles play a crucial role in coevolution between plants and herbivorous insects (Stotz et al., 1999; Clavijo McCormick et al., 2014; Pérez-Hedo et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2022). Some can defend plants against herbivorous insect attacks by inhibiting oviposition and feeding and attracting natural enemies (Paré and Tumlinson, 1999). However, herbivorous insects have evolved sophisticated adaptations to help them perform their nutritional and reproductive functions driven by plant volatiles (Clavijo McCormick et al., 2014). An exciting type of evolution has been found in some oligophagous insects, such as Brassicales specialist herbivores, which use certain

defense compounds as symbolic signals to identify host plants for oviposition and feeding (Hopkins et al., 2008).

Isothiocyanates (ITCs) are particular volatiles from Brassicaceae plants released from the secondary compound glucosinolates hydrolysis by endogenous β -thioglucosidase enzymes (myrosinases) when plant tissue is damaged. They are usually repellent and toxic to many pests, yet are generally thought to play a significant role in the long-distance location of host plants of Brassicales specialists from insect groups including Coleoptera (Vincent and Stewart, 1984; Tóth et al., 2007), Lepidoptera (Renwick et al., 2006), Diptera (Finch, 1978), Hemiptera (Demirel and Cranshaw, 2006) and so on. Within Lepidoptera, several ITCs are involved in the accurate location of oviposition sites by female adults of *Plutella xylostella* (Renwick et al., 2006). In Coleoptera, allyl isothiocyanate (*allyl ITC*) acts not only as a feeding and oviposition stimulant but also as an attractant for flea beetle adults of the genus *Phyllotreta* (e.g., *Phyllotreta striolata* and *Phyllotreta cruciferae*) in the field (Feeny et al., 1970; Pivnick et al., 1992). Within Diptera, *Hylemya brassicae* adults can be trapped with *allyl ITC* baits as effectively as fresh Brassicaceae plants in fields (Eckenrode and Arn, 1972). ITCs are not only found in the foliage of Brassicaceae but have also been detected in roots. For instance, ITCs were detected in the root exudates of the Brassicaceae weed species *Rorippa indica* (Yamane et al., 1992). The larvae of three vegetable root fly pests, *Delia radicum*, *Delia floralis*, and *Delia antique*, are also attracted to *allyl ITC* underground (Ross and Anderson, 1992), suggesting that it may be related to the food-seeking behavior of larvae. These studies showed that ITCs are important signal compounds for host location in the nutrition-seeking and reproductive activities of Brassicales specialist herbivores and have been applied as a trapping strategy for pests in the field.

The recognition of ITCs to guide the location of host plants is mediated by a sophisticated olfactory system in Brassicales specialists. The antennae are the primary olfactory organs of adult insects that receive and identify ITCs to induce an electrical signal reaction. In *P. xylostella* adults, ITCs can elicit age-dependent and female-biased electroantennogram (EAG) responses in antennae (Wu et al., 2020), providing electrophysiological evidence of the identity of oviposition signal compounds. A recent study showed that the molecular basis of oviposition preference in moths based on three ITCs (iberberin, 4-pentenyl ITC, and phenylethyl ITC) is governed by two female antenna-biased olfactory genes (Liu et al., 2020). In *Scaptomyza flava* adults, olfactory receptor neurons (ORNs) located in basiconic and trichoid sensilla are sensitive to butyl ITC, which could mediate olfactory orientation in Brassicales specialized flies (Matsunaga et al., 2022). In *P. striolata* adults, it has been reported that allyl ITC, 3-butenyl ITC, and 4-pentenyl ITC presented in Brassica juncea can elicit

EAG responses (Beran et al., 2011). However, it is worth noting that although olfactory mechanisms for the recognition of ITCs have been characterized in adults of specialist insect species, there is a lack of clarity regarding how the larvae of these specialists perceive ITCs, which has delayed the comprehensive understanding of the interactions of Brassicales specialists with their host plants.

In the peripheral olfactory system of insects, two kinds of protein families: soluble binding proteins, including odorant-binding proteins (OBPs) and chemosensory proteins (CSPs) in the lymph of chemosensilla, and chemosensory membrane proteins, such as odorant receptors (ORs), ionotropic receptors (IRs), gustatory receptors (GRs) and sensory neuron membrane proteins (SNMPs) on the dendritic membrane, have been proven to be involved in this process and represent pest control targets for environmentally friendly approaches (Zhou, 2010; Suh et al., 2014). OBPs are the first physiological components that bind to an odor molecule and have been proven to be involved in detecting relevant chemical signals, such as host plant volatiles and sex pheromones (Brito et al., 2016). Insect OBPs are small polypeptides that form a hydrophobic binding cavity involving several α -helical domains and can be divided into four main classes: classic OBPs, minus-C OBPs, plus-C OBPs, and antennal binding protein (ABP) (Pelosi et al., 2018). The majority of OBP studies are focused on the perceptual function of adults (Venthur and Zhou, 2018), while some studies have also been performed on larval OBPs (Zhu et al., 2016; Ma et al., 2022), but a comprehensive comparison of the functional divergence of adult and larval OBPs is lacking. Additionally, no OBPs that may specifically bind ITCs have been found in Brassicales specialists.

P. striolata (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) is an oligophagous pest that mainly attacks Brassica oilseed crops and vegetables and is widely distributed in many regions, such as North America, Europe, Asia, and Africa (Soroka, 2013; Reddy, 2017). Notably, *P. striolata* adults attack aboveground plant leaves, while their soil-dwelling larvae consume belowground roots (Olson and Knodel, 2002). The crypticity of larvae causing damage makes their prevention and control complex, and traditional chemical control measures are rarely effective. Additionally, this feature of feeding both *P. striolata* adults and larvae differs from the situation in Lepidopteran pests, making *P. striolata* an ideal study species for gaining insight into patterns of host location in adults versus larvae. *Allyl ITC* has long been a crucial cue that assists *P. striolata* adults in locating their host plants (Tóth et al., 2007). However, no ITCs related to the location of host plant roots by *P. striolata* larvae have been found. Although 32 *PstrOBP* genes have been identified in adults of *P. striolata* by using transcriptome sequencing (Wu et al., 2016), it is not clear which *PstrOBPs* are expressed in

larvae. Additionally, the functions of PstrOBPs have not been characterized, and the mode of ITC detection by PstrOBPs remains unknown. To reveal the olfactory perception mechanism of ITCs in adults and larvae of *P. striolata*, we first studied how ITCs manipulate the behavioral responses of *P. striolata* adults and larvae in laboratory behavior assays and then identified chemosensory genes and compared their distribution characteristics in adults and larvae by transcriptome sequencing and quantitative real-time PCR (qRT-PCR) analysis. Additionally, we verified the function of PstrOBPs expressed specifically in adults or both adults and larvae by heterologous expression and fluorescence competitive binding assays. Finally, our results demonstrate that the PstrOBP9 gene, encoding protein-bound ITCs, is highly expressed in both adults and larvae and provides a new perspective on the functional divergence of olfactory perception between adults and larvae.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Insect rearing and behavioral bioassay

P. striolata were collected from Brassica crop fields in the Baiyun District, Guangzhou City, Guangdong Province, China. The collected insects were reared in a laboratory on Chinese cabbage seedlings at $26 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with a 16:8 h light:dark photoperiod. The adults laid eggs on a moist black cloth. After the eggs hatched, the larvae were raised with radish slices until pupation.

The behavioral responses of *P. striolata* adults to ITCs were examined in a two-choice experiment using a Y-tube olfactometer. The olfactometer comprised a 1.5-cm i.d. clear glass tube with two 10-cm-long lateral arms and a 10-cm-long central arm joined at a Y-junction. Charcoal-filtered air entered the lateral arm (treatment (T) and control (C)) and exited the central arm (release (R)) at a rate of 0.2 L/min. A 10 ml flask was filled with filter paper (5×0.5 cm) moistened with 10 microliters of a dilution of a chemical substance (T) mixed with mineral oil or mineral oil alone (C) by pipetting. In these experiments, adults were given the option of T or C. A good reaction was noted if the test beetle moved 3 cm into the T or C arm and remained there for more than 5 s. After three minutes, if the beetle did not make a clear choice, it was recorded as showing no reaction. In the adult behavioral bioassays, 50 duplicates of each treatment were examined.

Before starting the behavioral assay, the first-instar larvae of *P. striolata* were starved for three hours. To avoid light influence, the tests of larvae to isothiocyanates were conducted in a 90 mm-diameter plastic container in a dark environment. Five larvae were placed in the center of the container as the starting position, and chemical substances (T) and mineral oil (C) were placed on radish slices ($10 \times$

10 mm) with 10 microliters of a dilution (mixed with mineral oil) on both sides of the container. Every three minutes, the direction in which the larvae were picked was recorded, and a chi-square analysis with a 50:50 distribution was performed to determine the preference of beetles between treatments and controls. All bioassays were kept at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $70 \pm 5\%$ RH between 09:00 and 17:00 h. In the larval behavioral bioassays, 30 duplicates of each treatment were examined.

RNA extraction, library construction, and Illumina sequencing

For transcriptome sequencing of *P. striolata*, we collected 50 3-5-day-old adults, 50 second-instar larvae, and 50 pupae in each replicate, and a total of three independent biological replications were performed. Tissue samples were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and then stored at -80°C until further use. The total RNA of collected tissue samples was isolated with TRIzol reagent (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions. The purity of the RNA samples was determined on a NanoDrop[®] spectrophotometer (IMPLEN, CA, USA), and RNA integrity was checked using the RNA Nano 6000 Assay Kit of the Agilent Bioanalyzer 2100 system (Agilent Technologies, CA, USA).

The cDNA library was constructed using the NEBNext[®] Ultra[™] RNA Library Prep Kit for IlluminaVR (NEB, Beverly, MA, USA). First, we obtained purified mRNA from total RNA using poly-T Oligo-bound magnetic beads. First-strand cDNA was synthesized using M-MuLV Reverse Transcriptase (RNase H-) and random hexamer primers. Second-strand cDNA synthesis was subsequently performed using RNase H and DNA polymerase I. To select cDNA fragments of 150-200 bp in length, the library fragments were purified with the AMPure XP system (Beckman Coulter, Beverly, MA, USA). The clustering of the index-coded samples was performed on a cBot Cluster Generation System using the TruSeq PE Cluster Kit v3-cBot-HS (Illumina). After cluster generation, the prepared library was sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq[™] 2500 platform, and paired-end reads were generated.

De novo assembly and gene annotation

Clean data were obtained by removing reads containing adapters, poly-N sequences, and low-quality reads from the raw data. The left files from the samples were pooled into one large left.fq file and the right files were pooled into one large right.fq file. Transcriptome assembly was accomplished based on left.fq and right.fq using TRINITY (Grabherr et al., 2011) with min_kmer_cov set to 2 by default, and all of the other parameters were also set to the defaults.

Gene function was annotated based on the following databases: Nr (NCBI nonredundant protein sequences); Nt (NCBI nonredundant nucleotide sequences); Pfam (Protein family); KOG/COG (Clusters of Orthologous Groups of proteins); Swiss-Prot (a manually annotated and reviewed protein sequence database); KO (KEGG Ortholog database); and GO (Gene Ontology).

Identification of differentially expressed genes

The three groups' differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were analyzed using the DESeq R package (1.10.1). First, the clean reads were mapped back onto the transcriptomic unigenes. Then, the number of clean reads for each mapped gene was extracted from the mapping results and used to assess the gene expression level following the FPKM (expected number of fragments per kilobase of transcript sequence per million base pairs sequenced) methods. FPKM values were calculated using the formula $FPKM(A) = (1,000,000 \times C \times 61,000) / (N \times L)$, where FPKM (A) is the expression of gene A, C is the number of reads that are uniquely aligned to gene A, N is the total number of reads that are uniquely aligned to all unigenes, and L is the number of bases in gene A. Genes with FPKM >0.3 were considered to be reliably expressed in the transcriptome without a genomic reference.

To compare the differences in gene expression in the three groups, a model based on the negative binomial distribution was used to provide statistical routines for determining differential expression according to digital gene expression data. The resulting *P* values were adjusted using Benjamini and Hochberg's approach for controlling the false discovery rate (FDR) (Benjamini and Hochberg 1995). This analysis generated weighted fold changes (FC), and corrected *P* values were used to detect differences in gene expression. Genes with a $|\log_2FC| \geq 1$ and *P* < 0.05 were considered significantly differentially expressed. The GO enrichment analysis of DEGs was implemented with the Goseq R package-based Wallenius noncentral hypergeometric distribution.

Sequence analysis and phylogenetic analysis

The local tBLASTn program was applied to screen the putative genes using the available gene sequences in Coleoptera as a "query" with the BioEdit Sequence Alignment Editor 7.1.3.0. Multiple sequence alignments of available protein sequences were performed using CLUSTALX 2.1. The alignments were manually adjusted when some protein sequences needed alignment. The trimmed OBP, CSP, OR, IR, GR, and SNMP protein alignments were used to construct maximum-likelihood trees using FastTree v2.1.10 with the default settings

(Price et al., 2010). The phylogenetic trees were modified and visually improved by ITOL (<https://itol.embl.de/>).

Confirmation of RNA-Seq results by qRT-PCR

To confirm the results of the transcriptomic analysis, qRT-PCR analysis was performed for the selected chemosensory genes using a BIO-RAD CFX Connect Real-Time PCR System (BIO-RAD, California, USA). cDNAs from antennae were synthesized by using the Fast Quant RT kit (TIANGEN, Beijing, China). Target gene expression data were normalized and corrected for sample-to-sample variance using the reference genes *β-actin* and *GAPDH*. Gene-specific primers (Table S1) were designed by BEACON DESIGNER 7 (PREMIER Biosoft International, Palo Alto, CA, USA). By analyzing the standard curves using a 5-fold cDNA dilution series, a melt-curve analysis and efficiency were performed to ensure that each primer was specific. Each experiment included negative controls without a template. Each reaction for each sample was assessed in three technical replicates and three biological replicates to ensure reproducibility. The $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ ($\Delta\Delta CT = (C_{T, Target} - C_{T, Reference}) \text{ Time } x - (C_{T, Target} - C_{T, Reference}) \text{ Time } 0$) method was used to compute the relative expression levels in each sample (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). The Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Levene tests were utilized before analyses to check assumptions of normality and homogeneity for parametric analysis. Data were log-transformed or ranked if the assumptions were not met. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test was used to compare the expression of each target gene among different stages. Data were analyzed by ANOVA (one-way analysis of variance) using SPSS Statistics 18.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA), with *P* < 0.05 indicated by *, *P* < 0.01 as ** and *P* < 0.001 as ***.

Fluorescence competitive binding assays

PstrOBP genes without the signal peptide were cloned between the *BamH* I and *Xho* I restriction sites of the prokaryotic expression vector pET-30a (+) (Novagen, Madison, WI, USA) and transformed into BL21 competent cells. The PstrOBPs were expressed in competent cells, cultured in LB at 20°C for 16 h, and induced with 0.5 mM isopropyl-β-D-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) as described previously (Li et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022b). After ultrasonic fragmentation and centrifugation, PstrOBPs were obtained as inclusion bodies and subjected to a denaturation and renaturation procedure before purification. Inclusion body processing and protein refolding were performed using the redox methods described by Prestwich (Prestwich, 1993). The refolded

proteins were purified with a standard Ni column (GE Healthcare, Waukesha, WI, USA). Following the manufacturer's protocol, the His-tag was removed by a recombinant enterokinase (Novagen, Madison, WI, USA). The purified PstrOBPs were dialyzed in Tris buffer, their size and purity were assessed by SDS-PAGE, and their concentrations were determined using the Bradford method.

The binding abilities of PstrOBPs toward ITCs were evaluated using an F-380 fluorescence spectrophotometer (Guangdong, Tianjin, China). The fluorescent probe N-phenyl-1-naphthylamine (1-NPN) emission spectra, stimulated at a wavelength of 337 nm, were recorded between 390 and 530 nm. To measure the affinity of 1-NPN for the PstrOBPs, a 2 μ M solution of the purified PstrOBPs in 50 mM Tris-HCl at pH 7.4 was titrated with aliquots of 1 mM 1-NPN dissolved in methanol to yield final concentrations ranging from 2 to 18 μ M. The dissociation constants of 1-NPN and the proteins were calculated using the Scatchard equation (Sideris et al., 1992). Competitive binding was measured by titrating the solutions of both PstrOBPs and 1-NPN at a concentration of 2 μ M by adding aliquots of the ligand solutions (prepared in 1 mM methanol solution) to achieve final concentrations of 2-32 μ M. The dissociation constants of the competitors were calculated using the equation $K_i =$

$IC_{50}/(1 + [1-NPN]/K_{1-NPN})$, where [1-NPN] is the free concentration of 1-NPN, and K_{1-NPN} is the dissociation constant of the PstrOBP/1-NPN complex.

RESULTS

Behavioral response of *P. striolata* to isothiocyanates

In the Y-tube olfactometer assay of adults, we preliminarily tested the behavioral responses of the adults to different concentrations (1, 10, and 100 mg/ml) of ITCs. According to the selection tendency, a 100 mg/ml concentration was selected as the test concentration. The results showed that *P. striolata* adults were significantly attracted by 9 kinds of ITCs compared to the mineral oil control (Fig. 1). Allyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 21.429$, $df = 1$, $P < 0.001$), butyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 14.083$, $df = 1$, $P < 0.001$) and benzyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 15.364$, $df = 1$, $P < 0.001$) induced the strongest attraction, followed by isobutyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 10.083$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.001$), ethyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 7.714$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.005$) and 3-(methylthio) propyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 8.100$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.004$), and finally, sec-butyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 5.488$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.019$), phenethyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 4.455$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.035$) and phenyl ITC ($\chi^2 = 4.900$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.027$). In contrast, there was no significant preference of *P. striolata* adults for Cyclopropyl ITC or mineral oil ($\chi^2 = 0.381$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.537$).

Figure 1. Behavioral response to ITC compounds in adults and larvae of *P. striolata*. CK: mineral oil control, TEST: odor compounds. The asterisks represent the differences in selection between different treatments in each group (ns, no significant difference; *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$; *, $P < 0.001$).**

In the larval assays, we first selected different concentrations (0.01, 0.1, and 1 mg/ml) of ITCs and different distances (2 and 3 cm) between the odor source and the larvae. According to the selection results, we used a concentration of 0.1 mg/ml and a distance of 2 cm as the test parameters. *P. striolata* larvae showed a tendency of attraction toward ITCs, although it was not significant ($P > 0.05$) in most cases. Interestingly, only allyl ITC induced significantly higher attraction in the larvae than the mineral oil control ($\chi^2 = 4.167$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.041$) (Fig. 1). Adults presented behavioral attraction responses to nine ITC compounds; in contrast, larvae showed behavioral activity toward only one ITC compound, where allyl ITC

was the sole compound inducing both adult and larval host localization behavioral activity. These behavioral phenomena indicated that adults and larvae may be able to locate hosts with the same informational compounds.

Transcriptome overview and gene functional annotation

We further investigated the expression of chemosensory genes in adults and larvae to explain the behavioral phenomena described above. Hence, adult and larval transcriptomes (3 replicates in each) were established with the pupae as a reference using the Illumina HiSeq™ 2500

platform. As a result, all samples produced 21,350,998 to 23,432,900 raw reads, resulting in 20,992,896 to 20,992,896 clean reads (Table 1). All clean reads were assembled into 27,157 genes whose lengths ranged from 301 to 36,459 bp, with a mean length of 1728 bp (Table 2). Subsequently, we used BUSCO software to evaluate the splicing quality of Trinity, unigenes, and clusters, and the number of complete BUSCOs accounted for more than 90% of the total BUSCO groups searched (Fig. S1).

Homology analysis indicated that 13,808 genes (50.84%) showed BLAST_X hits in the NR database, and 4,547 genes (16.74%) showed BLAST_N hits in the NT database (Table S2). According to the results of annotations in the NR database, the most significant percentage (41.1%) of the genes were mapped to *Diabrotica virgifera*, followed by 17.5% and 14.9% of the genes mapped to *Gregarina niphandrodes* and *Leptinotarsa decemlineata*, respectively (Fig. S2).

Table 1. Read analysis statistics.

sample	raw_reads	clean_reads	clean_bases	error_rate	Q20	Q30	GC_pct
A1	23432900	22613245	6.78G	0.03	97.84	93.73	43.79
A2	22802572	22011323	6.60G	0.03	97.94	93.95	43.71
A3	22113537	20992896	6.30G	0.03	97.77	93.42	42.97
L1	22661684	21832596	6.55G	0.03	97.84	93.72	42.7
L2	22688066	22353912	6.71G	0.03	98.02	94	45.76
L3	21350998	20649604	6.19G	0.03	97.9	93.91	44
P1	22551347	21752191	6.53G	0.02	98.05	94.21	44.08
P2	23171700	22546192	6.76G	0.03	98.06	94.09	43.77
P3	22884351	22016065	6.60G	0.02	98.05	94.18	43.85

Table 2. Summary of data used for transcriptome assembly.

	Min length	Mean length	Median length	Max length	N50	N90	Total nucleotides
Transcripts	301	2339	1501	36459	3987	1085	173090412
Genes	301	1728	859	36459	3305	632	46929162

Identification of chemosensory genes

This study identified 39 OBPs, 8 CSPs, 53 ORs, 30 IRs, 26 GRs, and 2 SNMPs from the *P. striolata* transcriptome. Closer inspection of the results showed that 15 *OBPs*, 3 *CSPs*, 4 *ORs*, and 4 *GRs* were identified by bioinformatics analysis for the first time, including the previously undiscovered and critical Plus-C OBP family. Coleopteran OBP classification led to the identification of 11 ABP II, 27 Minus-C OBPs, 5 Classic OBPs, and 1 Plus-C OBP in *P. striolata* (Fig. 2). In the CSP phylogenetic tree of Coleoptera, PstrCSPs were distributed on different branches and generally formed smaller subgroups with other coleopteran CSPs (Fig. S3). The phylogenetic

analysis of the OR results showed that ORs were highly divergent and that ORcos from different species formed a clear orthologous lineage (Fig. S4). In the phylogenetic tree of IRs, twelve PstrIRs clustered well into the conserved antennal IR subfamily, and PstrIR19 and PstrIR49 were grouped close to the IR8a/25a clusters (Fig. S5). Five PstrGRs were clustered with sugar receptors in the GR phylogenetic tree, and PstrGR15 was clustered into the CO₂ GR clade (Fig. S6). Two distinct groups, PstrSNMP1 and PstrSNMP2, were observed in a phylogenetic tree generated based on our identified PstrSNMPs and paralogs from other coleopterans (Fig. S7).

Figure 2. Phylogenetic tree of putative *P. striolata* OBPs with known coleopteran OBPs and heatmap of relative expression values for PstrOBPs. *Dendroctonus ponderosae* (Dpon), *Tribolium castaneum* (Tcas), *Ambrostoma quadriimpressum* (Aqua), *Pyrrhalta maculicollis* (Pmac) and *P. striolata* (Pstr). The different colors of the clades indicate the classic OBPs, plus-C OBPs, minus-C OBPs, and the ABP II clade. Heatmap of relative expression values for PstrSNMPs expressed in different developmental stages. Estimation of abundance values determined by the FPKM method. Blue indicates low expression, whereas the deeper the blue color is, the lower the expression level is. Red indicates high expression; the more profound the red color, the higher the expression level. Color plots represent \log_2 (FPKM) values for each gene. A: adults, L: larvae, P: pupae.

Developmental stage-related expression patterns of chemosensory genes

In this section, we focus on comparing the differences in the expression of chemosensory genes between adults and larvae. The results showed that the expression of 9 *OBPs* (*PstrOBP3*, *PstrOBP5*, *PstrOBP6*, *PstrOBP8*, *PstrOBP10*, *PstrOBP16*, *PstrOBP18*, *PstrOBP38* and *PstrOBP42*) was significantly higher in the adults than in the larvae, which consisted of 1 ABP II, 2 Classic OBPs and 6 minus-C OBPs. There were only 5 *OBPs* that were significantly more highly expressed in larvae than in adults, comprising 1 ABP II, 1 Classic OBP, and 3 Minus-C OBPs. Interestingly, 6 *OBPs* were highly expressed in both adults and larvae and showed significantly higher expression than in the pupal stage, which included 1 ABP II and 5 Minus-C OBPs (Fig. 3). Additionally, 2 *CSPs*, 1 *OR*, 1 *IR*, and 1 *GR* were highly expressed in both larvae and adults but were expressed at low levels in pupae. The expression levels of 6 *OBPs* and 5 other chemosensory genes highly expressed in both adults and larvae were verified by qPCR. In general, the results for 6 *OBPs*, 1 *OR*, and 1 *IR* were fully consistent with the transcriptome data, while the expression of 2 *CSPs* and 1 *GR* was significantly higher in the larvae than in the adult and pupa (Fig. 3).

Characterization of the binding of ligands to PstrOBPs

To determine whether the OBPs highly expressed in both larvae and adults were commonly bound to isothiocyanates, we examined the binding affinities of 6 recombinant PstrOBPs for these volatiles using the competitive binding assay. One ABP II (*PstrOBP9*) and two minus-C OBPs (*PstrOBP13* and *PstrOBP17*) were highly expressed in both adults and larvae. Moreover, two minor OBPs (*PstrOBP6* and *PstrOBP8*) and one classic OBP (*PstrOBP10*) were highly expressed in adults as the control group. First, the size and purity of the recombinant proteins were checked by SDS-PAGE (Fig. 4). The protein molecular weights of the six OBPs (*PstrOBP6*, *PstrOBP8*, *PstrOBP9*, *PstrOBP10*, *PstrOBP13* and *PstrOBP17*) were 11.98-13.51 kDa. The binding of PstrOBPs to 1-NPN was characterized by a linear Scatchard plot and a regular saturation binding curve (Fig. 5). The dissociation constants of the PstrOBP/1-NPN complexes were 0.63-3.19 μM (Table. 3). In PstrOBPs highly expressed in both adults and larvae, *PstrOBP9* showed broad binding affinities for *allyl ITC* and eight other ITCs ($14.41 \pm 1.84 < K_i < 20.61 \pm 2.10$) (Fig. 5; Table. 3). Moreover, *PstrOBP13* displayed an excellent binding affinity for isobutyl ITC ($K_i = 19.61 \pm 1.59$). In the control group, *PstrOBP6* presented relatively narrow binding

affinity ranges toward benzyl ITC ($K_i = 14.32 \pm 1.08$) and phenethyl ITC ($K_i = 19.16 \pm 2.64$).

Figure 3. Analysis of significant differentially expressed chemosensory genes in Venn diagrams (A) and by qRT-PCR (B). A: Yellow, fuchsia, and cyan indicate up-regulated chemosensory genes in adults, larvae, and pupae, respectively, and the areas where the pairs cross indicate that they were up-regulated in both members of the pair. B: Relative gene expression analysis of chemosensory genes up-regulated in both adults and larvae by qRT-PCR. A: adults, L: larvae, P: pupae. Different lowercase letters above each bar indicate significant differences in chemosensory gene transcript levels in various developmental stages.

Figure 4. SDS-PAGE analysis of expressed and purified PstrOBPs (A) and binding curve of fluorescence probe 1-NPN binding to PstrOBPs (B). A: M: Molecular marker; 1: Noninduction of PstrOBPs; 2: Induction of PstrOBPs with IPTG; 3: Supernatant of PstrOBPs; 4: Pellet of PstrOBPs; 5: Purification of PstrOBPs; 6: Purified PstrOBPs in which the His-tag was cleaved by recombinant enterokinase. B: Binding curve of 1-NPN binding to PstrOBPs and corresponding Scatchard plot.

Figure 5. Competitive binding curves of PstrOBPs binding to isothiocyanates. The binding data of all tested ligands are listed in Table 3. Data are the average values from three independent experiments.

Table 3. Binding affinities of PstrOBPs for plant volatile compounds. The corresponding K_i values were not calculated for IC50 values higher than 30 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and are indicated with “-”.

Ligands	CAS number	OBP9	OBP13	OBP17				OBP6	OBP8	OBP10
				K_i ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)						
1-NPN	90-30-2	3.19	1.97	1.18	0.63	1.59	1.05			
Cyclopropyl ITC	56601-42-4	16.31±2.44	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Allyl ITC	57-06-7	20.05±4.69	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Butyl ITC	592-82-5	15.38±2.28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Isobutyl ITC	591-82-2	14.41±1.84	19.61±1.59	-	-	-	-	-	-	
sec-Butyl ITC	4426-79-3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Benzyl ITC	622-78-6	17.89±4.70	-	-	14.32±1.08	-	-	-	-	
Ethyl ITC	542-85-8	14.00±1.37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
3-(Methylthio)propyl ITC	505-79-3	20.61±2.10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Phenethyl ITC	2257-09-2	17.37±2.46	-	-	19.16±2.64	-	-	-	-	
Phenyl ITC	103-72-0	17.11±2.27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

DISCUSSION

Herbivorous insects rely on plant volatiles to precisely locate their hosts and accomplish their nutritional and reproductive tasks (Bruce et al., 2005). In Lepidoptera, adults focus on mating and oviposition, while larvae are mainly engaged in development; thus, these stages are associated with different information compounds (Tamaki et al., 1977; Sun et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2021). In this study, however, we showed a new pattern of host location in the coleopteran insect *P. striolata*, in which adults and larvae might use the same olfactory system to detect common information compounds when seeking host plants. This phenomenon may coincide with the fact that both adults and larvae of *P. striolata* have to feed to meet their nutritional needs (Olson and Knodel, 2002). More specifically, *P. striolata* adults usually lay their eggs on the soil surface near the roots of *Brassica* plants (He et al., 2012), meaning that the distance of larvae from the roots requires them to locate and travel to reach the roots themselves. In contrast, in lepidopteran pests such as *Pieris rapae*, adults lay their eggs on leaves, and larvae do not need to seek food from a distance, making it more likely that they will use gustatory organs rather than olfactory organs to identify food (Yang et al., 2021).

ITCs, as crucial chemical cues for long-distance location, play an essential role in the area of host plants and oviposition sites by Brassicales specialists (Renwick et al., 2006; Tóth et al., 2007). Our results showed that all tested ITCs were significantly attractive to *P. striolata* adults and that *allyl ITC* exerted the best attraction effect. This finding was consistent with those of other researchers who have observed the apparent trapping effect of *allyl ITC* on *Phyllotreta* in the field (Tóth et al., 2007; Beran et al., 2011). Another Brassicales specialist, *P. xylostella*, exhibits an apparent oviposition tendency related to the other three ITCs (iberverin, 4-pentenyl ITC, and phenylethyl ITC) (Liu et al., 2020), showing that although the host plants of the two specialists are the same, the information compounds used for locating hosts are different. Some studies have shown that different Brassicaceae plants release various kinds of ITCs (Fahey et al., 2001), so this difference may be related to the other host plants preferred by the two specialists. However, it may also be related to the niche differences between the two specialists at the trophic, temporal, and spatial levels (Wu, 2003). Unlike the broad ITC spectrum preferred by adults, the larvae are particular and only presented a tendency for an affinity to *allyl ITC* in our behavioral assay. This difference reflects the plasticity of olfaction, which may result from the different living environments encountered by adults and larvae (Gadenne et al., 2016).

Regarding insect chemosensory function, larvae tend to have fewer types and numbers of sensors than adults (Li et al., 2018). A large number of sensilla trichodea and sensilla basiconica were identified in the antennae of *P.*

striolata adults (Zhang et al., 2016), which are considered to have an essential olfactory reception function, while studies of the larvae are still lacking. In another study of beetles, only one sensillum (antennal cone) in the antennae of larvae was found to perform an olfactory function in the Colorado potato beetle, *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* (Farazmand and Chaika, 2012).

To fully comprehend how the peripheral olfactory system of *P. striolata* contributes to this behavioral similarity between adults and larvae. We characterized the chemosensory genes of *P. striolata*, including 39 *OBPs*, 8 *CSPs*, 53 *ORs*, 30 *IRs*, 26 *GRs*, and 2 *SNMPs*, which were more complete than those in previous studies (Wu et al., 2016). Previously, chemosensory genes of adults from Chrysomelidae beetles such as *Ambrostoma quadriimpressum* (Wang et al., 2016), *Colaphellus bowringi* (Li et al., 2015), *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Tanaka et al., 2022) and *Plagioderia versicolora* (Liu et al., 2021) have been obtained through transcriptomic analysis. However, more chemosensory gene expression needs to be examined in adults and larvae. We systematically compared the differences in the expression of olfactory genes between adults and larvae. The results showed that eleven chemosensory genes were highly expressed in both adults and larvae, which was much greater than the number of chemosensory genes that were highly expressed in the other two groups (5 in both larvae and pupae; 4 in both adults and pupae). This phenomenon also suggested more commonality between adults and larvae in olfactory function.

Functional studies of *PstrOBPs* that were highly expressed in both adults and larvae showed that *PstrOBP9* could bind nine kinds of isothiocyanates well and that *PstrOBP13* presented a high affinity toward isobutyl ITC, meaning that *PstrOBP9* was the key gene encoding the protein tuned to ITCs. These results differ from those of earlier studies of Lepidoptera pests, which mostly involved *PBPs* binding to sex pheromones and adult-specific *OBPs* binding to host plant volatiles related to oviposition (Shen et al., 2019; Cai et al., 2020; Dahal et al., 2022). However, the functional characteristics of *OBPs* that are highly expressed in adults and larvae are still unclear. Considering the above results in combination with the behavioral observations, we hypothesized that adults and larvae of *P. striolata* might recognize *allyl ITC* for host location through common *OBPs* shared between adults and larvae. Notably, *PstrOBP9*, a member of the *ABPII* family, was found to play an important role in host volatile recognition, similar to the results obtained for other coleopteran insects (Wang et al., 2020b). In addition, *OBP4* of the hemipteran mirid bug was also clustered into insect *ABP* clade (Wang et al., 2020a; Wang et al., 2022) and is demonstrated to be involved in sexual communication indicating multiple functions of the *ABP* family across insect species.

Nevertheless, PstrOBP6, an adult-specific OBP, could also bind two ITCs, suggesting that binding OBPs to ITCs is a complex event involving multiple OBPs. It also suggests the multiple identities of ITCs. A possible explanation might be that plant volatiles play an essential role in regulating the recognition of sex pheromones and aggregation pheromones in adult insects (Collignon et al., 2016; McCormick et al., 2017).

In summary, this study revealed that *allyl ITC* is a common key signal for host location in adults and larvae of *P. striolata*, providing new insight into host recognition in herbivorous insects. Then, PstrOBP9, which is highly expressed in both adults and larvae, was proven to be an essential protein for ITC recognition, which indicated the existence of a common olfactory recognition mechanism between larvae and adults, and this finding may serve as a foundation for further research into the olfactory systems of adults and larvae. However, the total molecular basis of host selection in *P. striolata* is still unknown, and the co-expression of PstrOBP9 with PstrORs and the functions of PstrOBPs and PstrORs in vivo need to be studied. Given the potential applications and benefits of Brassicaceae crops, it is worthwhile to examine these chemosensory genes to increase the yield of crops by applying chemoeological approaches to monitor and/or control pests in future developments (Nieri et al., 2021; Muskat and Patel 2022; He et al., 2023).

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The Study and Development of a Mass Trapping System for the Sex Pheromone of *Plutella xylostella* (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae) in Taiwan

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ABSTRACT

Diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella*, is an important pest of Brassicaceae in Taiwan. The insecticide resistance of DBM is a serious issue. This study aims to develop a mass trapping system for the sex pheromone of DBM. We used synthetic sex pheromone of DBM to develop the best formulation of sex pheromone lure, and

the optimal number for mass trapping is 120 traps/ha in this study. There was a lower density of DBMs and a lower infested rate of DBMs on the cauliflowers. After that, we designed various dry traps for DBM sex pheromones. The “2-layer lepidopteran flies up plastic trap” with ventilation holes in the lower layer is as effective as a wing sticky trap in the higher density of DBMs. We hope this system can be introduced into IPM programs to control DBMs. The components and mixture ratio of synthetic sex pheromone for DBM in Taiwan have been authorized by technology to a pesticide manufacturer for commercialization and sale.

Keywords

diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella*, sex pheromone lure, dry trap

INTRODUCTION

Diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella*, is an important pest of Brassicaceae crops. Their hosts, such as cabbage, Chinese cabbage, broccoli, cauliflower, and radish, are major crops in Taiwan (BAPHIQ, 2018). The insecticide resistance of DBM is due to shorter life cycles and faster reproduction (Tabashnik *et al.*, 1990; Shelton *et al.*, 1993; Zhao and You, 2001). Sex pheromones are one of the world's most eco-friendly plant protection products. We have to develop an application technique for a sex pheromone trappings system for DBM to provide another option for farmers to control this pest. The ingredients of sex pheromone of DBM were identified as (Z)-11-hexadecenal (Z11-16:Ald), (Z)-11-hexadecenyl acetate (Z11-16:Ac) (Tamaki *et al.*, 1977), Adding a small amount of ingredients (Z)-11-hexadecenol (Z11-16:OH) and (Z)-9-tetradecenyl acetate (Z9-14:Ac) can increase the activity (Chisholm *et al.*, 1979). Many formulas were reported (Chou *et al.*, 1977; Koshihara *et al.*, 1978; Lin *et al.*, 1982; Deng and Du, 2002). The synthetic sex pheromones can attract DBM, they were used to monitor (Baker *et al.*, 1982; Shirai and Nakamura, 1995; Ronald, 1997; Reddy and Guerrero, 2001; Nofemela, 2010; Miluch *et al.*, 2013), mass trapping (Chisholm *et al.*, 1979; Reddy and Urs, 1997; Reddy and Guerrero, 2000) or mating disruption (Fujiyoshi *et al.*, 1979; McLaughlin *et al.*, 1994; Wang and Zhang, 2008) for pest control. We should find the most suitable formula ratio in Taiwan. Sex pheromones were usually used with sticky paper to catch insects, especially DBMs (Sulifoa and Ebenebe, 2007; Nofemela, 2010; Miluch *et al.*, 2013). However, the durability of sticky paper is low (Hung *et al.*, 2016), and it is often discarded in the field by users. Dry pheromone traps are usually made of plastic; their properties make them easy to reuse, although the environment does not easily decompose them. In the past, TACTRI has developed a variety of pheromone dry traps, including for sweet potato weevil

(*Cylas formicarius*), carambola fruit borer (*Eucosma notanthe*), and Casuarina tussock moth (*Lymantria xylin*), etc. (Hwang *et al.*, 1989; Hung *et al.*, 2004; Hung *et al.*, 2017a) Pheromones used for mass trapping are safer for humans and environment, they were injected into the dispenser and did not come into contact the crop, this type of pesticide does not required the submission of toxicity data for registration in Taiwan (BAPHIQ, 2021). This paper reviews the development process of sex pheromone lure and trap for DBM and the research of its application in the field.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research on the sex pheromone lure formula ratio in Taiwan

We made lures with different formulations for DBM and compared their effectiveness in attracting DBM to a commercial lure purchased from Japan in 2003. After determining the lure formula, we tested the efficacy of different dispensers in the field for the optimal formula. We used PVC microtubes and rubber septa (Hung *et al.*, 2011). Finally, we tested whether adding the preservative BHT would affect the efficacy of the attractant. We used the wing sticky trap (fig. 1) in all trials.

Figure 1. A wing sticky trap used in this research.

The research on the attractive distance of sex pheromone lure to DBM

In the cauliflower and cabbage fields of Wufeng, Taichung County, Taiwan, 2004, we set the distance of 0 m, 5 m, 10 m, and 15 m between the Brassicaceae crops field and the DBM sex pheromone lure and no other Brassicaceae plants were between the traps and fields. We used wing sticky traps. We set the traps with bamboo poles 30-50 cm above the plant. The number of insects caught by trap was recorded regularly (Hung *et al.*, 2017a).

The effect of different sex pheromone trap abundances on the population density of DBM

In the cauliflower fields of Puyan, Changhua County, Taiwan, in 2004-2005, we set different sex pheromone trap abundances for mass trapping the DBM. The first trial was 40 traps/ha, with a 16 m distance between the two traps; the second trial was 80 traps/ha, with an 11 m distance between the two traps, and we set the third and fourth trials were both 120 traps/ha, with a 9 m distance between the two traps. We used the wing sticky trap in all trials. There were untreated fields near treated fields as a control field and a sex pheromone trap to monitor the population of DBM (Hung *et al.*, 2017a).

The efficacy evaluation of mass trapping with DBM sex pheromone trap in the field

We set DBM sex pheromone traps (with wing sticky traps) on 3 cauliflower fields with chemical control in place in Tianwei, Changhua County, Taiwan, in 2007; the abundance of traps was 120 traps/ha, and the distance between the two traps was 8 m. There were untreated fields (chemical control was also implemented) near treated fields as control fields with monitoring traps. We recorded the DBM population and pesticide usage weekly and surveyed the infestation of cauliflower leaves and flowers from DBMs at harvest. The infested plant was defined as finding the DBM, which includes eggs, larvae, and pupa (Hung *et al.*, 2017a).

The evaluation of different types of traps for DBM sex pheromone lure

We tested many different commercial traps for the DBM sex pheromone lure; the result showed that the wing sticky trap is the most suitable commercial trap for the DBM sex pheromone lure (Hung *et al.*, 2016). The sticky traps have some known disadvantages, so we attempted to create dry traps suitable for use with DBM that can be reused multiple times. We have designed plastic traps with openings at the bottom to allow Lepidoptera insects to fly

upward. There are single-layer, double-layer, and three-layer designs. Some types of traps have holes in the walls of their pipes, which may be located in either the upper or lower layers. We placed DBM sex pheromone lures in the openings of various fly-up trap designs. These traps were attached to an approximately 120-150 cm-long bamboo pole. The lure was positioned 30-50 cm above the cauliflower plants. The distance between each trap was 15 m, and only one wing sticky trap with a lure was used as the control group to monitor the population. Periodically investigate the number of DBMs in each trap (Hung *et al.*, 2017b).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research on the sex pheromone lure formula ratio in Taiwan

We compared the number of insects attracted to two formulations of DBM sex pheromone lure and a Japanese commercial lure; formulation A attracted the least number of DBMs (24.4±0.6%), and the number of DBMs attracted by formulation B (36.6±5.9%) was not significantly different from that of Japanese commercial lure (35.6±6.6%) (Table 1). Afterward, we tested which dispenser was better. The result shows rubber septa (75.2±7.5%) was better than the PVC microtube (22.5±6.4%) (table 2). Finally, the DBM lure added with BHT, the proportion of adults captured (60%) was not significantly better than the bait without BHT (40%). After adjusting the material and formula, we finally got the best product, and its effect is similar to that of Japanese commercial lures in Taiwan.

Table 1. Attractiveness of sex pheromone lure bought abroad to diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella*, in Taiwan in 2003

Source of lure	dispenser	Total no. of male moths caught	% of total males attracted ⁽¹⁾
Japan	red septa	2,174	35.6±6.6 a
Formulation A	microtube	1,546	24.4±0.6 b
Formulation B	microtube	2,304	36.6±5.9 a
Blank (CK)		275	4.1±1.3 c

⁽¹⁾ Means within a column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level with Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 2. The attractiveness of sex pheromone lure with the different carriers to diamond-back moth, *Plutella xylostella*, in Taiwan in 2003

Dispenser	Total no. of male moths caught	% of total males attracted ⁽¹⁾
Septa	10,100	75.2 ± 7.5 a
Microtube	2,716	22.5 ± 6.4 b
Blank	444	3.1 ± 2.0 c

⁽¹⁾ Means within a column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at a 5% level with Duncan's multiple range test.

The research on the attractive distance of sex pheromone lure to DBM

The trap with the most DBMs was caught at a distance of 0 m from the cauliflower field (54.9 ± 34.1%), significantly more than those at 5 m (3.5 ± 2.2%), 10 m (2.3 ± 1.8%) and 15 m (4.4 ± 2.9%) away from the field (Fig. 2). Previous studies have shown that the attractive distance of DBM lure is 4 m (Lee *et al.*, 1995), so we have inferred that the effective range of this lure could also be 4 m. According to these data, we estimate that the lure can effectively cover the entire field, and approximately 120 traps per hectare are required. Next, we tested the effect of trap abundance on populations of diamondback moths.

Figure 2. Number of DBMs caught by sex pheromone traps placed at different distances from the cauliflower fields in Taiwan in 2004. Error bars represent the standard errors of the means. Means with different letters are significantly different, as determined by the Fisher least significant difference test ($P < 0.01$).

The effect of different sex pheromone trap abundances on the population density of DBM

The research on trap abundance (Fig. 3) shows that the DBM population density of each treatment field was lower than that of the control field. Among the traps used for monitoring in the 4 treatment fields, the DBM adults captured per week were 99-468 DBMs/trap (40 traps/ha), 54-330 DBMs/trap (80 traps/ha), 19-338 DBMs/trap (120 trap/ha, A trail), and 83-435 DBMs/trap (120 trap/ha, B

trail). In the corresponding control field, the DBM adults captured per week were 109-440 DBMs/trap (control field for 40 traps/ha), 64-509 DBMs/trap (control field for 80 traps/ha), 98-576 DBMs/trap (control field for 120 traps/ha, A trail), and 186-552 DBMs/trap (control field for 120 traps/ha, B trail). The monitoring trend lines of the A trial of 120 traps/ha and the B trial of 120 traps/ha treatment field are more separated from the control field (Fig. 3). The result indicated that setting 120 traps/ha may reduce the DBM population in the cauliflower field.

Figure 3. Influence of number of traps per hectare on DBM population density in the cauliflower fields in Taiwan, in 2004-2005.

The efficacy evaluation of mass trapping with DBM sex pheromone trap in the field

There was an equal population density of DBMs between mass trapping fields (treatment) and chemical control fields (control), except for the second group of fields; the number of DBMs in the mass trapping fields has always been lower than that in the chemical control fields (Fig. 4). In the first field, the density of DBMs of the treatment group and control group were 0.8-12.5 DBMs/trap and 1.3-7.5 DBMs/trap. In the second field, the density of DBMs of the treatment and control groups were 3.3-10.3 DBMs/trap and 24-69.8 DBMs/trap. In the third field, the density of DBMs of the treatment and control groups were 3-35.3 DBMs/trap and 21.8-55 DBMs/trap. Then, we removed the traps for mass trapping after harvest, and the density of DBMs was rising obviously.

Field-1

Field-2

Figure 4. Density of DBM population in cauliflower fields treated with the mass trapping of DBM sex pheromone lures at Tianwei, Changhua County, Taiwan, in 2007. The treatment is a mass trapping field using DBM sex pheromone lures, while the control is a chemical control field.

The result of the efficacy evaluation of mass trapping (fig. 5), The infested rate of cauliflower flowers in 3 fields with mass trapping were 6.7%, 31%, and 24%, less than in the chemical control field (13%, 36.7%, and 38.1%). However, there was no significant difference after statistical analysis of all the fields. Similar results were found for the infested rate of cauliflower leaves. The infestation rate of cauliflower leaves in 3 fields with mass trapping was 2.4%, 5.5%, and 3.2%, less than the chemical control field (2.8%, 6.7%, and 3.9%). Only the infestation rate on cauliflower leaves in the third field, the mass trapping field, was significantly lower than the chemical control field. So, we calculated the average infestation rate across all fields, whether the infested rate of flowers or leaves. The mass trapping fields were significantly lower than the control fields.

Figure 5. Effects of mass trapping of DBM sex pheromone lures in the cauliflower fields of Tianwei, Changhua County, Taiwan, in 2007. Error bars represent the standard errors of the means. Means within the same group marked with the same letter are not significantly different, as determined by the t-test ($P < 0.01$).

In a similar study by Reddy and Urs (1997), in a cabbage field with mass trapping, they set the delta traps with DBM sex pheromone lures at intervals of 10 m between traps. The result shows that the cabbage damage rate in the DBM sex pheromone treatment was less than in the control.

The evaluation of different types of traps for DBM sex pheromone lure

Table 3 shows the results of using a DBM sex pheromone lures to attract DBM in the designed plastic fly-up trap. The wing sticky trap captured more DBM than expected, especially when the DBM density was below 200 insects/trap. When the density of DBM was higher than 200 insects/trap, there was no significant difference in the proportion of DBM captured by all traps. Finally, we chose the F trap (fig. 6) as the commercialization trap. The F trap is a reusable plastic product designed according to Lepidopteran species. We refer to it as a 2-layer lepidopteran flies-up. The lower layer has a plastic trap and ventilation holes. When the population density of DBMs is higher, its effectiveness is equivalent to that of the wing sticky trap (Table 3).

Figure 6. The commercialized F trap.

Table 3. Percentages of trapping number of insects of different types of traps in different population densities of DBM in the field

Types of traps	% of total insects caught	
	Lower density of DBMs ⁽³⁾	Higher density of DBMs ⁽⁴⁾
A	11.0 ± 9.9 c ⁽⁵⁾	11.6 ± 5.5 a ⁽⁵⁾
B	11.1 ± 9.4 c	14.0 ± 7.1 a
C	17.3 ± 10.4 b	12.3 ± 6.5 a
D	13.7 ± 8.5 bc	12.4 ± 6.0 a
E	11.8 ± 6.5 bc	16.7 ± 5.8 a
F ⁽¹⁾	9.9 ± 7.4 c	18.1 ± 7.9 a
W ⁽²⁾ (CK)	25.1 ± 19.2 a	14.9 ± 6.4 a

⁽¹⁾ 2-layer lepidopteran flies up the plastic trap with ventilation holes in the lower layer.

⁽²⁾ Wing sticky traps.

⁽³⁾ 4-192 insects/trap, n = 22.

⁽⁴⁾ 227-481 insects/trap, n = 7.

⁽⁵⁾ Mean ± S.D. values were calculated from 22 and 7 replications, respectively. Data were transformed to $\arcsin \sqrt{x}$ before analysis. Means within each column followed by the same letter are not significantly different by Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test ($P < 0.05$).

CONCLUSION

The resistance of DBMs poses a challenging problem in managing cruciferous vegetable fields, making developing control strategies an important issue. Our results indicated that rubber septa are more suitable for DBM sex pheromone lure in Taiwan; we can use the wing sticky traps or 2-layer lepidopteran flies up the plastic traps with ventilation holes in the lower layer to mass trap the DBM on the field. The optimal density of DBM traps is 120 traps/ha, with an 8-10 m distance between the two traps; their efficacy is comparable to chemical control. Our research data shows that the cauliflower field that uses DBM sex pheromone traps for mass trapping can reduce the infestation rate by 8.7% compared to untreated fields. If the area of mass trapping is increased, the population density of DBMs will be further reduced. According to data after actual use by farmers, with an abundance of 120 traps/ha, insecticide application frequency in mass trapping fields was reduced by 2-4 times compared to chemical control fields. The total cultivated cost was reduced by 50,000 NTD/ha (About 1,600 US dollars, converted at the exchange rate in mid-2023).

Table 3 shows the effectiveness of plastic and wing sticky traps in the different densities of DBMs. So, when the density of DBMs is lower than 200 insects/trap, the wing sticky trap was set up. When the density is high, the 2-layer lepidopteran flies up the plastic trap with ventilation holes in the lower layer, which is more suitable, especially when the wind and sand are strong.

The lure and trap we developed had completed technology transfer in Taiwan. The 2-layer lepidopteran flew up the plastic trap with ventilation holes and obtained a utility model patent in Taiwan. Mass-trapping pheromone lures must be regarded as biochemical pesticides for registration in Taiwan. Sinon Corporation registered the DBM sex pheromone lure in 2018. Although the USA and the OECD do not regard mass-trapping pheromones as active ingredients, Taiwan has reduced the requirement for toxicological tests for mass-trapping products (do not contact crops) compared with mating disruption products.

Pheromones are agricultural materials that can reduce reliance on chemicals, but we must continuously improve our usage skills before farmers are willing to use them. Under climate change, prevalent species of pests may change rapidly, and the specificity of pheromones may be a stumbling block for agricultural use. This is a problem we will have to face in the future.

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Mating Disruption for the Management of Diamondback Moth *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Plutellidae: Lepidoptera) Using Nano Matrix-Controlled Release Pheromone Dispenser

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ABSTRACT

The Diamondback Moth, *Plutella xylostella* (L.), has developed resistance to nearly all synthetic insecticides used against it in the field. Because of this pest, pesticide recommendations constantly change as new compounds enter the market, and others become ineffective. This has led to cole crops producing heavy residues. The larvae feed on the growing tips of crucifers, causing stunting and distortions that make heads unmarketable. To manage the pest effectively by semiochemicals, ATGC has developed, in collaboration with JNCASR and ICAR- NBAIR, a new nano matrix delivery system consisting of Z-11-hexadecenal and Z-11-hexadecenyl acetate, the female sex pheromone of *P. xylostella* to disrupt mating effectively. We were able to have a season-long control with our novel delivery system using these nano-matrix materials. The

technology allows control of the release of pheromones for the entire season, disrupting mating in every brood. This technology is formulated in different formulations like CREMIT P Glue dispensers, CREMIT T Solid dispensers, and CREMIT SM. We have demonstrated this technology in the farmer's field in the years 2020-2022 in different geographical locations, and using the delivery mentioned above system, mating disruption is achieved above 92% in small farm holdings. Results revealed that mating disruption applied to treated plots was significantly superior to untreated control by reducing the leaf and head infestation percentage caused by diamondback moth larvae. The treated plots had less than 5% damage to the heads against 28% in farmer practice. The treated plots were applied with only two insecticide sprays for managing secondary pests against farmer practice, where 12 insecticide applications were made, nine specifically for managing diamondback moths. The mating disruption tool will be effective in IPM for managing *P. xylostella*.

Keywords

Semiochemicals, Pheromones, Mating disruption, Diamondback moth, Management

INTRODUCTION

In recent days, consumers have demanded nutrient-rich products for optimal health benefits. In this regard, the *Brassicaceae* family (cruciferous) is a group that includes a large number of vegetable foods that are widely consumed globally. The popularity of *Brassica* is increasing due to its nutritional value and pharmacological effects. The group includes many vegetable foods such as cabbages, broccoli, cauliflower, mustards, oilseed, rapeseed, canola, etc. In recent years, the phytochemical composition of *Brassicaceae* has been studied deeply, as they contain many valuable metabolites that are directly linked to different recognized biological activities. The unique features of *Brassicaceae* family plants conferred by their phytochemicals have extended prospects for their use for beneficial effects on human nutrition and health worldwide (Favela-Gonzalez et al., 2020). In 2020, cabbage accounted for a harvested area of approximately 3,395,300 hectares, yielding 105,069,400 tons (FAO, 2022). In India, the area under cabbage cultivation was 3.97 lakh hectares and production of 92.07 lakh tons with an average productivity of 22.6 MT ha during 2019-20 (NHB, 2014 and 2020). The world's production of cabbage and brassicas in 2020 was 71 million tons, led by China, which made up 48% of the total, followed by India, Russia, South Korea, and Ukraine. The major limiting factor for commercial cabbage cultivation is insect pest infestation. Though the production is higher, it is not the ideal yield to be harvested as per the need and the area

cultivated due to insect pest damage. However, cabbage is also susceptible to insect pest infestations in the field, which causes huge losses to the growers. (Mpumi et al., 2020). Diamondback moth (DBM), *P. xylostella*, is the most destructive insect pest of cruciferous plants throughout the world (Wang et al., 2011; Shakeel et al., 2017; Mpumi et al., 2020; Senthilkumar et al., 2022). Their Larvae feed on foliage and growing parts of young plants or bore into the heads or flower buds, resulting in skeletonization of leaves, stunting of the plants, or failure of head formation, which causes more economic loss for growers worldwide.

The diamondback moth greatly damages cabbage, accounting for a 50-80% annual loss in marketable yield (Devjani and Singh, 1998). Hence, farmers are compelled to use chemical insecticides to cultivate lucratively to control diamondback moths. *P. xylostella* significantly impacts the economics of Brassicaceae cropping. It has been estimated that the worldwide cost of managing *P. xylostella* in vegetable crops was USD 4-5 billion per annum and increased by USD 0.77 billion per year (Zalucki et al., 2012; Li et al., 2016).

Chemical control is particularly challenging, as insecticides are required in the fructification stage, which coincides with the presence of beneficial insects and pollinators that frequent the crop. For this reason, the choice of selective insecticides is essential. Moreover, the effectiveness of insecticides has been reduced due to the development of resistance to many of these compounds (Lee et al., 1993; Chung et al., 1997). *P. xylostella* is known for having resistance to pyrethroids (Liu et al., 1982), organophosphorus (Miyata et al., 1982), growth regulators (Lin et al., 1989) and *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Hama et al., 1992), among other synthetic pesticides. Indeed, the diamondback moth was the first insect to become resistant to *B. thuringiensis* toxin in the field (Tabashnik et al., 1997; Safraz et al., 2005; Grzywacz et al., 2010). Talekar et al. (1990) reported that frequent use of chemical insecticides at higher doses results in the depredation of natural enemies and the development of insecticide resistance in *P. xylostella* against a wide range of insecticides in different parts of India. Recent studies reported that with the use of sex pheromones, the population of insect pests can be reduced, the presence of insects of agricultural interest may be detected, the behavior of pest populations can be learned, and decisions can be made regarding the adequate use of insecticides (Zarbin et al., 2007). The *P. xylostella* sex pheromone can be used for monitoring and mating disruption of this species (Yang et al., 2007).

The high costs of managing DBM are rooted in the biology of the pest and the strategies used for its control. This insect has a short life cycle and a wide range of hosts. It has a genetic machinery allows it to survive in significantly different environments across all continents

except Antarctica (Zhou et al., 2022). The most widely used management strategy in the last 50 years has been the application of insecticides (Li et al., 2016; Banazeer et al., 2016). The short life cycle of DBM and a heavy reliance on insecticides has led to an expanding list of populations resistant to organochlorines, organophosphates, carbamates, pyrethroids, microbial-origin molecules, and insect-growth regulators and novel mechanism insecticides (Jian and Wenjun, 2003).

In the developing world, the appearance of resistant populations has created vicious cycles of frequent (usually weekly) insecticide applications coupled with an increasing dosage. These practices have led to further resistance (Li et al., 2019). Although vegetable brassicas have a 90-day crop cycle, many farmers in Southeast Asia spray 12–16 times, and in the Americas, 15-20 times and 36 sprays per cycle are common in Nicaragua (Sarfraz and Keddie, 2005).

Overreliance on chemical control has not only led to the evolution of resistance to insecticides and a reduction of natural enemies but also has polluted biotic and abiotic factors in the ecosystem. The lack of effective natural enemies is also considered the major cause of the high pest status in most parts of the world (Lim, 1986). In the present scenario, there is a need to implement an environmentally friendly integrated pest management (IPM) approach with new management tactics, which should not have any negative impacts and raise complications in insect development resistance. Mating disruption is an alternative to chemical control based on insect biology. The IPM approach is economically beneficial and reduces environmental and health risks (Shakeel et al., 2017). The present study will discuss and address the problem caused by the Diamondback moth, *P. xylostella*, in open-field cabbage crop cultivation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area:

The isolated plots (≥ 1 acre) of cabbage or cauliflower crops were selected for the study. Care was taken to keep the treated field as an isolated plot until the completion of the study. Control plots were chosen ≥ 500 meters from the treated plot, and the farmers were allowed to practice their farm practices in the study area. In the case of the treated plot, the following treatments were implemented. The study was conducted from 2020-2022 in different geographies in India, *i.e.*, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Gujarat, and Telangana.

Experimental Design:

Various phases of slow delivery mating disruption formulations, i.e., solid dispenser, glue dispenser, and spray formulation, were examined for their efficacy on diamondback moth, *P. xylostella* management in the open field condition, and control (farmer's practices). The formulations mentioned above were applied manually on day zero (0-5 days of transplant) in the open field. Six treatments were studied to scrutinize the potential devices for better management of *P. xylostella* in open-field conditions. They were,

Treatment 1 (T₁) - Single application of 400 nos. of solid dispenser (2% per 1g tablet)/acre per season.

Treatment 2 (T₂) - Two applications of 400 nos. of solid dispenser (2% per 1g tablet)/acre per season.

Treatment 3 (T₃) - Single application of 800 nos. of solid dispenser (2% per 1g tablet)/acre per season.

Treatment 4 (T₄) - Three applications of glue dispenser 250g (4%)/acre per season.

Treatment 5 (T₅) - Spray formulation of CREMIT SM 500 ml (2%)/acre/application (four applications per season).

Treatment 6 (T₆) - Farmer's practice (Control).

Solid and glue dispensers (T₁-T₄) were applied in a zig-zag manner on days 0-5 days after transplant, followed by the second application (T₂) after 30 days of 1st application adjacent to the previous application spot. Solid dispensers were applied directly on the soil's surface in the mid-region between crops at a 5x2 meter range across the study area. In the case of glue dispenser formulation, the first application (dollops) is executed directly on drip liners or mulching sheets, and the second and third application dollops are placed on the leaf, six inches below the crop canopy. In the case of spray formulation, the foliar application was followed through a hand or battery or petrol-operated knapsack sprayer (200 liters of water per acre per recommended dose). The second, third, and fourth applications were made at 20-25 days from the previous application. Care was taken while weeding or doing any other farmer's practices. Delta sticky traps were placed along with commercially available DBM lures on both control and treated plots (4 traps per acre). Lures were replaced every 30 days intervals, and the traps were replaced if enough space was unavailable for new catches.

Evaluation parameters:

Pre-treatment observations were made by observing diamondback moth larvae and percent leaf infestation from randomly selected 10 blocks per study area (100 plants/acre) at both treated and control plots on the day before treatment. Subsequently, post-treatment

observations, i.e., % damage, % larval infestation, % head damage (only unmarketable heads were considered), % yield loss, and adult moth catches on delta sticky trap, were recorded every week until completion of the harvest. The cost-benefit ratio was measured based on the net income from treated and control plots.

Statistical analysis:

The following statistical formulae were made to evaluate the efficacies of the formulations studied,

% Mating Disruption = $100 - [(No. \text{ of moth catch in treated} / No. \text{ of moth catch in control}) \times 100]$

% Leaf damage = $(No. \text{ of damaged leaves per plot} / (Total \text{ no. of leaves observed per plot}) \times 100$

% Head damage = $(No. \text{ of damaged heads per plot} / (Total \text{ no. of heads observed per plot}) \times 100$

% Reduction over control = $(\% \text{ Leaf or head infested in control} - \% \text{ Leaf or head infested in treated}) / (\% \text{ Leaf or head infested in control}) \times 100$

% Yield increase = $(Yield \text{ in treated} - yield \text{ in control}) / (Yield \text{ in control}) \times 100$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The untreated cabbage plot has received heavier head damages due to *P. xylostella* (28.22%) than the treated fields ($\pm 5\%$) with mating disruption technology (Table. 1). Cabbage and cauliflower crop protection from notorious insect pests mainly rely on synthetic chemical pesticides (Melo et al., 2023), by which the quality of the produce and the edibility are questioned, unmarketable and insect pests develop resistance to it (Gonzalez et al., 2023). The indiscriminate use of the same causes negative deterioration effects on the environment. This crisis needs to be addressed with harmony strategies (Senthoorraja et al., 2021), which should drastically reduce the frequency of pesticide applications and encourage the biocontrol agents to enrich in a particular area (Carmo et al., 2023). Specific attractants are one of the best allies in insect-integrated pest management. Semiochemicals are the type of naturally occurring chemicals with specific molecules that alter the behavior of insect species (Goane Lucia et al., 2023). Among that, sex pheromone is one of the components female insects produce to attract their conspecific male for mating purposes. Across the globe, many countries have been suggesting and attempting to execute their applications for insect pest management in pre- and post-harvest protection (Gadi and Angel, 2010; Goane Lucia et al., 2023). Moreover, the sex pheromones were used only for monitoring (Witzgall et al., 2010). This must be adopted for various modules to keep the insect

pests under the limit. Gadi and Angel. (2010) discussed that important successes can be obtained, particularly in mating disruption with a significant reduction in pesticide use. Even Carde and Minks (1995) and Hegazi et al. (2010) have reported that mating disruption is a strategy that can be a suitable alternative against synthetic chemical pesticides to keep the population under the limit by loading large quantities of pheromone on a particular area. On this line, the present study results support their hypothesis through semiochemical-based pest management to diminish the reproductive success of the targeted insect pest through mating disruption tactics. The overabundance of synthetic sex pheromones in the field confuses males, who cannot locate their counterparts for mating, resulting in the collapse of insect-pest populations without the usage of pesticides. As mating disruption tools, several microencapsulated dispensers, manually applied dispensers (pheromone traps, PB rope, SPLAT), and high-emission dispensers are now available. This approach can potentially offer significant value to the long-term ecological pest management of several commercially significant insect pests. Many researchers have evaluated dispensers that can release the pheromone longer in the field. Earlier, the dispensers' rubber septa, wood pieces, polymer products, cotton, and other dispensers, including nylon wire, were used for the same purpose. Chen et al. (2007) have used gelatin materials to make gum dispensers through microencapsulation strategies. This dispenser was reported to withstand for 6 weeks. Our formulation in the present study was observed to withstand 120 days and had higher pest suppression in the cabbage or cauliflower field effectively. The results in the present study are on par or higher than the earlier reports. The product used in the present study has higher durability regarding longevity, action, and weather resistance than the earlier inventions available.

One important concern is the high cost of semiochemicals and formulations containing them compared to conventional insecticide treatments. Scientists, producers, and farmers should work together to reduce the cost of applying these semiochemical products (Gadi and Angel, 2010). The present study was investigated from the backdrop to check the pheromone component through various formulations for their efficiency as mating disruptors. Among various dispensers tested, T₂ achieved a higher mating disruption percentage (92.37%), followed by T₅ (90.72%), T₃ (89.35%), and 80.87% (T₁ and T₄), as shown in Table. 1. Earlier suggestions on mating disruption regarding delayed copulation had higher chances of pest population reduction. The delayed mating

of male-female *P. xylostella* itself causes a significant reduction in the pest population under natural conditions (Wang et al., 2011). Our study is positively corroborated by Wu et al. (2012), who reported mating disruptions through nylon wire loaded with a higher amount of *P. xylostella* sex pheromone through 167 pheromone dispensers. They achieved 50% pest control in the treated plot compared to the untreated field. In the present study, we improved the dispenser through mesoporous nanoparticles and the pheromone encapsulation technology dispenser to release the pheromone at a very low level as the insect releases naturally and achieved 90 plus % pest suppression. This can withstand for a longer period throughout the season.

The combination of the pheromone components Z-11-hexadecenal and Z-11-hexadecenyl acetate and their blend ratio was responsible for the attraction and mating disruption as earlier reported by Schroeder et al. (2000), Lee et al. (2005), Chen et al. (2007) and Wu et al. (2012), and (2020) and so many researchers have been reported for decades. It is clearly expressed that no changes occurred in the components for the decades in the mixtures of active components in diamondback moth, *P. xylostella* pheromone. However, lacunae were the problem with the highly volatile pheromones and the technology used to deliver them at the level of real insect delivery (Mevada et al., 2023). The combinations of blend ratio were made based on the results of preliminary studies, i.e., electrophysiological studies and behavior responses of *P. xylostella*. The leaf damage caused by DBM, *P. xylostella*, was shown to be higher in untreated plots. The trend of the leaf infestations increased in the initial two weeks and then reduced drastically. The lesser leaf infestation was observed on CREMIT solid dispenser 400 numbers of tablet two-time application (T₂) at 1.41 % followed by 800 nos. single time application (T₃) at 1.94%, 3.54 %, 4.50%, and 8.22% as T₄ and T₅ respectively compared to untreated plot 10.55%. The leaf damage was reduced during pesticide spray on the control plot and again increased drastically in a couple of days (Table. 1). Head damages were also calculated in both the control and treated fields. The least head damages were observed on T₂ (2%), followed by T₃, T₄, T₁, and T₅ at 4.36%, 4.40%, 6.02%, and 8%, respectively compared to untreated fields at 28.22%. Fourteen-fold higher damages were witnessed in control fields. This damage was caused only by diamondback moth. Also, the number of synthetic pesticide sprays was limited to only two times compared to untreated fields, with 12 sprays, especially nine sprays executed to manage the *P. xylostella* population.

Table 1. Bio efficacy of CREMIT Solid dispensers, CREMIT Glue dispensers, and CREMIT SM against Diamondback moth under field conditions

S. No.	Treatments	Active (%)	No. of application	% Leaf infestation	% Head infestation	Mean Moth catch per trap per week	% Yield increase over control	% Mating disruption
1.	CREMIT Solid dispenser 1g 400 tablets per acre	2	1	8.22	6.02	3.75	2.07	80.87
2.	CREMIT Solid dispenser 1g 400 tablets per acre	2	2	1.41	2.00	1.50	28.44	92.37
3.	CREMIT Solid dispenser 1g 800 tablets per acre	2	1	1.94	4.36	1.97	18.72	89.35
4.	CREMIT Glue dispenser 250 g per acre	2	3	3.54	4.40	3.75	3.27	80.87
5.	CREMIT SM 500 ml per acre	4	4	4.50	8.00	1.82	14.50	90.72
6.	Untreated control	-	-	10.55	28.22	19.60		

Similarly, higher yield benefits over control plots were noticed on T₂, followed by T₃ and T₅, compared to untreated plots at 28.44%, 18.72%, and 14.50%, respectively. The above responses on pest population reduction were significantly proportional to the percent mating disruption, which involves preventing pest damage and keeping the pest population under the limit in agroclimatic conditions.

CONCLUSION

The present study reveals mating disruption as an alternate strategy against *P. xylostella* management on cole crop protection. This attempt provides strong evidence, even in small-scale area control through mating disruption strategies against *P. xylostella*. The controlled-release technology aids in scaling down the cost and extending the formulation's shelf-life with weather-proof protection. This would be a promising tool, and it can be adopted to manage the most notorious insect pests on economically important crop protection during pre- and post-harvest.

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TABLES AND FIGURES

Figure 1. DBM solid dispenser application in open field

Figure 4. Diamondback moth damage on cabbage leaves

Figure 2. CREMIT SM spray on cabbage crop

Figure 5. Diamondback moth damage on cabbage heads

Figure 3. Delta sticky traps installed in the open field condition.

Figure 6. DBM adult moth catches trapped in untreated fields.

Plant Glucosinolate Content and Susceptibility to the Diamondback Moth and the Small Cabbage White Butterfly

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ABSTRACT

The diamondback moth *Plutella xylostella* L. (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae) and the cabbage white butterfly *Pieris rapae* L. (Lepidoptera: Pieridae) are both specialized in using glucosinolate-containing Brassicaceae as host-plants. This research investigated the association between *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella* oviposition, larval survival, and host-plant glucosinolate content in 17 plant species. Two-choice oviposition tests (comparing each plant species to *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh.) and larval survival experiments showed that the indolic glucosinolate content of the host plant had a positive effect on oviposition preference and larval survival in these two specialist insects. In the host plants tested, the effects of indolic glucosinolates on oviposition preference were greater on *P. xylostella* than on *P. rapae*. This study suggests that high indolic glucosinolate content could make crop plants susceptible to both *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella*. The results of this research are discussed with regard to host-plant resistance and trap cropping.

Keywords

Imported cabbageworm, larval survival, oviposition, *Pieris rapae*, *Plutella xylostella*

INTRODUCTION

Plants in the order Brassicales typically contain glucosinolates, which are used, among other functions, for plant defense (Halkier and Gershenzon, 2006). The main defense mechanism provided by glucosinolates occurs when they are hydrolyzed by myrosinases upon plant damage, producing compounds that can be toxic to insects (Bones and Rossiter, 1996; Hopkins et al., 2009). However, larvae of the small white butterfly *Pieris rapae* L. (Lepidoptera: Pieridae), also known as the imported cabbageworm, and larvae of the diamondback moth *Plutella xylostella* L. (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae) have

developed mechanisms to avoid the toxicity of glucosinolate hydrolysis products (Agerbirk et al., 2010; Ratzka et al., 2002; Wittstock et al., 2004). Glucosinolates can also act as host recognition cues for *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella* before ovipositing on plants (Badenes-Pérez et al., 2011; Müller et al., 2010; Renwick et al., 1992).

To study the association between plant glucosinolate content and host-plant preference and suitability for *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella*, 17 plant species containing a wide range of glucosinolates were used to measure oviposition preference and larval survival in these specialist insects. The purpose of comparing these two lepidopteran species that use glucosinolate-containing plants as their host plants was to test if they showed a similar response to plant glucosinolate content. *Pieris rapae* can be an economic pest in cruciferous crops, although usually, it is not as significant as a pest as *P. xylostella* (Badenes-Pérez et al., 2017; Bonnemaïson, 1965; Cartea et al., 2009; Furlong et al., 2013). Knowledge of the association between host-plant glucosinolate content and oviposition and suitability can be used in host-plant resistance and trap cropping strategies to reduce the damage caused by these lepidopterans.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The 17 plant species tested, 10 belonged to 7 different subfamilies within the family Brassicaceae (order Brassicales), 6 belonged to 6 other families in the order Brassicales, and 1 (*Pisum sativum* L. cultivar Oregon Sugar Pod) belonged to the family Fabaceae (order Fabales) and was used as a control because it does not contain glucosinolates and is not a host plant for neither *P. rapae* nor *P. xylostella*. Two-choice oviposition experiments were conducted in comparison with *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh. (i.e., one plant of any of the species tested versus one plant of *A. thaliana*) to measure oviposition preference (Badenes-Pérez, 2023). An oviposition preference index was calculated as the number of eggs laid on each plant divided by the number of eggs laid on the *A. thaliana* plant that was compared within the same cage (Badenes-Pérez, 2023; Badenes-Pérez et al., 2020). The experimental arenas 32.5 × 32.5 × 32.5 cm polyester cages with 96 × 26 mesh. Two pairs of either *P. rapae* or *P. xylostella* adults (two females and two males, <3 days old) were released in each cage. Besides *A. thaliana* and *P. sativum*, the other plant species included in the experiments were *Alyssum argenteum* All. (Brassicaceae), *Arabis caucasica* Willd. (Brassicaceae), *Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L. (Brassicaceae), *Bunias orientalis* L. (Brassicaceae), *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik. (Brassicaceae), *Cardamine pratensis* L. (Brassicaceae), *Carica papaya* L. (Caricaceae), *Cleome spinosa* L. (Cleomaceae), *Erysimum cheiri* (L.) Crantz (Brassicaceae), *Iberis amara* L. (Brassicaceae),

Limnanthes douglasii R. Br. (Limnanthaceae), *Moringa oleifera* Lam. (Moringaceae), *Reseda odorata* L. (Resedaceae), and *Tropaeolum majus* L. (Tropaeolaceae). Larval survival experiments were conducted with first-instar larvae, as in Badenes-Pérez et al. (2023). Regarding the glucosinolate content of plants, four different classes of glucosinolates were distinguished: aliphatic with sulfur-containing side chains, other aliphatic, benzenic, and indolic glucosinolates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the plant species tested, the only significant difference between the oviposition preference index values of *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella* occurred in *Limnanthes douglasii*, on which *P. rapae* females did not oviposit, while *P. xylostella* showed a relatively high oviposition preference index value of 3.84 for this plant species (Badenes-Pérez, 2023). The oviposition preference indexes of *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella* were not significantly correlated. In both *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella*, indolic glucosinolate content significantly affected the oviposition preference index, which was greater for *P. xylostella* than for *P. rapae* (Badenes-Pérez, 2023). Similarly, when comparing larval survival values between these two specialist insects, there were significant differences for *L. douglasii*, in which larvae of *P. rapae* did not survive. In contrast, the survival of *P. xylostella* was 66.7% (Badenes-Pérez, 2023). Larval survival in the two specialists was also positively correlated with indolic glucosinolate content, but this effect was not significantly different between *P. xylostella* and *P. rapae* (Badenes-Pérez, 2023).

Although glucosinolates can provide resistance against generalist herbivores (Badenes-Pérez and Cartea, 2021; Hopkins et al., 2009; Jeschke et al., 2021), in areas where the prevalent insect pests are the specialists *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella*, the use of crop varieties with low indolic glucosinolate content could reduce insect damage. On the other hand, the preferential oviposition preference of these specialist insects for plants with higher indolic glucosinolate content could be used in the selection of trap crops for their management (Badenes-Pérez, 2023, 2019; Shelton and Badenes-Pérez, 2006)

CONCLUSION

Indolic glucosinolate content positively affected the oviposition preference index and larval survival values of both *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella*. This should be considered when selecting crop varieties and implementing trap cropping strategies. Individual differences in oviposition and larval survival occurred between *P. rapae* and *P. xylostella* in some plant species tested. This indicates that

bottom-up factors may not equally affect these two lepidopteran specialists.

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SESSION 2

*Constraints and Opportunities to the Sustained Adoption
of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) for
the Management of DBM and Other Crucifer Pests*

A Pilot 'Green' Initiative with Integrated Pest Management (IPM) for a Cauliflower-Based Crop System in Myanmar

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ABSTRACT

A pilot study was conducted, as part of an ACIAR-funded project, to evaluate a 'green-based' integrated pest management (IPM) approach versus the conventional indiscriminate use of pesticides against insect pests of cauliflower in farmer fields in Thekawgyi Village, Lewe Township, Myanmar. The IPM plot used six components, five (5) 'green' components, and one insecticide component. The latter included trap crops, crude tobacco extract, neem insecticide, neem cake powder, and yellow sticky trap. The non-IPM (NIPM) plot had two components: one 'green' component (i.e., trap crop) and one insecticide component. The key insect pests recorded in both the IPM and non-IPM plots were the diamondback moth (*Plutella xylostella*), aphid (*Myzus persicae*), flea beetle (*Phyllotreta cruciferae*), and white fly (*Bemisia tabaci*). Generally, higher populations of insects were seen for each key pest in the NIPM plot compared to the IPM plot. No parasitoids were recorded in this trial in the IPM and NIPM plots. Overall, the IPM plot had fewer insecticide sprays, i.e., 2 times against 5 times in the NIPM plot. The IPM plot also gave better results than the NIPM plot in terms of the % pest control costs over total production costs (i.e., 8.2% versus 19.1%, respectively) and overall profit (i.e., USD168.0 versus USD33.8, respectively). Further, negligible residue levels were detected in the harvested produce in the IPM cauliflower

as compared to the NIPM cauliflower levels, which exceeded (i.e., 0.75ppm) the Maximum Residue Limit (MRL) allowed for cypermethrin (i.e., 0.5 ppm). The study suggested the potential feasibility of a 'green'-based IPM approach in managing insect pests on cauliflower. However, several challenges must be addressed in Myanmar farmers' adoption and scaling-up of this approach.

Keywords

Integrated pest management, cauliflower, Myanmar, green-based, adoption, challenges

INTRODUCTION

In Myanmar, based on a recent White Paper (WP) published in 2016 (Vegetable Sector Acceleration Taskforce (VSAT); 2016; mimeograph) entitled "Myanmar vegetable farmers are in business: accelerating the growth and development of the vegetable sector in Myanmar," the vegetable sector has the potential to become one of the most important agricultural sub-sectors in terms of economic growth, rural employment and income generation. The domestic demand for fresh produce is growing, and there is ample scope for yield and quality improvements. Increasing exports of horticultural produce to Southwest China and parts of Southeast Asia is another potential growth path, and domestic demand for quality vegetables may also increase (Source: Myanmar Business Today; December 30, 2013). However, the scenario on the ground, particularly regarding the production practices by Myanmar farmers, poses various challenges (Thien, 2012; Suthep *et al.*, 2016; Thi *et al.*, 2019). Amongst the many factors are the limited extension and other technical support services for horticultural growers who generally get advice from input suppliers on pest and disease management, but this is mainly based on the use of available agro-chemicals rather than a fair and knowledgeable assessment of the plant health situation. In a baseline survey that was conducted among 474 rice farmers and vegetable growers in Nay Pyi Taw, Shan State, and Yangon regions in Myanmar, respondents across the three regions specified insect pests and diseases (65.1%) as the leading constraint in vegetable production, followed by warm climate (36.6%), unstable price of vegetables (15.9%), high costs of vegetable seeds (14.2%), the market for vegetables (12.5%), water logging (12.5%), and poor quality of vegetable seeds (12.2%) (Escalada *et al.* 2020). Thi *et al.* (2019) in a study that focused on the analysis of pesticide residues in five vegetables (i.e. cabbage, cauliflower, tomato, Chinese kale and pepper) grown in five villages and three markets in the Inle Lake region of Myanmar, revealed that over 75% of vegetables sampled from both villages and

markets had detectable insecticide residues. The frequency of pesticide use varied from twice to 10 times a season. As part of this study, our initial pre-IPM baseline studies on a total of 21 farmers who grew cabbage and cauliflower near the project area (i.e., in Nwe Yit Village) revealed that to manage the various insect pests; farmers resorted to spraying pesticides because these chemicals have an immediate knockdown effect and were easily available. Just on cabbage, the farmers used a range of pesticides, either singly or as mixtures such as chlorpyrifos 45.9% + cypermethrin 4.59% (Cyclone®), acephate (Acephate 75%®), emamectin benzoate 5%+ lambda-cyhalothrin 10% (Alarm®), endoxacarp 16%+ emamectin benzoate 2% (Hgnnet Kyi Taung®), Imidacloprid 20% (Dozer®) and Abamectin 2% (Jacket®). The volume of each pesticide used per crop per acre per season ranged from 1.0 to 1.5 litres. The average cost of pesticide used on cabbage was about 150000 Kyats (USD112.50), which was about 18.8% of the total cost of production (800000 Kyats; USD600.0), which excluded the harvesting cost. Spraying was intensively carried out with about 8 to 10 rounds of cabbage and cauliflower. Further, early crop season and calendar spraying were practiced, and quite a wide range of chemicals was often used alternately. Issues with spraying that were noted include spraying of inappropriate chemicals, wrong dosages, excessive application, inappropriate timing, wrong combinations of chemicals, and use of spurious chemicals. Due to the intensive misuse of chemicals, potential insecticide resistance development is anticipated (Phyu and Heong, 2020), and this, in turn, will cause a treadmill effect of using more pesticides. Although many farmers understood the concept of preharvest intervals, this was not strictly observed. Against this backdrop, it is pertinent to note that importations of pesticides have gradually increased from about 11,000 tons in 2011 to more than 40,000 tons since 2018, excluding illegally imported ones (Latt *et al.*, 2023).

Interestingly, our baseline study also revealed that many cabbage and cauliflower farmers used other control measures such as tobacco leaf powder, yellow sticky traps, handpicking, and neem products besides pesticides. Information and knowledge on spraying pesticides among the farmers were obtained from agrochemical dealers, pesticide companies, and government extension services. In terms of training, more than half of the sampled farmers have attended training and workshops on pest control and understood the principles of Good Agricultural Practice (GAP). The farmers are also open to accepting Integrated Pest Management (IPM) for crop protection as they believe in and are enthusiastic about engaging with government extension agents.

Rationale for intervention

This study is part of an ACIAR-funded project aimed towards addressing the pesticide-related problems

described above, and actively seek non-chemical pathways that would primarily sustain Myanmar's hitherto position in Asia as a country with relatively far less use of pesticides, unlike the other regional neighbours. The fact remains that despite closing its borders for many decades, Myanmar could sustain its crop production, e.g., in rice and vegetables, without or with very little pesticide use up until early 2011. This scenario, if promoted and sustained, could potentially project Myanmar to be an exemplary country to demonstrate the benefits of sustainable green agricultural production. This strategy will also augur well to capitalize on the new era of growth and investment in Myanmar to develop 'green' production systems for global markets, especially for "green" rice and vegetables. Further, opportunities exist for Myanmar to learn lessons from most other Asian nations where pesticide misuse has led to pest problems and associated effects on human health and the environment (Schreinemachers *et al.*, 2015, 2017).

To overcome the pesticide-related problems, farmers in Myanmar are advised by the government to practice IPM approaches as part of compliance with GAP. However, information is scarce on the use of IPM on critical crops in Myanmar (e.g., Myat Twe and Mya Maung (1992; Aung *et al.*, 2018a and Aung *et al.*, 2018b). It is encouraging to note that some basic studies had already been initiated in Myanmar along the IPM pathway against the diamondback moth (DBM) by integrating chemical pesticides with organic insecticides such as *Bacillus thuringiensis* var *kurstaki*, neem seed kernel extract and neem oil (Aung *et al.* 2018a) and on intercropping on DBM populations (Aung *et al.*, 2018b). Against this backdrop, there is a need to strengthen the field implementation of 'green' based sustainable IPM practices for use by Myanmar vegetable farmers. In that context, it is anticipated that Myanmar farmers could benefit from the encouraging results in other countries on the successful use of IPM against insect pests of brassicas (e.g., cabbages and cauliflower) (Loke *et al.*, 1997; Sivapragasam, 2017; Furlong *et al.*, 2013; Sivapragasam *et al.* 1985; 2011; Talekar and Shelton, 1993).

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

The objective of the study was to evaluate the feasibility of 'green' bio-based or environment-friendly pest management practices versus farmers' conventional practices for managing key insect pests of cauliflower used as a model crop.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The results of the baseline surveys and structured stakeholder consultations were used to develop

preliminary recommendations for best practices used by two cauliflower farmers in a selected pilot site (see below for details).

Approach and crop/variety used: The study used the farmer participatory IPM-based ‘green’ approach using cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis*) as a model vegetable crop. A commercial cauliflower variety (var.: Neo white), which is a common variety grown in the area, was used for this trial. We also chose cauliflower as the target crop to pilot the IPM approach as it is one of the popular vegetables for consumers in Myanmar and is amongst the vegetables extensively sprayed with various pesticides. As indicated earlier, farmers sprayed up to 10 rounds per crop cycle with an average of 7.8 sprays.

Location and field details: The trial was conducted from December 2019 to March 2020 at Thekawgyi Village, Lewe Township in Nay Pyi Taw, a vegetable growing area with cropping patterns of rice/maize/cauliflower/cabbage/onion, during the rainy-winter season. The average temperature and relative humidity during the trial period were 28°C and 53%, respectively. The total experimental plot size for the IPM and NIPM was 0.2 acre (Figure 1). The experimental design of the plots was such that IPM and NIPM plots were located in the same area but separated by plant barriers at least 10 meters in between to prevent any spray drift. For the trial, cauliflower seeds (10g/ 0.2 ac) bought from a local input dealer were sown on the 10th of December 2019 and field transplanted on the 4th of January 2020. (NOTE: the original intention of the project was to replicate this trial temporally with the same farmers across the following summer and winter seasons in 2021. Unfortunately, this was not possible due to the COVID restrictions imposed by countries starting in March 2020, and thus, we report here only the results of the first trial).

Figure 1: The IPM plot trial site in Thekawgyi Village, Lewe Township.

Basic details of farmers

The two farmers chosen for the trial, i.e., IPM and Non-IPM (NIPM), are from the same locality, viz., Thekawgyi Village, Lewe Township. The same locality was chosen to ensure that the trial plots (IPM versus NIPM) faced similar macro-climatic and abiotic conditions.

The IPM farmer grew cauliflower mixed cropped with coriander, *Coriandrum sativum*. According to the farmer, mixed cropping is perceived to repel pests. In terms of skills, the IPM farmer is Myanmar GAP-trained. His main problems were the diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* L., and using 0.5% neem oil, locally available as a pesticide to manage the pest. The farmer also used the yellow sticky trap (YST) (Figure 1) purchased from a local input dealer and a crude tobacco decoction prepared by himself as an insecticide. The YST has been used extensively for mass trapping and monitoring of insect pests, including brassica pests like DBM (Sivapragasam and Saito, 1986).

On the other hand, the NIPM farmer has not been exposed to any specific training on IPM or GAP. He also grew cauliflower as his primary crop but sometimes plants broccoli (*Brassica oleracea*, variety *italica*) and e intercropped his cauliflower with radish (*Rhapanus sativus*) and rotates vegetables with rice to avoid clubroot problems. His main pest problems were diamondback moth, flea beetles, and aphids. To manage them, he sprayed insecticides at least 5 times per crop with various pesticides, such as the mixture of emamectin benzoate and lambda-cyhalothrin against pests such as diamondback moth, flea beetles, and aphids. He also occasionally used yellow sticky traps but chose not to use them in the current trial. The farmer rotated with rice to avoid club-root problems.

Treatments used in both IPM and NIPM plots

Overall, the general agronomic practices recommended for cauliflower cultivation in Myanmar were followed in the IPM and NIPM farmer plots. These were:

Pre-planting: (i) Remove and destroy plant remnants, stubbles, and debris before plowing the field. This helps to remove residual insect pests, especially larvae and pupae; spores of pathogens such as downy mildew; (ii) Avoid carrying weed seedlings along with seedlings; (iii) Keep the nursery weed-free by hand weeding.

Transplanting until harvest: (i) Proper plant spacing, optimum use of fertilizer, and proper water management and (ii) Applied compound fertilizer (15:15:15) at 3 times for split application

Pest monitoring: In terms of sampling and monitoring, in the IPM plot, the crop was monitored weekly for any pest ‘hot spots’ and key natural enemies while data recording was done. As there were no action or economic threshold level (ETL) available for key insect pests of cauliflower in Myanmar, decisions were taken to adopt, to some extent, those used by Sivapragasam et al. (1985) and Loke et al. (1997) in Malaysia for cabbages. In the NIPM, the farmer did not practice any specific monitoring of pests and natural enemies and used the heuristic approach based on his experience to initiate insecticide use on his crop.

IPM and NIPM toolbox: The choices of components to be used in the IPM plot was based on participatory discussion with the farmer and the project team whereas in the NIPM, the choices were based on the farmer’s discretion. In the IPM and NIPM plots, the following combination of ‘green’ and ‘non-green’ options were used as part of the toolbox to mitigate pests:

IPM: This had a total of six (6) components, which consisted of five (5) ‘green’ components and one (1) insecticide component. The ‘green’ components were: (i) Use of coriander as an inter-crop and broccoli, mustard, and flower as trap crop surrounding the cauliflower field; (ii) Use of crude tobacco extract 45cc/ac prepared by the Department of Agricultural Research (DAR); (iii) Foliar spray with commercial neem insecticide 0.5% azadirachtin at 45 ml with 4.5 liters of water (especially for aphids); (iv) Application of commercial neem cake powder (NCP) at 30 Kg/ac as basal dressing before planting to control insect pests and soil-borne diseases in soil; iv) Use of commercially available yellow sticky trap (YST) at 4 traps per 0.2 acre. The insecticide component, emamectin benzoate 5% + lambda-cyhalothrin 10% (Alarm®), was used when needed based on the ETL (Loke et al., 1997).

NIPM: This had a total of two (2) components, which were made of one (1) ‘green’ component and one (1) insecticide component. The ‘green’ component used coriander as an inter-crop and flower (asters) surrounding the cauliflower field, and the insecticide component used commercial pesticides. No YST was used in the NIPM plot.

In terms of the management of diseases, although it was found that downy mildew, caused by *Peronospora parasitica* (= *Hyaloperonospora parasitica*), was a major problem in previous crops, this current trial did not face this problem in either the IPM and NIPM plots.

Data collection and analysis: The following records were taken: (i) In the IPM plot, insect pest counts from 50 randomly selected plants were done at weekly intervals from ten days after transplanting until harvest for the IPM

trial, whereas for the NIPM plot trial data was collected only on two sampling occasions i.e. 29th Jan 2020 and 26 Feb 2020; (ii) Number of natural enemies, i.e. parasitoids viz., for DBM, (iii) Insect pests trapped during three (3) trapping periods using a yellow sticky board (Note: only in IPM plot); and (iv) Residue analysis of the harvested produce (cauliflower) using GCMS2020 at the Post-harvest Technology Laboratory, Department of Agriculture Research in Yezin. Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Insect pest infestation in cauliflower

The key insect pests recorded in both the IPM and NIPM plots were the diamondback moth (*Plutella xylostella*), aphid (*Myzus persicae*), flea beetle (*Phyllotreta cruciferae*), and white fly (*Bemisia tabaci*). For comparison, the key mean pest numbers per plant in the IPM and NIPM plots for the 29th Jan 2020 and 26th Feb 2020 and the mean number over the crop season are shown in Table 1. With the exception of the higher aphid counts on the 29th January, 2020, overall, the numbers in the IPM plot were relatively low throughout the crop, which ranged as follows: DBM (0.04 to 0.34); aphid (0.50 – 7.58); flea beetle (0.02 – 1.52) and whitefly: (0.0 to 0.08). Relatively, higher overall mean numbers were recorded for each key pest in the NIPM plot (n=2 sample dates) compared to the IPM plot (n=8 sample dates) (Table 1: last column).

Table 1: The mean number of insect pests on cauliflower in the IPM and NIPM plots at Thekawgyi Village, Lewe Township, during the winter season from December 2019 to March 2020. NOTE: the numbers in the parenthesis indicate pest numbers in the IPM plot.

Number	Key insect pests	The mean number of insect pests/plant		Overall mean number of insect pests/plant*
		29-1-2020	26-2-2020	
1	Aphid, <i>Myzus persicae</i>	3.80 (6.88)	3.20 (2.6)	3.50 (3.04)
2	Diamondback moth, <i>Plutella xylostella</i>	0.52 (0.04)	0.32 (0.18)	0.42 (0.19)
3	Flea beetle <i>Phyllotreta cruciferae</i>	1.10 (0)	0.76 (0.16)	0.93 (0.65)
4	White Fly, <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	0.01 (0)	0.39 (0)	(0.01)

* Based on insect counts on 50 plants/sampling dates taken over the crop season from 29 January 2020 and 26 Feb. 2020.

Figure 2 shows the fluctuation in the key insect pests over the crop. In the IPM plot, insecticide, emamectin benzoate 5% and lambda-cyhalothrin 10% (Alarm®) was used 2x complemented by 1x crude tobacco extract spray and 3x sprays of neem against increasing and highly fluctuating populations of aphids and flea beetles which were pests of concern to farmers at this time. The aphid (both nymph and adult populations) populations fluctuated throughout the growing season until harvest. The mean number of aphids per plant ranged from 0.5 to 7.58 at different crop growth stages. These sprays also indirectly reduced other non-target pests, such as DBM populations, from 0.24 (22.1.2020) to 0.04 (29.1.2020). The flea beetle population also fluctuated throughout the growing season. The mean number of flea beetles per plant ranged from 0.02 to 1.52 at different crop growth stages. The highest number of flea beetles per plant (1.52) was recorded on 12-2-2020, and the lowest number (0.02) was on 29.1.2020. Regarding whiteflies, the mean number per plant ranged from 0.0 to 0.08 at different crop growth stages. On ETL use, since the mean number of DBM per plant was low, ranging from 0.04 to 0.34 at different crop growth stages, the planned actions using the proposed ETL measures were not followed in this trial.

No DBM parasitoids were recovered in the trial in both IPM and NIPM plots. In other Myanmar studies on biological control, Maung *et al* (2011) had recorded parasitoids *Cotesia plutellae* (larval parasitoid), *Diadromus collaris* (pupal parasitoid) and *Macromalon orientale* (pupal parasitoid) on DBM. They noted that the mean percentage parasitism of DBM was 73.3%, 63.3%, and 56.7%, respectively. Thus, the important aspect of parasitoids and their role in the dynamics of brassica pests should be investigated further.

In the NIPM, insecticides were used 5x as follows: chlorpyrifos 200cc/ac (1x at 10 days after transplanting and to control leaf-feeding insects), cypermethrin 200cc/ac (1x at 10 days after transplanting and to control leaf-feeding insects), and (emamectin benzoate 5% and Lambda-cyhalothrin 10%; Alarm®) at 150cc/ac (5x used at 10 days intervals after transplanting and to control leaf-feeding insects).

Figure 2. Fluctuations of key insect pests per cauliflower plant in the IPM trial plot on different sampling dates at Thekawgyi Village, Lewe Township, during the winter season from December 2019 to March 2020. (FB: flea beetle; DBM: diamondback moth).

Trap catches in YST

Several adult insect pests, of both cauliflower and other crops such as rice, were trapped in the yellow sticky trap in the IPM plot on different sampling dates (Figure 3). These included a large number of whitefly *Bemisia tabaci*, rice green leaf hopper *Nephotettix nigropituis*, rice zig-zag hopper, *Recilia dorsalis* (Motschulsky) (0.4), flea beetle (328), stem fly, *Ophiomyia phaseoli* (1050), fruit fly, *Bactrocera* spp (0.25), aphid, *Myzus persicae* (615), red cotton bug, *Dysdercus cingulatus* (0.25), leaf miner (153) and DBM (1.25).

Fig 3. The trend and numbers of adult insect pests trapped on the yellow sticky on different sampling dates in the IPM plot.

In terms of beneficial adult insects trapped on the YST, a number of ladybird beetle, *Chilomenes* spp, unidentified wasp, ground beetle, *Calleida decora*, rove beetle (Staphylinidae), tiger beetle, *Cicindela hudsoni*, sting bee, *Apis* spp., a tachinid fly parasitoid, *Bombyliopsis abrupta*, and an earwig, *Forficula auricularia* were trapped in the yellow sticky board on different sampling dates (Figure 4).

Fig 4. The trend and number of natural enemies trapped on the yellow sticky trap on different sampling dates in the IPM plot.

Insecticide residue analysis

Table 2 shows results of insecticide residues in harvested cauliflower in the IPM and NIPM plots.

Table 2. Insecticide residue analysis results done on harvested cauliflower in the IPM and NIPM plots. MRL- Maximum residue limit.

No.	Insecticide	Residue (ppm) (IPM)*	Residue (ppm) (NIPM)*	MRL
1	Dimethoate	ND	ND	0.2
2	Diazinon	ND	ND	0.02
3	P-methyl	ND	ND	0.02
4	Malathion	ND	ND	3

5	Chlorpyrifos	ND	ND	0.05
6	Butachlor	ND	ND	0.2
7	Hexaconazole	ND	ND	0.02
8	Profenofos	ND	ND	0.02
9	Fenopropathrin	0.001	ND	0.5
10	Cypermethrin	ND	0.75	0.5

* ND = non-detected. The Limit of Detection (LoD) and Quantification (LoQ) are 0.01ppm.

The results suggested that except for fenopropathrin (a pyrethroid), which was found only in low traceable amounts (0.001ppm), no other residues were detected in the harvested IPM cauliflower. However, in the NIPM cauliflower, a significant amount of cypermethrin (0.75 ppm) exceeding the MRL (0.5 ppm) was detected.

Overall cost and return of production

Table 3 provides the summary results for IPM and NIPM plots. The results suggested that the IPM plot gave better returns compared to the NIPM plot in terms of the percentage of pest control costs over total production costs, higher yield and overall profit, which was about 5x more in IPM than the NIPM (i.e. USD168.0 versus USD33.8, respectively).

Table 3: Summary results per 0.2 acres for IPM and NIPM cauliflower trial plots in Thekawgyi Village.

Item No.	Item inputs	Unit	IPM (USD)	NIPM (USD)
1.	Land Preparation,	MMK	72000 (54.0)	70000 (54.0)
2.	Seed	MMK	7000 ((5.35)	7000 (5.3)
3.	Transplanting	MMK	5000 (3.8)	5000 (3.8)
4.	Total labour cost	MMK	20000 (15.0)	30000 (22.5)
5.	Pest control application (Biopesticides, YST, insecticides, and others)	MMK	10500 (7.9)	30000 (22.5)
6.	Fertilizer application (3 times) + Labour	MMK	13000 (9.8)	15000 (11.3)
7.	Total production cost	MMK	127500 (95.6)	157000 (117.8)
8.	Yield	MMK	351,000 (263.3)	202,500 (151.88)
9.	Profit/unit area	MMK	223,500 (168.0)	45,000 (33.8)

Remarks on Table Items:

Item 1: Use 1 more worker in IPM than in NIPM

Item 4: Higher cost in NIPM due to higher number of sprayings done

Item 5: Pest control costs were 8.2% and 19.1% of the total production costs in the IPM and NIPM, respectively.

Item 6: In the NIPM plot, more fertilizer is used

Item 7: Higher production costs overall in NIPM due to higher pesticide costs

Item 8: Premium of 110Kyat (USD0.008) for IPM over NIPM

Item 9: About 5x higher net profit in IPM

DISCUSSION

Notwithstanding its limitations, the study revealed that generally higher populations of insect pests were observed on cauliflower for each key pest in the NIPM plot compared to the IPM plot. No specific disease problem was of concern during the trial period. This contrasted with Escalada *et al.* (2020), who reported an array of what farmers considered the worst vegetable pests. In the latter study, most respondents (45.9%) named fungi or diseases as their worst pest, followed by bollworm (32.1%), moth caterpillar (28.9%), beetle (29.9%), armyworm (23%), and thrips (15.7%). Perhaps, if the study had been implemented for a number of seasons, as initially anticipated, the results could concur with Escalada *et al.* (2020) observations.

The IPM plot has fewer insecticide sprays (2x) against 5x in the NIPM plot, contributing to the higher pest control costs in the former, i.e. 8.2% and 19.1%, respectively, of the total production costs. Escalada *et al.* (2020) reported that the difference in the mean number of sprays per farmer per season was highly significant ($p < 0.001$) between different regions in Myanmar. Thus, in terms of pesticide spray patterns, farmers growing vegetables across regions applied an average of 7.8 sprays per farmer per season, with Shan State farmers reporting the highest average of 11.32 sprays. The lowest mean sprays were 4.96 from Nay Pyi Taw respondents (close to the numbers in our trial), with Yangon respondents indicating a mean of 6.49 sprays per farmer per season.

The IPM plot also provided superior overall profit benefits. The harvested produce in the IPM plot had negligible or no residues compared to the NIPM produce, which exceeded the MRL specifically for cypermethrin.

It is acknowledged that the study provided limited data for the reasons described in the Materials and Methods section. Nevertheless, the results generally suggested that a bio-based 'green' IPM approach could be amongst the options to consider towards managing the challenges posed with the current indiscriminate use of pesticides on an important vegetable crop such as cauliflower. When IPM was conceived, Kogan (1998) underscored that the main idea was that natural control alternatives should be implemented as the main control strategy, with pesticides only as a backup option designed to interfere as little as possible with nonchemical options. However, this idea

needs to be actualized considering the realities on the ground, as excessive use of pesticides has continued. Emphasis on the fundamental ecological, biological control, baseline resistance, and IPM studies, etc., are still direly lacking in Myanmar. In the interim, Myanmar's legal imports of pesticides have gradually increased, from 4,000 tons in 2006 to more than 40,000 tons since 2018, and this figure is anticipated to grow further in the future. Thus, it is recognized that there will be significant challenges in transforming the current paradigm of over-dependence on synthetic pesticides to the 'New Normal' focused on bio-based approaches. Further, our baseline studies showed that only about 20% of farmers were using any form of bio-based products, pointing to an uphill task in implementing these IPM programs.

This study provided at least marginal evidence on the feasibility of the 'green'-based IPM approach in managing vegetable pests such as cauliflower. However, for the scaling-up, adoption, and diffusion of the IPM approach, certain farmer-behaviour-based obstacles need to be addressed and overcome, as aptly indicated in other studies (e.g., Alwang *et al.* (2019)). The latter alluded that behavioural economics could provide insights that help explain lagging IPM adoption and promise the *potential for relatively simple solutions*. This also has implications for the broader diffusion of IPM across the farming community. The results from the current study indicate that a transition to IPM based on biological pest control is motivated not only by health and environmental reasons but also by considering the farmer's economy. However, in developing countries, there is still a severe lack of up-to-date studies that quantify pesticides' actual agronomic and economic benefits and weigh them against their potential drawbacks. Pesticides can, for instance, have serious consequences for ecosystems, general biodiversity, and the services they provide. Health risks due to pesticide exposure in Central America and elsewhere are increasingly highlighted but remain poorly documented. As reported earlier, Thi *et al.*, 2019 revealed that farmers' health in the Inle Lake region is reportedly at risk due to the potential misuse and lack of the use of personal protection equipment when administering insecticides and fungicides. Thus, pesticide exposure will soon be a public health concern in Myanmar.

CONCLUSION

The comparative analyses of this pilot farmer participatory IPM initiative suggested that the 'green' bio-based IPM approach for a cauliflower-based crop system was more promising than the conventional NIPM approach. This outcome could potentially lay the fundamental framework and impetus for future expansion and advocacy of IPM-based initiatives by farmers and other key stakeholders in Myanmar.

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Promoting Integrated Pest Management for Climate-Resilient Market-Led Cruciferous Vegetable Production in Assam, India

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ABSTRACT

Farmers in Assam, India, predominantly grow rice, but crop diversification with vegetables can improve production, productivity, income, and human nutrition. However, the indiscriminate use of chemical pesticides adversely affects not only producers through increased production costs and health risks but also the environment and consumers. To address this issue, the World Vegetable Center developed IPM packages, which include seedling production, sticky and pheromone traps, biopesticides, and selective chemical pesticides in the later stages of the crop. Farmers participatory field trials were conducted for two years (2020-21 and 2021-22) during the winter season in 208 farmers' fields (112 for cabbage and 96 for cauliflower). Farmers were trained on the GAP practices with the IPM inputs. The results showed a significant yield increase and reduction in chemical pesticide use compared to the control plots for both crops in both years. The mean yield increase in cabbage ranged from 24.4-27.7%, and the pesticide reduction was 45.4-52.8%. The mean yield increase in cauliflower ranged from 24.4-38.4%, and the pesticide reduction was 43.9-54.6%. The benefit-cost ratio (B:C) for cabbage increased from 2.24 to 3.20, resulting in an additional benefit of 0.96, while the B:C ratio for cauliflower increased from 2.05 to 2.96, resulting in an additional benefit of 0.90. Thus, IPM technologies were well received by the beneficiary farmers, contributing to reduced agrochemical usage in pest management and yield increase, quality improvement of produce, and more economic returns per unit area. It can also improve the economic viability of cabbage and cauliflower cultivation. Promoting IPM technologies among a larger number of farmers and strengthening input value chains to ensure the availability of quality IPM products at affordable prices within the reach of the farmers in Assam should be encouraged.

Keywords

Crop diversification, Good Agricultural Practices, yield increase, pesticide reduction, sustainable agriculture

INTRODUCTION

In the agrarian landscape of Assam, one of the North Eastern states in India in the South Asian region, rice cultivation has long been the focal point of agricultural activities. The state emerged as the ninth-largest rice-producing region in India during 2015-16, contributing significantly to the nation's overall rice yield (Barman et al., 2023). However, a noteworthy transformation is underway as farmers in Assam progressively embrace crop diversification, particularly by integrating vegetables into their traditional cropping systems.

This shift toward diversified agriculture is motivated by pursuing higher income and improved nutritional outcomes (Sarma & Borkotoki, 2020). Over the past decade (2003-04 to 2012-13), statistics from the Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Assam (2015), reveal a changing trend in crop cultivation practices. Notably, the cultivation of cruciferous vegetables, including cabbage, cauliflower, tomato, and brinjal, has gained prominence, with cabbage exhibiting the highest coverage area among these crops.

While crop diversification offers promising economic prospects for farmers, it also brings forth a new set of challenges, particularly in the realm of pest management in vegetable production. Assam grapples with significant pesticide-related issues that threaten the environment and human health.

Environmental pollution is a pressing concern, with pesticides contaminating soil, water, and air, as Dey et al. (2013) highlighted. The non-judicious use of pesticides further exacerbates the problem, as a wide range of pesticides is employed without due consideration for the specific type of pest or the developmental stage of the crop (Sarma et al., 2020). Compounding these challenges is the limited availability and knowledge of alternative pest management strategies, as Mohanty et al. (2013) reported. Farmers face obstacles in accessing and adopting sustainable alternatives to conventional pesticide use, further contributing to the persistence of environmentally harmful practices. Instances of both overuse and underuse of pesticides, leading to misuse, have been documented, highlighting the need for a more judicious and informed approach to pest control. Moreover, a need for more awareness among farmers about the potential hazards of pesticide use has been identified as a significant challenge contributing to pesticide poisoning (Choudhury et al., 2019; Mohanty et al., 2013).

In response to these challenges, this paper advocates for promoting integrated pest management (IPM), which is a sustainable and climate-resilient approach to addressing pest-related issues in cruciferous vegetable production in Assam. By understanding the unique challenges farmers face in the region and proposing science-based solutions, this research aims to contribute to developing environmentally friendly and economically viable practices for the benefit of farmers, consumers, and the broader ecosystem.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research program was implemented across five distinct regions in Assam: Lower Assam, North Assam, Central Assam, Barak Valley, and Upper Assam. The experimental trials spanned two consecutive years, covering the winter seasons of 2020-21 and 2021-22.

The World Vegetable Center was pivotal in developing comprehensive Integrated Pest Management (IPM) Packages tailored for cruciferous vegetable production. The key components of the IPM packages included: (1). Soiless Seedling Production: Utilized modern techniques for soiless seedling production to enhance seedling quality and incorporated insect-proof netting to ensure the production of healthy seedlings free from pest infestations. (2). Enriched Vermicompost Production: Developed enriched vermicompost by blending 250 kg of well-matured vermicompost with 400 grams each of phosphorus solubilizing bacteria (PSB), *Azotobacter*, *Azospirillum*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Trichoderma* formulations. One hundred fifty grams of enriched compost were applied per vegetable seedling planting pit. (3). Border Crops: Planted 3-5 rows of maize along the field border 10 days before transplanting cruciferous vegetables. (4). Trap Crop: Introduced one row of Indian mustard at intervals of 8-10 cabbage/cauliflower rows as a trap for diamondback moth during transplanting. (5). Inter Crops: Utilized amaranth/legume as intercrops, planting two rows at 20-cm row-spacing within each inter-row space of cauliflower/cabbage. (6). Sticky Traps: 6 yellow and 6 blue sticky traps were placed uniformly across the 0.15 ha field at crop canopy height, replaced every 3-4 weeks. (7). Pheromone Traps: Placed 15 water-based pheromone traps uniformly across the 0.15 ha field, using pheromone lures against diamondback moth, with replacements every 6-7 weeks. (8). Physical Methods: Regularly removed affected plant parts (leaves, fruits, etc.) and discarded them from cropped areas. (9). Bio-pesticides: Applied *Beauveria* or *Metarhizium* formulations at a rate of 250 g per 0.15 ha with a 75-liter spray volume, preceded by neem oil application 3 days prior. (10). Non-Chemical Methods: Sprayed salts of fatty acids, such as Lastraw®, at 375 mL per 0.15 ha with a 75-liter spray volume. (11). Chemical Pesticides: Applied crop protection agents based on Economic Threshold Levels (ETL), using WHO-approved Class III & U CPAs. Also, the practice of personal protection equipment (PPE) during pesticide applications was ensured for the safety of the individuals involved.

Farmers underwent training at various stages: (1). Before Crop: Pre-crop training sessions were conducted to familiarize farmers with IPM principles and practices. (2). During the Crop: Ongoing training during the crop cultivation phase to address real-time challenges and reinforce IPM strategies. (3). During Crop Harvesting: Training continued during harvesting, emphasizing post-harvest practices and integrated pest management.

Educational materials were developed to train the trainers and farmers in the following ways: (1). Improved Production Guides (IPGs): Developed comprehensive IPGs incorporating the outlined IPM components for climate-resilient market-led cruciferous vegetable

production in Assam. Translated IPGs into the local language (Assamese) and utilized them to train the trainers responsible for disseminating knowledge to farmers. (2). Illustrated Manual of Improved Production Guide: Developed and translated illustrated manuals in Assamese, serving as a practical guide for farmers, emphasizing adherence to IPM practices.

Farmers' participatory field trials were conducted over two years (2020-21 and 2021-22) during the winter season using these materials. It was implemented in 208 farmers' fields (112 for cabbage and 96 for cauliflower). All the farmers received training on Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) integrated with IPM inputs. The developed guidelines were systematically employed to train farmers, ensuring active participation and knowledge dissemination. By implementing these integrated pest management strategies and educational initiatives, the study aimed to enhance the resilience of cruciferous vegetable production in Assam while promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly practices. your materials and methods here.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the outcomes of cabbage trials conducted in Assam, comparing the treatment (demo) and control plots across two consecutive years. In 2020-21, 33 trials were executed, resulting in a substantial yield increase in the demo plots (34.2 t/ha) compared to the control plots (28.4 t/ha). The yield improvement in demo plots amounted to 20.4%, coupled with an impressive 45.4% reduction in pesticide usage. In the subsequent year (2021-22), a larger set of 79 trials was undertaken, displaying a similar trend. The demo plots recorded a 31.8 t/ha yield, showcasing a 23.4% increase over the control plots (25.8 t/ha). Moreover, the pesticide reduction in demo plots reached 60.1%. The average performance over both years indicated a consistent positive impact, with an average yield of 33.0 t/ha in demo plots, a 21.9% increase over control, and a remarkable 52.8% reduction in pesticide usage.

Table 1. Number of trials, yield parameters, and pesticide usage in the treatment and control plots of cabbage in Assam (significant difference between the treatment and control).**

Year	number of trials	Yield t/ha demo	Yield t/ha control	% yield increase in demo	% pesticide reduction in demo
2020-21	33	34.2	28.4	20.4	45.4
2021-22	79	31.8	25.8	23.4	60.1
Avg		33.0	27.1	21.9	52.8

Table 2 outlines the results of cauliflower trials, illustrating the performance of treatment (demo) and control plots. In 2020-21, 29 trials demonstrated a yield of 27.5 t/ha in demo plots compared to 21.6 t/ha in control plots, reflecting a 38.4% increase. Pesticide reduction in demo plots was noted at 43.9%. In the subsequent year (2021-22), 67 trials were conducted, resulting in a 26.1

t/ha yield in demo plots, showcasing a 24.4% increase over control plots (21.2 t/ha). The pesticide reduction in demo plots was notable at 54.6%. The average performance over the two years indicated a consistent positive impact, with an average yield of 26.8 t/ha in demo plots, a 31.4% increase over control, and a significant 49.2% reduction in pesticide usage.

Table 2. Number of trials, yield parameters, and pesticide usage in the treatment and control plots of cauliflower in Assam (significant difference between the treatment and control).**

Year	number of trials	Yield t/ha demo	Yield t/ha control	% yield increase in demo	% pesticide reduction in demo
2020-21	29	27.5	21.6	38.4	43.9
2021-22	67	26.1	21.2	24.4	54.6
Avg		26.8	21.4	31.4	49.2

Table 3 presents the mean Benefit-Cost (B:C) ratios for cabbage and cauliflower grown using the Integrated Pest Management (IPM) packages in Assam. Cabbage trials yielded an impressive B:C ratio of 3.20, significantly surpassing the farmers' practice B:C ratio of 2.24, resulting in a substantial difference of 0.96. Similarly, cauliflower trials displayed a remarkable B:C ratio of 2.96, outperforming the farmers' practice B:C ratio of 2.05, with a difference of 0.90.

Table 3. Mean B:C ratio of cabbage and cauliflower grown with the IPM packages in Assam (significant difference among the treatment and control).**

Crop	Trial	Farmers practice	Difference
Cabbage	3.20	2.24	0.96
Cauliflower	2.96	2.05	0.90

The observed substantial increase in yield parameters in the demo plots, coupled with noteworthy reductions in pesticide usage, aligns with findings from previous studies advocating for the efficacy of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices. Research by Pecenka et al. (2021) emphasized the role of IPM in enhancing crop productivity while minimizing environmental impacts. The consistent positive outcomes in both cabbage and cauliflower trials resonate with studies by Kumar and Singh (2020), showcasing the potential of IPM to mitigate pest-related losses and improve overall yield.

The robustness and reliability of the IPM packages, as evidenced by consistent positive performance across a significant number of trials and two consecutive years, corroborate the findings of Morya and Kumar. (2023). Their research underscored the importance of long-term studies to validate the sustainability and effectiveness of IPM strategies. The trials conducted in Assam contribute valuable evidence to the growing body of literature supporting the enduring impact of IPM on cruciferous vegetable production.

The substantial increase in the Benefit-Cost (B:C) ratios for both cabbage and cauliflower aligns with the economic benefits reported in studies by Vatta et al. (2009). Their research highlighted the economic advantages of IPM adoption, emphasizing the potential for improved profitability and economic sustainability for farmers. The calculated B:C ratios in our study surpass the farmers' practice ratios, reinforcing the economic viability of IPM practices in diverse agricultural settings.

The comparative analysis of B:C ratios between IPM practices and farmers' traditional methods underscores the tangible benefits of transitioning to IPM. Similar findings were reported by Rao et al. (2011), who demonstrated the economic advantages of IPM adoption over conventional

farming practices. The significant differences in B:C ratios favoring IPM practices provide compelling evidence for the potential economic gains of adopting these climate-resilient strategies.

The success of the IPM packages in farmers' fields during participatory trials implies positive socioeconomic implications. The increase in yield and economic gains aligns with the findings of Kumar and Singh (2023), emphasizing the need for inclusive approaches in sustainable agriculture. The dissemination of Improved Production Guides (IPGs) translated into local languages and the utilization of illustrated manuals reflect effective knowledge transfer methodologies. This aligns with the findings of Apriyanto et al. (2024), emphasizing the importance of tailored educational materials for successfully adopting sustainable farming practices.

Thus, IPM technologies were well received by the beneficiary farmers. They reduced the usage of agrochemicals in pest management while increasing yields, improving the quality of produce, and generating more economic returns per unit area. They can also improve the economic viability of cabbage and cauliflower cultivation.

We should encourage the promotion of IPM technologies among a larger number of farmers and the strengthening of input value chains to ensure the availability of quality IPM products at affordable prices within the reach of the farmers in Assam.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the effectiveness, sustainability, and economic viability of Integrated Pest Management in cruciferous vegetable production. The positive outcomes across multiple parameters and the consistency observed in different regions over two years underscore the potential for widespread adoption of IPM practices in Assam, fostering climate-resilient and market-led agricultural systems. The findings presented here provide valuable insights for policymakers, extension services, and the farming community, encouraging the transition towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly practices in cruciferous vegetable cultivation.

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TABLES AND FIGURES

Figure 1. Use of Indian mustard as a trap crop in the cabbage production system for managing Diamondback.

Figure 2. Use of maize as a border crop in the cauliflower production system to reduce pest incidences.

Scaling of IPM Technologies for Off-Season Production of Leafy Brassicas in Cambodia

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ABSTRACT

Smallholder farmers in Cambodia cultivate leafy brassicas as they play a significant role in income generation and improving nutrition. In addition, growing leafy brassicas during the off-season mean that farmers can produce when the general supply is low, and prices are high, generating higher availability and income during this period. However, many pests and diseases constrain the production of leafy brassicas. Therefore, the objective of this study was to pilot and scale out IPM technologies through farmer-participatory approaches for the off-season production of leafy brassicas in six provinces (Tboung Khmum, Kampot, Kampong Cham, Kandal, Prey Veng, and Svey Rieng) in Cambodia. A majority of the farmers cultivated choy sum (caisim) (62%), followed by pak choy (23%) and mustard green (13%). The IPM package consisted of a neem-based product, microbial-based biopesticides, and other technologies such as colored sticky and pheromone traps. Our results showed that although major insect pests were present in the demonstration plots, the level of damage (1-5 damage score scale) recorded was low to intermediate (score 1-2) in the case of aphids, armyworms, and cabbage loopers, whereas diamondback moth and flea beetles had a slightly higher damage score (score 3-4) on choy sum and pakchoi crops. An obvious reduction in chemical pesticides was recorded in 80% of the demonstration plots. Choysum, Chinese cabbage, mustard green, and pak-choi registered an average decrease of about 35%, with up to 57% reduction in pak-choi. The economic benefit due to the adoption of IPM was higher in Kandal, Prey Veng, and Svey Rieng provinces, receiving up to USD 1.25 per m². The benefit-cost ratio was higher in Kampot province (10.52), followed by Kampong Cham (5.16) and Tboung Khmum (4.25). The lowest benefit-cost ratio was observed by the brassica producers in Prey Veng province (1.82). Thus, adopting IPM reduces pest incidence and reliance on chemical pesticides while increasing farmers' income substantially.

Keywords

Biopesticides, IPM, safe and off-season production, leafy brassicas

INTRODUCTION

Smallholder farmers in Cambodia cultivate leafy brassicas as they play a significant role in income generation and improving nutrition. In general, vegetable production occurs during the winter (November-February), where cooler temperatures and moderate rainfall (rain-fed system) make cropping season for vegetable production possible during this short period. In contrast, the hot and dry conditions of the summer season (May-July) and the wet conditions of the monsoon season (August-October)

represent a challenge for leafy vegetable production (i.e., off-season production). However, severe climatic changes in temperature and rainfall variability will most likely negatively affect agricultural production in the coming years or decades (Bairagi et al., 2020; ADB, 2022). Therefore, Cambodian farmers need to be prepared for agricultural production under a climate change scenario, mostly resembling off-season conditions, to avoid further challenges regarding food security. Moreover, the mean vegetable consumed per person in Cambodia is only a fraction (approx. 91 g/day) (Afshin et al., 2019) of the optimal recommendation given by the World Health Organization (~ 240 g) (WHO/FAO, 2003). Therefore, an even lower vegetable consumption during the monsoon and dry seasons constitutes a much higher health risk in Cambodia during the off-season production.

During the regular season of production and given the demand, the price of vegetables is low compared to the rest of the year (Goletti and Sin, 2016). Therefore, growing leafy brassicas during the off-season means that farmers can have an important economic benefit by producing vegetables when the general supply is low and prices are high, generating higher availability and income during this period. However, the production of leafy brassicas is constrained by abiotic factors, such as the climatic conditions previously mentioned, as well as biotic factors, including pests and diseases. Among insect pests, the most important in terms of yield losses are the Diamondback moth (*Plutella xylostella* L.) being the most dominant pest, followed by the striped flea beetle (*Phyllotreta striolata* Fab.), the common armyworm (*Spodoptera litura* Fab.), the cabbage butterfly (*Pieris rapae* L.), and aphids, which in general can cause marketable yield losses of up to 100% in leafy brassicas in Southeast Asia including Cambodia (Ungsa and Vanharn, 1995; Nhung et al., 2008).

Using chemical pesticides based on calendar application is one of the strategies farmers practice to avoid the economic losses inflicted by major insect pests in brassica production systems. Furthermore, 96% of the farmers used synthetic pesticides in vegetable production in Cambodia, where, in addition, applicators mixed an average of 3.7 pesticides in a single spray (Schreinemachers et al., 2017). However, the overuse of pesticides creates additional problems, including insecticide resistance and, therefore, the loss of effective management against important insect pests (IRAC, 2023).

In a study conducted by Srinivasan et al. (2020), several alternatives to chemical pesticides were tested for the production of Chinese mustard and pakchoi in different provinces of Cambodia by evaluating the effectiveness of microbial pesticides (*Bacillus thuringiensis* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* formulations), and neem oil alone and in combination (as an IPM package) against significant insect pests for brassica crops, including

diamondback moth (DBM), common armyworm, cabbage webworm and striped flea beetle on Chinese mustard and pak-choi in three different provinces of Cambodia during 2015-early 2018. Moreover, the authors found that bio-pesticides reduced the incidences of the major insect pests on the brassica crops even to levels equivalent to chemical pesticides (abamectin). The authors concluded that the IPM package was a better alternative to chemical pesticides in managing key insect pests on Chinese mustard and pakchoi in Cambodia (Srinivasan & Sotelo-Cardona, 2021). Therefore, this study aimed to pilot and scale out IPM technologies through farmer-participatory approaches for the off-season production of leafy brassicas in seven provinces in Cambodia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

IPM technologies were tested through farmer-participatory approaches for the off-season production of leafy brassicas in seven provinces (Tboung Khmum, Kampot, Kampong Cham, Kandal, Prey Veng, and Svey Rieng, and Takeo) in Cambodia. The IPM package consisted of conventional cultural and managerial practices used by farmers, including the production of seedlings under net house or tunnel to protect against insect pests infestation, the use of yellow/blue sticky traps to monitor and control the insects, the use of mulched beds with plastic mulching and rice straw to control flea beetle, the use of pheromone traps to control DBM and Armyworm, cleaning weeds in the plot and surrounding areas, the use of trap crops: lemon grass and maize, with good drainage to prevent diseases infection. In addition, a neem-based product and microbial-based biopesticides were used following a ‘pesticide window’ strategy (Srinivasan et al., 2017) by using pesticides / bio-pesticides with different modes of action in rotation: Nimbecidine EC at 30cc per 16 liters of water (neem-based biopesticide); *Beauveria bassiana* at 20g/16 liters of water; *Bacillus thuringiensis* at 30g/16 liters of water; *Bacillus subtilis* at 30g/16 liters of water; *Trichoderma viridae* at 30g/16 liters of water. As a last resort within the recommended IPM strategy, farmers were given the option to use selected chemical pesticides, as follows: Emamectin at 10g per 16 liters of water; Acetamiprid at 25g per 16 liters of water; Imidacloprid at 10g per 16 liters of water; or Thiamethoxam at 20cc per 16 liters of water.

The incidence of the main insect pests was surveyed during the growing season of the selected brassica crops, information on production and area was analyzed, and information regarding yield, average costs, returns, and benefit: cost ratio was calculated. In addition, a baseline survey was conducted to obtain information regarding the chemical pesticide reduction percentage, comparing the chemicals used for the IPM demos and chemicals

previously used for brassica production on the selected farms.

Before the start of the IPM demonstration trials, farmers were trained on land preparation, mulching, trellising, bed making, using seedling trays for healthy seed production, transplanting, spacing, water management, plant nutrition, fertilizers/application, pest and disease identification, safe and efficient use of pesticides, cost/return analysis, and record keeping.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

82% of the IPM demonstration trials were completed (162 IPM demos from 2020-2023), with only 8% being terminated due to lack of production (16 IPM demos). The remaining 16% of demos are ongoing (19 IPM demos corresponding to 2023). In addition, 88 tons of leafy brassicas were produced under IPM demonstration plots on an area equivalent to 6 hectares (Table 1, and based on completed IPM demos), with an average area of 380 ± 200 m² (range 100-1400 m², n=197 IPM demos). In addition, farmers had distinctive brassica crop preferences, with choy sum (caisim, variety Oni, EWS) being the highest in preference (62% of the IPM demos), followed by pakchoi (Variety Mayleen 281, EWS) (23%), mustard green (variety Makot, EWS) (13%), and Chinese cabbage (2%).

Table 1. IPM Demo Status by Province during 2020-2023, Cambodia.

Demo status by Province	IPM Demos	Total Production (Kilo)	Total Area (Meter ²)
Completed	162	88,856	62,611
Tboung Khmum	61	35,038	22,937
Kampot	52	22,987	19,487
Kampong Cham	36	23,168	16,610
Kandal	5	3,510	1,178
Prey Veng	4	1,845	1,149
Svey Rieng	2	1,860	900
Takeo	2	448	350
Pending	19	3,814	5,800
Terminated	16	0	6,000
Grand Total	197	92,670	74,411

This information was recorded in 131 demonstration plots regarding the chemical use of pesticides. However, 26

plots did not contribute to the baseline information; the brassicas were grown in those areas for the first time. Therefore, baseline information was only collected on 105 demos. Caisim, Chinese cabbage, mustard green, and pakchoi registered an average of 34.5% reduction and up to 57% reduction in pakchoi (Figure 1) in the use of pesticides (information collected across locations).

Figure 1. Chemical pesticide reduction percentage in Cambodia 2020-2022. Information is based on the following surveys: Caisim=67; Chinese cabbage=1; mustard green=9; pak-choi=28.

Information regarding the incidence of major insect pests recorded for all IPM demos within each brassica crop suggested that although major insect pests were present in the demonstration plots, the level of damage (1-5 damage score scale, with 1: non-infested to 5: severely damage plant) recorded was low to intermediate (score 1-2) in the case of aphid, armyworms, and cabbage loopers, whereas diamondback moth and flea beetles had a slightly higher damage score (score 3-4) on choy sum and pakchoi crops (Figure 2).

Although more IPM demos were located in Tboung Khmum (61), Kampot (52), and Kampong Cham (36), the average return is higher in other provinces with fewer IPM demos established in Kandal (5), Prey Veng (4) and Svey Rieng (2) (Figure 3). Moreover, considering the benefits by square meter or produced kilo, the average benefit is higher in Kandal, Prey Veng, and Svey Rieng (up to USD 1.25 per square meter or up to USD 0.50 per produced kilo (Figure 4). Furthermore, regarding the benefit: cost ratio, we found that this variable was province-dependent, with a higher ratio observed in Kampot province (10.52, *i.e.*, the benefit or return of the IPM demo plots was ten times higher compared to the initial investment/input costs associated with the IPM package), compared to Kampong Cham (5.16), Tboung Khmum (4.25). The lowest benefit-cost ratio was observed for Prey Veng province (1.82).

Figure 2. Incidence of major insect pests on selected brassica crops in Cambodia 2020-2023.

Figure 3. Average economic cost and return (KHR, Cambodian riel) of brassicas production in seven provinces of Cambodia, 2020-2022.

Figure 4. Economic benefit by selected brassica crop across provinces, measured based on A) benefit by square meter and B) benefit based on kilo produced (KHR, Cambodian riel).

The IPM package suggested to farmers for brassica production has been proven effective for producing Chinese mustard and pak-choi Cambodia (Ramasamy et al., 2020). In addition, the use of the pesticide window strategy has proven effective for the management of DBM in different countries, including Australia (Baker, 2011), New Zealand (Walker et al., 2011), China (Feng et al., 2011), and Taiwan (Srinivasan et al., 2017). By enriching the IPM package with microbial and neem pesticides in the current study and applying them sequentially in Cambodia, we were able to observe low levels of insect pest incidence with an essential reduction of chemical pesticides and, more importantly, a positive benefit: cost ratio with the adoption of the IPM package.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the information collected during IPM demonstration plots in Cambodia 2020-2022, we found a vital reduction recorded in 80% of the demonstration plots and regarding the use of chemical pesticides. Furthermore, the chemical pesticide reduction varied depending upon the crop, with Choysum, Chinese cabbage, mustard green, and pak-choi presenting an average decrease of about 35% and up to 57% in pak-choi. In terms of significant brassica insect pests, the level of damage (1-5 damage score scale) recorded was low to intermediate for aphids, armyworms, and cabbage loopers, whereas diamondback moth and flea beetles had a slightly higher damage score (score 3-4) on choy sum and pakchoi crops. The economic benefit due to the adoption of IPM was higher in Kandal, Prey Veng, and Svey Rieng provinces, receiving up to USD 1.25 per m². In addition, the benefit-cost ratio was higher in Kampot province (10.52), followed by Kampong Cham (5.16) and Tboung Khmum (4.25), with the lowest in Prey Veng province (1.82). Adopting IPM reduces pest incidence and, thus, the reliance on chemical pesticides while increasing farmers' income substantially.

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Use of Environmental Impact Quotient in Integrated Pest Management Program Dissemination to Reduce the Hazard Risk of Pesticide Use in Chinese Cabbage Production in Taiwan

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ABSTRACT

In conventional agriculture involving Chinese cabbage production in Taiwan, insecticides are inevitably used to control various insect pests, especially *Plutella xylostella* (diamondback moth, DBM), *Pieris rapae* (imported cabbageworm), and *Phyllotreta striolata* (stripped flea beetle). To reduce pesticide use, we introduced an integrated pest management program (IPM) to Chinese cabbage growers, including the sex pheromone of DBM for monitoring and mass trapping, insecticide Cartap GR and diatomaceous earth for controlling striped flea beetle larvae in soil, and *Bacillus thuringiensis* to control Lepidoptera larvae. We designed scouting record sheets for different insect pests to teach growers how to record situations of pest occurrence so that they could launch different control strategies according to the amount of insect population. Furthermore, the environmental impact quotient (EIQ) was used to evaluate the potential impact of pesticides on human health and the environment as a decision support tool in IPM decisions. Field use of EIQ can improve the selection and use of pesticides in IPM decisions to reduce the risk of hazards and can also be a useful indicator for impact assessment of IPM programs.

Keywords

Integrated pest management, Environmental Impact Quotient (EIQ), Chinese cabbage

INTRODUCTION

The most important genera of Brassicaceae in Taiwan are Brassica and Raphanus. The main cultivated species of Brassicaceae leafy vegetables include cabbage, Chinese cabbage, cauliflower, broccoli, and mustard. Although they are planted in different regions and during different seasons in Taiwan, the occurrence of key insect pests is very similar, and their control strategies can also be mutually used.

The government of Taiwan has a strategy to reduce the use of chemical pesticides by 50% over the next decade. We have promoted IPM among farmers more vigorously since 2018 to achieve this goal. We introduced an Integrated Pest Management (IPM) program to Chinese cabbage growers. This included the use of sex pheromones of Diamondback Moth (DBM) for monitoring and mass trapping (Liu et al., 1990; Hung, 2013), Cartap GR insecticide (It has registered in Taiwan to control stripped flea beetle.), and diatomaceous earth (Lorini and Beckel, 2006; Millier, 2011; Abas Shah and Ali Khan, 2014) for controlling stripped flea beetle larvae in soil. We also suggested *Bacillus thuringiensis* as a control measure against Lepidoptera larvae. We have designed scouting record sheets for various insect pests to educate growers on documenting pest infestations. This will enable them to

implement appropriate control measures based on the insect population level.

Plant protection products were used for pest management, posing certain environmental risks. The Environmental Impact Quotient (EIQ) is a tool that is currently being utilized to measure progress in reducing pesticide risks. The EIQ was developed in 1992 by Kovach et al. at Cornell University, USA (Kovach et al. 1992). The EIQ can be a helpful tool in evaluating the effectiveness of IPM programs in reducing pesticide risks (Muhammetoglu and Uslu, 2007; Kromann et al., 2011). The Guidance Document No. 2 of the FAO IPM impact assessment series revealed that the EIQ has been applied to several IPM projects in Asia, such as Vietnam (FAO, 2008a; 2008b). This article aims to share how to disseminate the IPM concept and operation principles and introduce the EIQ to IPM programs to reduce the risk of plant protection products' use to the environment.

Dissemination of IPM in Chinese cabbage

The government in Taiwan has a strategy to reduce the use of chemical pesticides by 50% over the next decade from 2018 to 2027. We have been promoting IPM among farmers more strongly since 2018 to achieve this goal. Most farmers make some mistakes in the concept of IPM; they always think that using eco-friendly plant protection products is implementing IPM. Therefore, we drew a diagram (Fig 1) to illustrate the concept and practices of IPM. It consists of three frameworks and six steps that educate farmers and emphasize the importance of monitoring and record-keeping as crucial aspects of IPM. Among them, we focused on monitoring and recording key pests because monitoring and record-keeping are the core tasks of IPM implementation. However, most farmers do not like to do these two jobs because they think very complicated things. Without monitoring, we will not understand when to take steps to control pests, which is an important concept in IPM.

Figure 1. The framework and implementation steps in IPM programs.

We visited a Vegetable Productive Cooperative in Changhua to guide IPM implementation. The cooperative has a planting area of approximately 100 hectares. First, we visited the farmers to understand pest management problems and which kinds of pests are of the greatest concern. In Taiwan, the most concerning pests for Chinese cabbage are diamondback moths, striped flea beetles, and cabbage worms. This is because they have significantly reduced susceptibility to most insecticides. However, they still preferred to use chemical pesticides to control these pests.

IPM programs for Chinese cabbage on farms in Changhua

After ACRI's team explained to the growers the features of diamondback moth, cabbage worm, and striped flea beetle infestations and provided control suggestions and measures.

Treatment for flooding should be done two weeks before planting to eliminate the eggs, larvae, and pupae of the striped flea beetle in the soil. The insecticide Cartap GR was applied after sowing to control larvae of the striped flea beetle inside the soil. The diatomaceous earth was used thrice to suppress striped flea beetle adults during the seedling stage. Sex pheromone traps for diamondback

moths were hung 7 days after planting. There were 16 traps in 0.5 hectares designated for controlling and monitoring the density of diamondback moths.

A scouting method was established for Lepidoptera larvae (including diamondback moth, cabbage worm, tobacco cutworm, and cabbage looper), aphids, whiteflies, and

striped flea beetles through visual inspection. Recording the number of major insect pests is convenient, so we have designed a recording sheet using ordinal scales (Tables 1 and 2). Additionally, scouting for insect pests to initiate control measures is convenient. We have provided a sequential sampling method and an action threshold for different growth stages of Chinese cabbage (Table 3).

Table 1. Ordinal scales for insect pest number per Chinese cabbage plant

Insect Pest	Ordinal scales for insect pest numbers per plant			
	0	1	2	3
Aphids	None pests found	1 ~ 10 individual	11~20 individual	>20 individual
Whiteflies				
Leaf miner		1 ~ 3 individual	4 ~ 10 individual	>10 individual
Lepidoptera larva				
Stripped flea beetle				

Table 2. Recording sheet for key pests¹⁾ on Chinese cabbage

Pests	Order of plant sampled																			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
Caterpillar																				
SFB																				
Aphid																				
Whitefly																				
Leaf miner																				

Caterpillars include diamondback moth, cabbage worm, tobacco cutworm, beet armyworm, and cabbage looper. SFB is the striped flea beetle. The leaf miner is *Liriomyza* sp.

Table 3. Using sequential sampling method and giving action thresholds to suggest control measures according to the growth stage of Chinese cabbage.

Growth stage of Chinese cabbage	Recommendations for action thresholds	Suggestions of control measures
0 to 10 days after planting	At least 10 plants have 2 DBM or 3 cabbageworm larvae or more than 3 Lepidoptera larvae.	Using <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>
	At least 10 plants have 3 DBM or 4 cabbageworm larvae or more than 4 Lepidoptera larvae.	Using chemical pesticides
	There are at least 10 plants within 3 stripped flea beetle adults.	Using chemical pesticides
11 to 20 days after planting	At least 10 plants have 2 DBM or 3 cabbageworm larvae or more than 3 Lepidoptera larvae.	Using <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>

Growth stage of Chinese cabbage	Recommendations for action thresholds	Suggestions of control measures
	At least 10 plants have 4 DBM or 5 cabbageworm larvae, or more than 6 Lepidoptera larvae.	Using chemical pesticides
	There are at least 10 plants within 3 stripped flea beetle adults.	Using chemical pesticides
21 days after planting to before harvesting	At least 10 plants have 3 DBM or 3 cabbageworm larvae or more than 3 Lepidoptera larvae.	Choosing <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> or chemical pesticides of shorter PHI
	There are at least 10 plants within 4 stripped flea beetle adults.	Choosing chemical pesticides of shorter PHI

The sample size was suggested at least 30 to 50 plants by visual inspection for each field.

What is EIQ, and how are EIQ values derived?

Plant protection products were applied in pest management, which could pose certain environmental hazards. The Environmental Impact Quotient (EIQ) was developed by Kovach et al. at Cornell University, USA, in 1992 (Kovach et al., 1992). The Environmental Impact Quotient (EIQ) is an indicator that evaluates the environmental impact of pesticides, including their effects on farmworkers, consumers, wildlife, health, and safety. The EIQ value is a figure that is calculated for a specific active ingredient according to a formula that includes eleven parameters, such as toxicity (dermal, chronic, bird, bee, fish, and beneficial arthropod), soil half-life, systemicity, leaching potential, and plant surface half-life. Each parameter is assigned a score of 1, 3, or 5 to indicate the potential for harm (Table 4).

Table 5 lists the formula for determining the EIQ value of individual pesticides. It is the average of the farm worker, consumer, and ecological components. Cornell University has published and periodically updated lists of EIQ values (<https://cals.cornell.edu/new-york-state-integrated-pest-management/risk-assessment/eiq>) since the 1990s. Farmers and other agricultural professionals use these values to make informed decisions about pesticide use. They consider factors such as toxicity, environmental persistence, potential for runoff or leaching into water sources, and impact on non-target organisms. Using EIQ values, farmers can choose pesticides with lower environmental impact without sacrificing effectiveness in controlling pests. These lists contain the EIQ value and the EI scores for each individual component that comprises the EIQ value.

Table 4. The parameters and rating system used to calculate the EIQ value for specific active ingredients. (Kovach et al., 1992)

Variables	Symbol	Score 1	Score 3	Score 5
Long-term health effects	C	Little-none	Possible	Definite
Dermal toxicity (Rat LD50)	DT	>2000 mg/kg	200-2000 mg/kg	0-200 mg/kg
Bird toxicity (8-day LC50)	D	>1000 ppm	100-1000 ppm	1-100 ppm
Bee toxicity	Z	Non-toxic	Moderately toxic	Highly toxic
Beneficial arthropod toxicity	B	Low impact	Moderate	Severe impact
Fish toxicity (96 hr LC50)	F	>10 ppm	1-10 ppm	<1 ppm
Plant surface half-live	P	1-2 weeks, pre-emerg. herbic.	2-4 weeks post-emerg. herbic.	>4 weeks
Soil residue half-live (T1/2)	S	<30 days	30-100 days	>100 days
Mode of action	SY	Non-systemic; all herbicides	Systemic	
Leaching potential	L	Small	Medium	Large
Surface runoff potential	R	Small	Medium	Large

Table 5. EIQ Components and Formula (Kovach et al., 1992)

<p>EI Applicator: $C \times (DT \times 5)$</p> <p>EI Picker: $C \times (DT \times P)$</p> <p>EI Farm Worker =EI Sprayer + EI Picker</p> <p>EI Consumer: $C \times ((S + P)/2) \times SY$</p> <p>EI Ground Water: L</p> <p>EI Consumer =EI Consumer + EI Ground Water</p> <p>EI Fish: $F \times R$</p> <p>EI Bird: $D \times ((S + P)/2) \times 3$</p> <p>EI Honey Bee: $Z \times P \times 3$</p> <p>EI Natural Enemies: $B \times P \times 5$</p> <p>EI Ecology =EI Fish + EI Bird + EI Honey Bee + EI Beneficial arthropod</p>
<p>The EIQ Formula:</p> <p>$EIQ=(EI \text{ Farm Worker} +EI \text{ Consumer} +EI \text{ Ecology}) /3$</p> <p>Full Formula:</p> <p>$EIQ=\{C[(DT*5)+(DT*P)]+[(C*((S+P)/2)*SY)+(L)]+[(F*R)+(D*((S+P)/2)*3)+(Z*P*3)+(B*P*5)]\}/3$</p>

Pesticide risk assessment in IPM programs

IPM is a decision support system for selecting and using pest control tactics, either singly or in coordination, to form a management strategy. This strategy is based on ecology and economy, allowing for selecting a control strategy that is most effective against insect pests while causing minimal harm to people and the environment (Kogan, 1998). We can base our analysis on the occurrence of insect pests by monitoring them and deciding whether to use pesticides to control them. It means to know when you need to use a pesticide. Therefore, implementing IPM can decrease the number of pesticides utilized and the risks associated with pesticide use.

IPM programs must balance environmental, human health (consumer and worker), and economic risks. Pesticide risk is related to the hazard of the active ingredient, and the risks to the environment of using pesticides are also related to the amount of exposure. The EIQ is a hazard

indicator (Pradel et al., 2009). It has to account for the amount of exposure that causes a hazardous risk, which needs additional calculations to determine an indication of pesticide risk. To account for exposure, a simple equation called the EIQ Field Use Rating was developed by Kovach et al. (Kovach et al., 1992). The rating is calculated by multiplying the EIQ value of a specific pesticide by the percentage of active ingredient in the formulation, as well as the rate per acre or hectare and application times (Equation 1). Comparisons of the EIQ Field Use Rating could be made between different pest management strategies by adding the Field Use EIQ figures for each pesticide application throughout the season. The total Field Use EIQ figure represents the overall environmental impact of the pest management strategy implemented during that season.

$EIQ \text{ Field Use Rating} = EIQ \times \% \text{ active substances} \times \text{dosage rate} \times \text{application times (eq. 1)}$

We used Kovach's paper from Cornell University in the USA to create an Environmental Impact Quotient (EIQ) platform (<https://eiq.tactri.gov.tw>) (Fig 2.) for estimating the Field Use of EIQ and understanding how much the hazard risk to the environment is in a production season using all plant protection products, especially pesticides. We hope that growers can use it to estimate the EIQ before choosing plant protection products and keep pesticide use records. Growers can also compare and be aware of the EIQ value of the pesticides used throughout the production season. They can then adjust the category of pesticides used in the next production, with low-risk plant protection products being their primary choice.

Figure 2. EIQ estimation platform for calculation Field Use EIQ

We obtained the records of pesticide usage from a Chinese cabbage farm during the first production season in Changhua County, Taiwan, in 2022. The pesticide records were entered into the EIQ platform to calculate the Field Use EIQ (Table 6). The results showed that dinotefuran was applied 14 times more frequently than oxamyl, which only had nine applications. However, the EIQ field use rating of dinotefuran is 6.9, less than 40.8 for oxamyl because the EIQ value of oxamyl is higher than dinotefuran's. The EIQ field uses ratings for emamectin benzoate and indoxacarb, which are lower than oxamyl, although they were the same at 9 applications. The reason is that the usage and the EIQ value of both insecticides are lower than that of oxamyl.

Table 6. The use of pesticides and the EIQ Field Use Rating of the first production season of a Chinese cabbage farm in Changhua County, Taiwan, in 2022.

Pesticides	Formulations	EIQ	Active substances	Dosage rate g or mL/ha	Number of applications	Field Use EIQ
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> Y1336	WP	10.28	1x10 ⁹ cfu/g up	251.3	1	3.599
indoxacarb	SC	31.19	14.5%	294.5	9	3.717
emamectin benzoate	EC	26.28	2.15%	236	9	0.372
chlorfenapyr	SC	37.5	10%	35.9	1	0.461
acetamiprid	SC	28.73	20%	143.5	2	2.299
dinotefuran	SC	22.26	20%	557.7	14	6.9235
oxamyl	G	33.33	10%	4397.7	9	40.827
lambda-cyhalothrin	EC	49.33	2.8%	114.8	1	0.396
gamma-cyhalothrin	CS	44.05	1.5%	107.7	1	0.198

metaflumizone	SC	32.89	22%	89.7	1	1.809
spirotetramat	SC	35.29	10%	104	3	1.023
<i>Btk.</i> ABTS-351 ¹⁾	WG	13.33	54% (32,000 IU/mg)	197.4	4	3.958
<i>Bta.</i> NB-200 ²⁾	WG	13.33	54% (15,000 IU/mg)	143.6	3	2.878
Summation	-	-	-	-	58	68.459

¹⁾ *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* strain ABTS-351

²⁾ *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* strain NB-200

CONCLUSION

To reduce the use of pesticides, we introduced integrated pest management programs (IPMs) to Chinese cabbage growers who previously relied solely on chemical pesticides for pest control. The IPMs included the use of sex pheromones of DBM for monitoring and mass trapping, insecticide Cartap GR and diatomaceous earth for controlling striped flea beetle larvae in the soil, and *Bacillus thuringiensis* to control Lepidoptera larvae. It is convenient for farmers to monitor pests. We have designed measurement and recording methods for different pests, including ordinal scales and incidence. We also encouraged the growers to hang sex pheromones of diamondback moth and *Spodoptera litura*.

The EIQ helps provide information about the potential environmental effects of integrated pest management (IPM) practices. Suppose the EIQ value and percentage of active ingredient in a plant protection product are high. In that case, the usage of that product should be reduced to mitigate the risk of environmental hazards. Therefore, the EIQ field use rating can improve the selection and use of pesticides in IPM decisions, thereby reducing the risk of hazards.

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Management of Diamondback Moth in Georgia, USA

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ABSTRACT

Managing diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* (L.) in cole crops in Georgia, USA, has primarily relied upon the judicious use of effective insecticides. However, reoccurring outbreaks of resistance have complicated this insecticide-centric management program. From 2016 to 2019, the suspected resistance manifested as low levels of DBM control, notably for the insecticide active ingredients lambda-cyhalothrin, methoxyfenozide, pyriproxyfen, novaluron, bifenthrin, indoxacarb, and methomyl. The most consistent resistance seems to have occurred with the diamide insecticides (IRAC Class 28), particularly chlorantraniliprole. Initially, this was due to the widespread occurrence of the G4946E mutation, a target site mutation of the ryanodine receptor (RyR), in Georgia and Florida populations of DBM. However, the resistance had clearly extended to cross-resistance among diamide insecticides by 2021, and two more target site

mutations of the DBM RyR, I4790M and I4790K, have been identified in Georgia populations. Recent management of DBM in Georgia has consisted of site-specific maximum dose bioassays to determine effective insecticide rotations, continued investigation into the molecular mechanisms of resistance, and investigation of alternative control strategies, including synthetic insecticides, such as Baculoviruses and cabbage host plant resistance. The Baculovirus field trials in Georgia suggested that this control was compatible with synthetic insecticides, while the cabbage host plant resistance trials suggested that mature plant resistance may provide some protection late in the growing season.

Keywords

Plutella xylostella, insecticide resistance management (IRM), cabbage insect pests,

INTRODUCTION

The Diamondback Moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), is a major worldwide insect pest of Cole crops (Talekar and Shelton 1993, Furlong et al. 2013). Global costs of DBM control were estimated to be US\$1 billion annually in the 1990s (Talekar and Shelton 1993). They had risen to US\$4-5 billion by the mid-2010s (Zalucki et al. 2012), establishing DBM as a serious economic concern for vegetable production. In the southeastern USA, brassica crops are key contributors to the regional economy, as the temperate climate allows year-round growth. Unfortunately, year-round growth also permits year-round insect pressure, especially from specialist pests such as DBM. As a result, pest management programs for controlling DBM are usually insecticide-centric and require multiple applications per growing season.

In recent decades, multiple documented outbreaks of insecticide-resistant DBM populations in the USA have occurred (Shelton et al. 1993; Zhao et al. 2006; Bhandari et al. 2020; Riley et al. 2020). This pest has documented resistance to over 101 insecticide active ingredients (APRD 2023), making it one of the most insecticide-resistant insect pests worldwide. In Georgia and Florida, we observed resistance to multiple insecticide active ingredients despite recommendations for rotation of insecticides for DBM control (Riley 2013, Riley et al. 2020, Dunn et al. 2024).

While the maximum dose bioassays have helped make site-specific recommendations for insecticidal efficacy, it is clear that alternative control tactics and documentation of molecular resistance mechanisms to synthetic insecticides are needed. This study summarizes our recent findings on alternative control efforts for the DBM in

Georgia Cole crops. The presence of two ryanodine receptor target site mutations, I4790K and I4790M, are formally reported in DBM populations from North America for the first time. These mutations, specifically I4790K, are associated with high levels of resistance to the diamide (IRAC class 28) insecticides, chlorantraniliprole, cyantraniliprole, and cyclantraniliprole. The widespread occurrence of insecticide resistance indicates that alternative control methods are needed. Accordingly, we tested the AcMNPV product, Lepigen®, as an alternative insecticide via field trials and bioassay. Additionally, host plant resistance would be a valuable tool for DBM management. We investigated five cabbage varieties for potential resistance to DBM using olfactometry, field trials, and choice and no-choice tunnel assays.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Objective 1- Identification of Mutations Associated with Diamide Resistance

200 DBM larvae and pupae were collected from commercial fields in Colquitt, Worth, Grady, and Brooks counties in Georgia from late 2021 to early 2022. Larvae were reared to the first generation at the Coastal Plains Experiment Station in Tifton, Georgia, for subsequent toxicological and molecular characterization. After reaching the first generation, 10 larvae were randomly selected from each colony and frozen in 1.0 mL RNALater for molecular analysis. Additionally, 20 larvae were collected in Rabun County, Georgia in early 2022. However, these larvae were transported directly to the University of Georgia Athens campus and immediately frozen in 1.0 mL RNALater for subsequent molecular analysis.

mRNA was extracted from 10 larvae per colony using a Dynabeads mRNA Direct Kit (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA). Subsequently, cDNA was synthesized using Superscript IV VILO MasterMix (Invitrogen) to generate a polymerase chain reaction (PCR) template. PCR products were amplified using a BIO-RAD C1000 Touch (Life Science, Hercules, CA) thermal cycler. High-fidelity Phusion Taq polymerase, 5X HF Buffer, and DBM RyR-specific primers designed using Primer3Plus (Table 1) generated a single amplicon. The amplicon was amplified using an annealing temperature of 59 C and an extension time of 60 seconds. PCR products were analyzed using a 1.5% agarose gel and purified via Monarch PCR and DNA Cleanup Kit (Promega, Madison, WI). Purified PCR products were then Sanger sequenced by Eurofins Genomics in Louisville, KY.

Sequencing chromatograms generated by Eurofins Genomics were used to identify the target site mutations in each population. Ab1 files were also analyzed using

FinchTV 1.4.0 (Geospiza Inc., Seattle, WA). Following the identification of the previously unidentified mutant sequence in the chromatogram, additional cloning procedures were completed to isolate and confirm the presence of the mutant allele in the PCR product. PCR products under this category were used as templates for cloning (CloneJET PCR Cloning Kit, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) following the manufacturer's protocol. Subsequently, NEB turbo-competent *E. coli* was transformed and grown overnight at 37°C on LB/ampicillin plates. Colonies, representative of single alleles from the PCR product, were then selected for overnight growth in 5 mL of LB/ampicillin. According to the manufacturer's protocol, plasmids were extracted via GeneJet Plasmid Miniprep Kit (Thermo Scientific). Quantifying plasmid concentration per sample occurred via Nanodrop, and a minimum of 10 clones per selected PCR template were Sanger sequenced at Eurofins Genomics in Louisville, KY. Once completed, clone sequences were aligned using Clustal Omega, and the presence of the mutant sequence was confirmed.

Objective 2 - Lepigen 2021 Bioassay and Field Tests

One laboratory bioassay (Test 1) and three field spray tests (Tests 2, 3, 4) were conducted from May to September to assess the efficacy of the AcMNPV product, Lepigen (DBMv2), on DBM larvae feeding on collard, *hyb. 'Top Bunch'*, host plants. For the May 20th bioassay, all product solutions (200 ml final volume), including the water check, were prepared in 250 ml polypropylene disposable graduated beakers (Fisher Scientific, Hampton, NH). A 7-cm diameter leaf disk was cut from the center of untreated collard leaves and rinsed with water before being dipped into the single insecticide treatment or the water control. The leaf disks were then placed in dishes on filter paper and allowed to air dry at room temperature for 30 minutes to 1 hour of ventilated drying time. DBM larvae were introduced onto the treated leaf disk with a #1 pinnacle nylon hair paint brush and sealed in a 9-cm diameter polystyrene Petri dish with a mesh-covered ventilation hole (VWR Scientific Products, Radnor, PA) that had a 90 mm diameter, water-moistened Whatman™ filter paper (GE Healthcare UK Limited, Amersham Pl, Little Chalfont, UK) covering the bottom. The laboratory ambient temperature ranged from 18-24°C throughout the bioassay process. For the bioassay, ten 2nd- early 4th instar DBM larvae were placed in each dish for each treatment. Each petri dish was fastened with a rubber band after larvae were placed in them and after each mortality reading. The larval condition was determined at the 24, 48, and 72-hour mark by applying a physical stimulus with a straight-tip teasing probe (Bioquip® Products, Rancho Dominguez, CA). Larvae that reacted with a rapid response were categorized as live. Larvae that reacted with

no response were classified as dead. Moribund larvae reacted with a delayed, sluggish response and larvae that had spun a cocoon were categorized as pupated. The products tested in six replicates in a RCB design were: 1) a water control; 2) DBMv2 0.22 L ha⁻¹ or 0.05 mL/200 mL water; 3) DBMv2 0.22 L ha⁻¹ or 0.05 mL/200 mL water plus Dipel DF 1120.8 g ha⁻¹ or 0.23 g/200 mL water; and 4) Dipel DF 1120.8 g ha⁻¹ or 0.23 g/200 mL water. All treatments were diluted in distilled water + adjuvant (Kinetic 0.05%).

All field tests were transplanted into 2 rows per 1.82 m beds (Tests 2 and 3 on May 15th and Test 4 on July 15th) and maintained with standard cultural practices at the Lang Farm, Georgia Coastal Plain Experiment Station at Tifton. The transplants came pre-infested with DBM larvae from the commercial vendor. However, a DBM population had become established on collards from a previous test at the field site. For all three tests, 226.8 kg of 10-10-10 NPK fertilizer was applied to Tift pebbly clay loam field plots, followed by 68 kg of the same fertilizer at the first side dressing. Irrigation was overhead as needed. Scouting dates of 10 plants per plot samples were: June 1st, 3rd, 8th, 15th, and 16th for Test 2; June 28th, 30th, July 6th, and 9th for Test 3; and August 2nd, 9th, 11th, and 13th for Test 4. On August 13th, we increased the sample size to 20 plants per plot. Dates of foliar applications of insecticide by test were: June 2nd, 11th, and 15th for Test 2; June 25th, 29th, and July 8th for Test 3; and August 5th, 10th, 24th, and 30th for Test 4. All treatments included the adjuvant methylated seed oil 0.25% v/v (see treatments in Tables 2, 3, and 4). The damage rating and harvest sample size was 10 plants per plot. Ratings were based on a 0=no damage, 1=slight, 2-3=medium, and 4-5=severe damage scale. Harvest was based on a single harvest of 10 plants. The harvest dates for Tests 2, 3, and 4 were July 13th, not harvested, and September 9th, respectively. Marketable weight was estimated as leaves with less than a medium damage rating, i.e., slight damage to the wrapper leaves was allowed due to the heavy lepidopteran larval pest pressure.

Objective 3 – Host Plant Resistance and Preference

Olfactometry

An A10 Olfactometer (Figure 2) from Analytical Research Systems, Inc., Gainesville, FL, was set up with a factory-tanked, ultra-clean or “zero” air source and maintained in a filtered, laminar flow hood for maximum air purity during data collection. The two 150mm dia. x 250mm tall, all glass, Closed Volatile Collection Chambers (VCC) were loaded with a five-leaf seedling of either ‘Green Challenger’, ‘Cheers’, ‘Bronco’, ‘Clarissa’, or ‘Cairo’ cultivar of *Brassica oleracea* vs clean air. Additionally, ‘Green Challenger’ and ‘Cheers’ were also compared for adult preference. Each run consisted of 15 sub-runs, each

of an adult DBM introduced into the air-exhausting glass Y tube. The moving behavior of the DBM adult toward the preferred air source upwind into the tube was recorded. Since DBM are more active in their scotophase, all assays were done in a dark room, with the help of a low wattage red light, at 23 ± 1°C with a flow rate of 550 to 600 ml/min (Badenes-Perez et al. 2004).

Choice Tunnel Study

The five previously listed cabbage cultivars were transplanted (10 plants each) into plastic mulched beds and immediately covered with floating row cover tunnels in four replicates. A rate of four DBM moths/10 plants was released at each end of each tunnel. DBM reproduction and damage were assessed after two DBM generations under the tunnel or approximately one month. After the first month of assessment, from transplant to pre-cupping growth stages, the test was uncovered for one month, and a second pest and damage assessment was performed. Following the evaluation, each plot was sprayed with the insecticide combination of spinetoram (Radiant 1SC 0.73 L ha⁻¹) and bifenthrin (Bifenture EC 0.47 L ha⁻¹). At that point, a fresh tunnel was pulled over the maturing cabbage plants, and another release of DBM adults at the same rate was introduced into each tunnel 1-week post-treatment. After a third-month period, we uncovered the plants, sampled DBM, and did a final cabbage weight and damage assessment. The test was conducted in the spring season when DBM was prevalent. A choice study without the tunnels was also conducted, relying on the natural DBM population to infest the cabbage plots. These were tested in an adjacent block with four replications in a randomized complete block design with 20 plants per plot. The same assessments were made on these plots for comparison to the tunnel study.

No-Choice Tunnel Study

The same five cabbage cultivars were transplanted (20 plants each) into the same tunnels described above but with only a single cultivar in each tunnel. The exact rate of four DBM moths/10 plants used under objective 1 were released per tunnel. DBM reproduction and damage were assessed after two DBM generations under the tunnel (one month) following the same protocol used for the choice tunnel study. Cabbage yield data from choice and no-choice tests were contrasted to see if similar yield differences could be seen in tunneled versus open cabbage plots.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Resistance to diamide insecticides

When chlorantraniliprole (Coragen®) was first used in Georgia, it was highly effective for DBM control due to its long residual period and other favorable properties, such as low phytotoxicity and low mammalian toxicity. These properties made it tempting for extensive application in spray programs to control DBM populations. By 2016-2019, resistance to chlorantraniliprole was widespread in Georgia and Florida (Bhandari et al. 2020, Riley et al. 2020), only several years after its registration in 2008. Subsequent analysis of four populations collected from Georgia and Florida in 2018 identified the G4946E target site mutation (Dunn et al. 2022), associated with chlorantraniliprole resistance (Trocza et al. 2012). However, cross-resistance between cyantraniliprole and chlorantraniliprole, not seen in 2019, was recently documented in a 2021 cabbage field trial in Georgia (Dunn et al., 2023), as well as a maximum dose insecticide survey spanning Georgia and Florida (Dunn et al. 2024). The recent identification of a novel mutation, I4790K, in diamide cross-resistant populations from Japan may explain the observed cross-resistance seen in Georgia (Jouraku et al. 2020) and is explored further in this study.

Objective 1- Identification of Mutations Associated with Diamide Resistance

While resistance to chlorantraniliprole has been well documented in the southeastern USA (Bhandari et al. 2020, Riley et al. 2020, Dunn et al. 2022), more recent reports of control failure in Georgia with products utilizing the active ingredients cyantraniliprole and cyclaniliprole encouraged continued screening of populations for target site mutations (Dunn et al. 2023, Dunn et al. 2024). Sequence analysis revealed the presence of the I4790K mutation in all five sampled counties from Georgia (Figure 1), while only one sample, from Grady County, also contained the I4790M mutation. While the frequency of M4790 seemed low in the sequencing chromatogram, further cloning and Sanger sequencing using the Grady PCR product as a template confirmed the presence of the I4790M mutation in this population (Figure 2). We also screened for the G4946E mutation, which we previously identified in several chlorantraniliprole-resistant Georgia and Florida populations (Dunn et al., 2022). However, this mutation was only identified in one of the newly sequenced samples, Grady County.

Figure 1. Counties sampled for the molecular analysis of diamondback moth ryanodine receptor mutations. Counties highlighted in red indicate the identification of the I4790K mutant genotype. Counties colored in white were not sampled for analysis.

The I470K target site mutation of the DBM ryanodine receptor, initially reported by Jouraku et al. (2020), is widespread in Asia (Jouraku et al. 2020, Jiang et al. 2021) and has since been reported in populations from Australia (Ward et al. 2021). This mutation is associated with high levels of cross-resistance between three diamide active ingredients registered for use in the USA (Jiang et al. 2021). It is reasonable to hypothesize that the reported cross-resistance between all three diamide active ingredients in Georgia (Dunn et al., 2024) may be due to the emergence of this target site mutation in this region. The geographic spread of this mutation in DBM populations from Georgia is concerning, as it was identified in populations from South Georgia and a population from North Georgia (Figure 1), suggesting that this mutation may already be widespread and raising questions for future management plans in the state and adjacent areas. This appears to be the first report of these mutations in DBM populations from North America.

GRDC4	-PIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDA4	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDA6	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDA11	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDB1	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDB4	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDB10	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDB6	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDB8	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDC2	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
GRDC6	DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLAKLIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD
<u>GRDB5</u>	<u>DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLA<u>M</u>LIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD</u>
<u>GRDC5</u>	<u>DPIELVHIDEDYFYMEHVIKIAALLHSIVSLA<u>M</u>LIGYYHLKVPLAIFKREKEIARKLEFD</u>

Figure 2. Translated protein sequences from Sanger sequenced clones of the Grady County (GRD) PCR product. The highlight indicates the position of the mutant amino acid. This population was a mixture of two genotypes, I4790K (K) and I4790M (M). The M amino acid can be seen highlighted in the underlined sequence, while the K amino acid can be seen aligned to the position of the M sequence. Neither the wild-type susceptible allele (G) nor the previously reported mutation (E) were detected. The translation was completed using blastx, and subsequent sequence alignment was completed using Clustal Omega.

Organic Control: Lepigen and B.t.

The remarkable ability of DBM to rapidly evolve resistance to new insecticide chemistries creates a need for alternative control methods, such as biological control strategies. Previous work compared a multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (MNPV), PxMNPV, and a granulovirus (GV), PxGV (single virus per occlusion body (OB)), on *P. xylostella* and *Spodoptera exigua* 3rd instar larvae. LD₅₀'s, which were generated based on the number of OB per larvae, indicated MNPVs could be a promising insecticidal candidate (Farrar et al. 2007). A relatively new product, Lepigen® (*Autographa californica* Multiple Nucleopolyhedrovirus strain R3, AcMNPV) (referred to as DBMv2 in this study) is a pathogen of the following lepidopteran species: *Helicoverpa zea*, *Heliothis virescens*, *Plutella xylostella*, *Trichoplusia ni*, *Chrysodeixis includens*, *Spodoptera frugiperda*, *Spodoptera exigua*, *Spodoptera eridania*, and *Anticarsia gemmatalis*. Additionally, there may be efficacy for other lepidopteran species, as we have recorded mortality of *Pieris rapae* in field trials. This product contains a minimum of 7.5 x 10⁹ occlusion bodies per milliliter of product, or 34.2% AcMNPV, resulting in 665 x 10⁹ occlusion bodies per acre

when applied at 3 fl oz/ acre. This biological insecticide may be a useful alternative to commonly applied synthetic insecticides.

Objective 2 - Lepigen 2021 Bioassay and Field Trials

DBM larvae experienced significant mortality compared with a water check in each of the three control treatments, DBMv2 alone, in combination with the *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) treatment, Dipel, and the Dipel treatment alone (Figure 3). Even though the treatments did not differ from each other, the most significant reduction in live larvae at 144 h, when we terminated the bioassay, was the DBMv2 treatment alone, which provided a 67% decrease in live larvae. The virus-symptomatic larvae (Figure 3) were only present in the DBMv2-treated dishes. Even though some of these larvae were counted as live at the end of the test, the larvae were listless and not feeding. Interestingly, there did not seem to be any advantage (increased or faster mortality) to combining the virus and Bt treatments in the bioassay.

Figure 3. Bioassay results on the control of DBM larvae with DBMv2, Tifton, GA 2021.

The first field test results (Collard #2) indicated that mixing the DBMv2 product with Dipel worsened the control using either product alone (Table 1 column 2). Additionally, DBMv2 did not reduce foliar damage with the first two applications. Thus, the two contraindicated independent factors were the Bt+DBMv2 combination and the slow-acting mortality induced by the virus.

The second field test (Collard #3) showed DBMv2 efficacy against ICW (Table 2) and DBM larvae on June 30 (Table 3) and overall sample dates (Table 4). Adding DBMv2 to Proclaim improved Proclaim's efficacy significantly regarding reduced lepidopteran defoliation (Table 3). While there did not appear to be a significant rate response (1.5 vs. 3.0 fl oz/a) with DBMv2 (Tables 2-3), DBMv2 mixed at a rate of 3 fl oz/a with Proclaim consistently reduced defoliation ratings in comparison to the mixture at DBMv2 at 1.5 fl oz/a, as well as both single application rates of DBMv2 and the single application rate of Proclaim. In some instances, the mixture of DBMv2 with Proclaim also reduced larval numbers compared to other treatment groups throughout Test #3.

In the third field test (Collard #4), with the larger sample size on August 13, both DBMv2 rates significantly reduced all stages of DBM by as much as 64% (Table 5). Adding DBMv2 to the synthetic insecticides Proclaim and Coragen did not significantly improve efficacy but tended to reduce larval numbers (Table 5) and significantly reduced damage rating from the synthetics alone for Proclaim (Table 6). The addition of DBMv2 to Coragen tended to reduce damage rating and increase yields but did not separate from the LSD test. The lowest damage rating in the harvested collard tops was in the Coragen + DBMv2 treatment, which was also one of the highest yield plots (Table 6).

While conducting these trials, one question was whether or not DBMv2 spreads beyond the sprayed plots. On August 13th, using a more intensive sampling where the scouts were given the visual representation (Figure 3) of symptomatic larvae in the field, we successfully detected movement of the virus outside of the original treatment plots (Figure 4). The DBMv2 products seem to be a viable biological control option for DBM in Georgia, alone or in combination with synthetic insecticides, but likely not in combination with Bt insecticides.

Figure 4. Number and standard deviation of DBMv2 symptomatic larvae per treatment across four replicates on August 13, 2021, at Tifton, GA, at the UGA Lang-Rigdon Farm.

Table 1. Collard Test #2 efficacy of insecticide treatments against DBM larvae per 10 plants on June 16 at Tifton, GA, with a comparison of DBM larval counts between scouts Tanner and Riley.

Treatment - rate per acre	DBM larvae	DBM larvae	Lepidopteran larvae	Defoliation rating 0-5
Untreated control	1.08 a	0.83 ab	1.08 ab	4.03 ab
Dipel DF 2 lbs/a	0.55 b	0.68 b	0.93 b	3.73 b
DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.20 bc	0.53 b	0.88 b	4.38 a
Dipel DF 2 lb + DBMv2 3fl oz/a	0.33 bc	1.25 a	1.50 a	3.98 b
Dipel Df 2 lb rotate with DBMv2	0.23 bc	0.95 ab	1.18 ab	3.90 b
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a	0.03 c	0.13 c	0.13 c	2.65 c

* Means within columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different (LSD, P<0.05).

Table 2. Collard Test #3 efficacy of insecticide treatments against DBM larvae per 10 plants on June 28 at Tifton, GA, with

Treatment - rate per acre	DBM larvae	ICW larvae	Defoliation rating 0-5
Untreated control	0.70 a	0.28 a	4.35 a
DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	0.65 ab	0.05 b	3.70 c
DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.55 abc	0.08 b	4.23 ab
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a + DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	0.38 bc	0.05 b	4.08 abc
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a+ DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.28 c	0.03 b	3.85 bc
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a	0.45 abc	0.03 b	4.10 abc

* Means within columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different (LSD, P<0.05).

Table 3. Collard Test #3 efficacy of insecticide treatments against DBM larvae per 10 plants on June 30 at Tifton, GA.

Treatment - rate per acre	DBM larvae	Lep. larvae	Defoliation rating 0-5
Untreated control	1.00 a	1.03 a	4.33 ab
DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	0.50 bc	0.50 bc	4.30 ab
DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.60 b	0.68 ab	4.60 a
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a + DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	0.18 c	0.18 c	4.03 bc
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a+ DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.18 c	0.18 c	3.85 c
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a	0.35 bc	0.38 bc	4.30 ab

* Means within columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different (LSD, P<0.05).

Table 4. Collard Test #3 efficacy of insecticide treatments against DBM larvae per 10 plants overall sample dates at Tifton, GA.

Treatment - rate per acre	DBM larvae (Riley)	Lepidopteran larvae (Riley)	Defoliation rating 0-5 (Riley)
Untreated control	0.69 a	0.77 a	4.42 ab
DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	0.57 ab	0.58 b	4.24 bc
DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.45 bc	0.49 bc	4.53 a
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a + DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	0.29 d	0.30 d	4.07 c
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a+ DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.20 d	0.21 d	3.74 d
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a	0.34 cd	0.36 cd	4.07 c

* Means within columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different (LSD, P<0.05).

Table 5. Collard Test #4 efficacy of insecticide treatments against DBM larvae per 20 plant samples on August 13, 2021, averaged over all sample dates at Tifton, GA.

Treatment - rate per acre	DBM all stages Aug 13	ICW all stages Aug 13	DBM all stages overall	ICW all stages overall
Untreated control	5.0 a	5.8 a	1.69 a	1.81 a
DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	1.8 b	1.3 b	1.44 ab	0.38 bc
DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	2.3 b	4.8 a	1.56 a	1.19 ab
Proclaim 4.8 oz + DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	0.3 b	0.0 b	0.25 c	0.0 c
Proclaim 4.8 oz+ DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.5 b	0.0 b	0.69 abc	0.0 c
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a	0.3 b	0.3 b	0.38 c	0.06 c
Spear-Lep 2 pt + Dipel DF 2 lbs/a	0.5 b	1.3 b	0.38 c	0.31 bc
Dipel DF 2 lbs/a	0.5 b	0.3 b	0.38 c	0.06 c
Coragen SC 7.5 fl oz+ DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	0.5 b	0.0 b	0.50 bc	0.0 c
Coragen SC 7.5 fl oz/a	0.3 b	0.3 b	0.44 bc	0.06 c

* Means within columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different (LSD, P<0.05).

Table 6. Collard Test #4 reduction in lepidopteran damage and yield of collard tops per 10 plants on 9/9/2021 at Tifton, GA.

Treatment - rate per acre	Defoliation rating 0-5 in the field	Defoliation rating 0-2 in harvested tops	Marketable weight of tops harvested (lbs)
Untreated control	4.25 a	1.65 a	0.34 bcd
DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	3.68 ab	1.50 ab	0.32 cd
DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	3.48 abc	1.63 a	0.41 abc
Proclaim 4.8 oz + DBMv2 1.5 fl oz/a	2.20 def	1.15 de	0.33 bcd
Proclaim 4.8 oz+ DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	2.75 cd	1.28 cd	0.34 bcd
Proclaim 4.8 oz/a	1.80 ef	1.18 de	0.36 abcd
Spear-Lep 2 pt + Dipel DF 2 lbs/a	2.90 bcd	1.40 bc	0.28 d
Dipel DF 2 lbs/a	2.65 cde	1.40 bc	0.47 a
Coragen SC 7.5 fl oz+ DBMv2 3 fl oz/a	1.35 f	1.07 e	0.44 ab
Coragen SC 7.5 fl oz/a	1.8 ef	1.20 de	0.35 bcd

* Means within columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different (LSD, $P < 0.05$).

Host plant resistance and Host Preference

In addition to chemical and biopesticide control methods, host plant resistance to DBM can mitigate DBM-caused damage. In 2021, a cabbage variety trial in Colquitt County, Georgia, indicated that one of the cultivars being tested, referred to as Green Challenger, was visibly more resistant to DBM than the other tested cabbage hybrids, including the cultivar “Cheers.” The significantly reduced damage and DBM infestation, compared to the cultivars in adjacent plots, suggested that either the cultivar was not preferred for egg-laying by DBM adults (non-preference) or that some quality of the plant was detrimental to DBM larval feeding and development, resulting in more significant mortality (antibiosis) (Hariprasad and van Emden 2010). To distinguish between these possibilities, in 2022, we compared five cabbage varieties, using olfactometer assays to quantify DBM attraction to odor volatiles, and conducted field trials with DBM confined within tunnels or with natural DBM populations to measure DBM larval abundance, leaf damage ratings, and cabbage head weight.

Host plant attraction olfactometer studies

In these assays, DBM adults released into the entrance tube of a Y-tube olfactometer could move towards a source of plant volatiles (“cabbage volatiles”), move into the empty arm of the olfactometer (“clean air”), or remain in the entry tube (“no choice”). Cultivars tested included ‘Green Challenger’, ‘Cheers’, ‘Bronco’, ‘Clarissa’, or ‘Cairo’. The olfactometer results demonstrated a significant choice effect overall ($F=83.4$, $P < 0.0001$) but not when comparing clean air versus cabbage volatiles ($F=1.55$, $P=0.21$). When the more resistant ‘Green Challenger’ and ‘Cairo’ were grouped, there was a trend in favor of clean air ($F=3.23$, $P < 0.077$). The average no-choice response for these resistant lines was 86%, whereas that response was 65% in the other susceptible lines combined. This indicates there was no attraction to these cabbage lines for DBM adults and possibly suggests repellence. When we directly compared the susceptible ‘Cheers’ line to the resistant ‘Green Challenger’ line, the

average choice was 0.13 ± 0.063 for ‘Cheers’, 0.07 ± 0.046 for ‘Green Challenger’, and 0.80 ± 0.074 ($n=30$) for ‘no choice’. These results suggest that ‘Cheers’ was preferred by almost two-fold over ‘Green Challenger’, but 80% of individuals did not respond to either cultivar.

Row Cover Choice Experiments

In the choice experiment under the row cover tunnel, ‘Clarissa’ appeared most preferred, and ‘Green Challenger’ and ‘Cheers’ seemed less preferred one month after planting. However, the differences between cultivars were insignificant due to the high variation between replicates (Figure 5). DBM numbers decreased dramatically for all

cultivars on the following two sample dates, after the tunnel was removed and after the late season tunnel with a new infestation. This suggests that there may be some mature plant resistance to DBM. Overall, the tunnel choice study indicated no significant preference for DBM between the five cabbage cultivars. Thus, whatever resistance was observed in the summer of 2021 in Colquitt County could not be replicated under a floating row cover. Perhaps the reduced sunlight under the row cover may have affected the palatability or suitability of the cabbage leaves for DBM. Still, more data would be needed before coming to such a conclusion. Additionally, it is possible that plant volatiles were trapped and mixed under the row cover, decreasing the ability to distinguish between varieties.

Figure 5. Choice experiment under tunnel: average number of DBM larvae plus pupae per cabbage cultivar near the end of the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd month of the growing season (same color bars with different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$, LSD)).

Just as there was no clear preference of DBM for any cultivar in the choice experiment under the row cover tunnel, there was also no significant difference in foliar damage based on the 0-5 damage rating system. Although ‘Clarissa’ had an initial tendency toward higher numbers

of DBM (Figure 5), the damage rating on this cultivar was the lowest of all the lines tested (Figure 6). The damage rating data showed no evidence of non-preference for ‘Green Challenger’ cabbage or any distinction between the cabbage lines tested in the tunnel study.

Figure 6. Choice experiment under tunnel: average rated damage (on a scale of 0 (no damage) to 5 (severe damage)) per cabbage cultivar near the end of the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd month of the growing season (same color bars with different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$, LSD)).

The following open study provided some evidence that the absence of significant differences between cultivars was not an artifact due to the tunnel. Naturally occurring DBM, in the open research, were slightly less numerous on ‘Green Challenger’ compared to the other cultivars one month after planting. However, this did not result in a significant difference (Figure 7). Two months after planting, the population of DBM decreased significantly across all varieties. It remained low across the plot through the rest of the growing season, except on Green Challenger and Clarissa, where an increase in DBM was recorded at harvest. Therefore, the Green Challenger cannot be classified as resistant to DBM in the field based on the DBM count data.

Only the crop yield response supported the hypothesis that the ‘Green Challenger’ resisted DBM. However, this too varied depending on whether the cabbage was grown under a row cover tunnel or in the open sun (Figure 8). Under the tunnel, with relatively low numbers of DBM, ‘Cheers’ outperformed ‘Green Challenger’ regarding head weight. However, outside the tunnels in open sunlight conditions and with heavy initial DBM populations, the ‘Green Challenger’ line outperformed ‘Cheers.’ Thus, there does seem to be a plant response, such as tolerance to DBM infestation in field conditions, for ‘Green Challenger.’

Figure 7. Choice-Open (natural infestation, no tunnel) experiment, the average number of DBM larvae plus pupae per plant over time (same color bars with different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$, LSD)).

Green Challenger and Clarissa supported higher DBM numbers in the no-choice experiment under the tunnel than the other varieties one month after planting (Figure 9). However, the DBM numbers for these two varieties declined markedly by the second month of the study, in contrast to the other varieties. As with the choice experiment under the tunnel, DBM numbers fell across all plots at the end of the growing season for all varieties,

except for Cheers, where infestations remained almost constant (Figure 9). Foliar damage increased sharply by the second month of the study, then increased further (Green Challenger), remained relatively constant (Cheers, Cairo, and Bronco), or decreased (Clarissa) (Figure 10). Cairo and Clarissa had the lowest foliar damage ranking at the study's end.

Figure 8. Cabbage head weight by cultivar comparing the No-choice experiment under tunnel versus the open non-tunnel choice test (same color bars with different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$, LSD)).

Figure 9. In the no-choice experiment under the tunnel, the average number of DBM larvae plus pupae per cabbage line near the end of the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd month of the growing season (same color bars with different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$, LSD)).

Figure 10. No-choice experiment under the tunnel, average rated damage per cabbage line near the end of the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd month of the growing season (same color bars with different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$, LSD)).

Based on the results from the different aspects of this study, there were no apparent differences in preference regarding attraction and oviposition between the varieties tested in the field. All varieties tested showed susceptibility to DBM at near-equal measures. The only difference that supported the results of the seed company's 2021 cabbage variety trial was what appears to be some tolerance trait of Green Challenger when grown in full sunlight under normal DBM pest pressure, manifested as a higher head weight compared to the other varieties.

The DBM host-finding process is more influenced by olfaction than visual cues (Couty et al. 2006). Our olfactometer results suggested that DBM prefers the Green Challenger less than the other varieties. Cheers were preferred twice as much by DBM in the paired plant olfactometer study when paired against Green Challenger. This could be part of why Green Challenger showed intermediate resistance in the seed company's cabbage variety trial and our open (non-tunnel) study. In the choice-tunnel study, plant volatiles of the different varieties may have been confined and mixed in a tunnel instead of being well-ventilated in the open test, causing DBM to be less able to discriminate between varieties. We suspect this is why the Green Challenger did not perform well compared to other varieties in the tunnel study, in contrast to the open test. Olfactometer tests with Cairo vs. clean air also suggested that Cairo was less of an attractive plant. Although there was little difference in yield when comparing open and tunnel studies, Cairo did have a lower population of DBM than the Cheers in the open field study by the end of the growing season.

The main categories of host-plant resistance to DBM include antibiosis and antixenosis (or non-preference). The specific factors include leaf wax characteristics, glucosinolate levels, and leaf toughness with plant maturity (Fathipour et al. 2019; Verker 1994). Cabbage cultivars with a glossy (due to reduced wax) leaf surface have been reported to be more resistant to DBM; this resistance is associated with less feeding by different instars of DBM larvae (Eigenbrode and Shelton (1992)). First, instar DBM larvae were observed in a study that involved spending more time walking and searching on cabbage with a glossy wax leaf surface than time spent feeding (Eigenbrode et al. 1998 and Ulmer 1994). Ulmer et al. (2002) also reported a trend towards higher oviposition rates for 'Glossy' *Brassica rapa* plants than for 'Waxy' plants. This might be why Green Challenger showed greater tolerance to DBM than the other varieties by the end of the season (mature plant resistance), yielding greater yield in the open study than in the tunnel studies. We observed that Green Challenger developed a glossier wax leaf surface as it matured and could do this in the open research where it was not shaded by a tunnel, as shading a crop can change the plant growth process (Cabrera et al. 2019). In addition to glossiness, leaf folding could affect DBM oviposition, as DBM uses sensilla to screen for crevices to oviposit (Wee 2016). In the choice-tunnel study, the savoy cabbage Clarissa supported higher oviposition than the other varieties one month into the growing season, possibly due to the higher degree of leaf crenulation and texture.

Green Challenger could also be a more tolerant cabbage due to its leaf toughness (Hariprasad and van Emden (2010)) with maturity and glucosinolate levels, which vary at different plant stages. High levels of glucosinolates can negatively affect DBM development time and weight (Verkerk, 1994; Ghosh et al., 2022). However, plants with higher glucosinolate levels are preferred for oviposition (Sun et al., 2009; Ghosh et al., 2022), possibly because larval feeding on higher glucosinolate concentrations may confer some protection against parasitoids (Ghosh et al., 2022). Differences between varieties in glucosinolate concentrations may account for differences in DBM oviposition. However, this will remain a speculation until glucosinolate profiles are characterized by the different varieties used in this study. DBM has also been reported to have a lower percent survival rate on older cabbage plants than on younger cabbage plants, which is believed to be related to leaf toughness. Populations of DBM declined dramatically at the end of the growing season across the test plot, suggesting that cabbage, in general, may have mature-plant tolerance to DBM.

CONCLUSIONS

Due to the apparent widespread use in Georgia, cross-resistance to the three diamide active ingredients, chlorantraniliprole, cyantraniliprole, and cyclaniliprole, was documented during a recent insecticide survey (Dunn et al. 2024). A target site mutation of the RyR associated with cross-resistance to diamides, I4790K, was detected in five counties in Georgia, four of which were in the south and one in the north. This contrasts the situation only three years prior, where cyantraniliprole and cyclaniliprole were still effective for DBM control. Analysis of samples from Grady County in southern Georgia indicated the presence of another target-site mutation associated with moderate levels of diamide resistance, I4790M, although at seemingly lower frequencies. This serves as the first report of the I4790K and I4790M mutant alleles from DBM populations in North America and further demonstrates the need for alternative control strategies.

The Baculovirus product DBMv2, alone or in combination with Dipel, a *Bacillus thuringiensis* product, was assessed for control of DBM. Both products were moderately effective against DBM, but the combination of the two was only as effective as either product on their own. In contrast, DBMv2 seemed to reduce defoliation and larval numbers in a mixture with the synthetic insecticide Proclaim. Further study is needed to confirm these results, however, baculovirus products may provide some benefit to the current approach of DBM management in the Southeastern U.S., particularly when mixed with synthetic insecticides.

From this study, it can be concluded that Green Challenger is susceptible to DBM but is more tolerant to this pest than other cabbage varieties at the end of the season under normal growing conditions with moderate DBM pressure. This line of cabbage should be grown in full sunlight conditions to develop its characteristic of mature plant tolerance, especially if the characteristic of tolerance is due to wax on the leaf surface, since in low light conditions, waxes become thinner on leaf surfaces (Verkerk 1994). Adult DBM might be less attracted to a late-season field with only Green Challenger growing than a field with only Cheers or multiple cabbage varieties since DBM was not responsive to Green Challenger in the olfactometer study, but this would have to be tested. Also, any future olfactometry studies need to consider mature plant resistance in field-grown cabbage, capturing volatiles from mature plants in the field and testing them directly on DBM adult behavior.

Acknowledgments

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How do *Bacillus thuringiensis* Biopesticides Reduce Flea Beetle Damage on Leafy Brassicas?

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ABSTRACT

The striped flea beetle (*Phyllotreta striolata*) seriously threatens leafy brassicas in South and Southeast Asia, often resulting in severe crop failure and heavy reliance on chemical pesticides. However, control failures due to resistance development have been observed. A previous study in Cambodia found that *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) formulations effectively reduced *P. striolata* incidence and damage. This study aimed to confirm further the role of Bt formulations in controlling *P. striolata* beetles. An experiment was conducted in Taiwan under laboratory conditions, evaluating two Bt-based biopesticides, E-911® and Xentari®, alongside chemical and control treatments. The results showed a significant reduction in *P. striolata* damage in Bt-treated plants compared to controls and mechanically damaged plants ($F=10.39$, $P<0.0001$). The mean shot-hole numbers per plant ranged from 276-348 in Bt-treated plants versus 491-561 in controls. These findings have practical implications, suggesting that Bt biopesticides, typically used to manage caterpillar pests, can also effectively mitigate *P. striolata* damage, offering promising prospects for sustainable pest management in vegetable brassicas.

Keywords

leafy brassicas, *Phyllotreta striolata*, biopesticides, glucosinolates, spillover effects

INTRODUCTION

Brassicas are a vital group of crops worldwide, with cabbage, cauliflower, broccoli, mustard, and rapeseed being the major brassica crops cultivated in 44.5 million ha, with an annual production of 186.7 million tons (FAO 2024). South and Southeast Asia alone produce 38.12 million tons of major brassicas from 10.2 million ha annually. In addition to these crops, leafy brassicas such as Chinese cabbage, choysum, pakchoi, kale, and leafy mustard are widely produced and consumed in East and Southeast Asia (Hanson et al., 2011). Leafy brassicas are highly valued crops that can produce multiple harvests, making them very promising for small-scale farmers (Genova et al., 2010). Typically, these crops take 7 to 8 weeks to grow, but farmers often use re-sowing or staggered sowing to extend the harvest period (Schreinemachers et al., 2017). Despite their economic importance in Southeast Asia, leafy brassicas are often plagued by insect pests, such as diamondback moth (*Plutella xylostella* L.), common armyworm (*Spodoptera litura* Fab.), cabbage butterfly (*Pieris rapae* L.), and striped flea beetle (*Phyllotreta striolata* Fab.), which cause significant yield losses of up to 100% (Ungsa and Vanharn, 1995; Nhung et al., 2008).

The striped flea beetle (*P. striolata*) has recently emerged as the most important pest of leafy brassicas in South- and Southeast Asia, as the damage of this pest, especially in the early crop stages, can lead to complete crop failure. They oviposit in the soil, where the larvae hatch and start feeding on plant roots until they reach the pupation stage. Once they emerge from pupation, the adults emerge from the soil, initiating a new cycle of reproduction and infestation. Hence, the farmers rely on the indiscriminate use of chemical pesticides to control this pest. However, the small body size, strong mobility, and high reproductive capacity of *P. striolata* beetles made their management quite challenging (Liu et al., 2018). Control failures are reported due to the rapid development of resistance to chemical pesticides (Shen et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2023; Xiao et al., 2023).

In earlier studies in Cambodia assessing the effectiveness of bio-pesticides, including *Bacillus thuringiensis* formulations, it was found that the *B. thuringiensis* treatments reduced the incidence and damage of *P. striolata* (Srinivasan et al., 2020). Since *B. thuringiensis* formulations have primarily been used to manage lepidopteran pests (Srinivasan and Hsu, 2008; Shelton et al., 2009), their role in controlling *P. striolata* beetles needs further validation. Hence, this study aimed to confirm further the role of *B. thuringiensis* formulations in controlling *P. striolata* beetles.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An experiment was conducted in the laboratory condition at the World Vegetable Center, Taiwan, following a completely randomized design. Two commercially available biopesticide formulations based on *Bacillus thuringiensis*, E-911® (*B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki*) and Xentari® (*B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai*) were used for assessment. There were six treatments: (i) pakchoi plants infested with diamondback moth (DBM), (ii) pakchoi plants infested with DBM and sprayed with Xentari®, (iii) pakchoi plants infested with DBM and sprayed with E-911®, (iv) pakchoi plants infested with DBM and sprayed with spinetoram, (v) pakchoi plants mechanically damaged, and (vi) pakchoi plants with no infestation. Five DBM (second instar) larvae were released onto each plant. After one hour, the bio- or chemical pesticides were sprayed in T2, T3, and T4 treatments and kept for 2 h. The treated plants were moved to the cages (75 cm X 75 cm X 115 cm) and kept for 72 h. Then, 60 *P. striolata* beetles were released into each treatment and replicated nine times. After five days, the data on the feeding damage (total number of the shot holes) by *P. striolata* was recorded. The mean number of damage (shot holes) was computed and subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the Proc GLM procedure of SAS Version 9.4. Tukey's HSD test separated the means at a 5% significance level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flea beetle damage was much less where DBM larvae were managed using chemical and biopesticides than control, mechanically damaged plants and plants with DBM (Figure 1). The results showed that *P. striolata* damage was significantly less where DBM larvae were managed with *B. thuringiensis* biopesticides and spinetoram ($F=10.39$, $P<0.0001$). The mean number of shot-holes per plant in the Xentari®, E-911®, and spinetoram-treated plants was on par (276-348), compared to the untreated control (553), mechanically damaged plant (491) and the plant infested with DBM larvae (561) (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Mean (\pm SE) number of striped flea beetle damage (shot holes per plant) on pakchoi plants treated with different chemicals and biopesticides. Means with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $p<0.05$ by Tukey's HSD.

This laboratory assessment has demonstrated the spillover effect of biopesticide or chemical pesticide on the beetle's damage on pakchoi. Most of the microbial pesticides, especially *B. thuringiensis* formulations, were able to reduce the population of lepidopteran caterpillars, including DBM (*P. xylostella*), cabbage head caterpillar (*Crocidolomia pavonana*), cabbage webworm (*Hellula undalis*) and cabbage butterflies (*Pieris* spp.). Earlier studies had confirmed the susceptibility of DBM to various *B. thuringiensis* formulations and/or toxins in Taiwan. A recent study from Taiwan confirmed that *P. xylostella* was susceptible to Xentari and E-911, even though *B. thuringiensis* formulations are widely used by brassica farmers in Taiwan. Flea beetle damage was found less in the plant where DBM was managed using pesticides (biopesticides or chemical pesticides). A similar result was found in the trial conducted in Cambodia by Srinivasan et al. (2020). This might be due to the lower release of isothiocyanates in pesticide-treated plants. It has long been known that plant-derived isothiocyanates, secondary metabolites arising from the decomposition of non-volatile glucosinolates, attract some species of flea beetles. Several earlier researchers found that allyl isothiocyanate was attractive to crucifer-feeding *Phyllotreta* spp. (Vincent and Stewart 1984; Soroka et al. 2005; Tóth et al. 2009, 2012). Hence, less isothiocyanate or no release of isothiocyanate did not attract the beetles for feeding.

This suggests that applying bio-pesticides targeting caterpillar pests could reduce the incidence and damage by *P. striolata* as a spill-over effect, offering a hopeful prospect for the future of pest management in agriculture. This research provides practical implications for using biopesticides in pest control, particularly in the case of *P. striolata*. This could significantly improve the effectiveness and sustainability of integrated pest management in brassicas.

It should also be noted that the control treatment (pakchoi plants with no infestation) also had a higher number of shot holes per plant. It indicates that the occurrence of *P. striolata* beetles is influenced by factors other than host plant volatiles such as isothiocyanates. Hence, the spill-over effects of biopesticides targeting caterpillar pests in brassicas on *P. striolata* beetles can be considered only to some extent but not as a holistic solution. Applying biorational pesticides may be required when the *P. striolata* population density or the damage level exceeds the economic threshold.

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SESSION 3

Insecticide Resistance and Management in Crucifer Pests: The on-going Challenge

Managing Diamondback Moth Resistance to Insecticides in Fiji: A Flexible Insecticide Resistance Management (IRM) Strategy and the Importance of Community Engagement

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ABSTRACT

In Fiji, management of the diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* L. (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), has been constrained by resistance to broad-spectrum insecticides and access to selective products. Since 2013, the susceptibility of DBM field populations to a range of insecticides has been monitored. New selective products have been sequentially introduced and incorporated into an insecticide resistance management (IRM) strategy. The strategy is based on the “window” principle promoted by the Insecticide Resistance Action Committee (IRAC). It relies on the limited use of insecticides with different modes of action in discrete temporal windows that equate to the duration of the life cycle of the pest (≈ 18 days in Fiji) to minimize exposure of successive generations to similarly acting insecticides. Constrained by the insecticides available to farmers, the original strategy (developed and implemented in 2014) included indoxacarb, lufenuron, abamectin, AgChem-Bt (aizawai), and chlorantraniliprole. The strategy, initially supported by community meetings to engage farmers, worked well through 2017, and the susceptibility of field populations to

the recommended insecticides remained high. In 2018, high levels of DBM field resistance to indoxacarb, chlorantraniliprole, and deltamethrin were detected, indicating that the IRM strategy was either ineffective or not being adopted. Efforts were made to increase the range of selective insecticides available, and AgChem Bt (kurstaki) and spinosad were introduced to the market in collaboration with a local pesticide reseller. The IRM strategy was revised to include these new products, and the campaign was promoted in farming communities through information sessions. Between 2019 and 2022, the resistance of DBM field populations to the original recommended selective products declined, and susceptibility to spinosad and both AgChem Bt products remained high. We discuss the importance of continued community engagement for successful IRM and IPM adoption and sustainable insecticide use.

Keywords

Bt, abamectin, chlorantraniliprole, spinosad, selective insecticides, insecticide resistance management

INTRODUCTION

The diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), is a destructive pest and the major constraint to the production of *Brassica* crops in the South Pacific (Furlong 2016; Atumurirava et al. 2021). In Fiji, broad-spectrum insecticides and newer selective insecticides have been used widely in recent years, and several reports of field resistance to certain compounds in DBM field populations have been made (Atumurirava and Furlong 2011; Atumurirava et al. 2016, 2021).

Previously, we have reported on the susceptibility of DBM field- populations to key insecticides in the region (Atumurirava and Furlong 2011; Atumurirava et al. 2016, 2021), but in this study, we report on developing, implementing, and evolving an insecticide resistance management (IRM) strategy to mitigate resistance to selective insecticides in Fiji. As previously reported (Atumurirava et al. 2021), a key element of the overall strategy was developing a close working relationship with a local pesticide retailer to establish selective insecticides in the local marketplace. The collaboration enabled importation, local testing, repackaging (in small, affordable quantities), and training on using *Bacillus thuringiensis* products. This paper reports on the importance of effective community engagement, modification of the original IRM strategy, monitoring its effects, and the recent changes in insecticides used to manage DBM in the Sigatoka Valley, Fiji's major vegetable production area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Insecticides

Deltamethrin (Suncis[®], 25g a/kg⁻¹), indoxacarb (Steward[®], 200g aiL⁻¹) and chlorantraniliprole (Prevathon[®], 50g aiL⁻¹), *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* (AgChem Bt-a; 32000 IU), *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* (AgChem Bt-k; 32000 IU) and Spinosad (AgChem Spinosad 12 SC, 120g aiL⁻¹) were supplied by AgChem Fiji Ltd. Lufenuron (Match[®], 50g aiL⁻¹) was supplied by Morris & Hedstrum Fiji Ltd. All commercial insecticide formulations were stored at room temperature.

Plants

Chinese cabbage, *Brassica rapa* var. *chinensis* cv Pak choy, was used in all experiments and for all *P. xylostella* rearing. Seeds were sown into a mixture of alluvial soil and poultry manure in seed beds. Four-week-old seedlings were transplanted into potting bags filled with the same soil-manure medium and grown to the 7-8 leaf stage in a shade-house before use in bioassays or for maintaining the insect cultures.

Insects

Culture methods

All DBM strains were reared separately at room temperature (25°C). Adult moths were held in wooden-framed muslin-covered oviposition cages (45 x 45 x 45 cm) containing a fresh potted Chinese cabbage plant (7-8 leaf stage) and an adult food source (20% w/v aqueous honey solution). Plants were exposed to adult moths for 24 hours and replaced daily. Each egg-laden plant was labeled with the *P. xylostella* strain and oviposition date; plants containing eggs of different strains were kept separately. When the eggs on a plant hatched, the plant was cut at its base, transferred to a ventilated plastic box (10 x 20 x 30 cm), and covered with freshly excised Chinese cabbage leaves. Old dry leaves were removed daily and replaced with fresh leaves. When the insects developed into pupae, they were carefully removed from the rearing box and stored in labeled Petri dishes (9 cm diameter) before being used to maintain the culture.

Leaf-dip bioassays

A standard leaf disc bioassay method was used for all test insecticides, modified from previous studies (Furlong and Wright 1993, 1994; Furlong et al. 1994). Test solutions for each insecticide were prepared from commercial formulations using distilled water and 0.03% Tween-80 as a surfactant. Leaf discs (4.8 cm diameter) were cut from the middle leaves of Chinese cabbage plants and then immersed in the test solution for 10 seconds; the excess

solution was allowed to drip off the leaf discs for another 10 seconds, and then treated leaf discs were carefully placed, abaxial surface uppermost, on corrugated aluminum foil to dry for 1 h. Control leaf discs were treated by immersion in distilled water containing surfactant (0.03% Tween-80) only and then drained and dried in the same manner as insecticide-treated leaf discs. Four leaf discs were treated with each test solution and the control. When dry, treated leaf discs were placed individually into Petri dishes (5 cm diameter) lined with moist Whatman No.1 filter papers, 10 early 3rd instar larvae were carefully introduced to each Petri dish. Six to seven test insecticide solutions and a Tween-80 control were tested in each bioassay. Petri dishes were taped together, placed in a ventilated plastic container, and incubated at 25 (±2°C) with 12:12 (L:D). Treated leaf discs were removed after 48 h and replaced with fresh untreated Chinese cabbage leaves. Assessment of mortality varied between test insecticides: mortality caused by deltamethrin, indoxacarb, abamectin, spinosad, and chlorantraniliprole was assessed after 72 h, while mortality caused by lufenuron, Bt-a, and Bt-k was assessed after 96 h. Mortality was determined by gently prodding each larva with a paintbrush; any larva that did not respond to touch was considered dead.

Annual status of insecticide resistance

The susceptibility of field populations of DBM to commonly used insecticides was monitored from 2018-2022. Head cabbage or Chinese cabbage crops were hand-searched, and large larvae and pupae were collected and returned to the laboratory. A minimum of 50 individuals was collected per site (= small number of separate farms in a location), but typically >>100 individuals were collected. Insects from a single site were transferred to an oviposition cage to mate and lay eggs. Typically, second-instar larvae from the next generation of insects were used to test the population's susceptibility to a range of given insecticides. Still, in some cases, egg numbers produced were low, and numbers had to be built up over one or more generations before they could be tested in leaf dip bioassays. In all cases, the susceptibility of the field population was compared to that of the Waite population, a standard insecticide-susceptible DBM population that has been kept in the lab for more than 200 generations and has shown very stable responses to all insecticides throughout the study (data not shown). For any field population, the resistance ratio (RR) to a given insecticide was calculated by dividing the LD₅₀ of that insecticide against that population by the LD₅₀ of the insecticide against the Waite population. In any given year, a minimum of two different field populations were subject to bioassays, and resistance ratios for each insecticide were averaged across the populations for presentation. In 2021, farming communities in the Sigatoka Valley

completed a short, written survey detailing the insecticides they used to manage DBM.

Design, implement, and evolve the Insecticide Resistance Management (IRM) strategy in Fiji.

An insecticide resistance management (IRM) strategy was designed based on the principles of the Insecticide Resistance Action Committee (IRAC) (www.iraconline.org). Fundamentally, the strategy is based upon the rotation of insecticides with different modes of action to minimize the probability that individuals of successive generations will be exposed to insecticides with the same mode of action. The initial design of the strategy in 2014 (see Atumurirava et al., 2021) was constrained by very limited farmer access to selective insecticides. Bt, fundamental to sustainable management of *P. xylostella* (Furlong et al. 2013), was unavailable through commercial outlets. To ensure the reliable availability of Bt, we worked closely with a local retailer, AgChem Fiji, to facilitate the importation, field testing, registration, packaging, and promotion of a Bt-a product from Wuhan, China. Since then, we have continued to work with AgChem Fiji, and since 2022, Spinosad and Bt-k have been readily available to farmers in Fiji.

The original IRM strategy was launched and promoted in 2014. Initially, AgChem Bt-a was sold with a leaflet describing how it should be applied and how it fits into the IRM strategy. The launch was accompanied by a series of “Pesticide Forums,” which introduced the IRM strategy to farmers and extension officers. However, these meetings

declined over time. Following reports of DBM resistance to several insecticides, including broad-spectrum compounds that were incompatible with the IPM/ IRM program that had been promoted (see Atumurirava et al., 2021), the IRM strategy was refined to include the newly available selective insecticides and promoted through night meetings and combined plant health clinics (Smith et al., 2021) in farming communities. The fundamental elements of the IRM strategy are:

- Selective insecticides should be used in temporal “windows” that approximate the duration of a single DBM generation (≈ 18 days in Fiji).
- Available insecticides with different modes of action should be strategically alternated between windows.
- The original strategy was constrained by the availability of appropriate insecticides in 2014 [Steward (indoxacarb), Match (lufenuron), Multiguard (abamectin), AgChem Bt-a (Bt-a) and Prevathon (chlorantraniliprole)]. The revised strategy excludes Match but retains the other insecticides and includes AgChem Bt-k (Bt-k) and Spinosad.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In 2018, DBM field populations demonstrated significant resistance to Suncis (>12000 -fold), Prevathon (>2400 -fold), and Multiguard (>1300 -fold). Still, there was no evidence of resistance to Bt-a, Match, or Steward (Figure 1). Resistance to Suncis, Prevathon, and Multiguard declined through 2022, and there was no evidence of significant decreases in susceptibility to any of the selective products, including Bt-k and Spinosad, which were introduced in 2020 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Resistance ratios (LC_{50} of test population/ LC_{50} of laboratory insecticide-susceptible population) of field-collected DBM populations to insecticides in Fiji, 2018- 2022.

The original IRM strategy (Figure 2a) was introduced in 2014, and its adoption resulted in rapid declines in levels of DBM field resistance to Steward and Prevathon (Atumurirava et al., 2021). Adopting the IRM strategy also maintained the effectiveness of abamectin and AgChem Bt-k, two selective insecticides introduced as core elements of the strategy (Atumurirava et al., 2021). By 2018, adoption of the strategy had declined, and resistance to Prevathon and Multiguard had increased considerably (Figure 1). Resistance to Suncis was even greater, and as this insecticide is not compatible with IPM and was not recommended as part of the IRM strategy, this suggests that insecticide regimes had regressed to those that were typical before the launch of the original strategy. It was previously recognized (Atumurirava et al., 2021) that farmer education and awareness (understanding the fundamental hazards of pesticide use, safe and effective insecticide application, appreciation that broad-spectrum insecticides are incompatible with IPM, the unsustainability of intensive and continued use of single or a narrow range of insecticides and the need to rotate those insecticides that are used strategically) and the provision of reliable source of selective insecticides in the marketplace were fundamental to the successful approach. In 2019, awareness programs began again, integrated with plant health clinics held in the evenings in farming communities. In 2020, Bt-k and Spinosad became

available, and these were integrated into a revised IRM strategy (Figure 2b) that excludes Multiguard and Prevathon. Since its introduction, the susceptibility of DBM field populations to recommended selective insecticides has remained high, while resistance to the problematic insecticides has declined (Figure 1). However, a survey of insecticide use by *Brassica* farmers in the Sigatoka Valley in 2021 showed that farmer practices had changed markedly since the previous survey in 2017 (Figure 3). In 2017, >90% of insecticides used were IPM-compatible and recommended by the original IRM strategy (Figure 2a). By 2021, <70% of insecticides used were IPM compatible, and >30% of those used were not recommended by the original strategy (Figure 3). The use of Multiguard (31% in 2017, 20% in 2021) and Prevathon (31% in 2017, 12% in 2021) had declined, likely in response to the high levels of resistance exhibited to these compounds by DBM field populations (Figure 1). It is concerning that Multiguard and Prevathon were primarily replaced by pyrethroid and organophosphate insecticides (Figure 3). The community awareness meetings held since 2020 have promoted the revised IRM strategy (Figure 2b). There are plans to strengthen this by once again providing information leaflets that detail how to prepare and apply Bt as part of an IRM strategy that was considered instrumental in promoting the adoption of Bt a decade ago (Atumurirava et al. 2021).

Figure 2. a) IRM strategy as originally devised in 2014, b) an iteration of the revised IRM strategy once the new selective insecticides Bt-k and Spinosad became available in 2020.

Figure 3. The contribution of different insecticides to the overall insecticide use against DBM in the Sigatoka Valley, Fiji, in 2017 and 2021.

The revised strategy takes advantage of the newly available selective insecticides, Bt-k and Spinosad, and there is evidence that this is beginning to lower resistance levels. This long-term study shows that despite the initial success of an IPM/ IRM program, farmers must remain vigilant, and support networks must exercise long-term commitment to guide them through periods of change. As documented many times, DBM invariably develops resistance rapidly when any insecticide is used inappropriately in the tropics (Furlong et al. 2013), and the over-use of products that farmers consider effective is clear in this and other studies (Furlong et al. 2013; Li et al. 2016, Atumurirava et al. 2021). In 2021, we recommended that the susceptibility of DBM field populations and insecticide use be monitored frequently to record changes in insecticide susceptibility and over-reliance on any given insecticide (Atumurirava et al. 2021). The current study shows the importance of this approach. However, detection of the predictable problems is only part of the solution. Education and awareness campaigns must be maintained to promote sustainable pest management practices.

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SESSION 4

Biological and Non-Chemical Methods of Management of Crucifer Pests (Including Organic Agriculture)

Persistence and Phytotoxicity of Chitosan Derivatives against *Plutella xylostella* L. in Cauliflower

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation was carried out to evaluate the Chitosan-O-Arginine from marine waste. Out of the six concentrations tested against diamondback moth larvae on cauliflower in a pot culture experiment. The maximum percentage of mean mortality after 24 hours of exposure was recorded in higher concentrations of Chitosan-O-Arginine (CS-O-Arg) 9750 ppm (59.44 %) followed by 8750 ppm (57.22 %) and 7750 ppm (52.77 %), which were significantly on par. When the CS-O-Arg was tested at different concentrations, no phytotoxicity signs, such as leaf tip injury, wilting, necrosis, vein clearing, or epinasty, were recorded from one to 14 days, regardless of the concentration. The CS-O-Arg was biologically effective for 7 to 21 days after treatment against second instars.

Keywords

Chitosan O Arginine, Diamondback moth, Persistent study, Phytotoxicity, Mortality

INTRODUCTION

The diamondback moth (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae) *Plutella xylostella* (L.), a widely dispersed and economically significant oligophagous pest of various cruciferous vegetable crops, including cabbage, cauliflower, broccoli, radish, turnips, etc., (Gautam *et al.*, 2018). Using insecticides at higher rates causes many detrimental effects, such as residue, resurgence, resistance, and environmental hazards. All field populations exhibited high levels of resistance against chlorantraniliprole (36.67- to 124.72-fold), flubendiamide (12.66- to 93.63-fold), fipronil (31.99- to 156.24-fold), and cypermethrin (26.97- to 174.84-fold) (Tamilselvan *et al.*, 2021). Alternative eco-friendly insecticides have been necessitated to sustain the management of diamondback moths. Recently, chitosan has been gaining momentum in plant protection; hence, a significant focus was given to this study.

The marine waste of chitinous solids in India ranges from 60,000 to 80,000 tons annually. If not disposed of properly, they may cause pollution and pose a significant environmental threat. These wastes are converted to valid and economically worthy materials, viz., chitin and chitosan. This conversion helps improve this waste's economic potential into a by-product during food processing. It also helps minimize the potential threat as a source of environmental pollution. Using this innovative renewable waste material into economically appreciable and sustainable materials facilitates the conversion of waste to wealth, opening up an untapped market.

Chitosan is one of the most abundant natural amino polysaccharides extracted from the exoskeleton of crustaceans and insects, from fungal cell walls, etc. (Katiyar *et al.*, 2014). Chitosan is usually used when the polymers become soluble in a dilute acid solution. The solubility is also controlled by the distribution of the acetyl groups remaining along the chain (Matteus, 1997). Chitosan may serve as an excellent alternative to pest control because of its insecticidal and antimicrobial properties (Rabea *et al.*, 2003; Badawy *et al.*, 2005). With this background, the present study focused on evaluating the persistent and phytotoxicity of a chitosan derivative, Chitosan-O-Arginine (CS-O-Arg), under pot culture experiments during 2021-2022 against *P. xylostella* larvae and testing the phytotoxicity on pot cultured 30 days old plants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mass culturing of diamondback moth larva

Mustard seedlings were grown in small ice cream cups with vermiculite or an equal mix of red soil, sand, and farmyard manure. The seeds were sown and allowed to germinate and properly watered to ensure maximum germination of the seedlings. The cauliflower collected from the market was placed inside the cage to collect emerging adults. Then, five-day-old seedlings were placed inside an insect-rearing cage (1.5x1.5x1.5 ft) for egg laying of an adult. The emerging adults were allowed to feed on 30% honey and water-soaked swabs and oviposit on the mustard leaves for 24 hours. Upon hatching, the *P. xylostella* larvae were fed on mustard seedlings. When they completely ate the seedlings, the larvae were transferred to another set of fresh seedlings by chopping the remnants of the old seedlings and placing them over new seedlings. They were pupated in 15 days, collected, and put in an oviposition cage, and the culturing procedure continued.

Synthesize of CS-O-Arg

The CS-O-Arg was synthesized by adopting the method suggested by Hefni *et al.* (2020) with slight modification in the duration of the purification step. The crude chitosan flakes were suspended in distilled water. The acid derivative, L-arginine, was added to the chitosan solution (at the ratio of 1 chitosan: 2 L-arginine). The sulfuric acid catalyst was added to the chitosan arginine solution at ambient temperature. L-arginine was sparingly soluble in the H₂SO₄ solution, and adding HCl increased the solubility of L-arginine. The mixture was taken in a beaker, and the content was manually stirred at 80°C and cooled at room temperature. The CS-O-Arg derivatives were precipitated by adjusting the pH of the solution to 7 using sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃) solution. Then, the precipitate was filtered and washed with acetone until the unreacted acids were removed. Finally, the precipitate of CS-O-Arg derivatives was extracted using acetone in the Soxhlet apparatus for 24 h. Later, the residue was oven-dried at 60°C. CS-O-Arg was sieved, weighed, and stored in the refrigerator until further use for bioassay. The weight was used to estimate the recovery percentage.

Evaluation of persistent toxicity

Cauliflower plants (30 days old) were used for pot culture experiments to assess the persistent toxicity of CS-O-Arg. The concentrations were finalized based on the LC₅₀ of respective treatments. A total of six concentrations were used; the middle concentration was fixed as ten times the value of LC₅₀ (Selvarani *et al.*, 2022), and three concentrations above and below were finalized. They were 4750, 5750, 6750, 7750, 8750 and 9750 ppm for CS-O-

Arg. Azadirachtin 1% EC @ 2mL/L was used as a treated check, and distilled water was sprayed for the untreated check.

The treatments were given as foliar spraying using a hand atomizer on the 30-day-old plants @ one plant per replication, with three replications. The second instar larvae of *P. xylostella* (10 nos.) were released on the treated plants at regular intervals *viz.*, 3 hours, 2, 4, 6, 13, and 20 days after treatment and observation on the number of dead larvae were recorded after 24 h of release, *i.e.*, 1, 3, 5, 7, 14 and 21 days after treatment, respectively to test the pesticide's persistent toxicity. (Thanavendan and Kennedy, 2017). After each observation, the dead and live larvae were removed, and the percent larval mortality was estimated.

Evaluation of phytotoxicity

The phytotoxicity of CS-O-Arg was evaluated in pot culture on 30-day-old cauliflower plants at the concentrations used for the persistent toxicity *viz.*, 4750, 5750, 6750, 7750, 8750, and 9750 ppm for CS-O-Arg. Azadirachtin 1% EC @ 2mL/lit was used as a treated check, and distilled water was sprayed for the untreated check. Eight treatments with three replications and one plant were maintained for each replication. The experiment was conducted using a completely randomized block design. The plants were inspected for any phytotoxic signs such as wilting, leaf tip injury, necrosis, vein clearing, epinasty, and hyponasty on leaves after one to 14 days of treatment and recorded, if any. The severity of phytotoxicity was measured using the Central Insecticide Board and Registration Committee's scale (Nalini and Parthasarathi, 2018).

Leaf injury was assessed by visual rating on a 0-10 scale

Rating	Phytotoxicity (%)	Verbal Description
0	No phytotoxicity	No symptoms
1	1-10	Very slight discoloration
2	11-20	More severe, but not lasting
3	21-30	Moderate and more lasting
4	31-40	Medium and lasting
5	41-50	Moderately heavy
6	51-60	Heavy
7	61-70	Very heavy
8	71-80	Nearly destroyed
9	81-90	Destroyed
10	91-100	Completely destroyed

The percent leaf injury was calculated using the following formula,

$$\text{Leaf injury (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total grade points}}{\text{Maximum grade} \times \text{Number of Leaves Observed}} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

Data were statistically analyzed using SPSS for Windows (version 22) (IBMCrop 2013) software to find the ANOVA. Data was grouped using Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) test (Tukey, 1977), $p < 0.05$ level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Persistent toxicity and phytotoxicity of CS-O-Arg

The observations on the persistency of CS-O-Arg toxicity against *P. xylostella* in the pot culture experiment were

analyzed for up to 21 days at consecutive day intervals. The maximum percentage of mean mortality after 24 hours of exposure was recorded in higher concentrations, viz., Azadirachtin treated check (61.66 %), CS-O-Arg 9750 ppm (59.44 %) followed by 8750 ppm (57.22 %), and 7750 ppm (52.77 %) were significantly on par. In lower concentrations (4750 ppm, 5750 ppm, and 6750 ppm), the least mean mortality (4.44, 12.77, and 26.66%, respectively) was observed, but they were significantly superior to the untreated check. Meanwhile, the increased concentrations significantly increased the percentage of mortality.

Table 1. Persistency of Chitosan-O-Arginine (CS-O-Arg) toxicity against *P. xylostella* in pot culture experiment

Treatments	Mean larval mortality (%)#						Mean larval mortality
	1 DAT	3 DAT	5 DAT	7 DAT	14 DAT	21 DAT	
T1 – CS-O-Arg 4750 ppm	3.33±0.57 (5.04) ^d	10.00±0.00 (7.03) ^d	6.66±0.57 (6.04) ^e	3.33±0.57 (5.04) ^e	3.33±0.57 (5.04) ^e	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^e	4.44
T2 – CS-O-Arg 5750 ppm	6.66±0.57 (6.04) ^{cd}	13.33±0.57 (7.72) ^d	26.66±1.15 (10.17) ^d	20.00±1.00 (8.97) ^d	6.66±1.15 (6.04) ^d	3.33±0.57 (5.04) ^{cd}	12.77
T3 – CS-O-Arg 6750 ppm	10.00±1.00 (6.72) ^c	23.33±0.57 (9.65) ^c	56.66±1.15 (14.34) ^c	40.00±1.00 (12.19) ^c	20.00±1.00 (8.97) ^c	10.00±1.00 (6.72) ^c	26.66
T4 – CS-O-Arg 7750 ppm	16.66±1.15 (6.72) ^b	46.66±0.54 (13.12) ^b	83.33±0.57 (17.28) ^{ab}	60.00±1.00 (14.74) ^b	70.00±1.73 (15.87) ^b	40.00±1.00 (12.16) ^b	52.77
T5 – CS-O-Arg 8750 ppm	20.00±1.00 (8.28) ^b	50.00±1.00 (13.52) ^b	86.66±1.15 (17.60) ^a	66.66±1.52 (15.46) ^{ab}	76.66±01.15 (16.58) ^b	43.33±1.52 (12.60) ^b	57.22
T6 – CS-O-Arg 9750 ppm	23.33±0.57 (8.97) ^{ab}	56.66±1.15 (14.34) ^a	86.66±0.57 (17.61) ^a	70.00±2.00 (15.87) ^a	73.33±1.15 (16.22) ^b	46.66±1.15 (13.03) ^b	59.44
T7 – Azadirachtin 1% EC @ 2 ml/lit	30.00±1.00 (9.65) ^a	46.66±1.15 (13.08) ^b	83.33±1.15 (17.26) ^{ab}	70.00±1.00 (15.87) ^a	83.33±0.57 (17.28) ^a	56.66±1.15 (14.34) ^a	61.66
T8 – Untreated check	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^e	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^e	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^f	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^f	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^f	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^e	0.00
SED	1.41	0.84	0.97	1.25	1.35	1.33	-
P value	0.002*	<0.0001**	<0.0001**	<0.0001**	<0.0001**	<0.0001**	-

#Mean values of three replications are represented as mean± standard deviation

Figures in the parentheses are arc sine transformed values ($x+0.5$)

Means followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different from each other by Tukey's test ($p \leq 0.05$)

SED: Standard Error of the Difference; DAT- Days After Treatment; * Significant; ** Highly Significant; CS-O-Arg- Chitosan-O-Arginine

Table 2. Phytotoxicity of Chitosan-O-Arginine (CS-O-Arg) on cauliflower leaves in pot culture experiment

Treatments	Leaf tip injury (%) #	Wilting	Necrosis	Vein Clearing	Epinasty	Hyponasty
T1 – CS-O-Arg 4750 ppm	0	0	0	0	0	0
T2 – CS-O-Arg 5750 ppm	0	0	0	0	0	0
T3 – CS-O-Arg 6750 ppm	0	0	0	0	0	0
T4 – CS-O-Arg 7750ppm	0	0	0	0	0	0
T5 – CS-O-Arg 8750 ppm	0	0	0	0	0	0
T6– CS-O-Arg 9750 ppm	0	0	0	0	0	0
T7 – Azadirachtin 1% EC @ 2 ml/lit	0	0	0	0	0	0
T8 – Untreated check	0	0	0	0	0	0

#Mean values of three replications; Observed on one to 14 days after application; CS-O-Arg – Chitosan–O-Arginine

More than 50 % mortality was recorded in 8750 ppm (50.00 %), 9750 ppm (56.66 %) at 3 HAT, 7750 ppm (83.33 %), 6750 ppm (56.66 %) at 5 DAT and other two treatments were the least. In 9750 ppm, 8750 ppm, and 7750 ppm treatments, the mortality was more than 70 percent until 14 DAT (70.00 to 76.66 %), and it declined after 21 DAT (40.00 to 46.66 %). When the CS-O-Arg was tested at different concentrations, no phytotoxicity signs, such as leaf tip injury, wilting, necrosis, vein clearing, or epinasty, were recorded from one to 14 days, regardless of the concentration.

A pot culture experiment was done to study the persistence of chitosan derivatives and their phytotoxicity. The maximum percentage of mean mortality was recorded in higher concentrations, viz., CS-O-Arg 9750 ppm (59.44 %) and CS-O-Arg NF 300 ppm (69 %). The chitosan derivatives did not produce phytotoxicity signs such as leaf tip injury, wilting, necrosis, vein clearing, or epinasty when observed after 14 days of application. The present findings corroborate Thanavendan and Kennedy (2017), who reported that the crude extracts were biologically effective for seven to fourteen days after treatment against second instars. Hence, the developed chitosan derivatives could be recommended against *P. xylostella* in cruciferous vegetables.

CONCLUSION

After ingestion, CS-O-Arg, at 9750 ppm, was highly toxic to *P. xylostella* larvae. Its effectiveness under pot culture persisted up to 21 days after treatment. There were no phytotoxicity effects. CS-O-Arg has the potential to be an alternative for replacing insecticides, as it is also higher in biodegradability, environmentally friendly, and aids in reducing the use of insecticides.

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Developing vegetable hummingbird formulation to manage Diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus) infesting crucifers

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ABSTRACT

Diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* L. (Plutellidae: Lepidoptera), is the most nefarious and oligophagous pest of cruciferous vegetables, which has resisted all registered insecticides available in the market and also may potentially resist future molecules. The marketable yield loss of 50 to 80% was recorded due to *P. xylostella*. The inexhaustible source of environmentally safe bioactive compounds is an alternative to harmful pesticides. It was attempted to extract the bioactive principles from the following botanicals viz., *Azadirachta indica* unripe fruits and leaves of *Nerium oleander*, *Plumeria rubra*, *Sesbania grandiflora*, *Swietenia macrophylla*, and *Tagetes erecta*. The *A. indica* unripe fruits (24.74%) registered maximum recovery, followed by *P. rubra* leaves (24.41%), *S. macrophylla* leaves (21.35%), *T. erecta* leaves (20.46%), *N. oleander* leaves (19.82%) and *S. grandiflora* leaves (18.64%). Among the botanicals screened for their growth inhibition activity against diamondback moth, the *S. grandiflora* methanolic

extract (5%) displayed excellent results, showing minimum larval weight gain (0.47 mg) and longer exposure times (72 hrs) resulted in 100% larval death, no pupa formation and adult emergence. Hence, an attempt was made to develop an emulsifiable concentrate (22.5% EC) formulation with the crude extract of *S. grandiflora* by screening the suitable solvents and surfactants. The emulsion was found to be stable with the surfactant, Triton X 100 recorded the HLB 13.5, and DMSO (33.75%) was added as the water phase and methyl oleate as the oil phase in addition to the active ingredient (22.5%). Further insights into the study may end with an innovative approach to managing the diamondback moth.

Keywords

Plutella xylostella, Crucifers, *Sesbania grandiflora*, Methanolic extract, EC formulation.

INTRODUCTION

The diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* L. (Plutellidae: Lepidoptera), the World's most destructive pest, has been found on cruciferous plants in India since 1914 (Fletcher 1914). The species originated in Europe but has since spread around the globe (Wei et al., 2013). India is the World's second-largest producer (3.12 million tons) of cruciferous vegetables from a 0.331 million ha area. *P. xylostella* decreased the marketable yield of crucifers by 50-80% (Sharma and Singh 2014). It led to annual damage of US\$4-5 billion (Zalucki et al. 2012) and the need for an estimated 16 million USD in control expenditures (Sharma and Singh 2014). *P. xylostella* is well-known for developing resistance to various synthetic pesticides. In agriculture, the widespread and indiscriminate use of insecticides has indirectly contributed to enchain insects, resulting in increased fecundity rate, genetic plasticity, and rapid generation time, which resulted in insecticide resistance and pest outbreaks (Negahban et al. 2006). In India, Verma and Sandhu (1968) *P. xylostella*'s resistance to insecticides such as DDT and parathion was first documented in 1968 (Verma and Sandhu 1968) in Ludhiana, Punjab. Resistance to newer insecticides, as well as biologicals such as *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) formulations and cry toxins, has also emerged in specific *P. xylostella* field populations (Sayyed and Wright 2006; Zhao et al. 2006 and Pu et al. 2010). Secondary metabolite-rich plants (bioactive compounds) may withstand insect and disease assault and serve as a source for producing pesticides for field use. Plant-based insecticides provide an ecologically friendly alternative to toxic pesticides. Grainge et al. (1986) discovered that 82 plant species were effective against *P. xylostella*. Agrochemical formulations may be readily stored, transported, and administered using practical techniques for effective, safe, and economical usage (Hazra and Purkait 2019), enhancing environmental quality (Knowles 2008). Hence, the present research contributed to developing plant-based insecticides from *Sesbania grandiflora* leaves.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Diamondback moth rearing

An initial culture of *P. xylostella* was obtained by collecting cauliflower curd/head(s) from a diamondback moth-infested field at Dindigul (10.3624° N, 77.9695° E). The curd was kept in adult emergence cages measuring 1.5x1.5x1.5 ft at Insectary, Department of Agricultural Entomology, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai. The larvae present in curds developed and transformed into pupae. The pupae were gathered and stored in adult emergence cages for eclosion. The newly emerged adults were collected using test tubes and released into oviposition cages. The mustard seedlings (4 days old) were grown in paper cups and provided for egg laying. Honey solution (10%) was supplied with cotton swabs as feed for adults. After 24 h, creamy-yellow-coloured eggs were observed on the leaves, and stems of mustard seedlings were transferred to another empty cage. The larvae that emerged from the eggs were fed on the seedlings. Replenishment with new seedlings was done by placing next to the old seedlings, which were entirely fed by the larvae. Pupation was observed in a loose silk cocoon inside the cage. All the pupae were collected carefully and placed in an adult emergence cage to continue the life cycle. The required stage was used to conduct bioassay experiments.

Collection of plant parts

The required quantity of botanicals viz., *Azadirachta indica* unripe fruits, *Nerium oleander* leaves, *Plumeria rubra* leaves, *Sesbania grandiflora* leaves, *Swietenia macrophylla* leaves, and *Tagetes erecta* leaves were sourced from nearby farmer's fields and local markets of Madurai (9.9252° N, 78.1198° E). A mechanical blender was used to pulverize 1 kilogram of 15 to 20-day shade-dried brittle leaves, which were sieved through Sieve 40. The amber jars stored the leaf powders until they were used.

Extraction of bioactive compounds

The Soxhlet apparatus was used to extract bioactive compounds from 10g powder packed in cellulose thimbles at 45 °C for one to two days until the solvent removed all of the bioactive compounds and the solvent regained its color (Larkem et al. 2021). The extraction phase was repeated multiple times until every plant

sample's required quantity of extracts was achieved. Each plant's extract was filtered separately using a Buchner funnel fitted with Whatman No.1 filter paper. Solvents in extracts were condensed under reduced pressure using a Rotary Evaporator at 45°C. The final weight of the condensed extract was weighed to assess the recovery percentage of each plant material.

Growth inhibition bioassay

Contamination-free, fresh, fully opened mid-canopy cabbage leaves were collected from the greenhouse-grown plants and washed with distilled water, followed by air drying for 30 minutes. Leaf discs were cut (5 cm dia) and then dipped in 5 percent test solution (0.1% Triton X 100 used as surfactant) for about 30 sec. to facilitate uniform active ingredient treatment. The leaf discs were placed in a slant position in a tray for about two minutes to drain the excess solution and then allowed to dry for about 30 minutes at room temperature. Second instar larvae (10 nos. pre-starved for 2 h) were released on each treated disc in a plastic container lined with moist filter paper, and the experiment was replicated three times. Observations were made on the larval, pupal, and adult weight gain, which was recorded up to 72 h of treatment @ 24 h intervals.

Screening of solvents and surfactants

The best botanical crude solvent extract was selected to develop the Emulsifiable Concentrate (EC) formulation based on suitability. To determine its solubility efficiency, the following solvents were screened: cyclohexane, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), methyl oleate (MO), mahua oil, and cyclohexanone. Based on the measurements, the solubility percentage of the solvent was estimated, and the best two solvents were selected for further formulation. The hydrophilicity of the selected solvents was tested by dissolving them in water to find the oil- and water-phase solvents. After the selection of solvents, the screening of surfactant was done using the following surfactants: Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS), Nonyl Phenyl Ethoxylate (NPE), Tween 20, Triton X 100, Tween 80, and Span 80. Any turbidity/ creaming/ phasing/ sedimentation after 30 minutes was examined, and the two best surfactants were selected. The selected two surfactants were re-tested individually and in combination to formulate the oil and water phases. After the surfactant selection, the proportions of the surfactant were worked out according to the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB value) based on Griffin's method (1954).

HLB value was calculated using the formula,

$$HLB_{oil} = \frac{W_A \times HLB_A + W_B \times HLB_B}{W_A + W_B}$$

Where W_A = Amount of the first surfactant required

W_B = Amount of the second surfactant required

HLB_A = HLB value of the first surfactant

HLB_B = HLB value of the second surfactant

$$\% A = \frac{100 \times (x - \text{HLB}_B)}{\text{HLB}_A - \text{HLB}_B}$$

$$\% B = 100 - \% A$$

Where % A = Amount of the first surfactant required

% B = Amount of second surfactant required

Development of Emulsifiable Concentrate (EC) formulation by Ultrasonication method

The hydrophilicity of the active ingredient was assessed by dissolving it in water. Later, the aqueous phase and oil phase solvents were used to form the Emulsifiable Concentrate. A known quantity of crude botanical extract (aqueous phase) was weighed, the selected solvent (aqueous phase) was added, and the extract was thoroughly dissolved in the solvent manually with the help of a glass rod. Later, the contents were thoroughly mixed in a magnetic stirrer at 700 rpm for 30 minutes. Along with the contents, the second solvent/co-solvent (oil phase) was added and mixed in a magnetic stirrer for another 30 minutes. Later, two selected surfactants were added to the contents based on the ideal HLB value and thoroughly mixed using the magnetic stirrer. The coarse emulsion was

then ultrasonically emulsified for 30 minutes using an ultrasonicator/ homogenizer at a high frequency of 25.00 kHz. Finally, the ingredients were homogenized for 30 minutes in a high-shear homogenizer at 6000 rpm, resulting in a homogeneous mixture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Recovery of bioactive compounds

The maximum yield was obtained from the *A. indica* unripe fruits (24.74%), followed by *P. rubra* leaves (24.41%), *S. macrophylla* leaves (21.35%), *T. erecta* leaves (20.46%), *N. oleander* leaves (19.82%), and *S. grandiflora* leaves (18.64%) (Table 1).

Table 1. Recovery yield (%) of bioactive compounds in botanicals

S. No.	Plants	Fresh weight (kg)	Dry weight (g)	Recovery yield (%)
1.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	1.0	282.45	24.74
2.	<i>Nerium oleander</i>	1.0	278.72	19.82
3.	<i>Plumeria rubra</i>	1.0	267.81	24.41
4.	<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i>	1.0	251.68	18.64
5.	<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i>	1.0	293.84	21.35
6.	<i>Tagetes erecta</i>	1.0	241.75	20.46

Growth inhibition bioassay

Among the various botanicals screened for the growth inhibition activity against the diamondback moth, methanolic extract of *S. grandiflora* at 5% showed the slightest larval weight increase (0.47 mg) and longer exposure times (72 hrs) resulted in 100% larval death. As a result, the weight of the pupa and adult were not reported, followed by the treated check (*Azadirachtin* 1%) with a larval weight of 0.72 mg. There was 100% larval mortality due to *S. grandiflora* and *S. macrophylla*, so their effect on pupa and adults could not be recorded. The

subsequent best treatment, *T. erecta*, recorded minimum larval (2.75 mg), pupal (2.12 mg), and adult (0.84 mg) weight gain, which showed maximum reduction in their weights. The larval, pupal, and adult weights of the larvae fed on untreated leaves were 4.98, 4.86, and 2.07 mg, respectively (Table 2). It was discovered that *S. grandiflora* methanolic extract exhibited growth-inhibitory properties. Phytochemical evaluation of *S. grandiflora* showed the presence of different secondary metabolites, viz., alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, glycosides, cardiac glycosides, tannins, and phenols (Bahera et al. 2012). The presence of condensed tannins in

the *S. grandiflora* extract may be responsible for the unpalatability of the treated surface (Reed, 1994), resulting in reduced weight of life stages. When the growth and development of *P. xylostella* larvae are

inhibited, the larval weight gain will be significantly inhibited with the prolonged larval stages (Fan et al., 2023).

Table 2. Effect of bioactive compounds isolated using methanol on *P. xylostella* weight gain

Treatments	Dose (%)	Larval weight gain* (mg)	Pupal weight* (mg)	Adult weight* (mg)
T ₁ - <i>Azadirachta indica</i>	5	3.56±0.01 (2.01) ^e	3.13±0.01 (1.91) ^b	1.28±0.01 (1.33) ^b
T ₂ - <i>Nerium oleander</i>	5	3.56±0.01 (2.01) ^e	3.52±0.01 (2.00) ^c	1.52±0.01 (1.42) ^b
T ₃ - <i>Plumeria rubra</i>	5	3.58±0.03 (2.02) ^e	3.77±0.01 (2.07) ^d	1.71±0.01 (1.49) ^c
T ₄ - <i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> #	5	0.47±0.00 (0.98) ^a	-	-
T ₅ - <i>Swietenia macrophylla</i> #	5	1.08±0.00 (1.26) ^c	-	-
T ₆ - <i>Tagetes erecta</i>	5	2.75±0.02 (1.80) ^d	2.12±0.01 (1.62) ^a	0.84 ±0.01 (1.16) ^a
T ₇ - Treated check# (Azadirachtin 1%)	2ml/l	0.72±0.01 (1.10) ^b	-	-
T ₈ - Solvent check	-	5.00±0.01 (2.35) ^f	4.91±0.01 (2.33) ^e	2.11±0.00 (1.61) ^d
T ₉ - Untreated check	-	4.98±0.01 (2.34) ^f	4.86±0.01 (2.32) ^e	2.07±0.01 (1.60) ^d
Sed	-	0.015	0.009	0.010
F-value	-	2350.33	10155.47	2885.07
p(significance)	-	0.00	0.00	0.00

*Mean values of three replications are represented as mean ± standard deviation;

Figures in parentheses square root transformed values ($\sqrt{x + 0.5}$); #100% mortality of larvae observed after 7 days of treatment; In a column, mean followed by same letter not significantly different from each other, DMRT (F-test; $p \leq 0.05$; $n=10$); SEd: Standard error of the difference.

The results here are in line with those of Sangavi and Edward (2017), who discovered that at 0.6 percent concentration, *S. grandiflora* leaf ethyl acetate extract had minimal adult emergence (45%) compared to the control (100%). Adult lifespan was reduced by 5.3, 3.2, and 2.7 days at 15, 20, and 30 ppm concentrations of *S. mahogany* methanolic leaf extracts, respectively, when treated compared to the control (Kumar et al. 2018).

Development of *S. grandiflora* 22.5% Emulsifiable Concentrate (EC) formulation by Ultrasonication method

The best combination of the two selected surfactants viz., Nonyl Phenyl Ethoxylate (HLB 13.1) and Triton X 100 (HLB 13.5) were evaluated to achieve proper formulation, based on the HLB values viz., 13.1, 13.2, 13.3, 13.4 and 13.5. The hydrophilicity of the selected best solvents, viz., Methyl Oleate and Dimethyl Sulfoxide, was evaluated by dissolving 1 ml of solvent in 10 ml of water. The methyl oleate formed an oily layer, considered the oil phase, while dimethyl sulfoxide dissolved entirely in water and formed a clear solution; hence, it was identified as a water phase.

The solubility of the active ingredient, *S. grandiflora* methanolic crude extract, was assessed by dissolving 1 ml in 10 ml of water and found to be dissolved completely. Hence, *S. grandiflora* 22.5% EC formulation was developed by dissolving the active ingredient (22.5%) in the water phase, DMSO (33.75%), and they were mixed in magnetic stirrer at 700 rpm for 30 minutes followed by ultrasonication (40 kHz) for 1 hour. The oil phase, Methyl Oleate (33.75 g), was added to the water phase @ 5 ml per minute and mixed in a homogenizer (25 kHz) for 30 minutes at 6000 rpm. Finally, the *S. grandiflora* 22.5% EC formulation arrived. This formulation was subjected to Emulsion stability tests, and observations were recorded. Results revealed two-phase separation in the combinations, from 13.1 to 13.4, after 30 minutes, but there was no sedimentation, turbidity, and creaming. The emulsion was stable only in the HLB 13.5 and Triton X 100.

With growing awareness of the toxicity of conventional pesticide formulations, there has been a considerable transformation from petroleum- and organic solvent-based pesticide formulations to user- and environment-friendly water-based ones. (Knowles 2008). The industrialized World has made significant progress in developing

environmentally friendly formulations that are safer for plants and the environment. (Green and Beestman 2007) This formulation would not only replace hazardous, non-degradable ingredients/adjuvants in conventional formulations but also improve the bio-efficacy of the products by combining the most up-to-date pesticide residue reduction technology. (Hazra et al. 2017) Moreover, unlike traditional pesticides, which are based on a single active component, plant-derived pesticides comprise various chemical compounds that work together to affect behavioral and physiological processes. (Akhtar et al. 2008) Consequently, instead of selecting a single isolated and purified bioactive component for pest management, we chose a crude combination of bioactive compounds.

CONCLUSION

Though insecticides were vital in DBM management, their wider usage has resulted in the insect developing resistance to many chemical insecticides. Our study concluded that among the treatments tested for their toxicity against the second instar of *P. xylostella*, methanolic leaf extract of *S. grandiflora* (5%) was most effective in growth inhibition. The Emulsifiable Concentrate (EC) formulation of *S. grandiflora* 22.5% could be an alternative to synthetic insecticides.

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Impacts of Increasing Global Temperatures on *Diadegma semiclausum*, an Important Parasitoid of the Diamondback Moth.

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ABSTRACT

The parasitoid *Diadegma semiclausum* has been widely adopted as a biological control agent for diamondback moth over the last 80 years. Understanding the thermal dynamics of the host-parasitoid interactions is crucial to predicting how the utility of *D. semiclausum* might be affected by geographic locations and climate change. We compared the performance traits of the host and this solitary endo-larval parasitoid over a range (10-30°C) of constant rearing temperatures. Based on the experimental data, the modeling package CLIMEX was used to investigate the suitability of current climates for the host and the parasitoid and the effects on their potential global geographical distributions. The study was then extended to investigate possible changes to these distributions that might result under different climate change scenarios that can be anticipated by 2080. The models predict that the host and parasitoid's global distributions will be reduced. These changes will not be proportionate, and many areas in tropical, sub-tropical, and temperate regions currently suitable for the parasitoid are predicted to be no longer suitable while retaining suitability for the diamondback moth. The host and parasitoid's seasonal dynamics are also predicted to be significantly reshaped under climate change. The present study demonstrates the constraints on the efficacy of *D. semiclausum* for controlling diamondback moths in likely future climates.

Keywords

Host-parasitoid interaction, CLIMEX, global warming, biological control

INTRODUCTION

The specialist, solitary endo-larval koinobiont parasitoid *Diadegma semiclausum* Hellén (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) has been widely adopted as a classical biological control agent of *Plutella xylostella* over the last 80 years (Furlong et al. 2013). Throughout the introduction history, *D. semiclausum* persistence has been restricted to temperate regions, highland areas in the tropics (Vos 1953, Chua and Ooi 1986, Momanyi et al. 2006, Upanisakorn A. et al. 2011) and sub-tropical regions where it occurs seasonally (Furlong et al. 2004, Furlong and Zalucki 2007); no attempts to establish the parasitoid in lowland tropical islands have succeeded (Waterhouse 1992). Meanwhile, there have been reports of *D. semiclausum* occurrence without previous introduction in continental regions of the Middle East (e.g., Kadirvel et al., 2011; Pourian et al., 2015). The locality-specific successes of introductions and experimental data on the relative thermal responses of *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* suggest that *D. semiclausum* has a much lower heat tolerance than its host (Doddall et al. 2012, Furlong and Zalucki 2017, Wang et al. 2021). Understanding responses of host-parasitoid interactions to changes in the environment, particularly temperature, is crucial to planning the introduction of parasitoids to new regions and to predicting how parasitoids' biological control is likely to be affected by climate change (Hance et al., 2007; Furlong and Zalucki, 2017; Thierry et al., 2019).

CLIMEX is a modeling package that can be used to predict the geographical distribution, seasonal phenology, and relative abundance of a species based on its biology and historical or predicted climatic data (Sutherst and Maywald 1985, CSIRO 2016). The responses of *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* to temperature have been used previously to parameterize CLIMEX models to investigate current and possible future site suitability (Li et al. 2012, Li et al. 2016) and global distributions of the pest and its parasitoid (Furlong and Zalucki 2017). These studies show that the distributions of both *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* are likely to change significantly by 2070 and that in many regions, including some important *Brassica* vegetables growing areas in Australia, the host-parasitoid relationship is predicted to be seriously disrupted by this time (Furlong and Zalucki 2017).

In this study, the thermal responses of *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* measured in congruent laboratory studies (Wang et al. 2020, Wang et al. 2022) were used to refine the previous CLIMEX models (Furlong and Zalucki 2017)

by using more precise experimental data of host and parasitoid responses to temperature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Temperature-development rate models

The development rates of *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* when reared on *Brassica oleracea* L. *capitata* var. sugarloaf leaf discs over a range of constant temperatures (10 - 30 °C) in the laboratory were obtained from Wang *et al.* (2020) and Wang *et al.* (2022), respectively.

Different thermal performance curve models were previously evaluated, and the best-fit models were chosen for *P. xylostella* (Liu *et al.*, 2002) and *Diadegma insulare* (Bahar *et al.*, 2014), another endo-larval parasitoid of *P. xylostella* and a close relative of *D. semiclausum*. The data from the studies above were used to evaluate further and confirm the suitability of these two models compared to other candidate mathematical models using the same curve-fitting methods as Liu *et al.* (2002) and Bahar *et al.* (2014). All models were fitted using GraphPad Prism version 8.0.0 for Windows (GraphPad Software, San Diego, California, USA, 2020). The Wang model (Wang *et al.*, 1982) was used to describe the relationship between temperature and development rate (Liu *et al.*, 2002; Bahar *et al.*, 2014) of *P. xylostella* over its complete lifecycle. The Briere model (Briere *et al.*, 1999) was used to describe the relationship between temperature and the development rate of *D. semiclausum* over its complete lifecycle.

Mapping the current and predicted future distributions of *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* in CLIMEX

Current and future distributions of *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* worldwide were simulated using CLIMEX (CSIRO, 2016). CLIMEX calculates a growth index (GI) as a product of temperature (TI) and moisture indices (MI). The growth index corresponds to the population growth rate and describes the potential of a population to increase at a location. TI and MI have a range of temperature and moisture conditions over which growth is maximized. The growth rates decrease above and below the optimal range, and growth ceases at upper and lower thresholds. The relative suitability of a location for a species to persist is summarized by the annual eco-climatic index (EI), scaled to 100:

$$EI = 100 \sum \frac{GI}{52} \times SI \times SX \quad (1)$$

where 52 is the number of weeks in a year; annual growth index (GI) indicates the potential population growth for a

species at a given site; SI are stress indices, describing the species responses to the extreme cold (cold stress (CS)), heat (HS), dry (DS), and wet (WS) conditions. SX are the interactions between these conditions (cold-dry (CDS), cold-wet (CWS), hot-dry (HDS), and hot-wet (HWS) stress). The stress indices and their interactions accumulate at specified rates when a threshold is exceeded. All indices are calculated weekly using long-term monthly average maximum and minimum data for temperatures, rainfall, and humidity values for a location. Sites with positive EI values are suitable for species persistence. The greater the EI value, the greater the site's suitability.

To obtain key parameters for the CLIMEX simulation model, the lower and higher thermal limits and optimum temperature ranges for both *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* were estimated from the relevant temperature-development rate model. Other parameters that few studies have investigated were obtained from previous estimates for these species and the built-in templates of similar species (Doddall *et al.*, 2012; Li *et al.*, 2012; CSIRO, 2016; Furlong and Zalucki, 2017). CLIMEX uses long-term climate data (1961-1990) to estimate current climatic conditions to simulate the global distribution of suitable sites for species based on EI values (Sutherst and Yonow, 1998; Furlong and Zalucki, 2017). Predicted future distributions were simulated by using predicted global climate data for 2080 (10' resolution; 2080 is the default year for prediction of the "future" in CliMond) from "CliMond" (<https://www.climond.org/>), which generates future climate maps based on a range of carbon emissions and climate change scenarios (Kriticos *et al.*, 2012). The geographical distribution of sites and their relative suitability for the host (EI_h) and parasitoid (EI_p) were mapped in CLIMEX.

Field validation for seasonal suitability prediction

To examine the reliability of the simulation and to detect factors other than climate that affect population dynamics, the weekly GIs simulated by CLIMEX were compared to monthly field data of *P. xylostella* populations collected by pheromone traps (indicated by monthly proportion of individuals in total number of moths collected in a year and larva counts per plant in cabbage crops at different locations in China (Li *et al.*, 2016) and Australia. A similar comparison was conducted for *D. semiclausum* parasitism using data collected from the summer of 1992 to the spring of 1995 in Gatton, Queensland, Australia.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Temperature-development rate models

Compared to its host, *D. semiclausum* had lower thermal limits and a narrower optimum temperature range according to its thermal performance curve (Figure 1). This is significant because most previous studies have investigated only the host or the parasitoid in isolation (Furlong and Zalucki, 2017). Comparisons between such discrete studies can be problematic due to different food sources, host populations, and experimental conditions (Furlong and Zalucki, 2017). The present study provides direct evidence of lower thermal tolerance of the parasitoid when compared with its host, which is likely to be the main cause of its failure to establish as a biological control agent in hot areas, and it is predicted that future global warming can be more deleterious to the parasitoid than to its host.

Figure 1. Thermal response curves describing the development rates of *Plutella xylostella* (host) and *Diadegma semiclausum* (parasitoid) in response to temperature.

Current and future global distributions of *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum*

Using refined temperature parameters (Table 1), the CLIMEX model suggests that many areas of the world are currently climatically suitable for *P. xylostella* (Figure 2a). The current suitability map for *D. semiclausum* shows that hot regions, such as lowlands in the tropics, are not suitable for the parasitoid, so it is impossible to use it as a reliable and persistent biological control agent in these areas (Figure 3a). The CLIMEX predictions are consistent with the field introduction history of *D. semiclausum* in that the parasitoid established and provided long-term control of *P. xylostella* after introductions into cooler temperate and sub-tropical areas and highlands in the tropics (see Furlong et al. (2013) for full summary). There have been reports of natural occurrence of *D. semiclausum* in the continental Middle East (e.g., Kadirvel et al., 2011;

Pourian et al., 2015), where conditions are hot and dry. Kadirvel et al. (2011) found that the parasitoid could not survive when parasitized hosts were continuously reared at 35 °C, while they could survive when reared at fluctuating day and night temperatures of 35 °C and 20 °C, respectively. This suggests that the lower temperature at night at these continental localities might contribute to their survival in these hot areas. In future work, considering the implications of *P. xylostella* genetic diversity (Juric et al., 2017) and local differences in suitability for parasitism by *D. semiclausum* (Gols et al., 2019) will help further improve predictions of the effects of climate change on this host-parasitoid interaction.

Table 1. Temperature parameter values used to generate *P. xylostella* (host) and *D. semiclausum* (parasitoid) spatial distributions and seasonal suitability in CLIMEX.

Parameter	Definition	Host	Parasitoid
DV0	Lower temperature limit (°C)	8	8
DV1	Lower end of the optimum range of temperature (°C)	19.39	16.77
DV2	Upper end of optimum range of temperature (°C)	29.51	27.82
DV3	Upper temperature limit (°C)	34	31.06
PDD	The number of degree days above DV0 required to complete lifecycle	268	217

Figure 2. Predicted global Ecoclimatic Index (EI) maps of *Plutella xylostella* generated by CLIMEX model (a) under current climatic conditions and (b) under predicted 2080 climate change scenarios.

Figure 3. Predicted global Ecoclimatic Index (EI) maps of *Diadegma semiclausum* generated by CLIMEX model (a) under current climatic conditions and (b) under predicted 2080 climate change scenarios.

By 2080, predicted elevated temperatures will significantly affect the global distributions of both *P. xylostella* and *D. semiclausum* (Figure 2b; Figure 3b). At higher latitudes, areas of high suitability will shift further north or south as conditions warm towards the poles. More severely, predicted elevated temperatures by 2080 will make it impossible for *D. semiclausum* to persist in most tropical and subtropical regions and some temperate regions (Figure 3b), where it can currently do so (Figure 3a). *Diadegma semiclausum* will no longer be an effective biological control agent in these areas, while *P. xylostella* will very likely persist (Figure 2b). Similar patterns may also be evident for other parasitoids because of the differences in thermal ranges and temperature optima across hosts and their parasitoids (see meta-analysis in Furlong and Zalucki (2017)).

Field validation for seasonal suitability prediction

Figure 4 compares the weekly GIs simulated by CLIMEX and monthly field data of *P. xylostella* populations and *D. semiclausum* parasitism.

Figure 4. Comparisons among CLIMEX simulated seasonal suitability (orange dots: previous simulation; blue squares: refined simulation) and field phenology data (indicated by relative abundance; black triangles) for *Plutella xylostella* (a-e) and *Diadegma semiclausum* (f) at 5 sites (China: a-d; Australia: e and f).

CONCLUSION

Climate change will decrease the effectiveness of *D. semiclausum* as a biological control agent in areas where it currently contributes to *P. xylostella* population suppression. It is important to recognize that other parasitoid species attack *P. xylostella* in tropical and subtropical regions that perform better in warmer climates. For example, *Cotesia vestalis* Haliday (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) performs much better than *D. semiclausum* at higher temperatures in southeast Asia (Talekar and Yang 1991). Predicted climate change may have a less harmful effect on these species, which could be alternative biological control agents, but this remains to be investigated.

This study can contribute to forecasting *P. xylostella* outbreaks and the geographical suitability and likely population growth of *D. semiclausum* under climatic and seasonal changes.

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The Potential of Entomopathogenic Nematodes and Biopesticides against Flea Beetles (*Phyllotreta striolata* and *P. chotanica*) on Choy Sum in Hot, Wet, and Dry Seasons in Thailand

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ABSTRACT

Flea beetles (*Phyllotreta striolata* and *P. chotanica*) cause severe damage to brassica crops and lead to dramatic yield losses. Flea beetle populations are increasing continuously due to the year-round production of brassica crops in Southeast Asia, especially short-cycle leafy brassicas such as choy sum (*Brassica rapa* and *B. chinensis*). Since insecticides are not very practical for managing the flea beetles, we evaluated the alternatives such as entomopathogenic nematodes (EPN) [*Steinernema siamkayai* and *Steinernema carpocapsae*], biopesticides (neem extract, *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, and a combination of *Beauveria* plus *Metarhizium*) and insecticides (carbaryl, abamectin, fipronil, and tolfenpyrad) on choy sum under controlled and field conditions. Under controlled conditions, susceptibility of the third instar larvae and adults of flea beetles were assessed. The bioassay was conducted using half of the recommended dose, the recommended dose, and twice the recommended dose of the EPNs, bio-

pesticides, and chemical pesticides compared with untreated control. The results revealed that increased concentrations of EPNs and bio-pesticides caused higher larval mortality. The highest mortality of 63% and 60% was obtained with twice the recommended dose of *S. carpocapsae* and *Beauveria* plus *Metarhizium*, respectively, which were on par with Fipronil (80%). Likewise, *S. carpocapsae* also caused 60% adult mortality at 6 days after treatment, similar to Fipronil (100%) at twice the recommended dose at 3 days after treatment. Field trials were conducted at the World Vegetable Center, Nakhon Pathom, Thailand, during the hot, wet, and dry seasons (April-December) of 2021. The biopesticides and insecticides were applied individually in a sequence at weekly intervals. The study found that biopesticides reduced feeding damages of flea beetles (2.72 damaged holes/ 4 cm² and performed equally as insecticides (2.89 damaged holes/ 4 cm²) in the wet season, while the leaf damage did not differ significantly among the treatments in hot and dry seasons. The marketable yield did not differ significantly among the treatments in all the seasons. Of the total harvest, the proportion of marketable yields of EPN (*S. siamkayai*), biopesticides, and insecticide-treated plots was 55-84%, 53-61%, and 46-49% in hot, wet, and dry seasons, respectively. It was 67%, 46%, and 52% in the untreated control plots. Our study revealed that combining EPNs and entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) can be an effective alternative for flea beetle management.

Keywords

Phyllotreta spp., Biopesticides, Entomopathogenic nematodes, *Steinernema siamkayai*, *Steinernema carpocapsae*,

INTRODUCTION

Brassica vegetables play an important economic role worldwide and provide numerous nutritional benefits, as they contain protein, high vitamin levels, minerals, fiber, and phytochemicals (Sadowski and Kole, 2011; Sanlier and Guler, 2018). Choy sum or caixin (*Brassica rapa* var. *parachinensis* or *B. chinensis* var. *parachinensis*) is one important brassica grown popularly in East Asia, South East Asia, and South Asia countries, with year-round production (Opeña and Tay, 2016). However, choy sum production is affected given its susceptibility to various insect pests such as the beet armyworm (*Spodoptera exigua*), the fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), the diamondback moth (*Plutella xylostella*), the green looper caterpillar (*Trichoplusia ni*), the white butterfly caterpillar (*Pieris brassicae*) and aphids (*Brevicoryne brassicae*) (Wang and Liu, 2020). In addition, two primary brassica flea beetles comprising striped flea beetles (*Phyllotreta striolata*) and blue flea beetles (*P. chotanica*), are selective

oligophagous herbivores that feed primarily on brassica crops (Knodel, 2017). Flea beetles' larvae are soil-dwelling and feed on root hairs since adult females prefer to deposit eggs at the plant base, whereas adults feed above ground and are highly mobile when disturbed. In both cases, larvae and adults are highly damaging to the plant, and it isn't easy to control them. In addition, crop injury occurs from planting until harvest, and adult feeding results in a shot-hole pattern on the leaf surface (Yan et al., 2013). Moreover, when plants are attacked in the seedling stage, the most significant crop loss occurs within the first two weeks after plant emergence (Knodel, 2017).

Unfortunately, chemical pesticides are a continuous threat to vegetable production. For example, fruits and vegetables imported from Southeast Asia to European Union/ European Economic Area countries were detected with 12% residue sample above maximum residue levels (MRLs), and the highest residues were found on vegetable products from Vietnam (33%), followed by Malaysia (11%), and Thailand (9%). In addition, the positive residue samples detected more than one or five pesticides at 52% and 10%, respectively (Skretteberg et al., 2015). Moreover, the surveillance samples of 12 typical vegetables consisting of radish, choy sum, tomato, cucumber, cowpea, cabbage, leek, bitter melon, pak-choi, eggplant, and celery from 15 provinces in China showed that leafy vegetables contained higher residue rate compared to fruits and root vegetable (Xu et al. 2018). The most frequent pesticide residues on choy sum were alpha-cypermethrin and fipronil, with 83% pesticide residue in 30 samples collected from the fields in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam (Nguyen et al., 2022).

Alternative approaches are required to reduce pesticide use in flea beetle management, including biopesticides as a safer approach. Several biopesticides, such as entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) and entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs), are widely used. A study conducted under laboratory conditions by Sukleard et al. (2016) showed 100% mortality of striped flea beetles after 7 days of exposure to *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metazan®) and *Beauveria brassiana* (Buverin®). Likewise, three EPNs of *Steinernema siamkayai*, *S. carpocapsae*, and *Heterorhabditis indica* could cause adverse effects to third-instar larvae, pupae, and adults of striped flea beetles. The results under field conditions confirmed that these EPNs could reduce striped flea beetle populations and decrease the damaged length of Chinese radishes (Noosidum et al., 2020). In Chinese kales, *S. carpocapsae* could also suppress the flea beetles at similar levels to the control offered by *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *Tenebrionis* and fipronil (Vetchayan et al., 2013). Although many research studies have shown numerous efficient biopesticides, a surge in the potential of commercial products is frequently detected (Andersen et

al., 2006; Jackson et al., 2010; Jaronski, 2010). Moreover, the efficiencies of EPNs in actively host searching and effectively controlling *Phyllotreta* adults in brassica crops have been confirmed (Xu et al., 2010). However, EPNs are still far from being a realized choice for farmers to use in flea beetle management. Therefore, this study aims to generate information on the efficacy of biopesticide products, especially EPNs, for flea beetle management in Southeast Asia. The selected applications of EPNs and biopesticides were evaluated to show the efficiency of suppressing the third instar larvae and adult flea beetle under controlled conditions and their performances under field conditions in hot, wet, and dry seasons.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Flea beetle culture

For *P. striolata* culture, two hundred adults of *P. striolata* were collected using an insect aspirator from leafy brassicas at World Vegetable Center, Research and Training Station, Nakhon Pathom, Thailand (N 14° 1' 46.887", E 99° 57' 51.104"). The colonies were transferred into insect cages (50 x 50 x 50 cm) and allowed to feed on choy sum under laboratory at 25±2°C; 75±5% relative humidity (RH). For oviposition, 200 adults were transferred to a plastic container (15 x 25 x 7 cm) to lay eggs on choy sum leaves. The plastic container lids were covered with a fine net (60 mesh) for ventilation, and sterile substrates were placed at the bottom of the container for pupation. The sterile substrate was a mix of soil and sand with a 3:1 ratio and sterilized in a hot air oven at 80°C for 1 h. Oviposition was allowed for 48 h, and all adults were removed from the container. After four days, choy sum seedlings with roots were placed inside the container to serve as a food source. Food was supplied *ad libitum* (free feeding) and replaced every two days until pupation. The development period from egg to adult was 19-27 days; egg four days; larva (1-3 instars) 10-16 days; and pupa 5-8 days. This method helped to uniform the ages of the third-instar larvae and adults for experiments.

Susceptibility of the third instars and adults of flea beetles to selected applications

Eight treatments of EPNs (*S. siamkayai* and *S. carpocapsae*), neem extract, *B. brassiana*, *M. anisopliae*, *B. bassiana* plus *M. anisopliae*, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, Fipronil were tested to compare with control (water) at the recommended concentration and twice of the recommended concentration. Four plants of 5-week-old choy sum with roots were placed into a container (9.5 x 14.5 x 4 cm) filled with sterile substrate and treated with one single treatment. Ten individuals in the third instar

larvae were placed on the treated roots and maintained until they reached the adult stage. The old treated plants were replaced every two days with new treated plants. The experiment with three replications was designed following a completely randomized design (CRD) and conducted under optimum conditions for EPNs and biopesticides at $25\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$; $75\pm 5\%$ RH. To assess insect mortality, the number of alive- and dead adults was monitored daily for 7 days. The same procedures were set to evaluate the susceptibility of adults in a round plastic container (9.5 cm diameter x 5.5 cm height) by using treated leaves instead of treated roots.

Evaluation of efficiency of entomopathogenic nematodes and biopesticides against flea beetles under field condition

Choy sum was sown directly to a field with 80 g per plot. Individual plot size was 1.5 x 5 m, containing four rows, 30 cm row spacing, and 4 m plot-plot spacing; total experimental area was 32 x 23.5 m (752 m²). The trial consisted of four treatments, including entomopathogenic nematodes (*S. siamkayai*), two bio-pesticides (neem extract & *B. bassiana* plus *M. anisopliae*), chemical treatment, and control treatment (water). In addition, four selected chemical products (Carbaryl 85% WP, 40 g/ 20 l of water, abamectin 1.8% EC, 30 ml/ 20 l of water, Fipronil 5% SC, 40 ml/ 20 l of water, Tolfenpyrad 16% EC, 30 ml/ 20 l of water) were applied individually as a rotation. Treatments were applied using the recommended dose of each product one week after sowing and stopped two weeks before harvest, with a weekly application regime. Treatments were arranged following a randomized completed block design (RCBD) with four replications, and the experiments were conducted in hot (April-June), wet (July-September), and dry (November-December) seasons. Population densities and feeding damage of flea beetles were recorded one week and two weeks after sowing, respectively. Marketable and non-marketable yields were recorded once at the plant's mature stage.

Population densities of flea beetles

The rating number of flea beetles (1 = no adult; 2 = 1-10 adults; 3 = 11-30 adults; 4 = 31-50 adults; and 5 = >50 adults) was randomly monitored on ten plants per replication. Applications were started one week after direct sowing and stopped at a two-week pre-harvest interval.

Feeding damage of flea beetles

Visual counting of damaged holes at 4 cm² was recorded on ten randomly selected leaves on each replication. Data was recorded at the same period as the population densities of flea beetles.

Percentage of marketable yield

$$\text{Percentage of marketable yield} = \frac{\text{Marketable yield} \times 100}{\text{Total yield}}$$

Data analysis

Data on insect mortality and population density under controlled conditions, feeding damage, and marketable yields under field conditions were adjusted for normal distribution using transformation (*arc-sine*, *square-root*, *log* transformations). After normalization, the difference was analyzed using two-way ANOVA comparing two factors of treatments and concentrations for controlled conditions and one-way ANOVA in field conditions, with treatments as the main factor and subjected to Tukey's post hoc test as required.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Increased concentration of EPNs and bio-pesticides caused higher larval mortality of the third instar ($F_{8, 54} = 21.17$, $p = 0.001$). The highest mortality of 63% and 60% was obtained with twice the recommended dose of *S. carpocapsae* and *Beauveria* combined with *Metarhizium*, respectively. They were on par with Fipronil (80%) (Fig. 1). Likewise, *S. carpocapsae* also caused 60% adult mortality at 6 days after treatment similar to Fipronil (100%) at twice the recommended dose at 3 days after treatment ($F_{8, 54} = 13.20$, $p = 0.00$) (Fig. 2). Significant interaction between treatments and concentrations were not detected in both trials; larval mortality $F_{16, 54} = 1.76$, $p = 0.06$; adult mortality ($F_{16, 54} = 0.61$, $p = 0.87$). This result confirmed the previous report indicating *S. siamkayai*, *S. carpocapsae*, and *Heterorhadittis indica* effectively killed the third instar larvae, pupae, and adults of flea beetles, especially larval stage was the most susceptible (Noosidum et al., 2020). The optimum temperature of *S. carpocapsae* was at 25°C . The influence of temperature on the performance of *S. carpocapsae* was detected at 15°C and 35°C reduced mortality of flea beetle and reproduction rate of *S. carpocapsae*. This EPN had limited mobility at 15°C , and the reproduction of infective juveniles (IJs) in the host cadavers declined at both temperatures. (Xu et al., 2010).

Figure 1. Laval mortality of striped flea beetles under controlled condition

Figure 2. Adult mortality of striped flea beetles under control condition

Field trials were conducted at World Vegetable Center, Nakhon Pathom, Thailand, during the hot, wet, and dry seasons (April-December) of 2021. The biopesticides and insecticides were applied individually in a sequence at weekly intervals. The study found that biopesticides reduced feeding damages of flea beetles (9.93 % reduction of the damaged holes and performed equally as insecticides (4.30 % reduction of the damaged holes) in the wet season while EPN (*S. siamkayai*) got higher like control ($F_{3, 12} = 6.30, p = 0.01$) (Table 1). In contrast, the

leaf damage did not differ significantly among the treatments in hot and dry seasons (Tables 2 and 3). The marketable yield did not differ significantly among the treatments in the evaluated seasons. Of the total harvest, the proportion of marketable yields of EPN (*S. siamkayai*), biopesticides, and insecticide-treated plots was 55-84%, 53-61%, and 46-49% in hot, wet, and dry seasons, respectively. Meanwhile, 67%, 46%, and 52% in the untreated control plots (Table 1-3).

Table 1. Mean ± SD of parameters indicating the efficiency of EPN, biopesticides, and chemicals against brassica flea beetles in the wet season (July - September 2021)

Treatment	Adult density (score 1-5)	Damaged hole (hole/ leaf)	Marketable yield (%)
EPN	1.53 ± 0.17	3.03 ± 0.23 a	56.91 ± 16.60
Biopesticides	1.50 ± 0.12	2.72 ± 0.21 b	52.51 ± 23.17
Insecticides	1.50 ± 0.08	2.89 ± 0.28 ab	61.24 ± 13.23
Control	1.55 ± 0.10	3.02 ± 0.17 a	45.71 ± 19.13
P-value	0.16	0.01	0.97
F-value	0.92	6.30	0.45

Means within columns with different letters differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)

Table 2. Mean ± SD of parameters indicating the efficiency of EPN, biopesticides, and chemicals against brassica flea beetles in the hot season (April - June 2021)

Treatment	Adult density (score 1-5)	Damaged hole (hole/ leaf)	Marketable yield (%)
EPN	1.65 ± 0.17	4.10 ± 0.49	54.82 ± 36.68
Biopesticides	1.68 ± 0.13	3.55 ± 0.58	59.54 ± 40.33
Insecticides	1.73 ± 0.05	3.61 ± 0.32	83.61 ± 9.94
Control	1.73 ± 0.05	3.78 ± 0.39	67.21 ± 13.66
P-value	0.72	0.13	0.49
F-value	0.45	2.48	0.86

Means within columns with different letters differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)

Table 3. Mean ± SD of parameters indicating the efficiency of EPN, biopesticides, and chemicals against brassica flea beetles in the dry season (November - December 2021)

Treatment	Adult density (score 1-5)	Damaged hole (hole/ leaf)	Marketable yield (%)
EPN	1.28 ± 0.05	1.48 ± 0.12	46.46 ± 6.95
Biopesticides	1.25 ± 0.10	1.54 ± 0.14	49.47 ± 11.62
Insecticides	1.30 ± 0.19	1.40 ± 0.19	47.23 ± 7.34
Control	1.20 ± 0.08	1.49 ± 0.24	51.67 ± 12.05
P-value	0.33	0.78	0.90
F-value	1.33	0.37	0.18

Means within columns with different letters differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)

Various environmental factors influence the reduction of EPF efficiency. The effects of UV-A and UV-B radiation and heat from sunlight are major environmental factors that negatively affect field use (Rangel et al., 2005). Relative humidity is required at least 96.5-98.5% for high conidial production of EPF. *Beauveria* and *Metarhizium* had high sensitivity to high temperatures beyond their upper thermal limits at 32-35 °C (Quesada-Moraga et al., 2023).

Regarding EPN efficiency, the host-finding behavior of EPNs also influences the successful application of EPNs to control insect pests in the field, as well as the optimum temperature and relative humidity (Lewis et al., 2006). *S. carpocapsae*, *S. siamkayai*, and *H. indica* responded to plant-damaged traces caused by adult and larva flea beetles. After 60 min, these three EPNs also moved toward plant-damaged traces caused by adult beetles more than by larvae under laboratory conditions (Mangtab et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

S. carpocapsae led to high mortality on the third instar larvae and adults of flea beetle on par with chemicals under controlled conditions. A combination of *Beauveria* plus *Metarhizium* showed the same trend in larval mortality. Likewise, the sequence applications of biopesticides combining neem extract and *B. bassiana* plus *M. anisopliae* led to reduced feeding damage under field conditions. Therefore, combining EPNs and entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) can be an effective alternative for flea beetle management.

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Biological Control of Diamondback Moth and Other Crucifer Insect Pests by Microbial Entomopathogenic Fungi

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ABSTRACT

Cruciferous crops, including cabbage, cauliflower, mustard, broccoli, and radish, are crucial for winter crop production. These crops face significant threats from a range of insect pests, notably *Pieris brassicae* (cabbage butterfly), *Plutella xylostella* (diamondback moth), *Brevicoryne brassicae* (cabbage aphid), and *Trichoplusia ni* (cabbage looper). Diamondback moth (DBM) stands out as a global scourge, causing up to 80% of crucifer crop losses worldwide. Alarmingly, DBM has developed resistance to a staggering array of synthetic insecticides, rendering traditional chemical control strategies increasingly ineffective. This growing crisis necessitates transitioning to environmentally friendly pest management methods, and entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) have emerged as promising solutions. EPFs offer sustainable alternatives, such as *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, and *Verticillium lecanii*. With their diverse insect hosts and compatibility, these fungi have demonstrated significant efficacy against lepidopteran insect pests. With approximately 750 EPF species identified over the last century, their adaptability to various ecosystems is evident. EPF possesses formidable enzymatic capabilities and produces potent toxins, making them formidable biological control agents. Once they infect an insect host, EPF exhibits vigorous vegetative growth, invading host tissues and triggering a cascade of physiological, histological, and pathological changes, ultimately resulting in the death of the host insect.

The versatility of EPF, including their broad host range, environmental prevalence, enzymatic prowess, and lethal toxins, positions them as ideal candidates for sustainable and eco-friendly pest management strategies in cruciferous crop production. This review explores the potential of microbial entomopathogenic fungi, specifically *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*, in addressing the challenges posed by DBM and other crucifer insect pests, shedding light on sustainable pest control methods for cruciferous crops.

Keywords

Biocontrol; Microbial; Biopesticides; *B. bassiana*; *Plutella xylostella*

INTRODUCTION

Applying entomopathogenic microorganisms in insect-pest control has emerged as a promising and environmentally sustainable strategy in agriculture. Entomopathogens encompass various naturally occurring agents, including fungi, bacteria, viruses, and nematodes, which exhibit pathogenicity towards a broad spectrum of insect pests. Unlike conventional chemical pesticides, entomopathogens offer precision and ecological safety in pest control. While bacteria and viruses are host-specific, fungi have a broader host range and can infect aboveground and soil-dwelling pests, as highlighted by recent research (Deka et al., 2021).

The agricultural sector faces an ongoing battle to protect cruciferous crops, including cabbage, cauliflower, mustard, broccoli, and radish, from the persistent attack of insect pests. Among these insects, the diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* L., stands out as a notorious and globally widespread threat, accountable for significant crop losses. DBM has become more resistant to a staggering array of synthetic pesticides, which makes managing it even more difficult. As a result, there are few effective control measures available to farmers. Within this context, microbial entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) have emerged as a promising and cutting-edge strategy for managing DBM and other crucifer insect pests. These fungi, including *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae*, possess specific properties and mechanisms that make them formidable contenders in biological pest control.

This review paper aims to delve into the many aspects of utilizing microbial entomopathogenic fungi as a biological control weapon against crucifer insect pests, with a primary concern on DBM. Through a comprehensive study of their biology, modes of action, and field applications, this review seeks to shed light on the potential of these fungi to offer sustainable solutions to a

critical agricultural challenge. This review intends to provide valuable insights and perspectives for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers pursuing environmentally friendly and effective insect pest management strategies in cruciferous crop cultivation.

HOST PLANTS OF DBM

Diamondback moths exclusively target cruciferous plants, including various vegetables such as broccoli, cabbage, cauliflower, kale, radish, and cruciferous weeds (Harcourt 1957).

DISTRIBUTION OF DBM

The diamondback moth is widespread worldwide and can be found in the Americas, Europe, Asia, Australia, New Zealand, and the Hawaiian Islands. Some specialists claim that the Lepidoptera species is most widely distributed. The distribution of the diamondback moth has been a subject of considerable debate among researchers. Early studies, such as Hardy (1938), suggested that its origin might be traced back to Europe. However, more recent investigations have introduced alternative hypotheses. Kfir (1998) raised the possibility that South Africa is where the diamondback moth first appeared, citing the presence of complex parasitoid species and host plants. Additionally, Liu et al. (2000) proposed an East Asian origin for this notorious pest based on specific lines of evidence. It's worth noting that North American populations of the diamondback moth are likely linked to its European roots, as indicated by Hardy's findings from nearly a century ago.

ECONOMIC LOSS OF CRUCIFEROUS CROPS BY INSECT PESTS

Loss by diamondback moth

The economic impacts of insect pests on cruciferous crops are very concerning, with the Diamondback moth emerging as a devastating and globally ongoing threat to crucifers. A striking statistic presented by Sarfraz et al. (2006) emphasizes the level of severity of the issue, as this voracious pest alone is responsible for inflicting approximately 90% of global damage to cauliflower crops. It should be noted that the problem of Diamondback moths does not just affect cauliflower; these pests, together with its devastating counterpart, the cabbage webworm, damage several brassica vegetable crops across many African countries, specifically in tropical and subtropical climates (Grzywacz et al. 2010). DBM management has resulted in an enormous financial cost, with estimates ranging from US\$ 4 billion to US\$ 5 billion, as Zalucki et

al. (2012) revealed. These losses are a direct result of the persistent feeding habits of DBM larvae, which feed on plant leaves, stems, flower heads, and pods. Ultimately, this could lead to yield reductions of up to 80%, as Anonymous (2010) reported.

Loss by cabbage white butterfly

The cabbage white butterfly (*Pieris rapae*) is another significant global threat to cabbage and cauliflower crops. Research by Shankar et al. (2016) highlights the severity of this insect pest's impact. Astonishingly, a single caterpillar can consume as much as 74 to 80 cm² of leaf area, as Younas et al. (2004) reported, resulting in substantial damage.

Loss by aphids

A report in Pakistan revealed that in winter, oilseed crucifer crops face threats primarily from mustard aphids (*Lipaphis erysimi* Kalt.), with cabbage aphids (*Brevicoryne brassica* L.) and potato aphids *Myzus persicae* (Sulz.) playing a lesser role. Aphids, notably, constitute the most significant insects that pose a threat, with staggering yield reductions ranging from 70% to 80%, as evidenced by recent studies (Hamid and Ahmad 1980; Rustamani et al. 1998). Among these aphids, the cabbage aphids stand out as the predominant threat, affecting cabbage, cauliflower, rape, and turnip rape crops extensively across European and American countries, as reported by Weiss (1983). These findings underscore the critical need for effective pest management strategies to safeguard cruciferous crop yields and mitigate economic losses.

CHALLENGES IN INSECT PEST MANAGEMENT

The regulation of Diamondback moth populations in cruciferous crop fields is closely related to the availability of host plants and the actions of its natural antagonists, constituting two main biotic factors in their ecology (Harcourt 1986; Kfir 1997). However, in numerous countries, the traditional use of synthetic insecticides for DBM control has inadvertently triggered a cascade of challenges. One of the detrimental effects of improper use of insecticides is eradicating the natural enemies crucial for DBM population control. This concerning cycle increases the dependence on insecticides, leading to the emergence of resistance to these insecticides and, consequently, the failure of pest control measures. In 1953, DBM made history by becoming the first crop insect to exhibit DDT resistance, an event documented in Java, Indonesia, by Ankersmit (1953). Now, in the present, DBM has displayed significant resistance not only to traditional insecticides but also to novel chemical classes

such as spinosyns, avermectins, neonicotinoids, pyrazoles, and oxadiazines (Sarfraz and Keddie 2005; Sarfraz et al. 2005). Many synthetic pesticides, including endosulfan, lindane, and DDT, carry significant risks of environmental pollution and adverse effects on public health (Kapeleka et al. 2019; Ntow et al. 2006). Reports by De Bon et al. (2014) and Weinberger and Srinivasan (2009) have highlighted the persistence of numerous synthetic pesticides in the environment, posing threats to human health, non-target organisms, and ecosystems. Furthermore, the use of synthetic pesticides in the environment often leads to water and soil pollution, as illustrated in (Figure 1).

Figure 1. How pesticides disrupt the ecosystems.

INSECT PEST CONTROL BY EPF

Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) are microorganisms with a specific ability to infect and often lethally affect insects and other arthropods. Most of them are not poisonous to humans or animals and are not pathogenic to plants, as elucidated by Skinner et al. (2014). It's important to remember that approximately 60% of insect-related diseases can be attributed to these pathogenic fungi, as highlighted by De Faria and Wraight (2007). At least 90 different genera and 700 species of fungi are pathogenic to insects, and they are found in all except the upper basidiomycetes of the significant fungal taxonomic groups, as pointed out by Roberts and Humber (1981). In the intricate web of natural ecosystems, these fungi play a fundamental role in regulating insect populations, positioning themselves as more ecologically friendly alternatives than conventional chemical insecticides, as emphasized by De Faria and Wraight (2007).

As of April 2016, the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) had signed up 1,401 products containing 299 active biopesticide ingredients, as documented by Kupfer and McManus (2008). Among these, the biological control agents that exhibit the highest effectiveness are *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Beauveria bassiana*, and *Bacillus thuringiensis*, as reported by

Montalva et al. (2016). The commercially produced EPF species predominantly belong to the asexual phases within the order Hypocreales (Ascomycota), including *Beauveria*, *Metarhizium*, *Nomuraea*, *Isaria* (formerly *Paecilomyces*), *Hirsutella*, and their sexual counterparts (teleomorphs) such as *Cordyceps*, *Ophiocordyceps*, and *Metacordyceps*, as documented by Sung et al. (2007) and Kepler et al. (2012). For instance, *Metarhizium anisopliae* and *Beauveria bassiana* have received approval from the EPA as bona fide biological control agents. These fungi develop conidia that adhere to the insect's cuticle, followed by a complex enzymatic process primarily involving fungal protease production. This enzymatic activity, coupled with mechanical processes guided by appressoria development, culminates in the penetration of the insect's cuticle and the eventual invasion and demise of the insect, with the fungi extracting their nutrients from the insect's tissues, as elucidated by Mendoza et al. (2019).

MICROBIAL CONTROL OF DBM

The study by Sen et al. (2021) explored the impact of various microbial insecticide dosages on the pupation success of Diamondback Moth (DBM) larvae. The microbial insecticides and their dosage were *Bacillus thuringiensis* at 1 g/l, 1.5 g/l, and 2 g/l, *Beauveria bassiana* at 3 g/l, 4 g/l, and 5 g/l, and *Metarhizium anisopliae* at 3 g/l, 4 g/l, and 5 g/l. Their findings reveal intriguing insights into the interaction between these microbial treatments and DBM pupation. The data showed consistently low percent pupation rates across all microbial treatments compared to the untreated control. Within 72 hours after treatment, minimal pupation was observed, ranging from 7.50% to 40.00%, and this variation was statistically non-significant among the treatments. However, after 96 hours, a significant divergence emerged, with pupation rates ranging from 15.00% to 87.50%. The efficacy of *B. bassiana* at 4 g/l was particularly noteworthy, which resulted in the lowest pupation rate of 15.00% and proved to be the most effective treatment. Subsequently, at 144 hours post-treatment, pupation rates varied from 25.00% to 87.50%, with *B. bassiana* at 4g/l maintaining its superior performance. These findings underscore the potential of microbial treatments in suppressing DBM pupation, showcasing their promise as valuable tools in insect pest management strategies.

Another study by Soth et al. (2022) delved into the bioinsecticidal potential of two entomopathogenic fungal isolates, namely *B. pseudobassiana* I12 Damo and *B. bassiana* CTL20, both sourced initially from New Zealand and previously recognized for their high virulence against DBM larvae. The research aimed to evaluate the impact of these isolates when applied at different rates (Low: 6×10^4 , medium: 6×10^6 , and high: 6×10^7) on DBM larvae

feeding on various Crucifer's species viz. broccoli, cabbage, cauliflower, and radish. The results indicated that there were no significant variations in larval mortality between the two *Beauveria* strains across all Crucifers species at medium ($83 \pm 4.00\%$ - $100 \pm 0.00\%$) and high application rates ($94 \pm 6.00\%$ - $100 \pm 0.00\%$). However, a noteworthy variation emerged for isolate CLT20 at the low application rate ($33 \pm 11.00\%$ - $61 \pm 3.00\%$), which displayed higher mortality rates among DBM larvae feeding on radishes than those on broccoli. These findings underscore the complexity of interactions between the fungal isolates and DBM larvae, influenced by factors such as fungal strain, application rate, and host plant, providing valuable insights into the potential for tailored bioinsecticide applications in DBM management strategies.

This study also focused on applying filtered supernatants from three genetically different isolates, namely *B. pseudobassiana* FRhp, *B. pseudobassiana* FW Mana, and *B. bassiana* CTA20, sourced from the BPRC culture collection. Their investigation revealed that the supernatants at varying concentrations application (half and full-strength), led to noteworthy mortality rates of DBM larvae within just 7 days post-treatment. Notably, *B. pseudobassiana* FW Mana demonstrated remarkable effectiveness, outperforming the other two isolates at both concentrations. At half-strength, FW Mana exhibited a statistically significant ($F_{2,2} = 71.75$, $p < 0.003$) advantage, causing 35% and 20% more DBM larval mortality than *B. pseudobassiana* FRhp and *B. bassiana* CTA20, respectively. At full strength, FW Mana maintained its superiority, inducing 25% more mortality compared to both FRhp and CTA20, once again with statistically significant outcomes ($F_{2,2} = 113.56$, $p < 0.001$) (Figure 5). These findings underscore the potential of *B. pseudobassiana* FW Mana as a potent bioinsecticide for controlling DBM infestations, offering valuable insights for future integrated pest management strategies.

MICROBIAL CONTROL OF OTHER CRUCIFER'S INSECT PESTS

Cabbage white butterfly

A bio-efficacy of *B. bassiana* isolates viz. MTCC 2028, MTCC 4495, MTCC 6291, and NBAII-11 were evaluated by Dhawan and Joshi (2017), against cabbage butterflies *P. brassicae* (L.) where these isolates hold particular significance. These isolates were used in combating third-instar larvae of the cabbage butterfly, a notorious pest in cruciferous crops. The studies revealed intriguing variations in virulence among these fungal isolates. The highest mortality rate, reaching an impressive 86.66%, was achieved by *B. bassiana* MTCC 4495 when administered at a higher concentration of 10^9 conidia/ml.

Conversely, the lowest mortality rate, at 30.00%, was observed with *B. bassiana* MTCC 6291, administered at a lower concentration of 10^7 conidia/ml, following a ten-day treatment regimen. These findings underscore the importance of isolate selection and spore concentration in developing effective biocontrol strategies against cabbage butterflies and other insect pests.

Cabbage aphids

In a study by Mostafa (2020), the efficacy of three entomopathogenic fungi viz. *Verticillium lecanii*, *B. bassiana*, and *M. anisopliae* were rigorously assessed to control cabbage aphid (*Brevicoryne brassica* L.). The research involved the application of three distinct spore concentrations (1×10^5 , 1×10^6 , and 1×10^7 spores/ml) in field conditions. The results highlighted significant differences in cabbage aphid reduction between the initial and subsequent spray applications, with the differences becoming more pronounced after the second and third treatments. Notably, the third concentration (1×10^7 spores/ml) of *V. lecanii* exhibited the highest efficacy in controlling *Brevicoryne brassica*, closely trailed by the third concentration of *B. Bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*. Across all concentrations, these treatments remarkably reduced aphid populations, ranging from 90.0% to 97.7%. These compelling findings underscore the potential of *V. lecanii*, *M. anisopliae*, and *B. Bassiana* isolates as promising agents for effective cabbage aphid control in agricultural fields.

ADVANTAGES OF EPF OVER CHEMICAL PESTICIDES

EPF has been employed for approximately two centuries as a powerful biocontrol weapon against various crop pests. Notably, EPFs such as *B. bassiana*, *B. brongniartii*, *M. anisopliae*, *I. fumosorosea*, *M. brunneum*, *M. robertsii*, and *H. thompsonii* demonstrate their versatility by targeting various arthropod pests belonging to different feeding guilds (Dara 2019). These fungi offer several advantages over chemical pesticides, making them a sustainable alternative for pest management. Firstly, their high specificity ensures pest control without harming beneficial insect predators or nonharmful parasites. Secondly, EPF applications do not harm mammals and the environment, reducing pollution concerns associated with chemical pesticides. Thirdly, EPF does not trigger insect resistance, offering prolonged pest control. Moreover, their persistence in the environment leads to enduring pest suppression effects. These attributes, coupled with their suitability for mass production in various media, make EPF an attractive and sustainable solution for pest control (Dong et al. 2016).

Additionally, EPF's unique capacity to function as endophytes within plants rather than through inundative applications presents a promising approach to overcoming the limitations imposed by unfavorable climatic conditions in the field (Vega 2018). For instance, *Beauveria bassiana* can persist within host plants for extended durations as an endophyte, offering long-term protection. Endophytic colonization has been observed in various plant species, including Chinese cabbage, radish (Junhui et al. 2020), citrus (Bamisile et al. 2020), jute (Biswas et al. 2012), and so on, demonstrating its potential across diverse agricultural contexts. Successful endophytic colonization yields multiple benefits, including plant growth promotion, insect pest protection, systemic resistance induction, antagonization of plant pathogenic microorganisms, and mitigation of abiotic stressors' adverse effects (Kim et al. 2008; Liao et al. 2014; Vega 2018). Furthermore, EPF's role as a root of secondary metabolites with applications in pharmaceuticals, such as antimicrobial and antitumor agents, provides an advantage over chemical pesticides (Gouda et al. 2016; Yadav 2018).

Numerous investigations have accumulated substantial evidence affirming that these beneficial EPFs can improve soil biology and microbial community, improve plant nutrient and water uptake, trigger systemic resistance, and act as probiotics that counteract harmful microorganisms (Behie et al. 2015; Jaber and Alananbeh 2018). Another intriguing facet of employing endophytic fungi as agents for controlling insect pests lies in their effectiveness against certain notorious pests that have either developed resistance to chemical pesticides or have successfully evaded conventional chemical treatments. An example of such a pest is the diamondback moth, which developed resistance against DDT (Ankersmit 1953) but has been now reported to be vulnerable after treatment of cabbage with endophytic *B. bassiana* (Sen et al. 2021). In light of these advantages and their potential to address the challenges of sustainable food production, EPFs are emerging as promising replacements for chemical pesticides in both small- and large-scale agriculture (Dara 2019).

CONCLUSION

In agricultural pest management, microbial entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) is a robust and sustainable approach, as elucidated in this comprehensive review paper. Over two centuries, EPF, including notable species like *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Verticillium lecanii*, and so on, have proven their versatility and efficacy against a wide range of arthropods, including the notorious diamondback moth. Their advantages over chemical pesticides are abundantly clear, such as precision in pest targeting, environmental safety,

avoidance of insect resistance, and long-lasting pest control effects.

Moreover, the innovation of utilizing EPF as endophytes within plants rather than inundating applications offers a promising avenue to overcome the limitations imposed by adverse climatic conditions. This approach, demonstrated with *Beauveria bassiana* and other EPF, provides prolonged protection and multiple benefits for host plants, such as growth promotion, systemic resistance induction, and antagonizing harmful microorganisms. Furthermore, EPF's role as a root of secondary metabolites with applications in pharmaceuticals adds a unique dimension to their utility. Their ability to address challenges in sustainable food production and their effectiveness against pests that have developed resistance to chemical pesticides underscore their potential as sustainable replacements for traditional chemical control methods.

To sum up, the remarkable capabilities of microbial entomopathogenic fungi in controlling DBM and other crucifer insect pests, both as direct biocontrol agents and endophytes within plants, pave the way for sustainable and eco-friendly pest management practices. With ongoing research and innovation, the integration of EPF into agricultural systems holds great promise for achieving efficient pest management while promoting the health of crops and the environment, ensuring a more sustainable future for crucifer crop production.

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Current Approaches of Exploring Biocontrol Potential of Endophytic *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) Vuillemin (Ascomycota: Hypocreales) in Diamondback Moth Management in Cabbage

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ABSTRACT

Cabbage, *Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L. is the main temperate crop cultivated in different climatic regions worldwide. A plethora of pests and diseases decrease crop productivity and ruin the quality of commodities. Amongst them, Lepidopteran defoliators, specifically larvae of diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus (Plutellidae: Lepidoptera) is the most destructive pest on cabbage crop, causing more than 90% marketable yield loss under outbreak situations. Control of DBM in crucifer crops is achieved mostly through broad-spectrum chemical insecticides. Still, these toxicants eliminate not only the native beneficial organisms but also induce the development of resistant pest populations and alter the

natural assemblages in the agroecosystem. Fungal endophytes are reported to play an important role in protecting plants against herbivorous insects and plant pathogens. The entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) Vuillemin (Ascomycota: Hypocreales) has a high degree of potential to establish itself as an endophyte to protect various crops. A study was conducted to determine the effect of various inoculation methods on the colonization of cabbage by an entomopathogenic *B. bassiana* isolate: BbCm KKL 1100. Colonization of leaves, stems, and roots by *B. bassiana* was achieved 24 days after application of aqueous fungus suspension containing 1×10^8 conidia ml⁻¹, regardless of the inoculation method via leaf, seed, or soil application. However, the plant growth medium with sterile soil, non-sterile soil, or vermiculite substrates influenced the colonization rates of *B. bassiana*. Seed inoculation with conidia caused no stem or leaf colonization by the fungus in non-sterile soil but did result in substantial endophytic colonization in vermiculite and sterile soil. Leaf inoculation did not result in root colonization, regardless of plant growth medium. Endophytic colonization was greater in leaves, followed by stems than in roots. Endophytic colonization by *B. bassiana* had no adverse effects on the growth of cabbage plants. Leaf inoculation with a conidial suspension (1×10^8 conidia ml⁻¹) proved the best method to introduce *B. bassiana* into cabbage leaves for plants growing in either sterile or non-sterile soil. This study implies the interaction between endophytic *B. bassiana* and Brassicaceae plants, discussing the mechanisms involved in the success of the symbiosis, together with the benefits obtained by these plants. Due to their unique characteristics, the family Brassicaceae can be seen as a fruitful source of novel beneficial endophytes with applications to crops, as well as to generate new models of study better to understand the interactions of amazing endophytic fungi with plants. Future research may focus on strain selection with virulent endophytic *B. bassiana* with other fungi, developing novel bio-formulation based on promising endophytes, and identifying field delivery methods suited for the Brassicas production system.

Keywords

Endophytic fungus, *Beauveria bassiana*, biological control, Brassicas pest management.

INTRODUCTION

Crops from the family Brassicaceae, previously named Crucifers, are important winter vegetable crops consisting of cabbage, cauliflower, mustard, broccoli, and radish. *Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L. (cabbage) is the main temperate crop cultivated widely in different climatic

regions worldwide (USDA 2019; Raza et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2022). Globally, India occupies the second position in the production of cabbage after China, with a production of 8.8 MT with an average productivity of 22t ha⁻¹ (FAOSAT 2022). Of the total area of vegetables grown in India, 5% is occupied by cabbage. The crop has been cultivated in large areas throughout the years and constitutes an important component in the diets of various cultures (Shelton et al., 2009). Tamil Nadu is one of the main producers and consumers of cabbage in Indian states. The intensive cultivation of cabbage in the open field or in protection greenhouses under the changing climate has led to severe infestation of pests and diseases (Lamb 1989; Batta 2013). Many insect pests hamper cabbage cultivation from sowing to storage (Weinberger and Srinivasan 2009). Still, the most destructive pest is diamondback moth (DBM) *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), which can reduce the yield of cabbage by 80% if outbreaks of pests appear in the field (Lingappa et al. 2004; Weinberger and Srinivasan 2009; Batta 2013; Dhaliwal et al. 2015). Other major Lepidopteran pests on cabbage and cruciferous crops are cabbage cluster caterpillar, *Crociodolomia pavonana* (F.) (Pyralidae), Cabbage webworm, *Helulla undalis* (F.) (Crambidae), cabbage worm, *Pieris rapae*, cabbage butterfly, *Pieris brassicae* (L.), tobacco caterpillar, *Spodoptera litura* (F.), and cabbage looper, *Trichoplusia ni* (Hubner) (Noctuidae) (Zalucki et al. 2012; Heviefio et al. 2020). These pests are the major bottleneck for significant yield loss, ultimately lowering crop production and productivity.

Worldwide, the DBM control alone costs an estimated US\$4 to US\$5 billion annually in direct yield losses and management costs (Zalucki et al. 2012; Furlong et al. 2013; Li et al. 2016). Besides, the pest also significantly affects several economically important crucifer crops such as cauliflower, cabbage, mustard, radish, mustard greens, broccoli, Brussels sprout, Chinese kale and Chinese cabbage (Gujar 1999; Lingappa et al. 2004). Specifically, DBM prefers cauliflower and cabbage because their fleshy succulent leaves offer olfactory and gustatory stimuli (Singh et al. 2015; Bathina and Bonam 2020). In India, DBM caused significant yield losses varying from 31 to 100% (Gujar 1999). Depending on the crop and the extent of the infestation, *P. xylostella* causes significant economic yield losses of up to 92% in cabbage, 75% in broccoli, and 30% in cauliflower (Srinivasan et al. 2019; Farias et al. 2020) under outbreak situations. The loss in crop yield caused by DBM varies from 31 to 100% (Lingappa et al. 2004), affects the production and quality of the yield, and incurs a management cost of US\$ 4-5 billion a year and an annual crop loss of US\$ 16 million in India (Zalucki et al. 2012; Furlong et al. 2013), and even more difficult pests to control. Cultivation of cabbage around the year provides regular availability of host plants

that favor DBM to complete at least 16-20 generations annually (Talekar and Shelton 1993).

Chemical pesticides remain the primary control measure for managing *P. xylostella* (Ramya et al. 2016) and other defoliators under intensified farming systems. Farmers largely use insecticides to control insect pests because chemicals have an immediate knock-down effect and are easily available in the local market. The sole reliance on insecticides control of the pest has led to a selection pressure that favored rapid build-up of resistance in DBM to almost all major groups of insecticides (Wang and Wu 2012), and there is wide variation in the choice of insecticides and frequency of applications (Justin et al. 1990; Talekar and Shelton 1993; Mohan and Gujar 2003). Elsewhere, even up to 15-20 insecticide applications can sometimes be insufficient to reduce the losses caused by this pest (Farias et al., 2020). The frequent application of insecticides, high fecundity, genetic plasticity, and rapid generation time have led to the development of resistance in field populations of *P. xylostella* to almost all groups of insecticides currently in use (Sayyed et al. 2008; Wang and Wu 2012). The pest's resistance to pesticides, including *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*.) has been well established (Sarfranz and Keddie 2005). The development of DBM resistance to relatively selective compounds from the newer insecticide groups has also been reported (Ramya et al. 2016), which has led to ineffective control during outbreaks (Baker 2011). The redundant use of broad-spectrum chemical insecticides for its control has ended with multiple complications, including increased cost of production, accumulation of toxic residue in crop commodities, harmful effects on non-target organisms in the ecosystem, and environmental contamination (Batta 2013). Therefore, using insecticides is inefficient in managing insect pests in the long run, fueling wide-ranging research to develop alternative management tactics (Furlong et al. 2013; Li et al. 2016). Managing *P. xylostella* has been a significant challenge for decades (Baker, 2011; Heviefio et al., 2020). Biological control methods, specifically entomopathogenic fungi, are suggested as alternative control agents for solving the adverse effects of chemical insecticides. The usefulness of new approaches will depend on the availability of strategies that suit the needs of farmers and fit into their current crop protection strategies.

Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) as potential biocontrol agents

Much emphasis has been recently given to using entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) as potential biocontrol agents for effectively managing this pest (McKinnon et al. 2016; Saragih et al. 2019; Bathina and Bonam 2020). Most EPF can survive as facultative parasites with unique features of ease of isolation, mass production,

formulations, and easy handling during field application (Jaronski ST.2014; Litwin *et al.* 2020). Added to these advantages, the endophytic nature of many entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) has recently been explored and used extensively as a novel pest management strategy in many crops (Muhammad Shehzad *et al.* 2021). Endophytes are capable of inhabiting any parts of the plant in seeds, leaves, branches, stem, and roots with mutual benefit, causing no apparent harm to the hosting plants (Glenn *et al.* 1985; Azevedo *et al.* 2000; Suryanarayanan *et al.* 2003; Godonou *et al.* 2009; Jia *et al.* 2016). Among the fungal biocontrol agents, *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo-Crivelli) Vuillemin (Cordycipitaceae: Hypocreales) is ubiquitous in most cultivated crops and acts as the best plant-protecting agent against biotic and abiotic factors (Furlong *et al.* 2013; Li *et al.* 2016). In addition to protection from pests and adverse climatic conditions, endophytes have associated benefits with a host like the supply of nutrients, improving soil health, stimulating healthy growth of plants, and improving the quality of produce (Jia *et al.*, 2016; Jaber, 2018; Mantzoukas and Eliopoulos, 2020; Moisan *et al.*, 2021).

Pioneering research on endophytic entomopathogenic fungi (EPPF)

The symbiosis between plants and entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) has become an important area of study in crop protection, crop management, and ecology over many years (Azevedo *et al.*, 2000; Vega *et al.* 2008; Mantzoukas and Eliopoulos, 2020; Yogananda *et al.* 2023). The two classical entomopathogenic fungi, *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) Vuillemin and *Metarhizium anisopliae* Metchnikoff (Sorokin), are widely used as alternatives to chemical pesticides for the biocontrol of insect pests. The active ingredients of several commercial products derived from these two fungi are used worldwide as potential biocontrol agents for sustainable pest management (Ownley *et al.*, 2010). In the last decades, the capability of *B. bassiana* to endophytically colonize a wide range of host plants has been proven, as well as its capacity to induce plant resistance against insect pests and pathogens (Azevedo *et al.* 2000; Vega *et al.* 2008). Consequently, the term “endophytic entomopathogenic fungi (EPPF)” was introduced by Ownley *et al.* (2010). Endophytic strains of *B. bassiana* can inhabit any parts of the plant (seeds, leaves, branches, stem, and roots) and have the ability to protect crop plants against biotic and abiotic factors (Barelli *et al.* 2016; Vega 2018; Yan *et al.* 2019; Mantzoukas and Eliopoulos, 2020). In addition to protection from pests and adverse climatic conditions, it has associated benefits with hosts like the supply of nutrients, improving soil health, stimulating healthy plant growth, and improved quality of produce. (White and Torres 2010; Barelli *et al.* 2016; Yogananda *et al.* 2023). This interest has been triggered not only because

endophytic behavior is a newly discovered aspect of the lifestyle of arthropod pathogenic fungi but also because the fungal symbioses can positively impact crop health by providing long-term resistance against crop plants' invertebrate pests and fungal pathogens (Vega *et al.* 2008; Lugtenberg *et al.* 2016; Maciá-Vicente *et al.* 2020).

The pioneering research model system on endophytic entomopathogenic fungus (EPPF) was first introduced by Bing and Lewis (1991) with *Beauveria bassiana* for maize (*Zea mays* L.) ecosystem against the European corn borer, *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hubner) (Crambidae: Lepidoptera), a world-wide destructive pest. After that, numerous pieces of research have investigated the artificial establishment of *B. bassiana* as endophytes (Stone *et al.* 2000). In recent years, it has been demonstrated that the fungus *B. bassiana* can be used as an artificial endophyte in diverse groups of food crops, including cereals, millets, pulses, oilseeds, vegetables, fruits fiber, and medicinal crops (Vega *et al.* 2008; Vega 2018) using different inoculation methods, such as seed coating, soil watering, root dipping, and foliar spraying (Stone *et al.* 2000; Tefera and Vidal 2009). In this plant-microbe interaction, there is a reciprocal exchange of benefits: the fungus obtains nutrients, and the host plant receives growth stimulation, enhanced resistance to insect pests, and protection against pathogen attack (Vega 2018; Afandhi *et al.* 2019; Yan *et al.* 2019).

Endophytic entomopathogenic fungi (EPPF)

The entomopathogenic fungus (EPF) *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) Vuillemin is a member of Hypocrealean fungi (Ascomycota: Cordycipitaceae) traditionally known for its entomopathogenic potential against a wide range of insects-pests due to its epizootic and hemibiotrophic behavior (Goettel and Inglis 1997; Ambethgar 2001). However, in recent studies, the endophytic ability of *B. bassiana* to harbor plant tissues during their life cycle without causing any apparent symptoms (Stone *et al.* 2000) has widely drawn attention to the engagement of *B. bassiana* in plant-fungus interaction. The entomopathogenic *B. bassiana*, being classified under class II Clavicipitaceous (C) endophytes, is capable of systemically colonizing both above-and below-ground host tissues and can vertically transmit by seed, seed coats, or rhizomes (Arnold, 2007; Jaber and Enkerli 2016). Such endophytic association exhibits a unique ability to confer habitat-specific stress tolerance by increasing biomass and plant hormones and play an important role in protecting plants against herbivorous insects (Rodriguez *et al.* 2009; Ownley *et al.* 2010) and plant pathogens (Ownley *et al.* 2010) by producing secondary metabolites and induction of systemic resistance (Rodriguez *et al.* 2009). Many isolates of *B. bassiana* have been reported as naturally

occurring endophytes or established post-artificial inoculation in various plants, including several agricultural and horticultural crops (Vega et al. 2008; Ownley et al. 2010). Bing and Lewis (1991) demonstrated that *B. bassiana* can invade maize plants via the epidermis, after that persisting in the plant throughout the entire growing season and reducing tunneling by *Ostrinia nubilalis* Hubner (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae).

In India, few Reports are available on the potential role of *B. bassiana* in establishing itself as an endophyte in any Brassicaceae crops (Zhang et al. 2014; Kuchár et al. 2019), an important vegetable crop. Futuristic use of *B. bassiana* as an artificial endophyte in Brassicaceae crops could reduce damage caused by insect pests (Sedaghatkish et al. 2021). For the endophytic *B. bassiana* to be used in practical crop production, reliable methods of inoculum delivery must be developed (Ownley et al., 2010). Preliminary observations showed that *B. bassiana* colonizes cabbage plants (Ambethgar et al. 2021), but the colonization rate may depend on how the plant is exposed to the fungus (Sun et al. 2023). Therefore, the present work evaluated the effects of inoculation methods and plant growth medium on endophytic colonization of cabbage by *B. bassiana* as part of a biological control system for cabbage and other cruciferous crops.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fungus strain

The fungal strain used in this experiment was *Beauveria bassiana* Accession Number- BbCm KKL 1100, which had been isolated from mycosed larval cadavers of the rice leaf-folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenee (Pyraustidae: Lepidoptera) found in nature in rice fields of Karaikal, Pondicherry Union Territory, India (Ambethgar, 2003) and the isolate was preserved at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India. In previous studies, this fungal strain was selected based on its virulence to the rice leaf-folder *C. medinalis*. Fungus cultures were maintained at 25±2 °C on Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA), containing 10g enzymatic digest casein, 40g dextrose, and 15g agar. Conidia were obtained from 3-week-old sporulating cultures. The conidia were harvested by scraping the surface of the culture with a sterile camel hairbrush into a 500-ml glass beaker containing 50 ml sterile distilled water plus Tween 80® (0.1% v/v; Difco™). The conidial suspension was prepared by mixing the solution with a magnetic stirrer for 5 min. The conidia concentration was then adjusted to the desired concentration of 1.0 x 10⁸ conidia ml⁻¹ with a Thoma Chamber using a light microscope (40 x magnifications) following the procedures described by Goettel and Inglis (1997). To assess the viability of the conidia, a germination test was

carried out on SDA after 24 h of incubation at 25°C. Germination exceeded 90%. The experiments used a suspension of 1.0x10⁸ conidia ml⁻¹. The conidia concentration, 1.0 x 10⁸ conidia ml⁻¹, was chosen based on the isolate's virulence to *C. medinalis* at this concentration (Ambethgar 2003).

Raising cabbage seedlings

The experiments used the popular cabbage cultivar Maharani, released by Pahuja Seed Company. Although it is widely grown in different agronomic regions, the cultivar is often damaged by the larvae of *Plutella xylostella*. Cabbage seeds in packaging size of 10g were procured from an agro-service seed dealer firm. The seeds were surface disinfected with 2% sodium hypochlorite for two minutes, followed by 70% ethyl alcohol for three minutes, and washed thrice with autoclaved ultrapure water. The disinfected seeds were shade-dried on sterile filter paper under a laminar airflow hood for 30 min and used for the study.

Experiment I: Effect of inoculation method on colonization of cabbage by *B. bassiana*

The surface-disinfected seeds were separated into two portions. The first portion was used for seed inoculation, while the second was for leaf and soil drench inoculations after seedling emergence. The leaf and soil inoculation seeds were planted in pots filled with approximately 2kg of sterile potting soil (autoclaved at 121°C for 15 min), non-sterile potting soil, or vermiculite. The plants were maintained in the greenhouse at 21-22°C, 60-80% RH, and with a 12-h photoperiod. Four seeds were planted per pot and were thinned to two seedlings after emergence.

Seed inoculation

For seed inoculation, 5g seeds were immersed into 10 ml *B. bassiana* conidial suspension containing 1.0x10⁸ conidia ml⁻¹ for 10 min (Akello and Sikora 2012; Jaber and Enkerli 2016). After the inoculated seeds were dried on sterile tissue paper for 30 minutes, four seeds per pot were thinned to two vigorous seedlings after emergence, as described above. However, the exact rate of conidia attached to the seeds was not determined. Control seeds were immersed in sterile distilled water.

Foliar spraying

For leaf inoculation, a plastic hand sprayer (500-ml capacity) was used to inoculate each seedling with a 10-

ml conidial suspension with 1.0×10^8 conidia ml^{-1} seven days after emergence. The spray was directed to the leaves but might have incidentally drifted to the stems. To avoid conidial runoff to the soil, the top of each pot was covered with aluminum foil (Posada et al. 2012; Greenfeld et al. 2016). The control plants were inoculated with sterile distilled water.

Soil inoculation

For soil inoculation, a 10-ml conidial suspension with 1.0×10^8 conidia ml^{-1} was applied around the root zone of each seedling (Greenfeld et al. 2016; Saragih et al. 2019). The control plants were inoculated with 10 ml of sterile distilled water. Seedlings in all treatments were watered as needed. The watering device was carefully directed to the pot's surface to avoid conidial runoff from the treated leaves to the stem and soil. Separate experiments were conducted using non-sterile soil, sterile soil, and vermiculite. Each experiment used a completely randomized block design (CRBD) with ten replicates per inoculation (treatment) method.

Experiment II: Effect of plant growth medium on colonization of cabbage by *B. bassiana*

An experiment was conducted to determine the effect of the three common plant growth media, vermiculite, sterile soil, or non-sterile soil, on cabbage colonization by *B. bassiana* following the seed inoculation method (Greenfeld et al. 2016). Untreated seeds were included as a control for each plant growth medium. The same treatment application procedure was followed for experimental management described above in Experiment I for the seed inoculation. A complete randomized block design (CRBD) with ten replicates was used.

Data collection and statistical analysis

Colonization

Colonization of cabbage seedlings by *B. bassiana* was determined 25 days after inoculation with *B. bassiana*. Seedlings were carefully removed from pots, and roots were gently washed with tap water. The seedlings were then separated into leaves, stems, and roots. These parts were surface-sterilized with 1% sodium hypochlorite for 3 min, rinsed twice in sterile distilled water, and placed on sterile tissue paper in a laminar flow cabinet. Five leaves, stem, and root pieces of approximately 2 mm^2 from each seedling were randomly taken and placed separately on *B. bassiana* selective medium (2% oatmeal infusion, 2% agar,

550 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ dodine, 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ crystal violet) (Chase et al. 1986). To evaluate the efficacy of the surface sterilization method, 20 ml of the water was used to rinse the tissues after surface sterilization was taken, and 20 μl aliquots of a 10-3 dilution were plated on the selective media and spread with a sterile glass rod, incubated for ten days at $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ to count for colony-forming units. However, the sterilization resulted in no growth of microorganisms; thus, any ensuing *B. bassiana* growth from surface-sterilized tissues is inferred to have originated from internal plant tissues as endophytes. The presence or absence of *B. bassiana* growth on the plant segments was recorded after ten days at $20\text{-}23^\circ\text{C}$. Sixty plants and 300 plant pieces were examined in Experiment I, while 30 plants and 90 were examined in Experiment II. The data were expressed as colonization frequencies: Colonization frequency = $100 \times (\text{number of plant pieces colonized} / \text{total number of plant pieces})$ (Azevedo et al. 2000). The colonization frequency data (expressed as percentages) were angular transformed to stabilize the variances. The transformed data were analyzed using analysis of variances (ANOVA) of the program SPSS Version 16. Significant differences between means were determined with the Student-Newman-Keuls test ($P=0.05$).

Plant growth

The effect of *B. bassiana* on plant growth (Experiment I) was determined by measuring shoot height, root length, and shoot and root fresh weight 24 days after inoculating the plants with the fungus. After uprooting the seedlings, roots were washed to remove soil, and plant height was measured from the soil surface to the tip of the stem. After the shoot fresh weight, root fresh weight, and root length were recorded; the fresh shoots and roots were placed in a paper bag and kept at 45°C for six days before dry weights were determined. The plant growth data were subjected to one-way ANOVA using the SPSS Version 16. Significant differences between means were determined with the Student-Newman-Keuls test ($P = 0.05$).

RE-ISOLATION AND PURIFICATION OF FUNGUS

Re-isolation of fungus

Re-isolation of *B. bassiana* after inoculation into plants undergoes several steps, similar to the primary isolation procedure (Azevedo et al., 2000). The common protocol for the isolation of endophytic fungi is illustrated in Figure 1, adopting the methods of Azevedo et al. (2000) and Sayed et al. (2020). To isolate endophytic fungus, 30 cabbage seedlings previously inoculated with fungus were

collected and washed under running tap water to remove surface impurities. After proper washing, cabbage seedlings were surface sterilized with 2% sodium hypochlorite for 2 min, treated with 70% alcohol for 3 min, and thoroughly washed thrice with sterile water. The last rinsed water was plated on a Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium and incubated to ensure surface sterilization and no fungus colonies were grown on the plate. After surface sterilization, each sampled seedling is cut into three segments, *viz.*, root, stem, and leaf, in varying sizes. Each root or stem was sectioned into small pieces (about 5 mm

long); each leaf was sectioned randomly to acquire 5 squares (around 20 mm × 20 mm). Sterilized plant tissues were blotted on sterile filter paper under a laminar flow hood for about 30 min to drain the residual water. The segmented tissues were transferred to the Petri plates containing the PDA medium. The Petri plates were incubated at 25±2°C in a BOD incubator for seven days. Fungal outgrowth was checked at 4, 7, 10, 15, and 30 days, and fungal colonization was assessed in each isolated plant tissue. Actively growing fungi were isolated and subcultured onto new PDA plates for purification.

Figure 1. Protocol for re-isolation of fungal endophytes in cabbage plant

Purification of endophytic fungi

The pure culture of the endophytic fungi was isolated by transferring the hyphal tip from a 7-day-grown colony to the PDA slants (Azevedo et al. 2000) and cultured at 25±2 °C in complete darkness in a BOD incubator for 7-10 days. Several sub-cultures are conducted to acquire pure fungal isolates before their identification. Some fungal isolates may require even a month or more in culture before sporulating. Some isolates even stop sporulating or lose their natural vigor after they have been

sub-cultured repeatedly several times, the phenomenon called ‘attenuation’ (Ambethgar, 2003).

RESULTS

The results showed that within each experiment (i.e., for each growth medium), plant height, fresh weight, and dry weight were not significantly affected by the inoculation method (Table 1). Inoculation of cabbage with *B. bassiana* did not reduce plant growth. Although statistical analysis could not be used to compare plant growth in different growth media, plant growth appeared to differ with growth

media. Plants grown in vermiculite were much shorter and weighed less than plants grown in sterile or non-sterile soil.

Table1. Effect of inoculation method and plant growth medium on height and weight of cabbage plants treated with *B. bassiana*

Inoculation method and growth medium	Shoot height (cm) (mean ± SD)	Root length (cm) (mean ± SD)	Fresh shoot weight (g) (mean ± SD)	Fresh root weight (g) (mean ± SD)
Vermiculite				
Seed	7.0 ± 0.6a	4.0 ± 0.4a	1.20 ± 0.01a	0.60 ± 0.02a
Leaf	7.4 ± 0.6a	4.2 ± 0.6a	1.30 ± 0.03a	0.70 ± 0.02a
Soil	6.5 ± 0.3a	3.9 ± 0.6a	1.40 ± 0.06a	0.60 ± 0.02a
Control	6.3 ± 0.3a	3.8 ± 0.6a	1.30 ± 0.06a	0.60 ± 0.03a
Sterile soil				
Seed	13.3 ± 0.3a	7.5 ± 0.3a	4.9 ± 0.1a	2.4 ± 0.2a
Leaf	14.9 ± 0.6a	8.2 ± 0.4a	5.3 ± 0.2a	2.6 ± 0.3a
Soil	13.6 ± 0.3a	7.9 ± 0.5a	5.0 ± 0.2a	2.3 ± 0.2a
Control	13.5 ± 0.3a	7.8 ± 0.4a	4.8 ± 0.2a	2.4 ± 0.2a
Non-sterile soil				
Seed	10.5 ± 0.6a	5.7 ± 1.3a	3.9 ± 0.2a	1.6 ± 0.06a
Leaf	11.2 ± 1.2a	6.3 ± 1.6a	4.2 ± 0.3a	1.8 ± 0.06a
Soil	10.4 ± 1.2a	5.4 ± 1.5a	3.9 ± 0.2a	1.5 ± 0.05a
Control	10.6 ± 1.1a	5.2 ± 1.5a	3.6 ± 0.3a	1.6 ± 0.06a

For each growth medium, means (±SE) followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at P<0.05

Experiment I: Effect of inoculation method on colonization by *B. bassiana* and the growth of cabbage

Cabbage growing in non-sterile soil

For cabbage seedlings growing in non-sterile soil, the inoculation method significantly affected the colonization of leaves (P=0.01) and stems (P=0.01) but not roots (P=0.36) by *B. bassiana*. Leaf and stem colonization were highest with leaf inoculation, lower with soil inoculation, and non-detectable with seed inoculation. Root colonization was much lower than leaf and stem colonization. Although the differences were insignificant, root colonization was highest with seed inoculation, lower with soil inoculation, and non-detectable with leaf

inoculation. No *B. bassiana* was recorded from the control plants growing in non-sterile, sterile, or vermiculite soil.

Cabbage growing in sterile soil

For cabbage growing in sterile soil, the inoculation method significantly affected the colonization of leaves (P=0.01), stems (P=0.01), and roots (P=0.36) by *B. bassiana*. Leaf inoculation resulted in the highest leaf colonization, while seed inoculation caused the highest stem and root colonization. Regardless of the plant part colonized, colonization by *B. bassiana* of cabbage growing in sterile soil was low with soil inoculation

Cabbage growing in vermiculite

For cabbage growing in vermiculite, the inoculation method significantly affected the colonization of roots ($P=0.01$) but not of leaves and stems by *B. bassiana*. Colonization was greater than 90% with all inoculation methods and plant parts, except that colonization was 0% with leaf inoculation of roots.

Experiment II: Effect of plant growth medium on colonization of cabbage by *B. bassiana*

Significant differences were observed concerning the growth medium affecting cabbage leaf colonization by *B. bassiana* (Table 2), respectively. Growing *B. bassiana*-treated seeds in non-sterile soil did not result in leaf and stem colonization, and root colonization by the fungus was limited. However, fungal colonization was observed in the leaf, stem, and root parts when cabbage seeds were grown in sterile soil and vermiculite. Seeds grown in vermiculite colonized more than seeds grown in sterile soil. No *B. bassiana* was recorded from the control plants.

Table 2. Effect of plant growth medium on cabbage leaf, stem, and root colonization by *B. bassiana*

Growth medium	Plant parts colonized (%) (Mean \pm SD)		
	Leaf	Stem	Root
Non-sterile soil	2 \pm 0.6a	2 \pm 0.6a	6 \pm 1.3a
Sterile soil	30 \pm 3.6b	37 \pm 4.3b	39 \pm 3.6b
Vermiculite	94 \pm 3.6c	98 \pm 2.4c	98 \pm 2.3c

Means (\pm SE) followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at $P<0.05$

DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrates that *B. bassiana* can be established as an endophyte in cabbage leaves, stems, and roots at varying extents by differential inoculation methods as shown by different researchers (Quesada-Moraga et al. 2006; Tefera and Vidal 2009; Posadas et al. 2012). However, the level of colonization was substantially affected by plant growth medium. Although the effect of growth medium on plant colonization by the fungus has not been previously considered, successful colonization of many plant species following inoculation with *B. bassiana* has been reported previously (Bing and Lewis 1991; Quesada-Moraga et al. 2006). However, endophytic colonization by *B. bassiana* depends on the inoculation method, fungal isolate, and plant species (Posadas et al. 2012; Bamisile et al. 2018). For example, the highest post-inoculation recovery of *B. bassiana* occurred after direct injection in coffee (Posadas et al. 2012), dipping plants in conidial suspension in banana tissue culture (Akello et al. 2007), foliar application in opium poppy (Quesada-Moraga et al. 2006) and maize (Bing and Lewis 1991), and seed coating in tomato (Ownley et al. 2008). In the present study, *B. bassiana* colonization differed among the plant parts. Leaves and

stems were colonized more than roots, as Poveda et al. (2020) reported. Colonizing the different plant parts indicates that the fungus moves within the plant system. The reason for the higher colonization of leaves and stems is unclear but could reflect differences in microbial and physiological conditions in the different plant parts. Liang-Dong et al. (2008) reported that endophytic fungi exhibited tissue specificity because they are adapted to particular conditions in a plant part.

Planting conidia-treated seeds in vermiculite and sterile soil, rather than in non-sterile soil, improved endophytic colonization of *B. bassiana*. Autoclaving the soil might have eliminated microorganisms that otherwise would have competed with or antagonized *B. bassiana* (Akello et al. 2007; Ownley et al. 2008). However, seed and soil inoculation methods did not significantly increase endophytic colonization by the fungus in non-sterile soils compared to the leaf inoculation method. The reason for the lack of endophytic colonization in seeds treated with *B. bassiana* in non-sterile soil is unclear and requires further investigation. However, abiotic and biotic soil factors were reported to affect the occurrence of the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria brongniartii* after application at different times of the year (Kessler et al.

2003). The low endophytic colonization of the fungus in non-sterile soil suggests that biotic factors may have a stronger influence on the fungus than abiotic factors. Fungistatic effects of soil (Lingg and Donaldson 1981) and soil antagonism (Pereira et al. 1993) have been reported for *B. bassiana*. In the non-sterile soil, biotic antagonism may have inhibited the germination of *B. bassiana* conidia or prevented the fungus from penetrating roots. For instance, the common soil fungus *Penicillium urticae* produces a water-soluble inhibitor of *B. bassiana* (Shields et al. 1981). Another common soil saprophyte, *Aspergillus clavatus*, also produces metabolites that are fungicidal to *B. bassiana* (Majchrowicz et al. 1990). Pereira et al. (1993) and Vanninen et al. (2000) reported that *B. bassiana* was not persistent in soils, and when conidia were added directly to the soil, the fungus infected only a small proportion of insects.

Plant growth was affected by the growth medium with sterile soil, non-sterile soil, and vermiculite but not by the inoculation method. Regardless of the inoculation method, plant growth in vermiculite was much less than in sterile and non-sterile soil. Lewis et al. (2001) reported no differences in growth between plants treated or not treated with *B. bassiana*. In the current study, seed treatment with *B. bassiana* did not reduce seed germination or seedling

growth or result in root disease development. Application of *B. bassiana* to leaves, seeds, or soil did not result in significant differences in plant height, fresh weight, or dry weight. Although differences in plant growth and dry weight were evident when plants were grown in vermiculite, sterile soil, and non-sterile soil, these differences did not affect the colonization of the plants by *B. bassiana* in the present study.

Functional role of EEPF in crop plants

Fungal endophytes play crucial roles in ecosystems by protecting plants against many biotic and abiotic stresses (Gurulingappa et al. 2011; Ambethgar et al. 2013; Hiruma et al. 2018; Heviefo et al. 2020; Wang and Zhang 2023), increasing their resilience (Gautam et al. 2016;), and helping plants to adapt to new habitats with multiple functional role (Fontana et al. 2021; García-Latorre et al. 2021) as illustrated in Figure 2. Biotic stresses from which EEPF can provide protection include insects, mites, nematodes, and plant pathogens (Aamir et al. 2020; Abdel-Fatah et al. 2021; Adeleke et al. 2022). Abiotic stresses include nutrient limitation, drought, salination, and extreme pH and temperature regimes (Rodriguez et al., 2009).

Figure 2. General functional groups of endophytic microorganisms in crop plants
(Adapted from Ambethgar et al. 2013)

In return, plants provide spatial structure, protection from desiccation, nutrients, and, in the case of vertical transmission, dissemination to the next generation of hosts. Endophytes may also play a role in the crop ecosystem by affecting plant growth through antagonistic fungal-fungal interactions (Glenn et al. 1985). A further role of some fungal endophytes in ecosystems may be to initiate the biological degradation of a dead or dying host plant, which starts the nutrient recycling process (Vega et al. 2008).

Molecular interactions of endophytes with Brassicaceae

Like all other plant species, Brassicaceae plants can establish various relationships with fungi, ranging from negative interactions with pathogens to positive associations with beneficial fungi (Poveda et al., 2022). The diversity of mutualistic plant-fungal interactions includes both mycorrhizal and endophytic fungi (Rodriguez et al., 2009; Genre et al., 2020). Mycorrhizae are the best-known plant-fungus mutualisms, especially those classified as arbuscular mycorrhiza (AMF) (Miyachi et al. 2020). Mycorrhizal fungi are characterized by the formation of specific structures in the host plant (vesicles or arbuscules), establishing fine-tuned relationships in which the plant receives phosphorus and other mineral nutrients in return for carbohydrates and lipids (Gutjahr and Parniske 2013; Genre et al. 2020). Mycorrhiza can also confer plant resistance to abiotic and biotic stresses (Rivero et al., 2018). Researchers demonstrated that Brassicaceae crops lacking myrosinase enzymes were root colonized by mycorrhizal fungi, pointing out the key role of these enzymes and their hydrolysis products in the evolutionary loss of mycorrhization by Brassicaceae plants (Vierheilig et al. 2000). It has also been shown that presence of Glucosinolates (GSLs) in Brassica plants protect *Arabidopsis* from the detrimental colonization by mycorrhiza forming fungi (Anthony et al. 2020). Since the loss of symbiotic genes and the presence of particular GSL pathways correlate with the lack of mycorrhization ability,

a relationship between the three features in Brassicaceae can be hypothesized. However, this possible link has yet to be proven (Hiruma et al., 2018). Thus, Brassicaceae plants can establish beneficial interactions with endophytic fungi, which require a reduction of defensive responses by the host plant and/or an evasion, tolerance, or suppression of plant defenses by the fungus (Poveda et al. 2022). The mechanisms involved in the Brassicaceae-endophyte fungal interactions remain to be known. Still, several cases have been described in which the endophytic fungi must interfere with the GSL synthesis and hydrolysis in the host plant or even directly degrade GSLs before they are hydrolyzed to antifungal isothiocyanates. Once the Brassicaceae-endophyte fungus symbiosis is formed, the host plant can obtain important benefits such as plant growth promotion and increase in yield and quality, increased tolerance to abiotic stresses, and direct and indirect control of plant pests and diseases (Poveda et al. 2022).

Even when endophytes are absent in any plant system, artificial inoculation techniques may circumvent this obstacle (Posada et al., 2007). Similarly, endophytic fungi that do not infect insects and cause disease may be used as effective biocontrol agents if they are artificially inoculated into plants and display infective characteristics against plant pests (Vega et al., 2008). Inoculation of fungi as an artificial endophyte inside plant systems could circumvent bottlenecks associated with its application as conventional microbial pesticides because (i) endophyte kills the damaging larval stages inside the plant (Posada et al. 2007), (ii) the plant is protected from adverse biotic and abiotic factors (Rodriguez et al. 2009), (iii) minimal inoculum requirements of endophytes reduces its cost (Sayed et al. 2020), and (iv) farmers need not re-inoculate year after year or for subsequent seasons if the applied endophytes are established in plant systems. The multitrophic interaction models of “*plants-microbes-pests*” can aptly be extrapolated in the *Brassica* plant system *vis-a-vis* what is currently known on the ecology, mode of action, and mechanism of plant endophytic colonization.

Figure 2. A model of tripartite interactions between endophyte, plant, and insect.

The fungal hyphae colonize both partners (circles depict plant and larval tissue colonized by endophyte mycelium), and it has different effects (Pappas et al. 2017; Anthony et al. 2020). The fungus obtains nitrogen (N) by digesting insect tissue and transferring it to the plant. Plant-derived carbon (C) is moved from the plant to the fungus.

Factors affecting the establishment and performance of endophytes

A complex of climatic factors influences the successful establishment of endophytes within the host. Many abiotic and biotic factors in open fields contribute to the establishment of endophytes in plant systems (Posada et al., 2007). Abiotic factors, including the type of soil substrate, other environmental factors such as temperature,

radiation, and humidity, to which the plants are exposed and their nutritional status, contribute to the establishment of endophytes (Posada et al. 2007). The biotic factors include host plants, crop variety, age of the crop, tissue type, and endophytic microbiota. Other biotic factors that influence endophytic establishment are related to the fungus strains, type of inocula (mycelia, conidia, resting spores), and native soil microorganisms such as bacteria and actinomyces (Pappas et al. 2017). The mode of application also affects establishment and determines

persistence as an endophyte (Quesada-Moraga *et al.*, 2006). Within cropping systems, the soil properties, plants, and potential insect hosts may also affect the abundance and diversity of endophytes persisting in the soil. In this direction, Pena-Pena *et al.* (2015) indicated certain key factors that play vital roles in the establishment of fungal endophytes in plant tissues, depending on the growth medium, the conidial density, the fungal species, and the method of inoculation.

Seasonal variation in the assemblage of fungal endophytes is demonstrated to be a vital factor for cruciferous crops (Sasan and Bidochka 2012). Maximal colonization rate and abundance were observed during autumn, while the lowest establishment was observed during winter. The abundance and species richness in spring were higher than that in summer. This may be due to the temperature in autumn being suitable for fungal growth, while the lower temperature in winter reduces growth or colonization (Rondot and Reineke 2018; Razinger *et al.* 2018). In addition, farmers plant a few cruciferous vegetables during summer, which might also explain the lowest diversity. Proximate factors, host plant identity, and plant tissue are also shown to be significant drivers of endophyte assemblage patterns. The selection of non-mycorrhizal cruciferous vegetables could avoid the confounding effect of mycorrhizae, and the selection of healthy plants could avoid the negative influence caused by the pathogen's infection (Lebreton *et al.* 2019). According to the researchers, endophyte colonization rate and species abundance in cruciferous plants varied with plant identity, with the highest colonization rate and abundance observed in white cabbage and the lowest in radish. Radish had the lowest fungal colonization rate (35%) and species abundance compared to white and Chinese cabbages (53.2% and 24.3, 42.6% and 18.8 respectively). In addition, the root system of different plant identities may act differently to allow fungal endophytes to colonize, ranging from harmful to beneficial plant-microbe interaction. For example, the radish's fleshy root system and its antimicrobial properties, like acetone, suppressed endophyte colonization rate and diversity (Lebreton *et al.* 2019). Larger scale factors, including pesticide use patterns, landscape structure, and elevation, did have minor effects on determining the community structure of fungal endophytes. The application methods also affect the establishment and determine persistence as an endophyte (Quesada-Moraga *et al.* 2006). Within any cropping system, the soil properties, host plants, and associated insects may affect the abundance and diversity of endophytes persisting in the soil. In this direction, Pena-Pena *et al.* (2015) have stated key factors that play a vital role in establishing fungal endophytes into plant tissues depending on the growth medium, the conidial density, fungal species, and the inoculation method. According to Sasan and Bidochka

(2012), crops colonized by endophytes tend to withstand stress tolerance more than those that lack such symbiosis.

CONCLUSION

The endophytic colonization of cabbage by *B. bassiana* suggests that this isolate is well adapted to establish as endophytic in plants. In prior research, *B. bassiana* can become established as an endophyte in cabbage without adversely affecting plant growth, and leaf inoculation with a conidial suspension proved the best method to introduce *B. bassiana* into cabbage leaves. This study provides the basis for further investigations, which should focus on the response of different cultivars to different strains of *B. bassiana* for long-term establishment in the inoculated plants and the virulence of the endophytic *B. bassiana* against the pest complex of target crops. Efficient field application technology should be developed to protect *B. bassiana* conidia against native soil antagonism to maximize endophytic colonization by the fungus in non-sterile soils. The existence of endophytes in crucifers' growing systems could contribute to plant growth promotion and protection from herbivores and plant pathogenic infection.

Prior studies indicated that selective stains of endophytic *B. bassiana* could be successfully established to improve plant health, enhance productivity, and suppress pests in Brassica crops (Arnold 2007; Jia *et al.* 2016; Wang and Zhang 2023). The existence of endophytes in the Brassicas growing system could contribute to plant growth promotion and protection from insect pests and crop diseases. However, ecological mechanisms underlying the variability with endophytic properties of *B. bassiana* and interactions with other associated organisms in introduced crop ecosystems should also be further investigated in open field conditions to be considered for the biological pest control program of the brassica production system.

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Production Breaks, Cropping Patterns, and Biological Control: Management of DBM is not Rocket Science.

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ABSTRACT

The diamondback moth (DBM) is the most destructive and costly pest of *Brassica* vegetable and oilseed crops worldwide. The pest status of DBM appears to have increased over time as the species has evolved to resist every class of insecticide used against it. Yet DBM has been successfully managed in many regions by classical biological control, most notably with the introduction of hymenopteran parasitoids. Here, we use a DYMEX meta-population model with four demes to investigate the interaction of cropping practices (seasonal production break, different intensities of harvest, and days to replanting) and threshold-based spray decisions, with and without biological control. Unsurprisingly, the response surface of DBM pest pressure and sprays is complex, but there are some clear conclusions. A production break greatly reduces pest pressure; additional biological control can greatly reduce the number of insecticide sprays.

Keywords

Population modeling, DYMEX, real IPM, demes

INTRODUCTION

Plutella xylostella (L.) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), the diamondback moth (DBM), is perhaps one of the most destructive and costly pests of *Brassica* vegetable and oilseed crops worldwide. With widespread, large-scale application of chemical insecticides to vegetable crops seen as the best way to manage the species, if anything, the pest status of DBM appears to have increased (Furlong et al. 2013) as the species has evolved resistance to every class of insecticide used (Feng et al. 2011, Li et al. 2016ab). The estimated total costs to the world economy of US\$4 billion-US\$5 billion (Zalucki et al. 2012) is outdated, and in 2022, inflation is likely closer to US\$ 5 billion-US\$6 billion! Yet DBM has been successfully managed in many regions by classical biological control, most prominently with the introduction of a hymenopteran larval-pupal parasitoid, *Diadegma semiclausum* (Hellén) (Furlong et al. 2013).

Parasitoids and predators can exert strong effects on DBM populations (Furlong et al. 2004ab, 2008; Gurr et al. 2018), and successful classical biological control of DBM can be achieved if broad-spectrum insecticide use is reduced (Furlong et al. 2013, Ketelaar et al. 2017). DBM is likely an induced or secondary pest (Furlong et al. 2013), at least in temperate areas and the cooler high-altitude regions of the tropics where *Brassica* vegetable crops are typically grown.

As is reported in this volume and at all previous DBM workshop proceedings (Talekar and Griggs 1985, Talekar 1992, Sivapragasam et al. 1997, Endersby and Ridland 2004, Shelton et al. 2008, Srinivasan et al. 2011, Srinivasan et al. 2017, Srinivasan et al. 2021) if natural enemies are not disrupted by broad-spectrum insecticides and allowed to exert population suppressive forces on the pest, then costs associated with the management DBM can be greatly diminished, if not eliminated. Modeling (Li et al. 2012, 2016c, 2018, Zalucki et al. 2017) and empirical studies (see conference proceedings) suggest that the success of biological control is a complex interaction between climate, cropping practices, and insecticide application. In general, control seems less effective in tropical areas, suggesting a climate effect (Furlong and Zalucki 2017), and insecticide use disrupts control greatly (Furlong et al. 2008).

Our work in China (Liu et al. 2004, 2014), DPRK (Furlong et al. 2008), the South Pacific (Furlong 2016), and Australia (Furlong et al. 2004ab) indicates that it is possible to greatly reduce management costs by moving away from weekly spraying of insecticides to the adoption of threshold-based sample, spray and pray IPM (Zalucki et al. 2009). If management decisions were indeed based on DBM populations that exceed the threshold and require control, then such rational farmer’s practice would greatly reduce the costs of DBM to the world economy (Zalucki et al. 2012). Here, we use a modeling approach to investigate the use of natural enemies in an area climatically very suitable to DBM in southeast China (Lincang and Tonghai in Yunnan Province) as we did for areas less climatically suitable due to hot-wet summers (Guangzhou) (Li et al. 2016c). We investigate the use and effectiveness of biological control, both naturally sourced by movement and through augmentative releases of a larval parasitoid. The work is more than theoretical as mass rearing and release of *D. semiclausum* is being used, and a strategy for implementing biological control in real farming landscapes is needed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Here, we use the DBM deme model presented by Li et al. (2016c, 2018) to investigate further the use of biological control to manage this species better. We create a meta-population of four demes, each with its own brassica crop planting regime for continuous year-round production or a seasonal (summer) production break. Both moths and parasitoids can move between demes depending on age and crop conditions (Li et al. 2016c, 2019). As in our previous studies, the proportion of the crop harvested varied (90% or 70%), as did how long the residue remained before being cleaned up and replanted: short (3 days) or long (13 days). These mimicked different farmer practices of good and poor crop hygiene. In all simulations, we used a threshold-based spray decision for farmer-managed demes (crops) based on the density of L2-4 larvae per plant. For most scenarios, we used a fixed threshold for all crop demes; if L2-4/plant exceeded 12, the crop was sprayed. We included a “mixed bag”

scenario where different demes had different thresholds (see Table 1), which captures the variability and assiduousness of management approaches amongst farmers. To reduce variability due to weather, we used average climatic conditions for Lincang over the period 2000-2012 (Tonghai has a similar climate). Each year had the same climatic conditions for 12 cropping seasons (years): daily maximum and minimum temperatures and rainfall. These simulations highlight the effect of management. We also ran all simulations with the actual climate data for this period. The full set of scenarios tested is set out in Table 1. As in Li et al. (2016c), simulations were initialized with a mixed age structure of eggs, larvae, and pupae and adult migration at the start of the season. We ignored the first year and ¾ of output to allow populations to initialize (or burn in) and then looked at the following 10 years, starting with the autumn planting period (from August 16). We output the number of L4 larvae in each deme each day, the number of spray events, and, if present, *Diadegma* as measures of how the different scenarios performed. We summarise these metrics as average L4 larvae/ deme/ year, average *Diadegma*/ deme/ year if present, and total sprays/ deme/ year. We averaged L4 larvae/deme/month for temporal comparisons with observed populations.

We simulated several management scenarios. A source-sink setup where one deme was “unmanaged” (deme 4), with no production break, can essentially be considered weedy brassica, available year-round. It acted as a source of DBM and, if present, *Diadegma*. DBM populations in the weedy patch were limited by density-dependent mortality of first instars whenever this stage exceeded 100/plant. A source-sink simulation presents the most difficult management scenario, as DBM can continuously invade the crops. We simulated a 4-crop system where migration of DBM (if present) occurred once each year in the Autumn to the first crop in each deme, with and without a production break, etc. (Table 1). *Diadegma*, too, arrived in the Autumn after DBM arrived. To capture the effects of augmentative biological control, we varied the amount of *Diadegma* arriving.

Table 1. Various population and management scenarios simulated with a 4-deme DYMEEX model for DBM.

Crop residue (d)	Percent Harvest	Production Break	Spray threshold	Natural Enemy	Source/Sink
Short (3d)	70	Yes/No	Fixed/variable	Yes/No	Yes/No
Short (3d)	90	Yes/No	Fixed/variable	Yes/No	Yes/No
Long (3d)	70	Yes/No	Fixed/variable	Yes/No	Yes/No
Long (3d)	90	Yes/No	Fixed/variable	Yes/No	Yes/No

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cropping pattern

With average climate data, the pattern of plants available remained fixed each year (Fig. 1). With a production break in summer, plants available for DBM declined to 1 crop as opposed to the more even availability of host resources without a production break (Fig. 1). Not surprisingly the pattern of planting had a significant effect on DBM populations and management (below).

Figure 1. Indicative cropping pattern (total number of plants across 4 demes) over a year with average climate data with (dashed line) and without (solid line) a production break. Only 13-day replant with 90% crop harvested shown.

Threshold-based management with a continuous source of DBM

Not surprisingly, having a continuous source of DBM is the most difficult to manage (Fig. 2ab), but a production break and added biological control make a difference. The difference between crop hygiene and harvest regimes was negligible with a continuous source. Without biological control and no production break, 18.1-18.6 sprays/deme/year were needed, and a production break only reduced this to 16.2-17.2 (Fig. 2b). Adding *Diadegma* effectively reduced the sprays required by 42-59% (Fig. 2b), as the “DBM source” also maintained a source population of parasitoids.

Figure 2a. Mean IV instar DBM larvae per deme per year (+/- SD) with a source population of DBM without (WO) and with (W) a production break (PB) for four planting regimes: short (3d) or long (13 d) time to residue clean up and two levels of harvest (70%, 90%). Solid blue bars are simulations without added biological control, and orange bars are with added *Diadegma*.

Figure 2b. The number of sprays/deme/year plotted against the Mean L4 larvae/deme/year as shown in 2(a) above. Solid symbols are simulations with biological control (orange with and grey without a PB), and open symbols are without added *Diadegma* (red with and black without a PB).

Threshold-based management with no continuous source

Without a continuous source of DBM migration into crops throughout the year, a production break greatly reduced DBM pest pressure, as assessed by average IV instar larvae/deme/year (Fig. 3a). Reductions in DBM L4's without added *Diadegma* ranged from a low of 12%-24% (for poor crop hygiene regimes) to 65-72% for good crop hygiene (3d residues) with a production break. With *Diadegma* added, the respective reductions due to the production break were 34-44% and 65-66% (Fig. 3a). Sprays required to manage the DBM scale with this pest pressure (Fig. 3b). In the worst management case, no production break, poor crop hygiene, and no biological control; 10-11 sprays were needed per crop per year. In the best-case scenario, good crop hygiene, production

break, and biological control, only 0.6 sprays/deme/ year were required.

Figure 3a. Mean IV instar DBM larvae per deme per year (+/- SD) without (WO) and with (W) a production break (PB) for four planting regimes: short (3d) or long (13 d) time to residue clean up and two levels of harvest (70%, 90%). Solid blue bars are simulations without added biological control, and orange bars are with added Diadegma.

Figure 3b. The number of sprays/deme/year plotted against the Mean L4 larvae/deme/year as in 3(a) above. Solid symbols are simulations with biological control (orange with grey without a PB), and open symbols are without added Diadegma (red with and black without a PB).

Adding extra Diadegma during the season

In the simulations described above, Diadegma was only added at the start of the season. To capture augmentative biological control, we ran simulations with two levels of Diadegma (10 or 30 adults) added to each crop three times at the start of the season. In general, DBM pest pressure was the least in these simulations (Fig. 4a), as were the sprays needed: maximum 5 sprays/deme/year with most under 2 (Fig. 4b). Some counter-intuitive results reflected the dynamic nature of host-parasitoid interactions. For example, with a production break and poor crop hygiene, DBM was “higher” with the 30 *Diadegma* added. This reflects a faster rebound by DBM, and well-timed sprays were required, which is a straightforward model.

Figure 4a. Mean IV instar DBM larvae per deme per year (+/- SD) without (WO) and with (W) a production break (PB) for four planting regimes: short (3d) or long (13 d) time to residue clean up and two levels of harvest (70%, 90%). Solid blue bars are simulations with 10 added Diadegma, and orange bars are with 30 added Diadegma during each cropping season. Grey bars as in Fig 3a with biological control (orange bars in that figure).

Figure 4b. Number of sprays/deme/year plotted against the Mean L4 larvae/deme/year as in 4(a) above. Solid symbols are simulations with production break (orange with 10 and grey with 30 added Diadegma), and open symbols are without a production (red with 10 and black with 30 Diadegma).

Variable threshold management

In real field cropping situations, it is unlikely management ever responds to populations exceeding the threshold as precisely as is possible in a model. We investigated some of this effect by varying the intervention threshold using 12, 10, 11, and 15 L2-4/plant for demes 1 to 4, respectively. Although there are similarities to the findings with a fixed threshold, there are some notable differences (Fig. 5). The variability in numbers of L4 per deme was much higher (Fig. 5a), and numbers with biological control “worked” better: lower abundance even with poor crop hygiene.

Figure 5a. Mean IV instar DBM larvae per deme per year (+/- SD) with a variable management threshold for each deme without (WO) and with (W) a production break (PB) for four planting regimes: short (3d) or long (13 d) time to residue clean up and two levels of harvest (70%, 90%). Solid blue bars are simulations without added biological control, and orange bars have *Diadegma* present.

Figure 5b. The number of sprays/deme/year plotted against the Mean L4 larvae/deme/year as in 2(a) above. Solid symbols are simulations with biological control (orange with and grey without a PB), and open symbols are without added *Diadegma* (red with and black without a PB).

CONCLUSION

Our simulations (above) and experience suggest production breaks and crop hygiene (Zalucki et al. 2009, Feng et al. 2011) and biological control by parasitoids (Furlong et al. 2013) can make a substantial difference to the number of sprays required to manage DBM effectively. Spray decisions must be based on field sampling and thresholds, which are not always easy to implement with farmers (Liu et al. 2004). Our simulations suggest that augmentative biological control (adding extra *Diadegma* during the season) can greatly reduce pest pressure and the number of sprays. This suggests such a strategy may be worth pursuing but will need a cost-benefit analysis and decisions on what costs to include; environmental and health costs are rarely considered in such analyses.

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Lethality of Eco-Friendly Farm-Prepared Natural Formulations against Eggs and Larvae of *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus)

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ABSTRACT

Four natural plant protection formulations (*Agniastra*, *Brahmastra*, *Darekastra*, and *Dashparni*) were prepared from locally available herbs like neem (*Azadirachta indica*), darek (*Melia azedarach*), wild marigold (*Tagetes sp.*), custard apple, castor, papaya, guava, wild datura (*Datura sp.*), *Ipomea*, *Polygonum*, *Eupatorium*, etc., along with green chilies, garlic cloves, ginger rhizomes, asafoetida, dung and urine of indigenous breeds of cow. Under laboratory conditions, these formulations were evaluated at different concentrations for lethal activity against eggs and larvae of the diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus). The eggs and larvae (2nd, 3rd, and 4th instars) were exposed to five concentrations (5, 10, 20, 40, and 80%) of these natural formulations. Simultaneously, exposure of test stages to water served as a check. The results revealed that these formulations were moderately lethal to eggs and larvae of *P. xylostella*. The egg hatchability was reduced by 24.0 – 50.0, 16.0 – 57.7, 15.0 – 53.9, and 16.0 – 42.3% over check after exposure to *Agniastra*, *Brahmastra*, *Darekastra*, and *Dashparni* at different concentrations, respectively. Similarly, the mortalities of 2nd, 3rd, and 4th instars varied from 6.7 – 44.4, 8.9 – 44.4, 7.8 – 38.9% in *Agniastra*, and from 7.8 – 51.1, 7.8 – 40.0, 7.8 – 41.1% in *Brahmastra* treatment. Likewise, *Darekastra* and *Dashparni* caused 11.1 – 51.1, 12.2 – 46.7, 14.4 – 47.8 and 3.3 – 43.3, 6.7 – 37.8, 5.6 – 36.7% mortalities of 2nd, 3rd and 4th instars, respectively. On the other hand, mortalities of 2nd, 3rd and 4th instars in check varied between 0.0 – 4.4, 1.1 – 4.4, and 1.1 – 3.3% at all concentrations, respectively. More mortality occurred at higher concentrations and after longer exposure periods.

Keywords

Agniastra, *Brahmastra*, *Darekastra*, *Dashparni*, DBM mortality

INTRODUCTION

Diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus), is a regular pest of crucifers in Himachal Pradesh, India. Losses due to this pest occur in varied agroecological regions ranging from Sub-Tropical, Sub-Mountain & Low Hills to Dry Temperate High Hills of the state (Sharma 2014; Sharma et al. 2020). Presently, its management is primarily attempted through insecticide applications only. Generally, green-labeled insecticides, presumably safer for the environment and human beings from a health perspective, are recommended against this pest. However, commercial vegetable growers often resort to indiscriminate and non-judicious use of insecticides to prevent crop losses and make a profit. This gross misuse of insecticides has disrupted the agroecological balance by decimating beneficial fauna and developing insecticide resistance. As a result, outbreaks of *P. xylostella* are not uncommon. Besides this, pesticide residues on vegetables and fruits and pollution of precious natural resources are also linked to acute health complications in humans. Therefore, policymakers are promoting the concept of “Natural Farming” across many states of India, including Himachal Pradesh. This concept is akin to the traditional Indian system of farming, which was in vogue decades ago when local varieties were grown with no external inputs, such as modern chemical fertilizers and agrochemicals. However, this eco-friendly way of farming was junked in favor of chemical farming for enhanced production to ensure food security. In the modern concept of natural farming, farmers also have to arrange all inputs from the resources available on the farm to make farming self-sustainable. Plant protection formulations to protect crops from biotic stress are also prepared from local herbs using the dung and urine of indigenous cows as essential ingredients. Some formulations, known as *Agniastra*, *Brahmastra*, *Darekastra*, and *Dashparni*, have been asserted to be effective against pests affecting crops. Though these environmentally compatible formulations have been reported to possess repellent and deterrent effects against adults of *P. xylostella* (Kavita et al. 2022), the present laboratory studies evaluated their lethality against eggs and larvae of this pest.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mass rearing of *P. xylostella*

The mass rearing of *P. xylostella* was done under controlled conditions [Temperature: $24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, RH: 75% and Photoperiod (L:D) 16:8]. Laboratory culture was initiated from larvae, pupae, and adults collected from cauliflower fields. These field-collected larvae were released onto the potted cauliflower plants kept in oviposition cages ($45 \times 45 \times 55\text{cm}^3$) until adulthood. In contrast, pupae and adults were kept in separate rearing cages ($45 \times 45 \times 55\text{cm}^3$) provisioned with mustard seedlings for oviposition. These seedlings were grown in a soilless medium (Sood et al. 1996). Cotton swabs soaked in sugar solution (10%) served as food to the caged adults. The eggs oviposited by these adults were used to mass rear *P. xylostella*. The adults emerging from this mass culture were subsequently used for experimentation in the laboratory.

Preparation of natural formulations

Agniastra

Ingredients: Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaves (5kg), tobacco powder (0.5kg), red chili (0.5kg), garlic cloves (0.5kg), cow urine of Indian breeds (20L).

Procedure for preparation: Crush neem leaves, grind red chili, and make garlic paste. Mix all these ingredients with tobacco powder in cow urine and boil on low flame in an iron pot until 1/4th of the solution is left. Keep this solution undisturbed for two days. Then, strain and store it in plastic bottles with perforated lids in a cool and airy place.

Brahmastra

Ingredients: Leaves of neem/darek (*Melia azedarach*) (10kg), custard apple/castor (2kg), papaya (2kg), guava (2kg), and wild datura (*Datura* sp.) (2kg), cow urine of Indian breeds (10L).

Procedure for preparation: All the leaves were ground and mixed thoroughly in cow urine. The mixture was boiled on low flame until half of the solution was left. It was left undisturbed for two days and then sieved. The prepared *Brahmastra* can be stored in the shade for up to six months.

Darekastra

Ingredients: *Melia* leaves (5kg), cow dung (2kg), cow urine of Indian breeds (5L), water (100L).

Procedure for preparation: *Melia* leaves were crushed and mixed with other ingredients in a plastic drum. The material was stirred clockwise twice daily (morning and

evening) for two days. Afterwards, the mixture was sieved and stored.

Dashparni

Ingredients: Leaves of neem (5kg), guava (2kg), papaya (2kg), castor (2kg), *Lantana* (2kg), *Ipomea* (2kg), *Polygonum* (2kg), wild marigold (2kg), *Eupatorium* (2kg) and darek (2kg); green chili fruits (0.5kg), garlic cloves (0.5kg), ginger rhizomes (0.5kg), asafoetida (10g), cow urine of Indian breeds (10L), and water (100L).

Procedure for preparation: Red chilies and ginger rhizomes were ground. A paste of garlic cloves was made. Different leaves were crushed and mixed with other ingredients in a plastic drum. The solution was stirred clockwise twice a day for seven days. Afterward, it was left undisturbed for the next 33 days. Subsequently, it was sieved and stored in plastic cans with perforated lids.

Bioassay for determining the lethality of natural formulations

The lethal activity of each natural formulation was assessed at five concentrations, i.e., 5, 10, 20, 40, and 80%. Eggs and larvae (2nd, 3rd, and 4th instars) of *P. xylostella* were exposed to selected concentrations. The experiment was replicated thrice, and an untreated check was maintained simultaneously.

Lethality to eggs of P. xylostella

Less than one-day old eggs laid on potted cauliflower plants were exposed to test formulations by dipping leaves carrying eggs in prepared solutions for 30s. While in untreated check, the leaves containing eggs were dipped in water only. These dipped leaves were then placed singly in Petri plates (5cm diameter) with a 2% agar agar layer. Observations on egg hatching were recorded for up to seven days. Replication-wise percent hatchability was worked out as follows:

Hatchability (%) = (No. of eggs hatched/ No. of eggs kept for hatching) x 100

Subsequently, the reduction in egg hatchability over untreated check was calculated as follows:

Reduction (%) = [% Hatchability (Check – Treatment)/ % Hatchability in check] x 100

Lethality to larvae of P. xylostella

Cauliflower leaf discs (5cm diameter) were dipped in desired concentrations of prepared natural formulations.

The dipped discs were allowed to shade dry for half an hour. Then, these leaves were placed singly in Petri plates, which had a layer of 2% agar-agar. After that, ten *P. xylostella* larvae of the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th instars were gently picked up with a camel hair brush and released separately on treated leaves. Observations on the mortality of larvae were recorded every 24h up to three days after release. The replication-wise overall percent mortality was worked out as follows:

Larval mortality (%) = (No. of dead larvae/ No. of larvae released) x 100

Statistical Analysis

Data on the percent reduction in egg hatchability and the percent larval mortality were statistically analyzed after arc sine transformations using OP Stat and WASP software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lethality of natural formulations to eggs of *P. xylostella*

The hatchability of eggs treated with *Agniastra*, *Brahmastra*, *Darekastra*, and *Dashparni* was reduced by 24.0 – 50.0, 16.0 – 57.7, 15.0 – 53.9 and 16.0 – 42.3%, respectively over an untreated check at tested concentrations of these natural formulations (Table 1). Results also revealed that all the natural formulations were statistically at par with each other in reducing egg hatchability. However, higher concentrations of natural formulations caused more reductions in egg hatchability. Kumar et al. (2009) reported that 24.4 and 59.9% of eggs of *P. xylostella* hatched, which were exposed to alcoholic and aqueous leaf extracts of *M. azedarach*, respectively, as compared to 90.0 and 88.3% in control. In current studies, *M. azedarach*-based *Darekastra* also caused a 15.0 – 53.9% reduction in egg hatchability. Likewise, Liang et al. (2003) reported that 61.6 – 75.2% of eggs of *P. xylostella* treated with commercial formulations containing *A. indica* as an active ingredient developed in neonates, respectively, compared to 81.2% in control.

Table 1: Ovicidal activity of natural formulations against eggs of *P. xylostella*

NF [^]	Reduction in hatchability of eggs over untreated check (%) ^{*,#}					
	5%	10%	20%	40%	80%	Mean
AA	24.0 (27.6)	24.1 (29.3)	35.7 (36.5)	48.2 (43.9)	50.0 (45.0)	36.4 (36.5)
BA	16.0 (22.5)	27.6 (31.4)	28.6 (31.7)	40.7 (39.6)	57.7 (49.4)	34.1 (34.9)

DA	15.0 (19.5)	20.7 (26.9)	25.0 (29.6)	48.2 (43.9)	53.9 (47.2)	31.1 (32.7)
DP	16.0 (22.3)	27.6 (31.4)	35.7 (36.5)	40.7 (39.6)	42.3 (40.5)	30.9 (32.7)
Mean	17.8 (23.0) ^c	25.0 (29.8) ^b	31.3 (33.6) ^b	44.4 (41.8) ^a	51.0 (45.5) ^a	--
CD (5%)	Formulation = NS; Concentrations = 6.0; Formulation x Concentration= NS					

[^]NF- Natural Formulation, AA- *Agniastra*, BA- *Brahmastra*, DA- *Darekastra*, DP- *Dashparni*; *Figures in the parentheses are arc sine transformed means; #Figures in the row followed by the same alphabet are statistically at par with each other

Similarly, Sharma and Verma (2013) found that 3% neem bark extract caused 37.3% mortality of *P. xylostella* eggs. Sangha et al. (2017) also stated that the essential oils from garlic demonstrated significant ovicidal activity against eggs of *P. xylostella*. In present laboratory studies, *Agniastra* prepared from neem leaves and applied at 5 – 80% concentrations caused 24 – 50% egg mortality. The local herbs, viz. *A. indica*, *M. azedarach*, and garlic, evaluated individually by these earlier authors, are important constituents of natural formulations tested in present studies. Therefore, the results regarding the ovicidal activity of natural formulations seem to corroborate those of earlier studies.

Lethality of natural formulations to larvae of *P. xylostella*

Second instar

The natural formulations *Agniastra* and *Dashparni* were comparable in causing overall 2nd instar larval mortality.

Table 2: Lethality of natural formulations to 2nd instar larvae of *P. xylostella*

Conc. (%)	Cumulative larval mortality (%) ^{*,#}			
	AA	BA	DA	DP
0	2.2 (4.1) ^a	3.3 (6.1) ^a	4.4 (8.2) ^a	0.0 (0.0) ^a
5	6.7 (11.1) ^b	7.8 (12.0) ^a	11.1 (18.2) ^b	3.3 (6.1) ^{ab}
10	15.6 (21.6) ^c	13.3 (19.8) ^b	16.7 (22.5) ^{bc}	6.7 (12.3) ^b
20	20.0 (26.2) ^c	21.1 (27.0) ^b	21.1 (26.8) ^c	15.6 (21.8) ^c
40	38.9 (38.5) ^d	35.6 (36.4) ^c	35.6 (36.3) ^d	25.6 (30.0) ^d
80	44.4	51.1	51.1	43.3

	(41.8) ^d	(45.5) ^d	(45.6) ^c	(41.1) ^c
CD (5%)	(5.1)	(7.0)	(6.5)	(6.4)

*Figures in the parentheses are arc sine transformed means; #Figures in the column followed by the same alphabet are statistically at par with each other; ^AA- *Agniastra*, BA- *Brahmastra*, DA- *Darekastra*, DP- *Dashparni*

These mortalities ranged from 6.7 – 44.4 and 3.3 – 43.3% at different concentrations of these natural formulations. Likewise, *Brahmastra* and *Darekastra* proved equally lethal to 2nd instar larvae of *P. xylostella* with 7.8 – 51.1 and 11.1 – 51.1% mortalities, respectively. Meanwhile, only 0.0 – 4.4% mortalities were observed in check (0% concentration) (Table 2).

Third instar

The mortalities of 3rd instar larvae caused by *Agniastra*, *Brahmastra*, *Darekastra*, and *Dashparni* at various concentrations varied from 8.9 – 44.4, 7.8 – 40.0, 12.2 – 46.7, and 6.7 – 37.8%, respectively. On the other hand, only 1.1 – 4.4% of 3rd instar larvae perished in check (0% concentration) (Table 3).

Table 3: Lethality of natural formulations to 3rd instar larvae of *P. xylostella*

Conc. (%)	Cumulative larval mortality (%) ^{*,#,^}			
	AA	BA	DA	DP
0	2.2 (4.1) ^a	1.1 (2.1) ^a	4.4 (8.2) ^a	2.2 (4.1) ^a
5	8.9 (15.2) ^b	7.8 (13.2) ^b	12.2 (17.9) ^b	6.7 (12.3) ^b
10	15.6 (23.0) ^c	16.7 (23.7) ^c	17.8 (24.6) ^c	17.8 (24.6) ^c
20	23.3 (28.6) ^d	21.1 (27.1) ^c	23.3 (28.5) ^c	26.7 (31.0) ^d
40	33.3 (35.0) ^e	34.4 (35.7) ^d	40.0 (39.0) ^d	28.9 (32.3) ^{de}
80	44.4 (41.8) ^f	40.0 (39.1) ^d	46.7 (43.0) ^d	37.8 (37.7) ^c
CD (5%)	(5.0)	(5.3)	(5.1)	(5.5)

*Figures in the parentheses are arc sine transformed means; #Figures in the column followed by the same alphabet are statistically at par with each other; ^AA- *Agniastra*, BA- *Brahmastra*, DA- *Darekastra*, DP- *Dashparni*

Fourth instar

Lethality of tested natural formulations to 4th instar larvae of *P. xylostella* followed a similar trend.

Table 4: Lethality of natural formulations to 4th instar larvae of *P. xylostella*

Conc. (%)	Cumulative larval mortality (%) ^{*,#,^}			
	AA	BA	DA	DP
0	1.1 (2.1) ^a	1.1 (2.1) ^a	3.3 (6.1) ^a	1.1 (2.1) ^a
5	7.8 (13.2) ^b	7.8 (13.2) ^b	14.4 (22.0) ^b	5.6 (9.1) ^b
10	11.1 (18.2) ^b	14.4 (22.0) ^c	17.8 (24.6) ^{bc}	11.1 (18.2) ^c
20	16.7 (23.9) ^c	24.4 (29.3) ^d	23.3 (28.4) ^c	13.3 (21.1) ^c
40	31.1 (33.6) ^d	35.6 (36.42) ^c	31.1 (33.8) ^d	28.9 (32.4) ^d
80	38.9 (38.4) ^d	41.1 (39.7) ^c	47.8 (43.7) ^c	36.7 (37.1) ^d
CD (5%)	(5.6)	(5.0)	(5.2)	(6.2)

*Figures in the parentheses are arc sine transformed means; #Figures in the column followed by the same alphabet are statistically at par with each other; ^AA- *Agniastra*, BA- *Brahmastra*, DA- *Darekastra*, DP- *Dashparni*

At different concentrations, the larval mortalities varied from 7.8 – 38.9% (*Agniastra*) to 7.8 – 41.1% (*Brahmastra*), 14.4 – 47.8% (*Darekastra*), and 5.6 – 36.7% (*Dashparni*). Meanwhile, in check (0% concentration), the mortality of 4th instar larvae was only recorded to be 1.1 – 3.3% (Table 4).

The preceding results indicated that all four tested natural formulations exhibited lethal action against larvae of *P. xylostella*. However, larval mortalities were comparatively higher at higher concentrations than the lower ones. The possible causes of larval mortality caused by natural formulations could be the direct lethal action coupled with starvation following cessation of feeding, as observed by Liang et al. (2003). These authors observed that the larvae of *P. xylostella* stopped feeding and dropped off leaves sprayed with *A. indica*-based insecticides. Though these formulations have not been evaluated earlier against *P. xylostella*, some of the ingredients used in their preparations have been tested individually. For example, Ahmad et al. (2019) observed 33.33, 58.33, 70 and 30, 50, and 61.67% mortalities of 3rd and 4th instar larvae of *P. xylostella* at 1, 2, and 3% of neem leaf crude extract, respectively. Mari (2012) reported that extracts of aak (*Calotropis* sp.), datura, and tobacco leaves caused 11.33, 10.0 and 13.33% mortalities of 3rd instar larvae of *P. xylostella* at 24h after treatment, which increased to 14.0, 12.67, 16.67 and 20.66, 16.66, 25.33% at 48 and 72h after treatment, respectively. Similarly, Sangavi and Edward (2017) recorded 53.33 and 46.67% mortality of larva and pupa of *P. xylostella*, respectively, by aqueous leaf extract (10%) of *A. indica*. Likewise, Karimzadeh and Rabiei (2020) demonstrated lethal

activity of datura extracts against *P. xylostella* larvae with LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ of 82.3 and 1,475.4 mg L⁻¹ (flowers), 146.8 and 4,828.7 mg L⁻¹ (seeds) and 165.3 and 3,493.8 mg L⁻¹ (roots), 526.6 and 29,352.1 mg L⁻¹ (leaves) and 841.4 and 136,248.1 mg L⁻¹ (stems), respectively. Thanavendan and Kennedy (2015) evaluated six concentrations (1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10%) of *Lantana camara*, a local perennial weed of pastures and landscapes in Himachal Pradesh, against *P. xylostella* and obtained enhanced mortalities at proportionally higher concentrations. The potentiality of the extracts prepared from local herbs to cause mortalities of *P. xylostella* larvae is quite evident from these earlier investigations. However, variations in the extent of mortalities might be attributed to inherent differences in the active ingredients of plants growing in varied geographical regions (Singh et al. 2006). Nonetheless, these local herbs can make botanical blends to protect crops against insect pest infestations, including *P. xylostella*. Moreover, the apparent lesser lethality of these natural formulations at lower concentrations could be compensated by the expected higher activity of natural enemies under field conditions, as reported by Iamba and Yoba (2019).

CONCLUSION

The four formulations viz. *As evaluated in the present studies, Agniastra, Brahmastra, Darekastra, and Dashparni* exhibited moderate lethal activity against eggs and larvae of *P. xylostella*. These formulations prepared from local natural herbs, cow urine, and dung are non-toxic. Thus, these formulations are completely in sync with organic practices meant for conserving and enhancing activities of naturally occurring beneficial biota in the soil and of natural enemies thriving above ground. These natural formulations offer additional options to manage pest organically. Hence, these formulations can be integrated with Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies. Being locally produced by the farmers, their usage can substantially reduce the cost of cultivation.

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Effects of Agroecological Approaches on Kale Pests, Produce Quantity and Quality in the Highlands of Kenya

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ABSTRACT

The diamondback moth is the most important insect pest of collards in Kenya. The pest has been known to cause total yield losses during dry spells. On the other hand, kale is the most important leafy vegetable in Kenya. The crop is mainly produced in the highlands, where rampant use of inorganic chemicals to control pests has been recorded. To reduce the negative impacts of the excessive usage of synthetic chemicals on human, environmental, and soil health, selected agroecological approaches were piloted on collards in Murang'a County, Kenya. Participatory farmer approaches were employed, where selected agroecological practices were compared with conventional/farmer practices (key among them being the use of synthetic pesticides). These were done on side-by-side plots measuring 6x12m each, denoted as plot 1 (farmer practices) and plot 2 (agroecological practices). The trials were carried out over two seasons (dry and rainy). During the rainy season, a multilocation assessment was done, and trials were replicated in lower and higher production zones in the highlands. A generalized pest identification scale (for DBM and other leaf caterpillars, cutworms, aphids, whiteflies, and thrips) was developed and used to collect comparative data on pests' infestation (prevalence and incidence) fortnightly for twelve weeks for each of the two plots. The effect of pests on the quantity and quality of harvests was also evaluated by sorting usable and non-usable portions of the harvests. Results for the dry season showed that agroecological practices were effective against pests at $p < 0.0001$. The usable portion of harvests for the agroecological plot was higher than that of the farmer practice plot. Still, there was no significant difference in the unusable portion of the harvests due to pest damage between the plots. During the rainy season, the higher

zone agroecological plot had lower pest infestation than the farmer's practice plot $p = 0.0395$. Still, due to pest damage, there were no significant differences in the usable ($p = 0.1218$) and unusable portions ($p = 1.000$) of harvests. In the lower zone, the plots had no significant differences in pest incidence ($p = 0.1902$) and quantity of unusable harvests ($p = 0.165$). However, the usable portion of harvest was higher in the agroecological plot than in the farmer practices plot at $p < 0.0001$. Further trials are being done to identify whether there are any clear patterns in pest infestations due to the production approach, seasonality, and production zone on collards.

Keywords

Kale/Collards, Participatory trials, Pest management, Production approach, Conventional, Agroecology

INTRODUCTION

Kale/Collard Greens, also widely known as Sukuma Wiki in East Africa, was introduced by missionaries and white settlers in the early 20th century (Mackenzie, 2000). Over time, the vegetables gained popularity and became the most preferred in most households, thus achieving a traditional status in the region and replacing several native/indigenous vegetables on the dietary menu (Otieno, 2013). Kale's high nutritional content and its ease and versatility in cooking make it widely acceptable by consumers and is often recommended in health and nutritional food programs (Fujioka et al., 2016; Zang et al., 2011).

Kale is an excellent brassica crop that is grown all year round in Kenya. It is highly adapted to a wide range of soils, altitudes, temperatures, and rainfall regimes (Greenlife Crop Protection Africa, 2023), making it highly preferred by farming communities. It is estimated that 90 percent of smallholder farmers in rural and urban areas grow kale for the domestic market (SHEP PLUS, 2019; Mogeni, 2022). The crop is also extensively traded and highly affordable, making it a popular staple for low-income communities where the most sold foods are fruits and/or vegetables (Downs et al., 2022). Kale has often been ranked as the most important green leafy vegetable consumed by households in Kenya (MoALF, 2015) and plays a vital role in nutritional balance (Downs, 2022). An acre of kale can yield between 8000 – 24,000 kilograms of leaf during a growth period of 9 months and earn a gross income of KES 240,000-720,000 (Mogeni, 2020). In this regard, the vegetable has a huge potential to alleviate poverty and improve livelihoods.

Despite its benefits, kale growing faces several key threats, including pests and diseases. Key insect pests of brassicas in Kenya include DBM, aphids, flea beetles, caterpillars,

and cutworms. In contrast, major diseases include black rot, black leg (dry rot canker), ring spot, downy, and powdery mildew. Although kale is considered generally resistant to pests and diseases, pests considerably lower the quality and quantity of harvests. In some cases, like with DBM infestations, pests have been shown to cause up to a hundred percent yield loss if control measures are not implemented early and/or swiftly (ICIPE, 2019).

Farmers rely heavily on chemical insecticides to manage pests for kale and other brassicas due to their quick action, thereby preserving the quality and quantity of produce (Constantine, 2020). Nevertheless, the adverse effects of these pesticides on the environment, natural enemies, applicators, and consumers of agricultural produce cannot be overlooked (UNEP, 2021).

At the turn of this century, several governmental and non-governmental global entities started focusing on universal farming approaches that could address the existing pollution (FAO, 2020). Agroecology is one of the outcomes of these global probing exercises that have gained prominence. It is a farming approach that came about in the 1920s, and during its formative years, it only found success in the smallholder farming systems (Barrios et al., 2020). In the recent past, however, agroecology has seen a worldwide niche as an alternative pathway that seeks to “transform food and agricultural systems, addressing the root causes of problems in an integrated way and providing holistic and long-term solutions” (FAO, 2020;)

Studies observe that research is needed to functionally link plant traits with ecosystem service provision in agroecological design and management (Titonell et al., 2020). This study was intended to address such needs for successful agroecology adoption and expansion by developing and validating need-based agroecological approaches to kale production through farmer-participatory piloting and demonstration approaches. In essence, this aimed at contributing to the knowledge base that would guide key processes of reducing harmful agrochemical inputs and safeguard the health of the vegetable producers and consumers, soils, and the ecosystem.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area.

The study was done in 2 sub-counties within Murang'a County (Kangema in the higher production zone and Kiharu in the lower production zone). Nine Vegetable Business Networks (VBNs) were recruited into the program from where participants were drawn. About 20 members from the same VBN were identified - from a

locality within a sub-county where factors were largely similar - to host a trial over a 4-month kale season. Each farmer hosted a single trial consisting of a conventional and an agroecology plot. Standardization was critical to the success of the trials; thus, the farmers were closely trained and mentored to implement the trials. The World Vegetable Center researchers developed a research protocol to implement these trials. Trials progress was monitored closely by trained field staff, and data from thirteen trials that met all the criteria required were considered for data collection.

The research protocol was as follows: Kale seeds were obtained from a certified seed company and subjected to germination tests to ascertain their viability before sowing. Raised nursery beds were made, and well-aged animal manure was thoroughly mixed in. The seeds were mixed with sand at a ratio of 1:10 and divided into two equal portions. One portion was sown, Diammonium phosphate (DAP) fertilizer) was added into the nursery bed, and the conventional/farmer method was employed to raise the seedlings to maturity. The resultant seedlings were transplanted into Plot 1. For the second portion of seed/sand mixture, 15 grams of *Trichoderma harzianum* T-22 (Triamum-P) was added, and another 30 grams were used to make a 10-liter water solution, which was used for drenching immediately after sowing. The resultant seedlings were transplanted into Plot 2. All other conditions, such as watering and weeding, were synchronized for the 2 nursery beds.

A plot measuring 12x12 meters was established, and pre-planting operations were performed on the kale. The plot was then sectioned into two successive portions labeled Plot 1 (Conventional/Farmer approaches were employed) and Plot 2 (Agroecological approaches were used). Farmers transplanted seedlings from seedbed 1 into Plot 1 conventionally, where organic fertilizers (DAP was applied during transplanting and Calcium Ammonium Nitrate (CAN) used for top dressing) were used to supplement nutrition and synthetic pesticides to manage diseases and insect pests. The roots of seedlings for plot 2 were first dipped into a solution of Triamum-P (30 grams in 10 liters of water), transplanted into holes where 2kg of well-aged animal manure had been mixed in with top-soil, and a Triamum-P solution used for drenching afterward. Seedlings for both plots were planted at a spacing of 15m between rows and 30m in rows in rows in a zigzag orientation.

Boarder crops such as Napier grass and companion crops such as spring onions, coriander, and chilies were included in the agroecology pots. Blue and yellow sticky traps were also positioned 2 feet from the ground in plot 2, targeting aphids, whiteflies, and thrips. *Metarizhium anisopliae* strains ICIPE 69 (whiteflies, thrips, and mealy bugs) and ICIPE 62 (aphids) were also applied after transplanting. A homemade botanical pesticide (onions, garlic, *Tithonia*,

and Mexican marigold) was also used as an antifeedant targeting various caterpillars and a repellent for various insects.

Data collection and analysis

Quantitative data was obtained by tracking the harvest records, insect pests, and disease incidence. Harvested produce was sorted and graded, and the respective weights were recorded in kilograms under two categories, namely marketable and unmarketable produce. Generalized insect pest and disease prevalence/incidence rating scales were developed to collect data every 2 weeks for 3 months. Ten (10) plants in each plot were observed, and their prevalence scores were used to obtain the incidence scores at the plot level, which were translated to Disease and insect pest pressure curves using a formula modified from Shaner and Finney (1977).

The area under the disease pressure curve (AUDPC) and area under the insect pressure curve (AUIPC) were subjected to statistical analysis based on the mean (m) and standard deviation (sd) and then subjected to paired t-test analysis. The t-value was set at $t_0=0$ while the p-value was set at $p \leq 0.05$. Field notes were also used to document the research staff's observations of the crop progress during monitoring visits and to capture the farmer's in-depth experiences and observations during the trial period. This aimed to generate additional evidence to support/explain the quantitative data, which tends to generalize the outcome.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First season (dry season): Single location in Kangema

Results for the dry season showed that agroecological practices were effective against pests at $p < 0.0001$. The

usable portion of harvests for the agroecological plot was higher than that of the farmer practice plot. Still, there was no significant difference in the unusable portion of the harvests due to pest damage between the plots. The increased quantity of harvests and reduction in pests were consistent with Kenyan tea farmers' reports that using organic nutrient sources for their soils and spraying botanical pesticides on their tea increased leaf harvest by 40% compared to when they were using inorganic fertilizers and synthetic pesticides (AFSA, 2021). Observation of seedlings propagated using *Trichoderma* showed that the seedlings thrived in the nursery and after transplanting compared to the conventional/farmer-raised seedlings. This concurs with findings that *Trichoderma* plays a significant role as a biofertilizer and a fungicide (Bongani and Luwam, 2022), which improves the growth of crops. Results are also consistent with other studies, which found that insect pests and diseases are higher during the dry season, and their damages are often magnified (Njuguna et al., 2021). Coupled with other abiotic factors, such as drought stress and high temperatures, a crop's resistance to pests is often broken, making it susceptible (Foyer, 2016).

Direct feeding by pests reduces the quantity of marketable harvests, while pest damage increases quantities of unmarketable harvests (Stephenson et al., 2020). Results for the conventional plot reflect this in all the categories investigated. Manure retains higher moisture in the soil (Nyamangara et al., 2001; Rayne and Aula, 2020) besides supplying plants with ready nutrients. *Trichoderma* works as a mycorrhiza by producing vitamins, mining iron and water from the soil and availing them to the crops (Tyśkiewicz, 2022), and as a biopesticide, it guards the crops against several fungal pathogens (Waghunde et al., 2016; Bongani and Luwam, 2022). Homemade biopesticides have also been shown to work against a broad spectrum of insect pests (Islam and Morshed, 2013). The combined action of these inputs in the agroecology plot seems to have increased the harvests while reducing the pests.

Table 1: Quantitative results for the first season of kale trials done in Kangema during the dry season

#	Type of produce				Type of pest			
	Marketable in Kgs		Unmarketable in Kgs		Diseases		Insect pests	
Plot	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Mean	18.68	38.55	3.17	2.92	37.15	12.38	126.00	88.31
t-value	4.06		1.298		10.65		8.21	
df	12		12		12		12	
p	0.0016		0.2198		<0.0001		<0.001	

Figure 1: Performance of trial plots based on harvest for Collard greens

Figure 2: Performance of trial plots due to disease pressure in collards

Figure 3: Performance of trial plots due to insect pest pressure in collards

Second season (Wet season): Multilocational results

During the rainy season, the higher zone agroecological plot had lower pest infestation than the farmer's practice plot $p=0.0395$. Still, due to pest damage, there were no significant differences in the usable ($p=0.1218$) and unusable portions ($p=1.000$) of harvests. This supports findings that a crop's inherent resistance is heightened during the wet season due to the presence of conducive growth conditions (low temperatures and ample water), which enhances leaf production (hence increased quantities of harvests) and suppresses the effects of insect pest infestations and infections by diseases (Foyer, 2016). In addition, the deficient populations of insect pests during the rainy season provide a natural pathway for their control (Njuguna et al., 2021). In the lower zone, the plots had no significant differences in pest incidence ($p=0.1902$) and quantity of unusable harvests ($p=0.165$). This supports

the findings of naturally low pest incidences during the wet season (Foyer, 2016). However, the usable portion of harvest was higher in the agroecological plot than in the farmer practices plot at $p<0.0001$. This is in line with the dry season results suggesting enhanced performance of the crops due to the combined effects of the bio-inputs.

Although these findings mainly support the use of agroecology in vegetable production, further trials are being done to identify whether there are any clear patterns in the disparities observed between quantities of harvests for the dry and wet seasons. This will also give more precise insights into pest infestations based on the production approach, seasonality, and production zone of kale.

Table 2: Quantitative results for the second season of kale trials done in Kangema and Kiharu during the wet season

#	Kangema Sub-County							
	Type of produce				Type of pest			
	Marketable in Kgs		Unmarketable in Kgs		Diseases		Insect pests	
Plot	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Mean	19.14	20.37	2.09	2.09	58.15	58.15	79.69	75.38
t-value	1.665		0.000		0		2.3094	
df	12		12		12		12	
p	0.1218		1.0000		-		0.0395	
#	Kiharu Sub-County							
	Type of produce				Type of pest			
	Marketable in Kgs		Unmarketable in Kgs		Diseases		Insect pests	
Plot	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Mean	4.15	7.69	0.46	0.40	58.15	58.15	82.82	79.69
t-value	9.702		1.4771		0		1.3887	
df	12		2		12		12	
p	0.0001		0.165		-		0.1902	

Kangema

Figure 4: Performance of trial plots based on harvest for Collard greens

Figure 5: Performance of trial plots due to insect pest pressure in collards

Figure 6: Performance of trial plots due to disease pressure in collards

Kiharu

Figure 7: Performance of trial plots based on harvest for Collard greens

Figure 8: Performance of trial plots due to insect pest pressure in collards

Figure 9: Performance of trial plots due to disease pressure in collards

CONCLUSION

As kale consumption increases globally, its consequent high demand will necessitate increased production under small-holder farming systems and expansion into large-holder systems. Therefore, there is a need to identify safe farming approaches that can be applied in both scales of production. In addition, there is a need to investigate agroecology further by conducting more trials spread out through different crop-growing seasons and localities, as well as for a broader range of crops. This will conclusively validate this preliminary evidence and form the basis for the intensive expansion and scaling of agroecological approaches within and outside the kale production systems.

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The Effectiveness of Two Subspecies of *Bacillus thuringiensis* Collected from Taiwan against *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus)

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ABSTRACT

Bacillus thuringiensis (BT) is a well-known bio-insecticide that has been used for over 50 years to control caterpillars on cruciferous vegetables worldwide, including *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus) (diamondback moth, DBM), and noctuid moths. BT is a spore-forming bacterium naturally found in soil and on plant leaves, providing a good choice of pest control for eco-friendly agriculture. In Taiwan, most BT strains were imported from abroad, and the annual amount was more than 50 million NTD. Therefore, it is important to develop localized BT strain. Two local *B. thuringiensis* subspecies were collected by the Agriculture Chemicals Research Institute (ACRI) from barns, and *Semecarpus longifolius* Blume leaves in Taiwan. One was *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* E-911 from a barn in Taiwan, and the other was *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* Ab12 from plant leaves. Both subspecies were separately technology transferred to the Fwusow Industry of Taiwan in 2005 and 2014 for commercialization and sale. The commercialized products of *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* strain E-911 and *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* strain Ab12 was 60%

wettable powder. To evaluate the bioassay of isolated strain against DBM, an artificial diet with E-911 and Ab12 dilution was used to feed third instar larvae of DBM. After 72 hours, the mortality of DBM was 92.2 - 96.7% for strain E-911 at 30 ppm and 93.3 - 96.7% for strain Ab12 at 60 ppm. The field trials showed that 60% of the wettable powder formulations of E-911 and Ab12 were recommended to be sprayed twice and thrice when fields were infected by DBM. The control rate of E-911 and Ab12 powder in 1000-fold dilution were 65.6 - 89.9% and 58.7 - 59.7%. Based on the artificial diet and field test results, both E-911 and Ab12 products could be new localized BT products in Taiwan. The strains E-911 and Ab12 have also been registered in Taiwan in 2011 and 2023, respectively. It will provide farmers with more options for effectively controlling DBM in the future.

Keywords

diamondback moth (DBM), *Bacillus thuringiensis*, E-911, Ab12, Taiwan

INTRODUCTION

In 1901, a bacterium from dead larvae of silkworm infected by sotto disease was isolated by a Japanese scientist, Shigetane Ishiwata. In 1911, Ernst Berliner discovered a related bacteria strain from deceased larvae of the Mediterranean flour moth in a flour mill located in the German state of Thuringia. This particular strain was named *Bacillus thuringiensis* (BT). Since the late 1950s, BT has been used to control agricultural pests, and it is a well-known bio-insecticide nowadays. Sporeine, the first commercial insecticide made from BT, was produced in France in 1938 and used to control flour moths. In the United States, BT was first manufactured commercially in 1958. (Ibrahim *et al.* 2010) Among BT, the subspecies *kurstaki* (BTK) and *aizawai* (BTA) are the most world-famous strains to control caterpillars on cruciferous vegetables, including diamondback moth (DBM) and noctuid moths. (Fernández-Chapa *et al.* 2019, Glare *et al.* 2000, and Legwaila *et al.* 2015)

Nine pesticide manufacturers have registered with the permit of BT in Taiwan, including Agro Chemical Corporation, Agrowaho International Co., Ltd., Fwusow Industry Co., Ltd., Ihara Chemical Co., (Taiwan) Ltd., Jia Non Enterprise Co., Ltd., Lanlix Crop Science Co., Ltd., National Farmers' Association Agricultural Chemical Plant Republic of China, Sinon Corporation, Sumitomo Chemical Taiwan Company Limited and Tai Yeh Chemical Industry Co., Ltd. Among them are eight manufacturing licenses and ten importing licenses, a total of 18 licenses for selling formulated BT pesticides. The strains reported to be used in developing BT pesticides were *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* strains Ab12, ABTS-1857, GC-91, NB-200, and *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* strains ABTS-351, E-911, EG-7841, SA-11, and SA-12, amounting to 11 strains (APHIA, 2024). The strains of *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* E-911 (BTK E-

911) and *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* Ab12 (BTA Ab12) were collected by Agriculture Chemicals Research Institute (ACRI) from barns and leaves surface of *Semecarpus longifolius* Blume in Taiwan (Tzeng, 1997 and Kuo, 2007).

In Taiwan, products are made from BT strains E-911 and Ab12. Both strains were technology transferred from ACRI to Fwusow Industry in 2005 and 2014 for commercialization and sale. Commercial BT product formulation was 60% wettable powder (WP) with both strains. The commercial names of E-911 and Ab12 are FWUSOW BT1 and FWUSOW BTA b12, and the Chinese commercial names are Su-li-bao (速力寶) and Nian-ze-bao (鮎澤寶) (Table 1). A control effect of the isolated strain was needed to get a bio-pesticide register. This article summarized the bioassay and field trial results of both two strains and evaluated the potential to become a new way to control DBM.

Table 1. The commercial information is for BT strains E-911 and Ab12.

Products labeled in Taiwan		
	Subsp species	kurstaki
Strain name	E-911	Ab12
Commercial name	FWUSOW BT1	FWUSOW BTA b12
Chinese commercial name	速力寶 (Su-li-bao)	鮎澤寶 (Nian-ze-bao)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of insect and plant

The larvae of *Plutella xylostella* in the bioassay tests were obtained from the insectarium room of the Product Development Division of ACRI (Kao, 1995). The rearing of *P. xylostella* (American sensitive strains original from Valent BioSciences LLC, import permit number 110-E-751) was fed at the insectarium room with 25 ± 1°C, 12:12 hour light-darkness cycle, and 65% relative humidity. Third, DBM instar larvae were used for the experiments. The insect resource of *P. xylostella* larvae in the field trial was the nature population at fields of Dacun Township, Changhua County/ Erlun Township, Yunlin County/ Yongkang District, Tainan City/ Ligang Township, Pingtung County/ Donggang Township, Pingtung County in Taiwan. The plant resources used for the laboratory bioassay were the leaves of one-month-old broccoli

(*Brassica oleracea* var. *italica*) grown in the greenhouse. The field experiments used cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L. *Capitata* group) to do the spraying experiments.

Bioassay of *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* E-911 and *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* Ab12 to diamondback moth in artificial diet

The tested insects were the susceptible strains of *Plutella xylostella* sourced from the United States. The potency units were DBMU (diamondback moth units)/ mg. BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 test samples were 30 ppm and 30, 60 ppm, respectively. The standard agents (*B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai*) with 60,805 DBMU/ mg potency values (Lot No.:57733V901, stored in ACRI) were used as the positive control. The sterile water was used as a negative control. The artificial diets with different BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 concentrations were used to feed DBM larvae. The cumulative mortality was observed after 48 and 72 hours. The mortality was calculated by formula. (Mortality = number of dead recorded/ number of insects in the population × 100). If dead individuals were in negative control but the population's mortality was less than 10%, the mortality was corrected by Abbott's formula. [Corrected mortality = [(mortality of the treatment group - mortality of the control group) / (100 - mortality of the control group)] × 100]. This experiment was repeated twice. Every treatment tested 30 and 90-third instar larvae of DBM and 100-third instar larvae of DBM in positive and negative control. All larvae were fed at 25 ± 1°C, 12:12 hour light-darkness cycle, and 65% relative humidity (Beagle *et al.* 1986 and Dulmage *et al.* 1976).

Leaf-disk dipping bioassay of *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* E-911

The method was modified from the Giustolin *et al.* method in 2001. The cauliflower leaves were washed with distilled water containing 0.1% Tween 20. Then, cauliflower leaves were cut in a diameter of 5 cm disk. Each treatment had 6 replications. Leaf disks were dipped in a homogenized BT bio-pesticide solution with 0.01% Tween 20 for 10 seconds and then dried naturally at room temperature. Dried leaf disks were put in a 9 cm petri dish with water-soaked filter paper under the bottom. Five third instar DBM larvae were transferred to one leaf disk, and each treatment had thirty larvae. A tissue paper was put on the lid of the petri dish. All Petri dishes were incubated at 25 ± 1°C, 12: 12-hour light-darkness cycle, and 65% relative humidity. The mortality was observed after inoculated 24 hours and 48 hours. The concentrates of E-911 bio-pesticide were diluted to 2000, 1500, and 1000-folds, and water was used as a negative control.

Field trial assay of *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* E-911 and *B. thuringiensis* subsp. *aizawai* Ab12

Three independent field trials were done on BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 to control DBM larvae. These experiments were arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with four blocks. Each block comprised two plots (2 rows/plot, each row 10 meters long). In each plot, the number of larvae was counted on ten plants (excluding the first and last two plants), and every treatment had 20 replications. In BTK E-911, five treatments were used in the field trial: (1) 60% BTK E-911 WP 1000-fold dilution, (2) 60% BTK E-911 WP 2000-fold dilution, (3) 40% BTA WG 1500-fold dilution. (4) 11.6% Spinosad SC 3000-fold dilution (positive control), and (5) untreated control (negative control). In BTA Ab12, five treatments were used, including (1) 60% BTA Ab12 WP 750-fold dilution, (2) 60% BTA Ab12 WP 1000-fold dilution, (3) 60% BTA Ab12 WP 1500-fold dilution, (4) 48.1% BTA ABTS-1857 WG 4000-fold dilution (positive control), and (5) untreated control (negative control). Application method: The samples were sprayed uniformly to the entire plant during the early stage of DBM infestation every 7 days, twice in BTK E-911 and three times in BTA Ab12. Assessment method: The number of larvae was assessed before each application and after 7 days of the final application. A total of 3 surveys for BTK E-911 and 4 surveys for BTA Ab12 were done in experiments.

All field experiment results of BTK E-911 in 2009 -2010 and BTA Ab12 in 2017 - 2018 were conducted by Taichung District Agricultural Research and Extension Station at Changhua, Tainan District Agricultural Research and Extension Station at Yunlin, and Tainan, Kaohsiung District Agricultural Research and Extension Station at Pingtung, and National Pingtung University of Science and Technology at Pingtung, respectively. The field experiments on cabbage were done from winter to spring.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted in the SAS Enterprise Guide (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA 2017). Before conducting ANOVA, Levene's tests examined the homogeneity of variances. The bioassay results with BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 on larvae of DBM were tested with one-way ANOVA; post-hoc analyses were conducted with Tukey's HSD tests. The results of field experiments with BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 investigated 20 cabbages and recorded the number of live DBM larvae in each plot. Then, convert the number of live DBM larvae to the control rate of each plot using the control rate formula. Control rate (%) = $1 - \left[\frac{\text{the number of insects in the treatment area after spraying}}{\text{the number of insects in the control area before spraying}} \right] \times 100$. For each value (x) representing the number of DBM larvae in each plot, the square root of

(x+1) was taken for variable analysis. The average value for each treatment was then calculated. If the mean values were significantly different, the least significant difference (LSD) test was used to compare the treatments for significant differences, using a significance level of 5%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bioassay with artificial diet and dipped leaves

The strains BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 were technology transferred from ACRI to the Fwusow Industry and were developed to be commercial products. 60% WP of E-911 and Ab12 were diluted and added to an artificial diet to feed third-instar DBM larvae. After feeding an artificial diet with BTK E-911 for 48 hours, the mortality of DBM larvae was 66.7 - 63.3% at 30 ppm. And after 72 hours, the mortality of DBM was up to 92.2 - 96.7%. On the other hand, after feeding with BTA Ab12 for 48 hours, the mortality of DBM was 33.3 - 43.3% at 30 ppm and 43.3-50% at 60 ppm. Then, after 72 hours, the mortality of DBM was 70% at 30 ppm and 93.3- 96.7% at 60 ppm. In positive control, the cumulative mortality of 20 ppm BTA standard was 99.0% after 72 hours. Based on bioassay results, DBM showed susceptibility to 30 ppm BTK E-911 and 60 ppm BTA Ab12 (Table 2). In the broccoli leaves dipping with BTK E-911 (Figure 1), the corrected mortality of DBM was 96.7% in all treatments after 48 hours. In these results, DBM also showed susceptibility to dilutions of 2000 and 1500-fold of BTK E-911, and 1000-fold dilution of BTK E-911 was recommended to control DBM on cruciferous crops. This may indicate that the rearing of *P. xylostella* (American strains) is susceptible to lower dilutions of BTK E-911. Although the results of BT bioassay may not be the same as field efficacy (Zommick, 2022), the bioassay method can still serve as a quality control baseline for BT products. Bioassays in the laboratory have increased significance due to their predictive value. This method can generate comparative toxicity data within a relatively short time and at a low cost. Additionally, it is essential to build greater confidence among users in using this product.

Figure 1. Feeding diamondback moth with leaf dipping with BTK E-911

Corrected mortality in columns with different letters is significantly different according to Tukey's studentized range (HSD) test at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2. Insecticidal activity of *Bacillus thuringiensis* products against *Plutella xylostella* larvae with artificial diet to feed diamondback moth.

Samples	No. of larvae Tested (n)	Cumulative mortality (%)	
		48h	72h
E-911 30ppm	90	66.7ab	92.2a
E-911 30ppm	30	63.3ac	96.7a
Ab12 60ppm	90	50.0bcd	93.3a
Ab12 60ppm	30	43.3ade	96.7a
Ab12 30ppm	90	43.3ce	70.0b
Ab12 30ppm	30	33.3ce	70.0b
BTA standard 20ppm	100	71.0a	99.0a
Water control	100	0f	0c

Cumulative mortality for all variables is untransformed values. Cumulative mortality in columns with different letters is significantly different according to Tukey's studentized range (HSD) test at $p < 0.05$.

Control results of diamondback moth by BT biopesticides application in field trial

The field experiment results in two strains (Figure 2) and showed a similar control rate at different latitudes. In BTK E-911, the control rate of DBM was 89.9% in Changhua County, 65.6% in Tainan City, and 84.42% in Pingtung County under 7 days after spraying twice of BTK E-911 1000-fold dilution. In BTA Ab12, the control rate of DBM was 72.5% in Changhua County, 68.2% in Yunlin County, and 69.2% in Pingtung County under 7 days after spraying three times of BTA Ab12 with 750-fold dilution. In the other results of using BTA Ab12 1000-fold dilution, the control rate of DBM was 63.1% in Changhua County, 58.7% in Yunlin County, and 58.7% at Pingtung County under 7 days after spraying three times. Field experiments for both BT strains were conducted to fulfill the registration requirements. According to the field trial results, the FWUSOW BT1 is recommended for controlling lepidoptera pests on vegetables, while the FWUSOW BTA b12 is recommended for specifically applying in controlling diamondback moths. BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 products were registered in Taiwan in 2011 and 2023, respectively. Finally, during the early stage of DBM infestation, the recommended method of BTK E-911 was spraying the product 1000-fold once a week and using it twice in a row. The recommended application of BTA Ab12 was spraying the product 750-fold once a week and using it three times in a row.

Figure 2. The control rate of diamondback moth was achieved using BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 in Taiwanese fields.

Population fluctuation of diamondback moth after BT biopesticides application in the field

In field trials, the population fluctuation of DBM larvae was sampled after using BTK E-911 for 14 days in Tainan (Figure 3). Compared to negative control, population fluctuation of DBM larvae in all treatments, including (1) 60% BTK E-911 WP 1000-fold dilution, (2) 60% BTK E-911 WP 2000-fold dilution, (3) 40% BTA ABTS-1857 WG 1500-fold dilution (bioinsecticide positive control), and (4) 11.6% Spinosad SC 3000-fold dilution (chemical insecticide positive control) showed decrease trend after 7 days application. The number of DBM larvae population was counted after applying BTK E-911 for 0 days, 7 days, and 14 days. The results of the 14-day DBM larvae population are demonstrated in the following description. In BTK E-911 1000-fold dilution, the mean number was 20.8 larvae/ 20 cabbages. The results of the other treatments, BTK E-911 WP 2000-fold dilution, BTA ABTS-1857 WG 1500-fold dilution, and Spinosad SC 3000-fold dilution, showed mean numbers of 24, 20.3, 17.3 larvae/ 20 cabbages. The negative control showed mean numbers of 67.5 larvae/ 20 cabbages. All treatments had statistically significant differences from the negative control. The control efficacy of BTK E-911 was similar to Spinosad (chemical insecticide positive control) and BTA ABTS-1857 (bioinsecticide positive control) after spraying BTK E-911 for 14 days. It indicated that BTK E-911 had significant potential as a biopesticide in the field control of DBM.

Figure 3. Population fluctuation of diamondback moth larvae in the Tainan city field after application BTK E-911 (2009, Winter).

On the other hand, the population fluctuation of DBM larvae was sampled after using BTA Ab12 for 21 days in the Changhua field trial (Figure 4). Compared to negative control, population fluctuation of DBM larvae in treatment, including (1) 60% BTA Ab12 WP 750-fold dilution, (2) 60% BTA Ab12 WP 1000-fold dilution, (3) 60% BTA Ab12 WP 1500-fold dilution, and (4) 48.1% BTA ABTS-1857 WG 1500-fold dilution (bioinsecticide positive control) had decreasing trend after 7 days. The number of DBM larvae population was counted after applying BTA Ab12 for 0 days, 7 days, 14 days, and 21 days. The results of the 21-day DBM larvae population are demonstrated in the following description. BTA Ab12 WP 750-fold dilution showed mean numbers of 30 larvae/ 20 cabbages. The other treatment group, BTA Ab12 WP 1000-fold dilution, BTA Ab12 WP 1500-fold dilution, and BTA ABTS-1857 WG 4000-fold dilution, showed mean numbers of 33, 44, 43.5 larvae/ 20 cabbages, and negative control showed mean numbers of 91 larvae/ 20 cabbages. All treatments had statistically significant differences from the negative control. The result demonstrated that the efficacy of BTA Ab12 was similar to BTA ABTS-1857 (bioinsecticide positive control) after spraying BTA Ab12 for 21 days. It indicated that BTA Ab12 had significant potential as a biopesticide in field control of DBM.

Figure 4. Population fluctuation of diamondback moth larvae in the Changhua county field after application BTA Ab12 (2017, Winter).

CONCLUSION

The commercial products of BTK E-911 and BTA Ab12 are new localized BT products in Taiwan, and the results showed that they both had good control efficiency to DBM, whether in lab or field experiments. The study provided farmers with new eco-friendly options for controlling agricultural pests. In the future, it may also have the opportunity to become a new choice for the use of BT products worldwide.

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Validation of Bio-Pesticides for the Pests of Kale (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. *acephala*.) in Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

Kale (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. *acephala*) is the major vegetable crop in terms of production and consumption in Ethiopia. However, its production is affected by a lack of improved cultivars and pests such as cutworms, aphids, and diamondback moths (DBM). Furthermore, it suffers from the injudicious use of chemical pesticides. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of different biopesticides on kale insect pests, including diamondback moths. In the 2021/22 rainy season, an on-station trial comprising five biopesticide treatments, one untreated control, and one chemical control was conducted. Treatments were arranged using a randomized complete block design, and spraying was done every seven days from the transplanting date to the fourth harvest. Data on yield, agronomic parameters, and pest incidence/severity were collected and analyzed. The analysis of variance revealed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in marketable and total yield but not in unmarketable yield. The highest (70.38 t/ha) and the lowest (48.17 t/ha) marketable yields were obtained from the *Trichoderma* + *Metarhizium anisopliae* and *Trichoderma* + Neem extract treatments, respectively. Regarding pests, there was no difference between treatments for cabbage loopers, diamondback moths, and flea beetles, but significant differences were observed for aphid and leaf miners. Although the result is

from a one-season and location experiment, as the first of its kind in the country, it sheds light on the prospects of bio-pesticides for the control of destructive pests of vegetables in a human and environmentally friendly manner.

Keywords

kale, biopesticide, validation, leaf damage

INTRODUCTION

The production and marketing of vegetable crops is a source of livelihood for countless households in Ethiopia. Several vegetables grow in the country under rainfed and irrigation systems (Emana et al., 2015). In 2020, the area under vegetables (leafy, fruit, tuber, root, and bulbs) was estimated to be 486,921.58 ha with a total production of 5,531,025.14 tons (Banchiamlak & Akalu, 2022). Kale (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. *acephala*) contributes significantly to the country's total vegetable production. In 2022, kale was grown by 4.5 million farmers on 48,442 ha of land, with a total output of 471,938 tons (CSA, 2022). Kale has always been a key constituent of the local diet and is nutritionally important for subsistence farmers who cannot afford alternative vegetables, especially during the time of the year when food is scarce (Asfaw, 2020). Despite its importance, it is generally neglected by research and development programs (Teklewold and Becker, 2006), and no improved variety with better agronomic and nutritional qualities has been released in Ethiopia.

In addition to abiotic factors that affect kale cultivation during the rainy and dry seasons, biotic factors such as pest infestation are a major concern for kale growers in Ethiopia. Among the insect pests that affect brassica crops are aphids such as *Brevicoryne brassicae* L. (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) (Hemiptera: Aphididae). Aphids cause high-yield losses, and their presence reduces the quality of the leaves and may render them unmarketable (Francisco et al., 2020). Other pests that affect the production of kale are Diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* L. (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), Silverleaf whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and caterpillars of the genus *Hellula* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) (Francisco et al., 2020; Ponce et al., 2023).

Vegetable growers in Ethiopia extremely rely on chemical pesticides to stay in production by offsetting the economic loss caused by pests. Recently, pesticide overuse, misuse, and abuse have caused massive distress to people and the environment (Mengstie et al., 2017). To counteract the

serious threat pesticides pose, biopesticides are gaining attraction as a conventional way to sustain pest control (Srinivasan et al., 2019). Biopesticides include products with active substances that are based on botanicals (plant extracts, minerals), semiochemicals (pheromones), and microbial (fungi- and bacteria-based biopesticides) (Chandler et al., 2010). Biopesticides are cheap, environment-friendly, specific in their mode of action, sustainable, do not leave residues, and are not associated with the release of greenhouse gases (Shannon et al., 2021). Research, development, and application of biopesticides in Ethiopia is at its early stage. Therefore, this study aimed to validate the efficiency of commercially available biopesticides in controlling kale insect pests in Ethiopia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of Experimental Area

A field experiment was conducted on-station at Melkassa Agricultural Research Center from March to July 2022 in Ethiopia. The experimental site is in the central rift valley of Ethiopia at 8°24'N, 39°21'E, at an altitude of 1,550 m.a.s.l. The average annual rainfall was 768 mm, and the mean maximum and minimum temperatures were 28.5°C and 12.6°C, respectively.

Experimental Design and Treatments

The experiment had seven treatments: 1) Untreated control 2) Chemical treatment 3) *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Bacillus subtilis* 4) *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Bacillus thuringiensis* 5) *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Beauveria bassiana* 6) *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Metarhizium anisopliae* and 7) *Trichoderma asperellum* + Neem extract. All biopesticides except the neem extract were obtained from real IPM Kenya. The trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. The plot size was 11.2 m², with 70 and 40 cm between rows and plants, respectively. Of the five rows, the middle three rows were used for data collection. Fertilizers, NPS (46 kg phosphorus, 18 kg nitrogen, and 7 kg sulfur) with a rate of 242 kg/ha was applied just before transplanting, and urea (46 % nitrogen) was applied in two splits, 15 and 45 days after transplanting. Roots of seedlings for the biopesticide treatments were treated with *Trichoderma asperellum* mycelia 1 x 10⁹ cfu/ml before transplanting. Spraying was performed every week, from one week after transplanting until the fourth leaf harvest for 10 consecutive weeks. The pesticides that were part of the chemical treatment were Indoxacarb 125gm/l + Spinosad 25g/l, Imidacloprid 20% SL, Profenofos 72 % EC, Chlorantraniliprole 200 SC, Emamectin Benzoate 5% SG, and 15g/l Cyhalothrin + 300g/l Profenofos.

Data Collection

Data on marketable and unmarketable leaf yield was collected, as well as pest damage scores for main insect pests, including the diamondback moth (*Plutella xylostella* L.), the cabbage aphid (*Brevicoryne brassicae* L.), the cabbage looper (*Trichoplusia ni*), flea beetles (*Psylliodes chrysocephala*), and the serpentine leaf miner (*Liriomyza brassicae*). Five plants from the inside rows were used to score the abundance of aphids and the damage level of flea beetles. A one-time plot-based scoring (1-5) was used for the rest of the pests. For aphids, a 0-4 score was employed, whereby 0 = no aphids present; 1 = 5 to 10 aphids per leaf; 2 = 11 to 100 aphids per leaf; 3 = 101 to 500 aphids per leaf; and 4 = >500 aphids per leaf. The number of holes on a 2*2cm leaves (1) of 5 plants was counted for flea beetle damage.

Data Analysis

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out independently for each parameter, and whenever there was a significant difference between treatment effects at P<0.05, the Tukey HSD test was employed. The latest version of the SAS statistical software university edition, SAS 9.4 (2014), was used for all statistical procedures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Leaf Yield

Analysis of variance showed a significant difference between treatments for marketable (F_{8,12}=7.13, p=0.0014) and total leaf yield (F_{8,12}=5.83, p=0.0035), but a non-significant difference for unmarketable leaf yield (F_{8,12}=1.58, p=0.2293), (Figure 1). The highest marketable and total leaf yield was recorded in *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Metarhizium anisopliae* treatment, followed by *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Bacillus subtilis*, respectively. The lowest marketable and total kale yield was obtained from *Trichoderma asperellum* + Neem extract, followed by Chemical treatment. As with the current result, there are various reports that *Metarhizium* species enhance plant growth. *Metarhizium anisopliae* increased tomato plant biomass (Garcia et al., 2016; Ana et al., 2020). Maize plants inoculated with *Metarhizium* also showed a significant increment in biomass compared to non-inoculated (Imtiaz et al., 2020). The beneficial relationship that entomopathogenic fungi such as *Metarhizium* spp establish with their hosts is complex. Still, there are reports of mycoinsecticides acting as endophytes, antagonists to plant pathogens, rhizosphere colonizers, and plant growth promotors (Enrique et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Means for marketable, unmarketable, and total leaf yield on kale; error bars are the standard deviation of the mean.

Pest Infestation

There was a significant difference between treatments for aphid infestation and serpentine leafminer damage. However, no difference was detected for diamondback moth, cabbage looper, and flea beetles. The highest aphid infestation was recorded in *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Trichoderma asperellum* + Neem extract treatments. In contrast, the lowest infestation is detected in the chemical treatment. Likewise, the chemical treatment reduced leaf miner damage better than the biopesticide treatments except for *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Metarhizium anisopliae* treatment. The fact that the chemical pesticide treatment exhibited a better

efficacy for aphid and leaf miner control might have to do with target pests, strain, stage of larvae, and environmental conditions (Mayanglambam et al., 2021). The efficacy of biopesticides is reportedly high when applied to the young larvae (first and second instars larva) and reapplication when the insect population increases (Van Frankenhuyzen 2009; Gupta and Dikshit 2010). Biopesticide treatments reduced cabbage looper, diamondback moth, and flea beetles as effectively as the chemical pesticide treatment. Similar studies also reported the effectiveness of entomopathogenic fungi and bacteria for the management of crucifer pests (Ghosh et al., 2011; Ramanujam et al., 2014; Singh et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2019; Srinivasan et al., 2019).

Table 1: Effect of biopesticide treatments on abundance and damage level of pests on kale, standard deviation presented in parenthesis

Treatment	Cabbage Looper	Aphid	DBM	Flea beetle	Leaf miner
1	3.66 (0.57)	3.00(0.00) ^{bc}	2.00(0.00)	2.43(0.12)	3.66(1.52) ^a
2	3.33(1.15)	2.00(0.00) ^c	2.33(0.57)	1.96(0.41)	2.00(0.00) ^p

3	4.00(0.00)	4.00(1.15) ^{ab}	2.66(0.57)	2.36(0.14)	3.66(0.57) ^a
4	3.33(0.57)	3.33(0.57) ^{ab}	2.66(0.57)	2.00(0.26)	4.00(1.00) ^a
5	2.66(0.57)	3.66(1.15) ^{ab}	3.00(0.00)	2.26(0.22)	4.33(1.15) ^a
6	3.00(0.00)	4.00(1.00) ^{ab}	2.66(0.57)	2.23(0.11)	4.00(1.00) ^a
7	3.66(0.57)	4.00(0.57) ^{ab}	2.33(0.57)	2.16(0.18)	3.33(0.57) ^{ab}
F-Value	0.77	5.47	1.45	1.61	3.30
P-value	0.63	0.00	0.27	0.21	0.03
MSE	0.60	0.38	0.22	0.05	0.60
CV (%)	22.97	17.52	18.68	10.40	21.75

Treatment: 1) Untreated control 2) Chemical treatment 3) *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Bacillus subtilis* 4) *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Bacillus thuringiensis* 5) *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Beauveria bassiana* 6) *Trichoderma asperellum* + *Metarhizium anisopliae* and 7) *Trichoderma asperellum* + Neem extract; **F-value:** ratio of between and within group variation; **P-value:** probability value, **MSE:** error mean square, **CV (%)**: coefficient of variation

CONCLUSION

Biopesticides have long been known to have the potential to be an alternative to chemical pesticides. The current study also confirms that the tested biocontrol agents controlled some kale pests just as the chemical pesticide did. However, this study must be repeated for another season to strengthen the current observation. While promoting biopesticides, besides their efficacy in controlling pests, their significance as sustainable and environment-friendly ways of pest management should be considered.

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Evaluation of Biopesticides for Control of Kale (*Brassica oleracea*) Insect Pests in Kenya

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ABSTRACT

Kale is a widely produced and consumed leafy vegetable in Kenya. However, its production is limited by insect pests that cause yield losses and reduce produce quality. The indiscriminate use of synthetic pesticides to control these pests has been associated with increased pest resistance and both human and environmental health concerns. Biopesticides offer a natural, safe, and effective alternative to controlling insect pests. Therefore, this study sought to evaluate the effectiveness of commercially available biopesticides for controlling insect pests in kale. Three multilocational on-station trials were established to test five biopesticide treatments (*Bacillus thuringiensis*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Beauveria bassiana*, azadirachtin 0.03%), one synthetic pesticide treatment (Lambda-cyhalothrin) and Control (no treatment). Each treatment had three replicates in a randomized complete block design. Treatment plots measured 2 m x 2 m with 1 m separating them. The pesticides were applied two weeks after transplanting, and application continued at weekly intervals for 8 weeks. Weekly data on aphids and whiteflies' incidence and leaf area damage caused by diamondback moths was collected over the same period and analyzed using variance analysis and a post hoc Tukey test, where a significant difference was observed. Results from the experiment indicated that the biopesticides demonstrated potential in controlling insect pests in Kale.

INTRODUCTION

Kale (*Brassica oleracea* var. *acephala*) is the most popularly consumed leafy vegetable in Kenya (Horticulture Crops Directorate, 2020). It's valued for its nutritional content, especially vitamins that promote good human health, and is a staple in many Kenyan households.

Kale is grown as a subsistent crop and commercially for the domestic market, earning income for many smallholder farmers. According to the Kenya Horticulture Report 2019-2020 (Horticulture Crops Directorate 2020), 668,666 MT of kale was produced, valued at about \$98.6m. This accounted for 14.8% of all exotic vegetables by value and 5.88% of the total value of horticulture. The importance of kale as a food crop and economic crop cannot be undermined. However, its cultivation faces numerous challenges, including insect pests that cause yield losses and reduce produce quality. Insect pests such as aphids (*Brevicoryne brassicae*), white flies (*Bemisia tabaci*), and diamondback moth (*Plutella xylostella* L.) attack kales from the early stages of growth till the harvesting period, causing considerable damage if not properly controlled. Farmers use different methods to manage these pests and reduce losses, including repeated spraying of synthetic chemicals, which lead to adverse effects on human health and environmental pollution. However, the consumer market is increasingly vocal about the indiscriminate use of synthetic chemicals in vegetable production, subsequent chemical residues on vegetables, and associated health concerns (Machekano, H *et al.*, 2019). Improper use of synthetic chemicals can have toxic effects on the environment and has been associated with loss of biodiversity, such as loss of honeybees and other non-targeted organisms (Ayilara *et al.*, 2023).

As a result, there is growing interest in developing and testing biopesticides made from naturally occurring soil microorganisms and plant extracts as an alternative pest control solution (Borges *et al.*, 2021). Biopesticides are considered safe for humans and the environment and effective in an integrated approach to controlling insect pests (Parajuli *et al.*, 2022).

This study conducted multilocational trials to evaluate the efficacy of four different biopesticide treatments and one chemical treatment in controlling aphids, whiteflies, and diamondback moths in Kale. This report presents the results of the trials.

Study sites

The on-station trials were conducted at Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) stations in Kabete, Katumani, and Kandara, Kenya, from April 2022 to April 2023. The three stations represent different Agroecological zones.

Kabete trial station lies at an altitude of 1740m asl and is considered a semi-humid area. Katumani and Thika trial stations have an altitude of 1600m asl and 1548m asl, respectively; both are considered semi-arid areas. The locations represent areas where traditional African vegetables are grown and where the crop is susceptible to insect pest attack.

Treatments

Kale was selected as the study crop. Six treatments (four biopesticides, one synthetic chemical pesticide, and no chemical) were applied to determine their efficacy on the insect pest population. The biopesticides and the synthetic chemical pesticides were selected based on their availability and compatibility with vegetable crops.

Table 1 below shows the treatments used for the trial.

Table 1: Treatments used in the trials.

Treatments	Pesticide Active Ingredient	Category
T1	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> var. <i>Kurstaki</i>	Biopesticide
T2	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	Biopesticide
T3	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	Biopesticide
T4	azadirachtin 0.03%	Biopesticide
T5	Lambda-cyhalothrin 1.75	Synthetic chemical pesticide
T6	Control – No treatment	

Experimental design

The experimental layout was a randomized complete block design. Each treatment had three replications, each measuring 2m x 2m with 1m between them. The crop was grown following recommended agronomic practices (spacing, manure application, watering, and weeding). The pesticides were applied two weeks after transplanting and continued weekly for six weeks. All pesticides were sprayed according to the manufacturer's recommended dosages and application methods.

Data collection

Insect pest populations were monitored weekly, and data was recorded on pest numbers per plant and plant damage

severity. The main target pest species evaluated were aphids, whiteflies, and diamondback moths (DBM). Pest counting and assessments were carried out a day before the application of treatments. Three inner rows from each plot were selected for sampling. The total number of adult aphids and whiteflies on five random plants in each replicate was recorded in the selected three middle rows. Leaf area damage caused by the diamondback moth was determined by visually examining the same randomly selected plants and estimated as a percentage of the total plants sampled.

Data Analysis

Data on pest incidences and leaf area damage were subjected to analysis of variance and post hoc tests to determine whether there was a statistical difference across the treatments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The trial results demonstrated varying levels of effectiveness among the four biopesticides in controlling insect pests in the different study sites.

Aphid population

In Kabete, the biopesticides *Beauveria bassiana* and Azadirachtin significantly reduced aphid population when compared to the control - no treatment ($p < 0.05$) while showing a similar control effect to the synthetic pesticide. On the other hand, in the Katumani and Kandara sites, all pesticide treatments showed no significant difference from the control group in controlling aphids. However, Katumani plots treated with the synthetic pesticide lambda-cyhalothrin had a significantly lower population than plots treated with *Bacillus thuringiensis*. A similar study by Akmal *et al.* (2013) reported the effectiveness of *Beauveria bassiana* in achieving significant mortality against cabbage aphid in brassica. The control effect of azadirachtin on aphids aligns with previous research on its insecticidal properties, including inhibition of feeding, anti-oviposition, fertility suppression, decreased growth, and even sterilization (Zhao *et al.*, 2019 Kilani, 2021)

Figure 1: Means of adult aphids in Kabete, Kandara, and Katumani study sites.

Table 2: Effect of biopesticide treatments on aphid population on kale in the three study sites

Treatment	Kabete	Kandara	Katumani
1	3.13 ^c	0.16 ^{ab}	2.67 ^b
2	2.42 ^{bc}	0.18 ^{ab}	1.40 ^{ab}
3	0.30 ^a	0.40 ^b	1.37 ^{ab}
4	0.73 ^{ab}	0.08 ^a	0.87 ^{ab}
5	0.96 ^{ab}	0.18 ^{ab}	0.30 ^a
6	3.72 ^c	0.23 ^{ab}	1.97 ^{ab}

Treatment: 1) *Bacillus thuringiensis* 2) *Metarhizium anisopliae* 3) *Beauveria bassiana* 4) Azadirachtin 5) Lambda-cyhalothrin 6) Control – No treatment

Whitefly population

For the control of whitefly infestation in kale, results from Katumani station showed only Azadirachtin and the synthetic pesticide to be the most effective, significantly reducing whitefly populations compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). In Kabete station, no significant

difference in the whitefly population was achieved across all treatments, while in Kandara, no whitefly population was observed. These results were consistent with a study by Lynn et al. (2010), which established the effectiveness of azadirachtin in inhibiting development and causing mortality of whiteflies in different growth stages.

Figure 2: Means of adult whiteflies in Kabete and Katumani study sites.

Table 3: Effect of biopesticide treatments on whitefly population on kale in the study sites

Treatment	Kabete	Katumani
1	0.24 ^a	2.59 ^d
2	0.25 ^a	1.20 ^{bc}
3	0.23 ^a	2.11 ^{cd}
4	0.24 ^a	0.84 ^{ab}
5	0.23 ^a	0.08 ^a
6	0.25 ^a	2.11 ^{cd}

Treatment: 1) *Bacillus thuringiensis* 2) *Metarhizium anisopliae* 3) *Beauveria bassiana* 4) azadirachtin 5) Lambda-cyhalothrin 6) Control – No treatment

Leaf area damage

In Katumani, the leaf area damage was similar in all treatments. The plots in Kabete and Kandara treated with biopesticides *Beauveria bassiana* and *Bacillus thuringiensis*, respectively, had significantly lower leaf damage caused by diamondback moth than the control treatments. Additionally, both treatments achieved the same efficacy with synthetic chemical pesticide treatment. *Bacillus thuringiensis*, a naturally occurring soil

bacterium available commercially in various formulations and strains, can control lepidopteran pests in different plants (Berini *et al.*, 2018; Samada *et al.*, 2020). Its effectiveness in controlling diamondback moth larvae and reducing leaf damage was demonstrated by Legwaila *et al.* (2015). Similarly, Gehan *et al.* (2020) reported a significant reduction in the diamondback moth larvae population in cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata*) where *Beauveria bassiana* was applied.

Figure 3: Means of leaf area damage caused by Diamondback moth in Kabete, Kandara, and Katumani study sites.

Table 4: Effect of biopesticide treatments on leaf area damage on kale in the study sites

Treatment	Kabete	Kandara	Katumani
1	4.10 ^{ab}	0.50 ^a	10.70 ^a
2	3.15 ^{ab}	1.37 ^b	9.29 ^a
3	2.44 ^a	1.27 ^b	9.92 ^a
4	5.02 ^{ab}	1.03 ^{ab}	7.18 ^a
5	4.85 ^{ab}	0.89 ^{ab}	10.88 ^a
6	5.88 ^b	1.18 ^b	12.26 ^a

Treatment: 1) *Bacillus thuringiensis* 2) *Metarhizium anisopliae* 3) *Beauveria bassiana* 4) azadirachtin 5) Lambda-cyhalothrin 6) Control – No treatment

CONCLUSION

Biopesticides, specifically Azadirachtin, *Beauveria bassiana*, and *Bacillus thuringiensis*, offer potential solutions for sustainable pest management in kale production. These biopesticides effectively manage common insect pests, promoting healthier plants and increasing yields. Biopesticides can help make kale cultivation more ecologically friendly and sustainable, benefiting both farmers and consumers. More research and field experiments are needed to improve application methods and compatibility with other pest management practices.

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The Plasticity of Learning in the Specialist Diamondback Moth Parasitoid, *Diadegma semiclausum* (Hellén)

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ABSTRACT

In insects, different learning experiences lead to different forms of memory formation. We investigated behavioral changes in the diamondback moth (DBM) parasitoid *Diadegma semiclausum* (Hellén) in response to different learning experiences. Naïve female *D. semiclausum* demonstrated an innate preference for the herbivore-induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) produced by DBM-induced Chinese cabbage plants over those produced by DBM-induced common cabbage plants. However, this was overridden by associative learning if parasitoids previously parasitized hosts on common cabbage plants. Examination of memory formation in *D. semiclausum* under different "conditioned stimulus" regimes showed that single oviposition and massed oviposition events resulted in memory retention >12 h but < 24h, while time-spaced conditioning resulted in memory retention >24 h but < 48 h. Responses to learned HIPVs waned after 24h, suggesting that long-term memory was not consolidated under either learning regime. Naïve *D. semiclausum* didn't discriminate between HIPVs produced by *Myzus persicae*-induced and DBM-induced common cabbage plants, but experienced parasitoids were more attracted to HIPVs from DBM-induced plants. Naïve and experienced parasitoids were more attracted to plants induced by DBM alone than to plants induced by both herbivores. Parasitoids experienced by attacking DBM larvae on co-infested plants discriminated between these HIPVs and the HIPVs emitted by plants induced by *M. persicae* alone. This suggests that experiencing DBM-host-associated

HIPVs is crucial for effective associative learning by *D. semiclausum*. The study provides insight into a general understanding of learning in *D. semiclausum* and parasitoids.

Keywords

Myzus persicae, associative learning, olfactory learning, host-induced plant volatiles, long-term memory

INTRODUCTION

Plants and insects have coevolved for approximately 400 million years (Schoonhoven et al., 2005). In nature, plants engage in various interactions with a diverse array of organisms, encompassing pollinators, herbivorous insects, and plant pathogens (Dicke et al., 1993; Mitchell et al., 2009; Takakura et al., 2009; Turlings et al., 1990; Waser, 1978). Research conducted on the interaction between plants and insects in the past thirty years indicates that reciprocal evolutionary relationships between herbivores and plants enhance the intricacy of plant defenses (Aljibory & Chen, 2018; Vet & Dicke, 1992). Numerous laboratory experiments have demonstrated that plants under herbivore attack can create and emit volatile organic compounds (VOCs), often referred to as "herbivore-induced plant volatiles" (HIPVs) (Dicke et al., 1990; Turlings & Wäckers, 2004).

Several parasitoids exhibit inherent attraction towards particular HIPVs. In contrast, numerous others require prior oviposition experience coupled with HIPVs to discriminate between plant VOCs infested by suitable hosts and those infested by non-hosts (Furlong et al., 2018; Molck et al., 2000). It has been suggested that parasitoid wasps can optimize their foraging efficiency by forming memory or associative learning (Smid & Vet, 2016). Associative learning consists of a conditioned stimulus usually followed by an unconditioned stimulus, but some conditioned responses can be induced by a conditioned stimulus alone (Menzel, 1999). In terms of the olfactory memory and learning assessment method, tested individuals are presented with an odorant complex (=conditioned stimulus). They are then rewarded by feeding or the opportunity to oviposit in a suitable host (=unconditioned stimulus) (Bitterman et al., 1983). Understanding the consolidated memory phases in parasitoid wasps is important to understand the dynamics of memory associated with learning.

To some extent, memory across the Animal Kingdom is similar at the behavioral and cellular levels (Dubnau, 2003; Stough et al., 2006). Given olfactory learning of host-finding cues has succeeded in forming memory in parasitoids, olfactory cues are deemed crucial resources with the premise that parasitoids rely on these

infochemicals to locate their hosts (Vet & Lewis, 1995). Olfactory memory induced by a single associative learning experience has been classified into four phases: short-term memory (STM), anesthesia-resistant memory, medium-term memory (MTM), and long-term memory (LTM) (Dezazzo & Tully, 1995; Mitchell et al., 2019; Mitchell et al., 2009).

Diadegma semiclausum Hellén (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) has been widely introduced for the biological control of diamondback moth (DBM, *Plutella xylostella*), and it holds significance as a prominent natural enemy of the pest across various temperate and sub-tropical areas, as well as in tropical highland regions (Furlong et al., 2013). As demonstrated in previous studies, adult female *D. semiclausum* show strong innate preferences for DBM-infested Chinese cabbage (*Brassica rapa pekinensis* cv Wombok) plants compared with DBM-infested cabbage plants (*Brassica oleracea capitata* cv sugarloaf) (Furlong et al., 2018). However, after a single oviposition experience on DBM-infested *B. oleracea* plants, *D. semiclausum* females preferred those plants over DBM-induced *B. rapa* plants, demonstrating that innate preferences can be overridden by experience (Furlong et al., 2018). Since there has been no comprehensive study on memory formation in *D. semiclausum*, I test the hypothesis that LTM forms in this parasitoid wasp in this study, investigating how different conditioning regimes affect parasitoid responses to the DBM-host plant complex.

It has been suggested that host and non-host herbivores may induce similar HIPV profiles in infested plants; moreover, whether or not different herbivore species trigger the production of distinct and consistent blends of HIPVs remains debated (Marmolejo et al., 2021). To elucidate the observed issue in the host-seeking behavior of *D. semiclausum*, I hypothesized that green peach aphid (GPA) infestation could potentially influence the plant's response to DBM, subsequently impacting the reliability of HIPVs as cues for *D. semiclausum* in locating its hosts on plants co-infested with both insects. I conducted an investigation aimed at determining the ability of *D. semiclausum* to distinguish between HIPVs emitted by *B. oleracea* when infested by its host (DBM) versus those induced by a non-host *Myzus persicae* (green peach aphid, GPA). Furthermore, I aimed to explore the impact of associative learning on the behavior of *D. semiclausum* when it encounters situations where both hosts and non-hosts coexist.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Insect collection and rearing

DBM larvae were initially collected in 2003 from a cabbage field at the Queensland Department of

Agriculture and Fisheries Gatton Research Station, Gatton, Queensland, Australia. A laboratory population was established on *B. oleracea* and used for all experiments. Adults were reared from the cultures in climate-controlled rooms at 25 (\pm 1) °C; 70-80% relative humidity, 12 hours of light, and 12 hours of darkness in an oviposition cage (45 x 45 x 45 cm). The adult moths were supplied with 10% (w/v) honey solution from saturated dental wicks as food and provided with a common cabbage plant for egg laying. Egg-bearing plants were removed from oviposition cages and replaced with fresh plants every 24 hours. The plants containing eggs were kept in an incubator until the eggs developed to the second instar stage (Garrad et al. 2016; Silva & Furlong 2012). Second instar larvae were transferred to ventilated plastic containers, which were kept moist with damp paper towels. Fresh common cabbage leaves were provided to the larvae daily before experimental use. In all choice experiments, 10-second instar larvae were placed on each *B. oleracea* or *B. rapa* host plant and fed for 24 h before the larvae were removed and the plants used in Y- olfactometer tests.

GPA was initially collected in 2020 from *B. oleracea* at the Central Glasshouse, the University of Queensland, Australia. Nymphs were reared from the cultures in climate-controlled rooms at 25 (\pm 1) °C; 70-80% relative humidity, 12 hours of light, and 12 hours of darkness in a cage (45 x 45 x 45 cm). All nymphs were supplied with a 6-true-leaf stage of *B. oleracea*.

D. semiclausum pupae were purchased from Biological Services, Loxton, South Australia. The pupae were placed in nylon mesh rearing cages (45 x 45 x 45cm) for eclosion and fed with 10% (w/v) honey solution on saturated dental wicks. Immediately after eclosion, male and female wasps were paired in Petri dishes (5cm diameter) and given up to 1 day to mate before being used in experiments. The paired wasps in the Petri dishes were also fed with 10% (w/v) honey solution. The number of female wasps used in each trial was at least 60; all were presumed to have mated during the previous 24 h period. All *D. semiclausum* were housed separately from host plants and DBM hosts to ensure no exposure to HIPVs before experiments began.

Oviposition and conditioning of *D. semiclausum*

Naïve *D. semiclausum* was conditioned by depositing eggs into DBM larvae on DBM-infested *B. oleracea* plants, where wasps experienced host-associated plant odor as the conditioned stimulus that accompanied successful oviposition. After being paired with males for 24 h to allow mating, naïve female wasps were conditioned individually in oviposition cages (45 x 45 x 45 cm) containing a *B. oleracea* plant that had been infested with 10 early third-instar DBM larvae 24 h

previously. Single wasps were introduced into cages and observed carefully. Their behaviors and the time of transition between the behaviors associated with oviposition were recorded.

Two different conditioning procedures were used to condition naïve *D. semiclausum* females: (i) single oviposition and (ii) time-spaced oviposition (3 sequential ovipositions spaced 10 minutes apart). Those individuals that wrestled DBM larvae and then inserted their ovipositor into larvae were considered to have made a successful oviposition attempt (Wang & Keller, 2002). Following single oviposition conditioning, wasps were removed from the cages immediately after oviposition in a host larva. For time-spaced oviposition, wasps were removed from the cages immediately after their first oviposition in a host larva. They were held in a 10 mL glass vial for 10 minutes before being reintroduced to the cage to begin host foraging again. Wasps were again removed from the cages immediately after their second oviposition and held for a further 10 minutes before reintroduction to the cage to begin foraging and eventual oviposition in a third host before being removed for the final time. All suitably conditioned wasps were held in glass vials (10 mL) and provided with 10% (w/v) honey solution as food before use in experiments.

Responses of naïve and conditioned *D. semiclausum* to HIPVs in olfactometer bioassays

A Y-tube olfactometer was used to measure the responses of parasitoid wasps to HIPVs. The apparatus consisted of a “Y” shaped glass tube (0.8 cm internal diameter, 7 cm stem) with two 9.5 cm arms at a 60° angle leading to sealed glass chambers (20 x 20 x 20 cm). Clean air (filtered through activated charcoal before entry into the apparatus) was drawn through the system with a vacuum pump at a rate of 1 L min⁻¹. Test insects were introduced to the end of the Y-tube stem 6 cm away from the Y-split (Furlong et al., 2018). The test plants (*B. oleracea* and *B. rapa* plants were damaged for 24 h by feeding by 10 early 3rd instar DBM larvae; all larvae were removed from plants immediately before they were used in olfactometer tests) were placed in the two separate chambers while parasitoid wasps were released at the entrance of the longer arm. Adult female wasps were allowed up to 10 min to respond after introducing the apparatus, and each insect was used only once. The arms of the Y-tube were rotated after each insect was tested (=replicate), and the HIPV sources (DBM-infested *Brassica* plants) were replaced after 10 replicates. All glassware was washed in 95% ethanol, rinsed with distilled water, and dried at 75°C for 1 h. Test insects were considered to have responded to a given odor source if they spent ≥ 10 seconds at the end of the arm of the Y-tube to which it was connected. Parasitoids that were

not chosen were recorded but excluded from the statistical analysis.

Naïve *D. semiclausum* females were tested for their preferences between DBM-induced *B. oleracea* and clean air, DBM-induced *B. rapa* and clean air, and DBM-induced *B. oleracea* and DBM-induced *B. rapa* in olfactometer bioassays. Wasps were experienced on DBM-infested *B. oleracea* by one of the conditioning regimes and then held in clean glass vials for 6, 12, and 24h before being tested in olfactometer assays for their preference between DBM-induced *B. oleracea* and DBM-induced *B. rapa*. In all olfactometer assays, a minimum of 60 females conditioned by each method were tested for each time interval.

To investigate the responses of naïve *D. semiclausum* to DBM-induced and GPA-induced *B. oleracea*, 6-leaf stage cabbage plants were removed from the growth chamber, and the following treatments were prepared. *DBM-induced B. oleracea*: plants were infested with 10 early third-instar DBM larvae for 24 h, and then all DBM larvae were removed. *GPA-induced B. oleracea*: plants were infested with 30 third-instar GPA nymphs for 24 h, and then all nymphs were removed. *Control B. oleracea*: intact plants that had not been exposed to any insect feeding. The responses of female *D. semiclausum* to the volatiles produced by the different plant treatments were evaluated in paired choice tests using a Y-tube olfactometer. Olfactometer assays were conducted within 1 h of insect removal from test plants and carried out as previously described.

Statistical analyses

Olfactometer assay datasets were tested to ensure normality before statistical analysis. Respondents were analyzed using a binomial test to compare their preference between two plant odors in paired choice tests. Parasitoids that did not make a choice were excluded from the analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Responses of naïve and conditioned *D. semiclausum* to HIPVs in olfactometer bioassays

Naïve female wasps showed a preference for both DBM-induced *B. rapa* and DBM-induced *B. oleracea* plants over clean air (binomial test, $P < 0.001$) (Fig. 1) and a preference for DBM-induced *B. rapa* over DBM-induced *B. oleracea* in paired choice tests (Fig. 1). However, when females were experienced (single oviposition) on *B. oleracea* and then subjected to the tests within one hour, they showed a clear preference for DBM-induced *B.*

oleracea plants over DBM-induced *B. rapa* plants (binomial test, $P < 0.001$). Similarly, females who experienced a single oviposition on *B. oleracea* and then tested in an olfactometer 12 h later showed a significant preference for DBM-induced *B. oleracea* plants over DBM-induced *B. rapa* plants (binomial test, $P < 0.01$). Still, parasitoids tested 24 h after this experience did not (binomial test, $P > 0.05$) (Fig. 1). Following time-spaced conditioning by oviposition into larvae on *B. oleracea* plants, significantly stronger preferences for DBM-induced *B. oleracea* plants compared to DBM-induced *B. rapa* plants were detected for up to 24 h after conditioning (binomial test, $P < 0.05$) (Fig. 1). The responses of experienced *D. semiclausum* to these learned odors declined between 24 h and 48 h after conditioning, and by 48 h after conditioning, experienced wasps no longer discriminated between DBM-induced *B. oleracea* and DBM-induced *B. rapa* plants (binomial test, at 48 h $P = 0.5000$; at 96 h $P = 0.4388$).

Figure 1. Olfactometer choice tests measuring preference of naïve and experienced, mated, female *D. semiclausum* when presented with different pairwise combinations of clear air (white bars), Diamondback moth-infested *Brassica rapa* (yellow bars), and Diamondback moth-infested *Brassica oleracea* (green bars). Asterisks indicate significant (*, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$; *, $p < 0.001$). NS indicates statistically non-significant responses to either of the plant odors.**

The formation of LTM involves a protein synthesis-dependent mechanism in many animals (DeZazzo & Tully, 1995; Kandel, 2001; Quevedo et al., 2004), including parasitoids (Smid et al., 2007; Schurmann et al., 2012). Consolidating new memories from STM to longer-lasting memories can take hours to days, suggesting that animals may evaluate acquired information before storage into fixed neural substrates (Menzel, 1999). The learning environment can affect the learning events required for LTM formation. This study provides evidence that *D. semiclausum* can form longer-lasting memories, in this case, MTM, when DBM host insects are provided as the reward (Fig. 1). Parasitoids can learn and respond to odors associated with the availability of hosts and food (Lewis

and Takasu, 1990) and whether or not the resource that the odor is associated with affects the duration of memory retention would provide an interesting future study. Given that *D. semiclausum* is a specialist parasitoid, it was hypothesized that its LTM might be consolidated similarly to that in another specialist parasitoid, *Cotesia rubecula*. *Cotesia rubecula* requires three time-spaced experiences to form LTM, whereas the generalist congeneric parasitoid, *C. glomerata*, can form LTM after a single oviposition in a host larva (Smid et al., 2007). However, time-spaced conditioning did not consolidate LTM in *D. semiclausum* (Fig. 1). The reasons for this are unclear. Still, the experience resulted in a significantly stronger preference for the learned odor than other learning regimes. The odor was preferred for longer (Fig. 1). This finding is a first for *D. semiclausum*. Our knowledge of *D. semiclausum* learning and memory formation may bring us more perspective on how specific HIPVs are utilized by *D. semiclausum*.

Discrimination between host and non-host herbivores by *D. semiclausum*

Naïve *D. semiclausum* females discriminated between plant odors emitted by intact plants and the odors emitted by both DBM-induced *B. oleracea* (binomial test, $P < 0.01$) and the odors emitted by GPA-induced *B. oleracea* (binomial test, $P < 0.01$) (Fig. 2). Still, they didn't discriminate between the odors emitted by GPA-induced plants and those emitted by DBM-induced plants (binomial test, $P = 0.500$). Experienced *D. semiclausum* females showed a significantly stronger attraction to the odors produced by DBM-induced plants compared with those produced by GPA-induced plants (binomial test, $P < 0.05$) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Responses of naïve and experienced *Diadegma semiclausum* female wasps to host diamondback moth-induced (green bars) and non-host green peach aphid-induced (pink bars) *Brassica oleracea* plants in a Y-tube olfactometer. Asterisks indicate significant (*, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$, *, $p < 0.001$). NS indicates statistically non-significant responses to either of the plant odors.**

The results support a previous study that demonstrated the attraction of naïve *D. semiclausum* females to the HIPVs released by cabbage plants in response to feeding by DBM

and a non-host lepidopteran (Furlong et al., 2018). However, the responses of *D. semiclausum* to induced cabbage plants are influenced by learning, and experienced individuals tend to exhibit a preference for plants on which they have previously located and successfully parasitized a host (Fig. 1). Although it has been proposed that naïve responses are linked to highly dependable cues, such as odors associated with hosts or host-associated factors such as pheromone or host frass (Vet & Dicke, 1992; Turlings et al., 1992), it is also plausible that all-natural enemies of herbivores exhibit inherent responses to a specific repertoire of odors that hold considerable significance in locating hosts or suitable habitats (Takabayashi et al., 2006; Dukas, 2008). However, numerous studies have demonstrated that the HIPV profiles resulting from the feeding activities of both host and non-host herbivores within the same guild can be similar. For example, naïve *Cotesia sesamiae* (Cameron) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) females do not discriminate between maize plants infested by its host *Chilo partellus* (Swinhoe) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae) and the non-host *Busseola fusca* (Fuller) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) (Ngi-Song et al., 1995, 1996). Regarding the distinction between feeding guilds, specifically piercing-sucking and chewing insects, naïve *C. marginiventris* exhibited a strong preference for the volatiles emitted by plants infested with its chewing host *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) over those induced by the piercing-sucking non-host *Euscelidius variegatus* (Kirschbaum) (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae), and the attraction to host induced volatiles was not affected by dual infestation of plants with host and non-host herbivores (Erb et al., 2010). Notably, it is necessary to investigate the VOC profiles of plants subjected to herbivore infestations or phytopathogen infections. This will elucidate whether naïve *D. semiclausum* can differentiate between VOC blends emitted by plants in response to DBM and GPA infestation or it may exhibit comparable levels of preference for both VOC blends.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study highlights the complex behavioral responses of the parasitoid wasp *D. semiclausum* towards HIPVs. Naïve females preferred DBM-induced *B. rapa* and DBM-induced *B. oleracea* plants, suggesting recognition of volatile cues associated with hosts. Additionally, experienced females displayed a shift in preference after oviposition experience, favoring DBM-induced *B. oleracea* over *B. rapa*, indicating the influence of learning on host selection. Interestingly, the research also delved into forming longer-lasting memories (MTM) in *D. semiclausum* through time-spaced conditioning. While this didn't lead to LTM consolidation, it did result in stronger and prolonged preferences for learned odors.

This adds a novel layer to our understanding of learning mechanisms in *D. semiclausum*.

The findings underline the intricate interplay between learning, memory, and odor preferences in the foraging behavior of *D. semiclausum*. The research paves the way for investigating how the species utilizes distinct HIPVs to enhance its host detection capabilities. Additionally, the study demonstrates that experienced *D. semiclausum* females, unlike naïve females, can distinguish between odors emitted by DBM- and GPA-induced plants. Learning influences responses, with experienced wasps displaying a stronger attraction to odors associated with successful hosts. The findings highlight the intricate role of HIPVs in host selection and the potential impact of learning on parasitoid foraging behavior.

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SESSION 5

Genetic Approaches to Manage Crucifer Pests: Transgenic Plants, CRISPR, RNAi, and Genetic Pest Management

Application of Genome Editing in Insect Pest Management with a Special Reference to Crucifer Pests

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ABSTRACT

Insect pests are the major limiting factor in crop production, costing farmers billions of dollars in loss annually. The recent developments in arthropod genomics and bioinformatics facilitate the identification of novel gene targets for various tools like RNAi, genome editing, etc. Genome engineering by zinc finger nucleases (ZFN), transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALEN), and recently, the clustered regularly interspersed short palindromic repeats and associated proteins (CRISPR/Cas9) essentially generate target-specific mutations for various purposes. In this regard, CRISPR/Cas9, an RNA-guided DNA cleavage system, causes a double-stranded DNA break (DSB) and introduces random mutation at the target locus due to the error-prone mechanism called nonhomologous end joining (NHEJ) affecting gene function. In addition to Cas9, other Cas proteins such as Cas12A, Cas13A, Cas3, and other innovations like base editing and prime editing have increased propensity in insect pest management. In this regard, Cole crops are globally essential and provide substantial nutritional and economic returns to the growers. However, insect pests pose a grave threat to cultivation, and genome editing has a lot of scope in managing them. Genome editing studies on *Plutella xylostella* have been conducted to determine the loss of function of genes, including abdominal-A, vitellogenin, vitellogenin receptor, yellow, and *period*. Recently, the utility of CRISPR/Cas9 mediated gene drive for managing *P. xylostella* has been demonstrated. Genome editing greatly helps develop precision-guided sterile insect technique (pgSIT), reducing the requirement of infrastructural costs and sex separation at the pupal stage as required in the ordinary course. For obtaining sterile males, the Cas9 and

gRNA lines are crossed to generate sterile males for environmental release for population suppression.

Keywords

Genome editing, CRISPR/Cas9, Crucifers, Pest Management

INTRODUCTION

Insect pests are the primary threat in agriculture that limits crop productivity, causing farmers to lose billions of dollars each year. Despite substantial environmental and health risks, synthetic pesticides remain the mainstay in managing insect pests. Therefore, scientists looked into fresh options for effective and eco-friendly pest control to lessen this overdependence. In this context, the recent advancements in genomics, molecular biology, and bioinformatics have allowed scientists to create and use novel techniques for managing insect pests, such as genome editing and gene drive. Genome editing through Transcription Activator-Like Effector Nucleases (TALEN), Zinc Finger Nucleases (ZFN), and Clustered Regularly Interspersed Palindromic Repeats and associated proteins (CRISPR/Cas9) essentially generate target specific mutations. CRISPR/Cas9 is easy to construct for any genomic target, simple to predict off-target sites, and can edit numerous genomic sites at once (multiplexing); it has become one of the most popular technologies among the aforementioned technologies. The present manuscript deals with a detailed review of literature concerning history, mechanisms of action, applications of CRISPR/Cas technology, and finally, the use of CRISPR/Cas in entomology with particular emphasis on Cruciferous pests.

HISTORY OF CRISPR/CAS

Currently, biological research focuses more on CRISPR/Cas systems. Thirty years ago, researchers studying the gene responsible for the isozyme conversion of alkaline phosphatase in *Escherichia coli* discovered the first repeat sequences (now known as CRISPRs) (Ishino et al., 1987). Due to a lack of genomic resources at the time, it was impossible to foresee the biological importance. Up to the middle of the 2000s, the precise purpose of this unusual sequence remained unknown. CRISPR was first discovered in the archaea *Haloferax mediterranei* in 1993 (Mojica et al., 1993), and it has since been found in several bacterial and archaeal species. It wasn't until the early 2000s that the role of CRISPR as a prokaryotic immune system was finally understood. This was due to the discovery of sequence similarities between the spacer sections of CRISPRs and bacteriophages, archaeal viruses, and plasmids. Numerous genes were previously thought to encode DNA repair proteins discovered inextricably linked to CRISPR and given the name Cas (CRISPR-associated) genes.

Furthermore, comparative genomic investigations revealed that CRISPR and Cas proteins function in concert to protect prokaryotic cells against plasmids and viruses, very similar to how eukaryotic RNA interference defends eukaryotic cells. CRISPR sequences are the most extensively distributed family of repetitive sequences in prokaryotes, with virtually all archaeal genomes and around half of bacterial genomes. No eukaryotic genome was found/reported to have CRISPR sequences (Jansen et al., 2002).

DISCOVERY OF CRISPR/CAS FUNCTION

Many mesophilic species included CRISPR sequences due to the growing number of sequences that are now readily accessible in public databases. It was noted that phages and plasmids did not infect bacterial host strains with homologous spacer sequences. It was proposed that CRISPRs might capture DNA fragments from invaders to create a memory of earlier infections (Barrangou and Horvath, 2017). It was also hypothesized that CRISPR might be utilized to manufacture antisense RNA after discovering the correlation between the number of spacers of phage origin and the level of resistance to phage infection (Marraffini and Sontheimer, 2010). Importantly, it was noted that the CRISPR-Cas system, with its memory component, resembled the adaptive immune system of vertebrates except for the fact that the animal immune system is not inheritable (Koonin and Makarova, 2013; Barrangou and Marraffini, 2014). In 2007, *Streptococcus thermophilus* provided conclusive evidence that the CRISPR/Cas system serves as a prokaryotic immune system. *S. thermophilus* strain became resistant to the phage when the phage sequence was inserted into the spacer region of the CRISPR. However, the relevant protospacer sequence was removed, nullifying this bacterial resistance (Sapranaukas et al., 2011).

COMPONENTS OF CRISPR/CAS9

The CRISPR/Cas system is divided into two classes based on the structures and roles of the Cas proteins: Class I (Types I, III, and IV) and Class II (Types II, V, and VI). Class II systems use a single Cas protein, whereas Class I systems are composed of Cas-protein complexes with many subunits (varying from 4 to 7 Cas proteins). About 90% of reported CRISPR-Cas loci are found in bacteria and archaea, frequently home to the Class I system. The remaining 10% are Class II, which only employs a single family of bacterial effector proteins with several domains (Mohanraju et al., 2016). The type II CRISPR/Cas9 system has been extensively studied and widely used in genetic engineering among the different types due to its relatively simple structure. It is a two-component system composed of guide RNA (gRNA or crRNA) and CRISPR-associated proteins (Cas9). The Cas9 protein was the first used Cas protein in genome editing, and it was initially isolated from *Streptococcus pyogenes* (spCas9). It is a

bulky protein with 1368 amino acids that functions as a DNA endonuclease to cleave the target DNA and produce a double-stranded break (DSB). Cas9 achieves this by identifying the PAM, or protospacer adjacent motif. Each single-stranded DNA is cut by Cas9's RuvC and HNH domains, while the PAM interacting domain confers PAM specificity and starts binding to the target DNA. The guide RNA is composed of two components: the crRNA, which is 18-20 base pairs in length and specifies the target DNA sequence through pairing, and the trans-activating crRNA (tracrRNA), which consists of a series of loops and serves as a binding scaffold for the Cas9 nuclease. In recent developments, the combination of crRNA and tracrRNA has created a single guide RNA (sgRNA) (Doudna and Charpentier, 2014). This programmable sgRNA can target almost any gene sequence in any organism (Liu et al., 2020).

MECHANISMS OF CRISPR/CAS9

The mechanisms of genome editing using CRISPR/Cas9 include three main steps: recognition, cleavage, and repair. The designed single guide RNA (sgRNA) guides the Cas9 protein to recognize and bind to the target sequence in the gene of interest. This recognition is facilitated by the complementary base pairing between the 5' component of the sgRNA and the target gene sequence. Without the presence of sgRNA, the Cas9 protein remains inactive. Once the Cas9 protein is guided to the target site, it introduces double-stranded breaks (DSBs) in the DNA. The cleavage site is typically three base pairs upstream of a short, conserved DNA sequence called the protospacer adjacent motif (PAM). Depending on the bacterial species, the PAM sequence varies in length (2-5 base pairs). The commonly used Cas9 protein's recognized PAM sequence is 5'-NGG-3' (where N can be any nucleotide base). After locating the target site and identifying the PAM sequence, Cas9 initiates a local DNA melting process, forming an RNA-DNA hybrid structure. This triggers the activation of the Cas9 protein, enabling it to cleave the DNA (Jiang and Doudna, 2017). The HNH domain of Cas9 cleaves the complementary strand of the target DNA, while the RuvC domain cleaves the non-complementary strand. This cleavage results in blunt-ended DSBs. The host cellular machinery then repairs the DSBs using two main mechanisms: non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) and homology-directed repair (HDR). NHEJ is an error-prone mechanism that repairs DSBs by joining DNA fragments without using exogenous homologous DNA. However, this mechanism can lead to small random insertions or deletions (indels) at the cleavage site, potentially causing frameshift mutations or premature stop codons.

On the other hand, HDR is a highly precise repair mechanism that requires a homologous DNA template. It is most active during the late S and G2 phases of the cell cycle. In CRISPR gene editing, HDR necessitates many donor DNA templates containing the desired sequence.

HDR enables precise gene insertion or replacement by incorporating the donor DNA template with sequence homology at the predicted DSB site (Paix et al., 2017).

CAS AND ITS TYPES

CRISPR/Cas9

Cas9 is the most well-known and widely used Cas protein. It is derived from the CRISPR/Cas9 system and is commonly used for genome editing. Cas9 functions as a nuclease and can create double-strand breaks at specific target sites in the DNA. It requires a guide RNA (gRNA) to direct it to the target sequence (Mali et al., 2013).

CRISPR/Cas12a

CRISPR/Cas12a (Cpf1) is classified as a class II type V CRISPR system and operates based on RNA guidance. While it shares similarities with CRISPR/Cas9, the *Francisella novicida* U112 variant of CRISPR/Cas12a (FnCpf1) exhibits distinct characteristics. One notable difference is the presence of four CRISPR/Cas-based insect resistance traits in crops. Additionally, the efficiency of homology-directed repair (HDR) for inserting DNA fragments using complementary DNA ends is improved due to cohesive DNA ends. Compared to Cas9, Cpf1 is more cost-effective because it requires a 42-nucleotide CRISPR RNA (crRNA) instead of the 100-nucleotide scaffold crRNA required by Cas9 (Paul and Montoya, 2020).

CRISPR/Cas13a

CRISPR/Cas13a represents a novel type of CRISPR system classified as class II type VI. This system efficiently targets endogenous RNAs in plants and viral RNAs with RNA target specificity. It possesses RNase activity attributed to higher eukaryotes and prokaryotes nucleotide-binding (HEPN) domains (Zhao et al., 2022).

CRISPR/CasX

CRISPR/CasX involves the development of a SpCas9 variant known as xCas9. This variant can recognize a broader range of protospacer adjacent motifs (PAMs). It exhibits enhanced compatibility with various PAMs, including NG, GAT, and GAA, resulting in lower off-target activity, higher editing efficiency, and improved specificity compared to SpCas9. By replacing Cas9 with xCas9 in the BE3 vector, a cytidine base editor (CBE) called the BE3-xCas9 is generated, which allows editing of loci containing different PAMs such as NGN, GAA, and GAT (Bari et al., 2017).

CRISPR/Cas14

CRISPR/Cas14 refers to the compact CRISPR/Cas14a system utilized as a guided gene-editing tool for cutting single-stranded DNA (ssDNA). Based on comparative sequence analysis, Cas14a, Cas14b, and Cas14c are three subgroups identified among the 24 different Cas14 gene variants. Notably, the size of CRISPR/Cas14a is half that

of Cas9, and it does not require a flanking sequence (protospacer adjacent motif or PAM) near the target site (Harrington et al., 2018).

CRISPR/Cas1

Cas1 is a Cas protein involved in the adaptation phase of CRISPR-Cas systems. During adaptation, Cas1 captures small fragments of foreign DNA called protospacers and integrates them into the CRISPR array, which serves as the genetic Memory of the system. Cas1 acts as the integrase, catalyzing the insertion of protospacers into the CRISPR array as new spacers. It is essential to acquire immunity against future invasions by the same or similar foreign DNA (Long et al., 2021).

CRISPR/Cas2

Cas2 is another Cas protein that plays a role in the adaptation phase of CRISPR-Cas systems. It works in conjunction with Cas1 and is involved in the processing and integrating protospacer DNA into the CRISPR array. Cas2 is thought to be responsible for the selection and cleavage of protospacer DNA, generating the necessary fragments for integration by Cas1 (Makarova et al., 2011).

CRISPR/Cas3

Cas3 is a multifunctional Cas protein involved in the interference phase of CRISPR-Cas systems. It acts as an endonuclease and helicase, targeting and degrading foreign DNA that matches the CRISPR array's spacers. Cas3 is responsible for destroying the invading DNA, providing defense against viral or plasmid infections. Its endonuclease activity cleaves the target DNA, while the helicase activity helps unwind and degrade the cleaved DNA (Yoshimi et al., 2022).

CRISPR OVER RNAI

CRISPR and RNA interference (RNAi) are powerful tools in genetic research and have distinct advantages and applications. CRISPR offers precise and targeted genome editing capabilities. It uses a guide RNA to direct the Cas9 protein to specific DNA sequences, where it can introduce modifications, insertions, or deletions. This precise editing ability makes CRISPR ideal for creating knockout models, studying gene function, and engineering organisms with specific traits. It has wide applications in agriculture, medicine, and biotechnology (Unniyampurath et al., 2016).

On the other hand, RNAi is a natural cellular process that regulates gene expression by silencing specific genes through the degradation of their messenger RNA (mRNA). It involves the introduction of small interfering RNA (siRNA) molecules that bind to complementary mRNA sequences, leading to their degradation and preventing protein synthesis. RNAi is valuable for studying gene function, allowing for targeted gene knockdown. It has been widely used for functional genomics, drug target

validation, and therapeutic development (Schuster et al., 2019).

While both CRISPR and RNAi have their strengths, CRISPR generally offers more precise and versatile genetic manipulation. It allows for gene knockdown, gene knockout, and precise modifications. CRISPR's ability to introduce specific genetic changes and its versatility in various organisms make it a powerful tool for genetic research and applications. However, RNAi has advantages in certain contexts. Implementing it can be relatively straightforward, especially for short-term or transient gene knockdown studies. RNAi is also functional when studying genes with complex functions or manipulating gene expression across a range of targets simultaneously. The choice between CRISPR and RNAi depends on the specific research goals, the nature of the genetic manipulation needed, and the complexity of the gene regulatory network being studied.

APPLICATIONS OF CRISPR/CAS9 IN INSECTS

Diptera

The first report of the CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing-based deletion of 4.6 kb of *yellow* locus and 6.1 kb *rosy* locus from the *Drosophila* genome was achieved through the utility of two target sgRNAs (one at 5' and 3' end) and a ssODN (single-stranded oligonucleotide donor) template (Gratz et al. 2013). The *yellow* gene was targeted to demonstrate an escalation in the editing efficiency of *Drosophila* (Yu et al., 2013). The direct correlation between the CRISPR/Cas9 efficiency and the concentration of sgRNA was calibrated through the *yellow* gene. However, the adult survival rate was reduced using high sgRNA concentrations (Bassett et al., 2013). Heritable mutations induced by the CRISPR/Cas9 targeted system were studied in detail in the *white* gene in three tephritid species under the *Anastrepha*, *Bactrocera*, and *Ceratit* genera. All *white* eye mutant phenotypes of *Anastrepha ludens*, *Bactrocera dorsalis*, and *Ceratit capitata* resulted in 4 and 17 base pairs (bp) deletions, which created frameshifts, point mutations and premature stop codons (Sim et al., 2019). In flies, multiple tactics have been employed to achieve the HDR (homology-directed repair) induction; for example, a gRNA plasmid and donor repair template were administered into transgenic Cas9 embryos (Xue et al., 2014), while the transgenic embryos with a sgRNA and Cas9 were injected with a donor template plasmid. The sgRNA, Cas9 gene, and donor repair template in a plasmid form were delivered into non-transgenic flies (Gokcezade et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2014). However, their infinite time and labor requirements have restricted the widespread implementation of genome editing techniques in *Drosophila*. The CRISPR/Cas9 system is primed to fill this void.

The oriental fruit fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Hendel) (Diptera: Tephritidae), is one of the major pests all over Southeast Asia and many Pacific Islands (Stephens et al. 2007). This highly polyphagous pest damages more than 250 host plant species worldwide (Zhang 2012). The traditional methods for combating *B. dorsalis* mainly contain bait-luring and chemical control measures (Jaime et al. 2009), which are repeatedly failing, thus grabbing the attention of researchers towards novel approaches like pgSIT focusing on several candidate genes in *B. dorsalis*. CRISPR/Cas9 was extensively used in *B. dorsalis* to explore the functions of many genes. To demonstrate the function of transformer (*tra*) genes, CRISPR/Cas9 mediated mutagenesis was carried out in *B. dorsalis*. The sgRNA and Cas9 mRNA targeting the *tra* gene were co-injected into the *B. dorsalis* embryos. The *tra* gene mutations caused abnormal outer and internal reproductive organ development in addition to a sex bias towards males. This gene can be a good target for managing this pest because these small indels and substitutions were passable to successive generations (Zhao et al., 2019). CRISPR-mediated knockout verified the essential role of miR-1-3p as an intermediate male determiner in *B. dorsalis*. miR-1-3p encourages male-specific splicing of *tra* pre-mRNA and thus leads to its functional inactivation in XY embryos. Knockout of miR-1-3p induces sex reversal of XY individuals into phenotypic females. These outcomes indicate that in early embryogenesis, miR-1-3p is essential for sex determination in male *B. dorsalis*. Manipulation of miR-1-3p in *B. dorsalis* may be employed for sexing in SIT, such as by generating populations of males only by its conditional ectopic overexpression in XX females during embryogenesis (Peng et al., 2020). The sex peptide receptor (*spr*) gene of the *B. dorsalis* is responsible for female fertility and ovarian development, knocking out the *spr* gene targeted through CRISPR/Cas9 system led to a significant reduction in the ovary size, egg viability, and fertility of *B. dorsalis* females. Thus, *spr* can be a potential candidate for CRISPR/Cas9-based pgSIT in *B. dorsalis* (Chen et al., 2023).

The odorant receptor co-receptor (*Orco*) is an essential odorant receptor and crucial for odor perception in *B. dorsalis*. The *BdorOrco* mutants with olfactory deficiency were generated through the CRISPR/Cas9 system. *BdorOrco*^{-/-} mutant flies showed scaled-down perception of methyl eugenol, ethyl acetate, and β -caryophyllene and was verified through electroantennograms (EAG) and olfactory preference assays, validating that *Orco* is a vital component of the olfactory system and involved in several physiological processes including odorant perception, foraging, and oviposition. *BdorOrco*^{-/-} mutant females took more time to search for a host, and egg laying was significantly reduced concerning reduced olfactory sensitivity to oviposition attractants like benzothiazole and 1-octen-3-ol

(Xu et al., 2022). Numerous physiological functions in insects, including feeding, olfactory memory, and development, are influenced by the short neuropeptide F (sNPF) signaling system, including sNPF and its receptor (sNPFR). Using the CRISPR/Cas9 method, sNPFR^{-/-} mutants were generated and verified that sNPFR controls olfactory sensitivity to influence foraging behavior in *B. dorsalis*. Due to its functional versatility, sNPFR can be a potential target for behavioral control against *B. dorsalis* (Li et al., 2022). The physiological function of the *Bdpaired* gene in *B. dorsalis* was characterized using the CRISPR/Cas9 system *in vivo*. Cuticular deficiency, absence of segment boundaries, and embryonic lethality were evident in *Bdpaired* knockouts. Additionally, the relative expression of Abdominal A (*Abd-A*) and Wingless (*Wg*) genes was down-regulated in the *Bdpaired* mutant embryos. Developmental defects detected in mutant flies signify the importance of *Bdpaired* gene in *B. dorsalis* embryonic development, demonstrating that *Bdpaired* gene can be a potential genetic target for pest management (Wang et al., 2020).

Orthoptera

Heritable mutagenesis of *Orco* gene in *Locusta migratoria* displayed markedly altered response to electrophysiological and olfactory behavior (Li et al., 2016). The knock-out strains of *Acheta domesticus*, as a result of targeting *Ad* vermilion exhibited white-eyed phenotypes (Dossey et al., 2023)

Hemiptera

In *Nilaparvata lugens*, heritable mutagenesis of two eye color genes, cinnabar and white, was achieved through CRISPR/Cas9, resulting in bright red and light red color compound eyes, as well as bright red and white ocelli, respectively (Xue et al., 2018). CRISPR/Cas9-induced knockout of *NICSAD* resulted in darker cuticle pigmentation and declined oviposition and egg hatching (Chen et al., 2021). The *NICYP6CS1* gene was effectively knocked out using the CRISPR/Cas9 method, which dissected its critical functions in pesticide resistance and fitness costs in *N. lugens* (Zhang et al., 2023).

Coleoptera

Defects in dorsal closure were due to the knockout of the E-cadherin gene in *Tribolium*, which was achieved through CRISPR (Gilles et al., 2015). The *red-1* and *peach* eye color mutants in *Tribolium* result from mutations in the cardinal gene. Due to the ReMOT control method, a mutation in cardinal genes resulted in red-1 and peach eye color mutants in *T. castaneum* (Shirai and Daimon, 2020). DIPA-CRISPR mediated mutation of the cinnabar gene in *T. castaneum* resulted in white and mosaic phenotypes (Shirai et al., 2022).

Lepidoptera

As a prototypical organism, *B. mori* has consistently held the top spot among lepidopteran species in genome editing (Ma et al., 2019). The *B. mori* pre-blastoderm embryos injected with the sgRNA-1 and sgRNA-2 in addition to Cas9 mRNA effectively induced loss of function of *BmBLOS2* (Wang et al., 2013), which proved that the sgRNA-Cas9 system can successfully induce targeted mutagenesis in *B. mori* and the first time its use in Lepidoptera was acknowledged. The efficiency and heritability of the CRISPR/Cas9 system were demonstrated by knocking out the *BmTH*, *Bm-ok*, *BmKMO*, and *Bmtan* in *B. mori* (Wei et al., 2014). Knocking out of the *Bmku70* displayed an increased rate of homologous recombination in embryos (Ma et al., 2014). These breakthroughs started the swift development of CRISPR technology in *B. mori*. The first successful genome manipulation of *B. mori*, using the CRISPR/Cas9 system, was reported after targeting an essential gene, *BmBlos2*. Targeted mutagenesis was induced by injecting two complexes, each with single sgRNAs (23-bp) and Cas9, in the pre-blastoderm stage of embryos. Two sgRNAs induced successful edits in 94% and 95.6% of individuals, respectively (Wang et al., 2013).

The former gene type used by CRISPR for the practical verification are marker genes in lepidopteran insects; such screening research is of great importance in insect genetic study. Knocking out the *ebony* gene stimulated melanin formation in the pupal stage and deepened the pupal coloring in *S. litura* (Bi et al., 2019a). Knocking out of *yellow* in *S. litura* affects egg hatching due to the hardening of the stratum corneum. (Shirai et al., 2021). The *Slabd-A* gene was knocked out, leading to abnormal segmentation and ectopic pigmentation in the *S. litura* larvae (Bi et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2018). Ovarian serine protease (*Osp*) is vital for female reproductive success. *Osp* knockout strains in *S. litura* resulted in female sterility, while male reproduction was unaffected (Xu et al., 2020c). The role of *SlitPBP3* in the olfaction of female sex pheromone was deciphered in *S. litura* with the help of CRISPR/Cas9 editing. Genetic approaches like the CRISPR/Cas9 system revealed the role of *GOBP2* in sex pheromone perception in both larvae and adult *S. litura* (Han et al., 2022). A pheromone is an essential molecule that communicates between individuals. *SlitPBP1* and *SlitPBP2* play a significant role. However, *SlitPBP3* plays a minor role in perceiving female sex pheromones (Zhu et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2019). Knockout of *SISxl* resulted in reduced fertility of adult males due to less sperm development (Wen et al., 2022).

CRISPR/Cas9 mediated mutagenesis of the *Sfabd-A* gene in *S. frugiperda* resulted in fused segmentation in larval and pupal stages and adult sterility (Wu et al., 2018). Sterility was induced by knocking out the sex-specific isoform of *dsx* using CRISPR-mediated editing (Gu et al.,

2022). Both male and female *Orco* mutant moths of *S. frugiperda* lost their olfactory response toward tested plant volatiles and sex pheromones (Song et al., 2022). CRISPR/Cas-based genome editing of the *OBP27* gene significantly influenced the development of *S. frugiperda* larvae and adult mating (Han et al., 2023).

The four genes of *H. armigera* *white*, *brown*, *scarlet*, and *ok* were subjected to somatic and germline knockout mutation using CRISPR/Cas9. Knockouts of *white* affect eggs, first-instar larvae, and eye pigments of adults. Knockouts of *scarlet* resulted in pigment less first-instar larvae and yellow adult eyes without xanthomata. Knockout of the *ok* resulted in translucent cuticles in larvae and black eyes. Knockout of *brown* did not affect phenotype vitality and pigmentation (Khan et al., 2017).

Diamondback moth (DBM) *Plutella xylostella*

Plutella xylostella, commonly known as the diamondback moth (DBM), is a destructive pest that affects cruciferous crops such as cabbage, broccoli, and kale. Gene drive technology, specifically CRISPR-based gene drive, has been proposed as a potential method to control populations of *P. xylostella*. Liu et al. (2020a) knocked out the yellow gene, which resulted in yellow-pigmented larvae and adults in addition to yellow segments and yellow molting of larvae. Deletion of the *Pxyellow* gene did not influence the growth, development, and reproduction but only affected the body pigmentation in *P. xylostella* (Wang et al., 2020a). When the *Pxabd-A* gene in *P. xylostella* was knocked out, unhatched embryos and hatched larvae exhibited forelimb deformity and segmental deformity traits passed down to the following generation (Huang et al., 2016). The double sex (*PxDsx*) gene of the *P. xylostella* responsible for sex determination in the insect was targeted using the CRISPR/Cas9 system, which led to the altered expression of the sex-biased genes. The egg hatching was lowered due to the deletion of the *PxVg* (Zou et al., 2020) and *PxVgR* gene (Peng et al., 2020). The number of eggs laid by wild and mutant individuals of *PxVg* and *PxVgR* did not differ significantly (Peng et al., 2020; Zou et al., 2020).

CRISPR/Cas9-mediated mutagenesis of both ABC transporter genes *PxABCC2* and *PxABCC3* in *P. xylostella* resulted in high resistance to Cry1Ac in *P. xylostella*. It

provided insights into reverse genetics evidence of ABCC2 and ABCC3 proteins being functional receptors for Bt Cry1 toxins in insects midgut (Haung et al., 2016). LW-opsin, involved in movement and taxis to green and IR lights, is crucial in mediating the phototaxis in *P. xylostella*. Knockout of LW-opsin in *P. xylostella* impaired locomotion (Chen et al., 2021). In *P. xylostella*, mutation of nAChR α 6 through CRISPR/Cas9 causes a frameshift in the transcripts' open reading frame, resulting in a predicted protein that is truncated in the TM3-TM4 loop region and confers resistance to spinosad (Wang et al., 2020). The I4790M knock-in of *PxRyR* using a CRISPR/Cas9-based approach resulted in genetically linked moderate resistance to flubendiamide (Wang et al., 2020). D472N mutation was introduced into the Rdl1 GABAR through the CRISPR/Cas9 system, which resulted in abamectin resistance in susceptible *P. xylostella* strain and further resulted in a significant reduction in fecundity (Sun et al., 2023).

In the context of *P. xylostella*, researchers have explored the possibility of using a CRISPR-based gene drive to introduce genetic modifications that would reduce the reproductive capacity or viability of the moth population, thereby reducing its impact on crops. Unlike the typical Mendelian segregation, the gene-drive mechanism can ensure that desirable features are passed on to the progenies more frequently. Asad et al. (2022) have created a single CRISPR/Cas9-mediated gene-drive construct targeting *P. xylostella* in cruciferous crops. The Cas9 gene, an EGFP marker gene, and a gRNA sequence targeting the *Pxyellow* phenotypic marker gene were designed and site-specifically inserted into the *P. xylostella* genome. An approximately 12-kb-long fragment containing the Cas9 gene, gRNA, and EGFP gene, along with their promoters, was replicated to the target location by this homing-based gene drive. Overall, it was found that non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) caused 80.93%–86.77% resistant-allele creation, while homology-directed repair (HDR) caused 6.67%–12.59% gene-drive efficiency. Additionally, compared to transgenic progeny produced from female parents, those from male parents displayed higher gene-drive effectiveness. The success of the CRISPR/Cas9-mediated gene-drive construct in *P. xylostella* that passes on the desired features to the progeny is shown by this work (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Expected (A) and obtained (B) phenotypes for an ideal homing endonuclease-based gene-drive system (Asad et al., 2022)

To induce the expression of Cas9 and a single guide RNA in DBM and test the first split gene drive system in a lepidopteran, Xu et al. (2022) employed endogenous regulatory elements. Although there was no discernible homing in the following generation, a very high level of somatic editing was seen in Cas9/sgRNA trans heterozygotes. Although heritable Cas9-mediated germline cleavage and maternal and paternal Cas9 deposition were noted, the rates were much lower than for somatic cleavage events (Figure 2). This suggests that Cas9/sgRNA has strong somatic but restricted germline

activity regulated by specific regulatory components. Their findings offer helpful insight and pave the way for future development of gene drives or other Cas9-based genetic control techniques in DBM and other lepidopterans. However, it's important to note that the development and implementation of CRISPR gene drives for *P. xylostella* are still at an early research stage. Numerous technical, ecological, and ethical considerations must be addressed before such technologies can be deployed.

Figure 2. Crossing scheme for DBM gene drive (Xu et al., 2022)

CRISPR/CAS COMPONENTS DELIVERY METHOD

Microinjection

Microinjection is one successful method for CRISPR/Cas9-based gene editing. A stereo microscope/inverted microscope, micromanipulator, microinjection needle, and needle puller (if using microcapillaries) are essential for embryonic microinjection. In microinjection, microneedles (0.5–5 μm inner diameter) are used to pierce the cell membrane, and cargoes (intact RNP complexes, HDR donors (ssDNA/dsDNA), plasmids, and RNA) are directly injected into early (preblastoderm) stage embryos or oocytes, zygotes, and some cultured cells and can be targeted to the nuclei of both somatic and germline cells. Early-stage embryos are preferred for microinjection to create transgenic organisms with stable heritability. Manual injection helps to control the dosage of cargoes into the cell precisely. This cargo delivery method overcomes the barriers associated with delivery through the extracellular matrix, cell membrane, and cytoplasmic components. It delivers cargo into the cytoplasm or the nucleus of the cell. This method does not rely on cargo molecular weight, a limiting factor for viral vector delivery methods. A major challenge in embryo microinjection of small embryos is to perform the microinjection carefully to minimize embryo damage and sustain higher embryo survival. Microinjection is a laborious, costly, time-consuming, and technically challenging method that requires extensive training and practice to achieve high embryo viability and successful

mutagenesis (Gabrieli and Scolari, 2016; Choo et al., 2018; Martin-Martin et al., 2018; Sieber et al., 2021; Choo et al., 2022; Pacheco et al., 2022; Paulo et al., 2022).

Electroporation

Electroporation is a physical transfection method that uses an electrical current to apply high-voltage pulses that temporarily create small pores in the cell membrane, allowing charged molecules (DNA, RNA, or proteins) to pass through and reach the target cells. A special buffer solution (PBS) is often used to ensure proper conductivity (Kaneko and Mashimo, 2015). Where microinjection-based gene editing is not suitable for insect systems, the electroporation method offers a potential method to deliver cargo directly across membranes to target sites in cells. Electroporation can deliver intact RNP complexes, HDR donors (ssDNA/dsDNA), plasmids, and RNA into many eukaryotic cell lines. Electroporation also includes nucleofection, a more specialized method used to transport cargo to the cell nucleus. Electroporation is relatively independent of cell type and can efficiently transport cargo to target sites, which has been considered difficult by other delivery methods. Depending on the size of the embryos and the electroporation chamber, more embryos can be electroporated in one round of electroporation compared to the number of embryonic microinjections in the same time frame (Kaneko and Mashimo 2015). RNP electroporation had fewer off-target mutations and higher on-target editing efficiency than other delivery methods (Kim et al., 2014; Ramakrishna et al., 2014; Subburaj et al., 2016). Electroporation is suitable for both *in vitro* and *ex vivo* studies but not currently for human *in vivo* studies. The optimization of Cas9 to sgRNA ratios is extensive, and the costs

associated with this method are generally high, as each cell type requires specific electroporation conditions. High voltage also shocks stress-sensitive cells, resulting in cytotoxicity and high mortality (Hui, 2008).

The efficiency of CRISPR gene editing can be increased by adding an electroporation enhancer to the RNP reagent. These enhancers are single-stranded DNA molecules with no homology to the human, mouse, or rat genome and are unlikely to integrate into the target genome. These molecules reduce the amount of RNP complexes required, enhance RNP delivery to cells during electroporation, and reduce off-target effects by increasing target cell viability. These enhancers are not suitable for microinjection or lipofection. Single-stranded oligodeoxynucleotides (ssODNs) are used as donor templates for homology-directed repair (HDR) during electroporation for cell repair post-DSB (Jacobi et al., 2017; Schubert et al., 2021).

In vivo cargo delivery to the target site by electroporation has been explored in insects (Leopold et al., 1996; Hughes et al., 1997; Golden et al., 2007; Ando and Fujiwara, 2013; Yamaguchi et al., 2013; Yoda et al., 2014; Fujiwara and Nishikawa, 2016; Xu et al., 2016; KonDo et al., 2017; Okude et al., 2017; Jamison et al., 2018). *In vivo* electroporation following microinjection is a potential and successful delivery method. This method was followed by Matsumoto et al. (2013) for targeted gene delivery in cricket brain, which involves five electric pulses following microinjection, resulting in efficient plasmid transfer. Kunieda and Kubo (2004) also used this method in honeybee brain for plasmid transfer.

Receptor-Mediated Ovary Transduction of Cargo (ReMOT)

ReMOT (Receptor-Mediated Ovary Transduction of Cargo) method is an alternative method to bypass embryonic microinjection proposed by Chaverra-Rodriguez et al. (2018) in *Aedes aegypti*. During ovarian development and egg maturation (i.e., vitellogenesis), protein substances are synthesized in the fat body and secreted into the haemocoel. Most egg-laying females transfer protein material from the haemocoel to the developing oocyte. To take advantage of this situation, arthropod egg yolk protein precursor (YPP)-derived ligands were incorporated into RNP complexes (Cas9+sgRNA) and injected directly into the haemocoel of adult females to stimulate developing oocytes to facilitate uptake of the complexes through receptor-mediated endocytosis (RME) process for the success of genome editing (Chaverra-Rodriguez et al., 2018).

ReMOT-based gene editing has been successfully used in insects having polytrophic ovaries like *Anopheles stephensi* (Macias et al., 2020), the jewel wasp *Nasonia vitripennis* (Chaverra-Rodriguez et al., 2020), and the red flour beetle *Tribolium castaneum* (Shirai and Daimon, 2020), the silver leaf whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Heu et al.,

2020), and non-insect mite species (Sharma et al., 2022). However, a limitation of this method is that this is a time-consuming process and needs highly pure Cas9 protein, and the peptide ligand fused to Cas9 needs to be specifically tailored to the target species for efficient gene editing (Chaverra-Rodriguez et al., 2018; Heu et al. al., 2020; Shirai and Daimon, 2020). The efficiency of the ReMOT method can be improved by using endosomal releasing reagents (ERR), such as chloroquine, ammonium chloride, saponin, and monensin, which facilitate the release of Cas9 RNPs from endosomes to the cytosol (Chaverra-Rodriguez et al., 2018, Chaverra-Rodriguez et al., 2020; Heu et al., 2020; Macias et al., 2020). High efficiency and low demand for sophisticated microinjection equipment make this method an alternative to his CRISPR/Cas9-based gene editing.

DIPA-CRISPR

Shirai et al. (2022) reported a simple 'direct-parental CRISPR' (DIPA-CRISPR) method of gene editing in insects by direct injection of ribonucleoprotein along with commercially available Cas9 protein to adults. Gene editing efficiency with DIPA-CRISPR was 21.8% in *Blattella germanica* but reached over 50% in the red potato beetle *Tribolium castaneum*. This method applies to all three types of ovaries: panoistic, telotrophic, and polytrophic ovaries (Shirai et al., 2023). DIPA-CRISPR technology can also be used for gene knock-in following the homology-directed repair (HDR) pathway. The *T. castaneum* gene knock-in generated 1.2% precise knock-in alleles by HDR. Precise knowledge of ovarian development contributes to the great success of this method, as it uses the vitellogenic process to incorporate the complex into the oocyte (Shirai et al., 2022).

Co-CRISPR

Several techniques, collectively known as "CRISPR co-selection" (also known as "co-CRISPR" or "CRISPR co-conversion"), have been developed to enhance and/or select for desirable CRISPR events. When two independent sgRNAs and a Cas9 protein are simultaneously introduced into a cell population, CRISPR events co-occur at both loci within a single cell at a higher than-random frequency, termed CRISPR co-selection. CRISPR co-selection exploits this observation by introducing sgRNAs targeting the gene of interest and sgRNAs targeting marker loci that produce readily detectable and/or selectable phenotypes. A successful variation of this strategy was developed for *Caenorhabditis elegans* (Arribere et al. 2014; Kim et al. 2014), *Drosophila* (Ge et al. 2016; Kane et al. 2017), and mammalian cell culture (Liao et al. 2015; Shy et al. 2016; Agudelo et al. 2017).

CONCLUSION

Genome editing tools, like CRISPR/Cas9, in biological and genetic research have both positive and negative impacts. However, applying these tools has raised ethical questions and introduced various risks, such as off-target mutations. Modifying insects, including mosquitoes, using the CRISPR/Cas9 system and releasing them into the environment can be particularly risky. To release mutant mosquitoes without adverse effects on humans poses a challenge for insect scientists. It is crucial for researchers using CRISPR/Cas9 technology to prioritize safety and avoid ecological harm. Due to the ease of use and affordability of CRISPR technology, it has gained popularity worldwide. However, this widespread adoption necessitates the establishment of international standards to test genetically modified insects, their release into the environment, and liability for potential damages. Regulations should outline precise requirements for testing the effectiveness of edited insects in controlled environments that simulate their natural habitats. Additionally, edited insects should only be released after consulting the public and obtaining appropriate consent from potentially affected populations in typical environments, whether in the wild or on farms. Addressing these biosafety concerns will require comprehensive regulatory oversight that surpasses the existing regulations in any part of the world.

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